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Agri-food and Tourism
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Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

24-26 May 2012
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EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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***Journal of EcoAgriTourism, dissemination path for Bioatlas
International Conference 2012***

The Research Center Eco-biotechnology and Equipment for Food and Agriculture (EBIOTEFA) from the Institute of Research Development of Transylvania University, but also of Food and Tourism Faculty – the IMAT Department, represents the top structure for our research activity. The new research on programs and projects specific to the field are the object for certain technologies, to make ecologic and biologic food products, to optimize the respective equipment, brevets and, of course, certain scientific papers. These research results, for which we have important contributions from researchers from different institutions from Romania and many other countries are disseminated through two very important for us activities: *The BIOATLAS International Conference* and the *Journal of EcoAgriTourism*.

Within this context, the information dissemination, trough its variuos forms, should be homogeneous and harmonious. In the light of this particularly expressed desire, we conceived a correspondece between the structure of the Journal and the International Conference we organize every two years. Therefore, we present below the links between the headings of Journal of EcoAgriTourism (J of EAT) and communication session of the International Conference on New Research in Food and Tourism – BIOATLAS.

J of EAT	BIOATLAS Conference
Biodiversity	Biodiversity Capitalization and Tourism Applications
CalitaTerra	Agri-food and Tourism Equipment
Sanogeneous Food	Bio-food, Public Health and Culinary Production (i.s.ecological and biological technologies)
Sustainable Tourism and Hospitalty Ideas and Concepts	Management, IT and Law in Agri-Food, Tourism and Hospitality Industry

Papers with high degree of originality and scientific contribution as well as with important conclusions for the practice in food and tourism have been selected to be published in Journal of EcoAgriTourism.

Romulus GRUIA
Director of the Journal of EcoAgriTourism

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THRIPS SPECIES (INSECTA: THYSANOPTERA) OF ORNAMENTAL PLANTS FROM GREENHOUSES ADP PITEȘTI

D. BĂRBUCEANU*, LILIANA VASILIU-OROMULU**

Abstract: Observations carried out in 2008 in the A.D.P. Pitești greenhouses on the species of thrips harmful to cultures of *Zantedeschia aethiopica*, *Dianthus caryophyllus* and *Rosa sp.* revealed a single species of thrips, *Frankliniella occidentalis*. Attack rate was 100%, and treatments alternating with insecticides were made for pest control. In cultures of *Rosa sp.*, in the vicinity of the greenhouses, the thysanoptere association consists of three species, *Frankliniella occidentalis* being accompanied by polyphagous *Frankliniella intonsa* and *Thrips tabaci*. Numerical abundances record low values, *F. occidentalis*, dominating the other two species at all the moments of collection with relative weight values that ranged between 50.72%- 80%.

Keywords: *Frankliniella occidentalis*, greenhouses, numerical abundance, chemical treatment.

1. Introduction

Until 1990, in Romania, the literature mentions several species of thrips as pests of ornamental plants in greenhouses: *Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis* (Bouché 1833), *Thrips dianthi* (Priesner 1921), *Parthenothrips dracaenae* (Heeger 1854), *Hercinothrips femoralis* (Reuter 1891), *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, 1889 (Knechtel, 1951; Manolache et al., 1982). Research conducted since 1990 have revealed a new thrips species with major potential for damaging: the western flower thrips (WFT), *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande 1895) (VasilIU-Oromulu, 1993). The species native to California, a remarkably polyphagous species with over 500 different species of host plants, is a quarantine pest. First appearance in Europe was believed to be before 1983 (Mantel et de Vrie, 1988).

The western flower thrips is vector for important viruses from the Bunyaviridae family: tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) and impatiens necrotic spot virus (INSV). Thrips can vector plant viruses in less than 30 minutes during feeding. Efficient transmission of TSWV by *F. occidentalis* is of 66%, by *F. intonsa* of 31.8%, and *Thrips tabaci* of 9.8%, while *F. occidentalis* is the only one capable of transmitting INSV with an efficiency of 85.4% (Wijkamp et al, 1995). Winter generations, dark colored, and the summer ones, light colored have the same capacity of virus transmission.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Observations were conducted from May to July 2008, in the greenhouses with ornamental plants of ADP Pitești, in *Zantedeschia aethiopica*, *Dianthus caryophyllus* and *Rosa sp.*

Subsequently, the culture of *Dianthus* was dissolved by transforming the plants into rooted cuttings, the culture of *Z. aethiopica* entered into diapause, as for *Rosa*, because of the massive attack of thrips that debilitated the plant affecting the flowering, collections were no longer possible.

Because in recent years some of the greenhouses were closed down, maintaining only the culture of *Rosa sp.* on that area, several collections were made from this culture, in the months of July - August 2008.

Collecting the thrips from the flower was performed using a square frame with sides of 30 cm, covered with a white cloth, and for greater precision collection was also made directly from the flower with a brush, and 10 samples were taken every week, a flower representing a sample. On all three host plants, all samples showed thrips. To track the rate of attack, 10 flowers taken at random, at each collection, were collected from the cultures of the three ornamental plants.

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Because pronymph and nymph stages live in the soil, were collected only stages present in flowers, as adults and larvae of age I and II. The specimens were preserved in vials with

AGA, a mixture of 60% ethyl alcohol (10 parts), glycerine (1 part) and glacial acetic acid (1 part). Treatments performed during the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Treatment system during observations

Plant species	Date of treatment	Insecticide
<i>Zantedeschia aethiopica</i>	16 May	Diazol
	20 May	Mavrik 2 F 0,1%
	29 May	Actellic 0,3%
	17 July	Actara 25 WG 0,05%
<i>Dianthus sp.</i>	29 May	Actellic 0,3%
	11 July	Actara 25 WG 0,05%
<i>Rosa sp.</i>	16 May	Diazol
	12 June	Actellic 0,3%
	17 June	Actellic 0,3%
	25 June	Confidor Energy 0,2%
<i>Rosa sp.</i> (in abandoned greenhouses)	12 June	Actellic 0,3%
	4 July	Actellic 0,3%
	13 August	Confidor Energy 0,2%

3. Results and discussions
a. Thrips species in greenhouses of ADP

and *Rosa sp.* showed 5,937 individuals, adults and larvae. They belong to a single species, *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Table 2).

Collections made during May-July 2008 on *Zantedeschia aethiopica*, *Dianthus caryophyllus*

Table 2. The numerical density of *Frankliniella occidentalis* populations on ornamental plants in greenhouses ADP Pitesti, 2008

Plant species	Date of collection	No of specimens				average no./ flower
		larvae	adults			
			total adults	♂♂	♀♀	
<i>Zantedeschia</i>	23 May	31	343	22	321	37.4
	30 May	23	371	32	339	39.4
	6 June	181	159	13	146	34
	12 June	73	210	35	175	28.3
	20 June	26	193	27	166	21.9
	27 June	27	209	23	186	23..6
Total		361	1485	152	1333	30.7
<i>Dianthus sp.</i>	23 May	8	205	19	186	21.3
	30 May	25	283	31	252	30,8
	6 June	81	115	27	88	19.6
	12 June	32	130	28	102	16.2
	20 June	36	197	26	171	23.3
	27 June	20	363	28	335	38.3
	4 July	23	507	40	467	53
11 July	18	525	60	465	54.3	
Total		243	2325	259	2066	32.1
<i>Rosa sp.</i>	23 May	146	120	14	106	26.6
	30 May	80	444	24	420	52.4
	6 June	131	143	2	141	27.4
	12 June	166	293	15	278	45.9
Total		523	1000	55	945	38.07
Total general		1127	4810	466	4344	

According to literature data, in greenhouses, *Frankliniella occidentalis* can have up to 15 generations per year. The total life-cycle from egg to egg at 20, 25 and 30°C is 22.4, 18.2 and 15 days, respectively (Bryan and Smith, 1956; Lublinkof and Foster, 1977).

The short duration of development of the species stages, large interval between collections (weekly) and lack of monitoring on a longer period (cultures were dissolved) have allowed to clearly reveal the number of generations in this case. To those is added the fact that, due to the large number of generations and female high longevity, an overlapping of the development stages of several generations is found. The female usually lives about 40 days under laboratory conditions but can survive as long as 90 days.

During observations were favorable conditions for the development of WFT populations. At all data collection, *F. occidentalis* showed large

numerical abundances of the two stages, adults and larvae (Table 2). According to Figs. 1 and 2, in *D. caryophyllus* and *Z. aethiopica*, numerical abundance in *Frankliniella occidentalis* presents a maximum of the number of adults in collections from 30th May, and subsequently it regresses as a result of treatments on 29th May. Treatments do not affect the eggs, so that the pest population is maintained at high values due to the emergence of larvae, but also due to the lack of further treatments.

Sex ratio

In *F. occidentalis*, as in most species of thrips, females are much more numerous than males, sex-ratio having a sub-unit value: 0.11 (Table 3).

This situation may be caused by short-lived males and to the fact that higher temperatures favor the emergence of a greater number of females to many species, in greenhouses.

Table 3. Sex ratio to *F. occidentalis*

♂♂		♀♀		♂♂ / ♀♀	
No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
466	9.7	4344	90.3	466/4344	0.11

Fig. 1. Population dynamics of *Frankliniella occidentalis* on *Zantedeschia aethiopica*, May-June 2008

Potential pest

According to literature data, the tolerance threshold of ornamental plants is of 10-12 individuals/flower. The data obtained show high values of numerical abundance far exceeding this

threshold, highest values occurring in *Dianthus* - 54 individuals/flower and *Rosa* - 52 individuals/flower (Table 2). Moreover, to *Rosa*, as a result of aggressive attack of thrips,

debilitated plants have not flowered, limiting the number of collections.

Regarding the frequency of attacks, all plants had seen the attack, it is 100%, with intensities

ranging from one plant to another. The attack was reported on flowers and leaves as holes and areas of silvery discoloration when the plant reacts to the insect's saliva.

Fig. 2. Population dynamics of *Frankliniella occidentalis* on *Dianthus caryophyllus*, May-June 2008

b. Thrips species from cultures of *Rosa* sp. in the abandoned greenhouses

During July – August from the flowers of *Rosa* sp. from the abandoned greenhouses, 803

individuals were collected, of which 242 larvae, belonging to the species of *Frankliniella occidentalis*, *Frankliniella intonsa* (Trybom 1895) and *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman 1888) (Table 3).

Table 3. The numerical density of thrips species populations from cultures of *Rosa* sp. in the abandoned greenhouses

Date of collection	Species									Total specimens
	<i>F. occidentalis</i>			<i>F. intonsa</i>			<i>Thrips tabaci</i>			
	♀♀	♂♂	average no./ flower	♀♀	♂♂	average no./ flower	♀♀	♂♂	av. no./ flower	
30 July	94	3	9.7	30	0	3	3	0	0.3	130
8 August	30	5	3.5	32	0	3.2	2	0	0.2	69
15 August	80	1	8.1	48	0	4.8	0	0	0	129
22 August	30	27	5.7	10	5	1.5	0	0	0	72
29 August	103	13	11.6	44	1	4.5	0	0	0	161

F. occidentalis constantly present in the samples dominates the other two species; relative abundance values ranged from 50.72% to 80% (Fig. 3). However, this species is unable to survive cold winters, so when cold weather comes most individuals go into the greenhouses, and in spring capture again the niche in the

neighbourhood. At all data collection, numerical abundances are much lower than those observed in greenhouses, and damage is insignificant.

Thrips tabaci, polyphagous, florivorous and cosmopolitan species, has been encountered only sporadic presence in collections in late July and

early August, with insignificant values of relative abundance: 1.82 % and 2.90 %.

Euro-Siberian polyphagous *Frankliniella intonsa*, known as inflorescences thrips, is constantly present in all samples collected, and is very well adapted to temperate conditions. However, the relative abundance values are

below those of *F. occidentalis*. Close values of the the dominance of the two species of *Frankliniella* is observed on 8th August. *Frankliniella intonsa* and *Thrips tabaci* have migrated from the spontaneous flora in the vicinity of greenhouses.

Fig. 3. Relative abundance of thrips species on *Rosa* sp.

Fighting of thrips species in greenhouses ADP Pitesti

Despite all its disadvantages, the chemical method remains the only method used for the control of Californian thrips in the ADP Pitesti greenhouses. In Denmark, for example, 98% of the area of greenhouse vegetables is presently managed with biological control practices, but biological control in ornamentals is in its infancy (Bradsgaard, 1995).

Chemical control is difficult due to the phenomenon of resistance to insecticides. To prevent this, were used by alternating different types of insecticides (Table 1). However, insecticides used fail to combat the pest population drastically, so it remains at high levels. Nymphae remaining in the soil is surfacing, attacking new plants.

4. Conclusions

Research conducted during the year 2008 in cultures of *Zantedeschia aethiopica*, *Dianthus caryophyllus* and *Rosa* sp. from the ADP Pitesti greenhouses, revealed 5937 individuals, adults and larvae, belonging to a single species of thrips, *Frankliniella occidentalis*. This is an invasive species, that was able to eliminate the other species of thrips mentioned in the literature before 1990 as pest of greenhouse ornamental plants.

At all data collection, *Frankliniella occidentalis* populations showed large numerical abundance.

The females are much more numerous than the males, so the sex-ratio has a sub-unit value: 0.11

Climatic conditions during the summer favour the development of individuals of *F. occidentalis* in the vicinity of greenhouses, with low numerical abundances values.

To control the population of this pest, several types of insecticides are used by alternation, but they fail to drastically reduce the pest population.

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THE INFLUENCE OF FOREST EXPLOITATIONS, WHEN COLLECTING THE WOOD WITH THE TRACTOR, OVER THE HEALTH CONDITION OF THE TREES FROM CASOCA SITE

A.N. BRICIU* **M.S. STROESCU**** **C.M. BRICIU****

Abstract: *This study looks into the different influences, biotic, abiotic and anthropogenic on the state of health of the stand in Casoca site.*

Keywords: *forestry exploitation, collecting wood, standing trees, damage, state of health.*

1. Site and method of research

In order to establish the various influences on the state of health of the trees in the Casoca site there were conducted determinations in various places on the site, as well as in forest divisions of main products, reengaged, from within the Private Forestry Nehoiu. From a territorial point of view the Casoca site is located in the North-West of Buzau County; geographically, the surface is in the external part of the Carpathians, in the Podu Calului Mountains, part of Buzau Mountains.

To estimate the state of health of the trees it is necessary to record the physiological damage (defoliation, discolouring), as well as physical damage caused by various factors (game, insects, fungus, abiotic agents, anthropic agents, etc, as presented in table 1 (according to the M.AP.A.M Order no. 454/July 14 2003 concerning the approval of the Technical Regulations for the protection of forests and of the guidelines concerning the practice of the Technical Regulations for the protection of forests).

Table 1

Damage types	
1.Physiological damage	2.Physical damage
a. defoliation	a. game and large domestic animals
b. discolouring	b.foliated and xylophagus insects
	c. foliated and xylophagus fungi
	d.abiotic agents (wind, snow, frost, hail, etc)
	e.anthropic agents (skratching, barking, branding by axe, resin tapping, damage caused by exploitation and collecting of wood)
	f.other damage (fire, pollution, etc.)

As far as the physical damage are concerned, the presence of biotic pest will be analyzed, setting the intensity of the attack, as well as the presence of the hygienic and accidental products for 2008-2011 in the stand of Casoca site, to stress the destabilizing and limiting factors.

To determine the level of damage on the standing trees the following were taken into consideration:

- The samples with a basis diameter of ≥ 10 cm were recorded;
- The damage caused by collecting wood with a tractor was recorded;
- The damage since the last forestry intervention was recorded;

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The damage caused to the standing trees was recorded on the samples placed along the tractor collecting tracks.

Based on the office and field documentation for the monitoring of the ipidae and defoliation agents populations in the Cașoca site for the period 2008-2011, pest attacks were of a very weak intensity - weak (eg the situation of the population of *Lymantria monacha*, Table 2 and the average number of beetles captured in a pheromone trap - Table 3 and Fig. 1).

2. Research results

Table 2

Specifications	2008	2009	2010	2011
Number of traps	5	5	5	5
Number of captured male butterflies				
	281	257	358	276

Table 3

Specifications	2008	2009	2010	2011
Number of traps	5	5	5	5
Average number of captured beetles in a pheromone trap				
	149	135	163	185

Fig. 1. Variation of the average number of beetles in ipidae 2008-2011

In the Ipidae populations there is noticed a tendency to increase in Figure 1, which is closely related to an occurrence of accidental products with significant volumes of softwood.

respective moments, after which they were pointed out and exploited, the volume distribution into groups of species being specified in Tables 4 and 5.

Hygiene products and accidents occurred during the period 2008-2011, were related to the

Table 4

Nature of product	Volume (m ³)			
	2008	2009	2010	2011
Hygiene cuttings	457	613	1444	366
Accidental I	0	0	212	1461
Fellings I	0	0	0	1362
Accidental II	0	0	0	24
TOTAL	457	613	1656	3213

Table 5

Nature of product	Total volume (m ³)	Out of which:			
		Softwood	Beech	D.T.	D.M.
2 0 0 8					
Hygiene cuttings	457	362	91	0	4
2 0 0 9					
Hygiene cuttings	613	334	275	0	4
2 0 1 0					
Hygiene cuttings	1444	587	838	0	19
Accidental I	212	144	68	0	0
<i>Total:</i>	<i>1656</i>	<i>731</i>	<i>906</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>19</i>
2 0 1 1					
Hygiene cuttings	360	191	169	0	6
Accidental I	921	608	853	0	0
Fellings I	1362	703	654	5	0
Accidental II	24	23	1	0	0
<i>Total:</i>	<i>3213</i>	<i>1525</i>	<i>1677</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>
TOTAL	-	2952	2949	5	33

Fig. 2 Volume distribution into groups of species for 2008-2011

Figure 2 shows that the volume of the hygiene and accidental products has increased considerably over the years 2010 and 2011, mainly in beech, compared with softwood, which are more vulnerable. For 2011 should be considered the fellings and tears made by the snow in winter, which affected an area of 227.9 ha (9.6%), to which were added the windfalls and wind breaks in May and June, that affected an area of 229.1 ha (9.7%). The major problem is

that some wind breaks overlap the ones made by the snow, thus affecting the health of trees in the same compartments. As to the damage caused by the collection of wood with tractors there was made an inventorying and recording of operating data from three exploitation forest divisions within which there had been made progressive cuts in the light, as presented in Table 6, noting the species, diameter at 1.3 m, orientation position, type of injury, damage size, etc.

Table 6

Nr. crt.	Forest division	U.P./u.a.	Gross volume (m ³)	Surface (ha)	Average tree volume (m ³ /item)	
					Softwood	Deciduous trees
1.	204 Berteia	VI Cașoca /27B%	1527	11,2	2,51	4,53
2.	203 Tehărau	VICașoca /33B	859	10,1	0	4,34
3.	175 Pruncea	VI Cașoca /127E	453	4,0	3,44	5,73

Total:	2839	25,3	-	-
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By centralizing the field data, in table 7, we find that the intensity of the average damage is 30.2 times more significant in deciduous trees.

Table 7

Nr. crt.	Forest division	Inventoried number of trees	Percent of analyzed trees (%):					
			Total	Conifers	Deciduous trees	Of which damaged:		
						Total	Softwood	Deciduous trees
1.	204 Berteia	148	65,9	27,2	38,7	34,1	13,8	20,3
2.	203 Tehărău	76	67,5	0	67,5	32,5	0	32,5
3.	175 Prunca	41	76,0	22,7	53,3	24,0	9,8	14,2
% average damage			-	-	-	30,2	11,8	18,4

Fig. 3 Distribution of the percent of analyzed trees

In all the injured trees it was calculated the ratio of each surface damage (Sp) and the basis surface (S_{1.3}) of the tree in question, then centralized through average values for each forest division, resulting in an indicator. Depending on its value, the following levels of damage were established:

- $[(Sp) / (S_{1.3})] * 100 < 8 \%$, slightly damaged tree;

- $[(Sp) / (S_{1.3})] * 100 = (8 - 12 \%)$, moderately damaged tree;
- $[(Sp) / (S_{1.3})] * 100 > 12 \%$, highly damaged tree;

After analyzing the damage produced to the standing trees by collecting wood with tractors and the centralization of values for each forest division, resulted the levels of damage, their distribution being shown in Table 8.

Table 8

Nr. crt.	Forest division	Average basis surface	Average damage surface	Ratio value	Fitting
1.	204 Berteia	2860	76.10	11.3	moderately damaged tree
2.	203 Tehărău	2104	196.6	10.7	moderately damaged tree
3.	175 Prunca	1802	243.51	7.4	slightly damaged tree

After analyzing and processing the above data on the health of the trees in Casoca site, there were the following conclusions:

- The action of the injurious agents on the stand was due both to the biotic pests and abiotic, anthropogenic, etc., this being largely dependent on the structure and composition of the trees and especially the evolution and intensity of the climate factors, which later eased the formation and development of outbreaks of pests;
- The presence of abiotic agents almost in the same forest subdivisions lead to the idea of destabilizing and limiting factors in the affected stands; also there is a tendency of the affected volume to increase;

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3. Conclusions

- The physical injuries made by the anthropogenic factors are more significant in deciduous trees than in softwood, and the levels of damage for the three analyzed forest divisions are from weak to moderate.

As recommendations, to maintain a state of normal health, it is necessary to consider the following:

- Permanent and urgent retrieval of dried, broken or felled trees;
- Proper cleaning of the forest divisions after finishing the exploitation;
- Forbidding gazing;
- Permanent monitoring of forest pests and diseases.

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QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE ASPECTS OF THE STAND SUBJECT TO THINNINGS

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Abstract: *This study shows quantitative and qualitative aspects, important characteristics of the forestry production in our country.*

Keywords: *tree quality, tree growth, slenderness value, stand volume.*

1. Qualitative aspects of the stand

-Class of production – the stand’s capacity to produce timber depending on climatic and edaphic conditions, established with tables of production, depending on the average age and height of the even-aged stand and in relation to the height of the reference diameter, set at 50 cm, in the multi-year stands.
-The quality of the stand – it is estimated visually depending on the ratio of the timber to a specific number of sample trees.
-vegetation state – it is expressed through the growth power (vitality) of the constituent trees, as luxurious, highly active, active and slow, dependent on the general aspect of the trees. To establish it we consider the size of the growth from recent years, the density and colour of the leaves, the proportion of the crown, the proportion of the trunk pruned, as well as the presence or absence of lichens on the tree trunk.

-trees and stand health – it is estimated based on periodic investigations showing the presence or absence of fungal agents and pest attacks. We consider also the damage caused to the trees by game, abiotic agents (wind, snow, frost, hail, white frost, etc) and by the harvest and collecting the timber from within the stands upon the maintenance and hygiene work of the main and accidental products.

2. Quantitative aspects of the stand

- Tree growth
 - height growth
 - thickness growth
 - volume growth
- Stand growth and productivity
 - the average growth of the total production – it is obtained by dividing the total volume to its age, along the stand life, which makes a maximum, also known as the age of absolute exploitation.

Table 1

Species	Production class	Growth type	growth, in m ³ , at ages of.....years									
			30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	110	120
Mo	I	C.C.	21,2	22,0	19,5	17,0	14,9	12,4	10,6	9,1	7,6	6,3
		C.M.	14,2	16,1	17,0	17,1	16,9	16,4	15,7	15,1	14,4	13,8
	V	C.C.	6,1	7,2	7,8	8,0	7,7	6,9	6,2	5,0	4,1	3,0
		C.M.	2,8	3,8	4,6	5,1	5,5	6,7	5,8	5,8	5,6	5,4
Fa	I	C.C.	13,3	15,0	15,2	14,2	13,1	11,9	10,6	9,3	8,0	6,9
		C.M.	8,2	9,8	10,9	11,5	11,8	11,9	11,7	11,6	11,3	10,9
	V	C.C.	3,6	5,2	6,1	6,2	6,2	5,7	5,1	4,5	3,8	3,0
		C.M.	1,5	2,2	3,0	3,6	3,9	4,1	4,3	4,3	4,3	4,2

The periodic current growth and average growth for the pure and echiene stand is

extracted from production tables (table 1) which shows a variation from one species to

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the other, and for the same species the growth is differentiated by the stationary conditions.
 -the stand productivity (the average growth of the total production) – with different values,

depending on the potential of the species and station grade of fertility (table 2).

Table 2

Species	Stand productivity (m ³ /year/ha)		
	superior	medium	inferior
European silver fir	14,2	9,7	5,9
Norway spruce	17,1	11,1	5,8
Scots pine	13,1	7,5	3,1
Common oak (s)	12,7	8,2	4,8
Sessile oak (s)	10,5	6,7	3,8
Turkey oak	10,5	6,9	3,9
Hungarian oak	8,0	5,7	3,7
Common beech	11,8	7,8	4,3
(black) locust	19,2	10,7	5,1
Common hornbeam	10,5	7,5	3,9
Indigenous poplar	20,9	11,7	4,8
White willow	29,3	19,2	7,2
Silver lime	14,0	9,2	5,7

-timber production- it is estimated at exploitability age of the stand, reported per hectare, due to the growth of the trees and stand, expressing the quantitative and qualitative production of forest woody biomass.
 -the green mass of the foliage – it is estimated as 6-8t/ha in deciduous and 35-40 t/ha in softwood.

During the works of care and management of trees used in our country, we differentiate between the following groups
 -maintenance of seedlings and cultures through achieving massive state;
 -maintenance after achieving massive state (table 3);
 -special maintenance works.

Table 3

Denomination of the category and type of works	Development stage to execute the work
Maintenance works after achieving massive state	
release cutting	seedling, thicket
respacing	seedling, thicket
cleanings	pole forest, thicket stage
gladings	timber stage, high forest

To determine the stand volume we used a regression equation like:

$$V = bo(hg - b1) * P$$

where:

P- degree of canopy closure

hg - average height of the stand;
 bo, b1- regression values set according to the species (for Norway spruce and silver fir trees bo = 30 and b1 = 5, and for beech and oaks bo = 32 and b1 = 10), apud Giurgiu, V. 1979.

3. Research venue

In order to analyze and interpret various data were selected 5 forest subdivisions that were already covered with maintenance cuts (table 4), respectively thinnings. Enhancement

works were carried out by different forestry staff and the exploitation and utilization of timber by different economic agents.

Table 4

Nr. crt.	APV	U.P.	u.a.	Treatment	age	Surface (ha)		CLP	Extracted vol. m ³	Vol. m ³ /u.a.	growth. m ³ /year/ha	Closure degree
						effective	covered					
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	126	VI Casoca	28	SR	20	13,9	7,0	3	91	889	6,3	0,8
2	205	VI Casoca	29E	SR	45	1,0	1,0	3	49	367	12,7	0,9
3	122	VI Casoca	43A	SR	25	6,4	6,4	3	130	621	10,1	0,9
4	160	XI Goidea sca	27D	SR	50	4,9	4,9	3	260	2347	15,0	0,9
5	107	II Monteoru	7B	SR	40	7,0	5,6	3	140	1988	9,3	0,9

4. Research result

Table 5

Nr crt.	APV	Inclination g	Covered surface ha	Extracted volume (m ³)										Extracted vol. per ha
				Total		Resinuos		Beech		D.T.		D.M.		
				gross	l. work	gross	l. work	gross	l. work	gross	l. work	gross	l. work	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	126	38	7,0	91	65	79	64	10	1	-	-	2	0	13,0
2	205	28	1,0	49	38	48	38	-	-	1	0	-	-	49,0
3	122	23	6,4	130	102	114	95	14	6	2	1	-	-	20,31
4	160	20	4,9	260	218	260	218	-	-	-	-	-	-	53,06
5	107	28	5,6	140	90	97	82	26	5	17	3	-	-	25,0

Table 6

Specifications	Average diameter, cm			Average height, m			Slenderness value H/D		
	Br	Mo	Fa	Br	Mo	Fa	Br	Mo	Fa
u.a. 28	10	10	8	7	7	6	0,7	0,7	0,75
u.a. 29E	-	22	-	-	19	-	-	0,86	-
u.a. 43A	10	10	-	8	8	-	0,8	0,8	-
u.a. 27D	-	28	-	-	23	-	-	0,82	-
u.a. 7B	29	22	20	17	18	17	0,58	0,81	0,85
APV 126	17,0	19,0	14,1	13,1	14,2	10,0	0,77	0,74	0,71
APV 205	-	31,1	-	-	20,3	-	-	0,65	-
APV 122	31,5	22,5	29,4	24,4	21,2	22,0	0,77	0,94	0,74
APV 160	-	26,6	-	-	22,7	-	-	0,85	-
APV 107	32,5	24,9	43,3	22,6	18,9	24,1	0,89	0,76	0,55

By analyzing fig. 1 it shows that the percent of timber is quite high, especially in softwood, which means that in the field there was carried out the top thinning, made out of

high diameter and height trees, not extracting specimens with a small diameter from lower floors.

Fig. 1. Distribution of volume extracted into groups of species

Fig. 2. Comparing the slenderness values (a. and b.) (a. forest division description; b. APV)

The analysis of slender values, calculated from the forest divisions descriptions and acts of exploiting shows a slight increase in softwood and a decrease in hardwood, resulting from the enhancement of upper floor

specimens. Also, between the slender value and the injuries caused by wind and snow, there is a strong connection, and thus the frequency of the damage is accentuated as the ratio h / d increases above the unitary value.

Table 7

Nr. crt.	U.P./u.a.	Volume of the stand				
		According to the regression equation (V1)	Adjusted to the growth (V2)	Extracted through thinnings (E)	Standing	
					V1-E	V2-E
0	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	VI/28	1309	1449	91	1218	1358
2	VI/29E	413	458	49	364	409
3	VI/43A	1091	1138	130	961	1008
4	XI/27D	2579	2612	260	2319	2352
5	II/7B	2690	2281	140	2550	2141

The analysis of table 7 and figure 3 shows that the volume of the stand, as a significant feature of the forestry production, differs as a method of calculation, as there are no significant differences, except lot 107 (U.P. II, u.a. 7B).

Fig. 3. Analysis of the standing volume

5. Conclusions

Table 8

Nr. crt.	Stages (age, development stage)	Biometric parameters and structure	Technical recommendations
1	Thicket stage 12(15)-25 years old	Large number of specimens of the basis species Height active growth Average diameter.....cm Ratio H/D Number of specimens 2500-3500 items/ha	For spruce and fir are required combined interventions, moderate to strong in intensity, every 5-8 years, which provides the most significant growth in the basis surface and volume by the age of 50 years. After that we recommend moderate thinnings every 8-10 years.
2	Pole forest 25-45 years old	Highly active growth in height Average diameter.....cm Average heightm Number of specimens 1500-2500 items/ha Ratio H/D	For beech are required thinning and mass selection, respectively
3	Timber stage 45-70 years old	Highly active growth in width Average diameter.....cm Average heightm Number of specimens 400-800 items/ha Ratio H/D	extracting overwhelming species (aspen, willow, birch, alder, etc.), as well as qualitatively unfit items. In the first thinning the tree crown spacing is recommended and the uniformity of their arrangement in the field. For the second and third thinnings can be executed strong intensity interventions (25-30%) and can be reduced to 0.7 for a growth in thickness. In these intervention will take into consideration the future trees,

			<p>reducing their number. The frequency of the damage caused by wind and snow grows as the value of the ration h/d exceeds unitary value. Taking on a higher periodicity in thinnings requires frequent hygiene cuttings on the same surface, which leads to a marked increase in exploitation costs and injuries caused to the standing trees during the harvesting and collecting of wood.</p>
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MOISTURE CONTENT DETERMINATION AT FRESHLY FELLED COMMON HORNBEAM WOOD

V.R. CÂMPU*

Abstract: *The paper presents, on the one hand, the results of the research concerning moisture content determination of freshly felled common hornbeam wood and, on the other hand, two distinct methods of determining the moisture content. The results obtained show that the absolute moisture content of freshly felled common hornbeam wood varies between 68.84% and 85.05%. Significant differences have been noticed between the values obtained by using the classical method, which presupposes the drying of the wood in the oven, and the electrical method. Differences vary between 19.58 and 68.81%.*

Keywords: *common hornbeam, wood moisture content.*

1. Introduction

Wood is a hygroscopic material, its moisture content being dependant at all times by the humidity and temperature of the surrounding environment. Any change of these two elements triggers a change of wood moisture content (Vintilă, 1942). Moisture content represents a very important characteristic of wood with significant influences on its physical and mechanical properties (Beldeanu, 2001). For this paper it is important insofar as it is one of the factors which help to determine the apparent specific volumic mass of wood which is used in the measuring and the recording of wood volumes. All forest measurement tables which refer to wood apparent volumic mass, to wood weight or to conversion factors for the transformation of tones into cubic meters, have wood moisture content as main determining factor. With any change of wood moisture content situated under the fibre saturation point, there is a change of wood dimensions, a

contraction or a swelling of wood takes place therefore a change of wood apparent volumic mass. Above the fibre saturation point, wood dimensions and volume remain constant and the influence upon wood apparent volumic mass is due to the filling with water of the spaces between cells and of cell empty spaces (Beldeanu, 2001). Wood moisture content can be absolute, when it represents the water content of wood as opposed to its mass in an anhydrous state and, it can be relative when it represents the quantity of water as opposed to the wood mass in a hydrous state (Leahu, 1994). Therefore, the purpose of the present paper is to determine the moisture content of freshly felled common hornbeam wood and to identify the most precise method of moisture content determination.

2. Research Method

The research has taken place in four forest districts according to table 1.

Research venue				
Species	County Forest Administration	Forest District	Management Unit	Felling Area
Common hornbeam	Sibiu	Mediaş	U.P. I Şeica Mică	504
			U.P. IV Bazna	610
		Dumbrăveni	U.P. IV Valchid	613
	Vâlcea	Râmnicu Vâlcea	U.P. II Goranu	841

In every work venue wood moisture content has been determined by two methods:

a) From every wood piece a slice has been extracted and weighed with the help of an electronic balance with a precision of 1 gram. In

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the laboratory the slices have been dried in the oven at a temperature of $103 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (Vintilă, 1943; Ghelmeziu, 1944; Leahu 1994; Dumitraşcu and Bădescu, 2009) until their mass remained

constant, this representing the wood mass in a totally dry state or the wood mass in an anhydrous state (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The weighing and drying of wood slices

Once the dry mass of sample pieces has been determined, the wood moisture content could be calculated by using the following relations:

- absolute moisture content

$$u = \frac{m_u - m_o}{m_o} \cdot 100[\% ,] \quad (1)$$

- relative moisture content

$$x = \frac{m_u - m_o}{m_u} \cdot 100[\% ,] \quad (2)$$

where:- m_u represents the mass of the green slice
- m_o represents the mass of the dry slice

b) Because in real situations the determination of wood moisture content based on the difference between the mass of green wood and the mass of dry wood is difficult, the moisture content of wood slices has also been determined by measurements with the Gann Hydromette HT 85 T electric humidometer. The wood relative moisture content in transversal section has been determined, this being the average of three measurements. Measurements have been made at a distance from the periphery of the transversal section of approximately one third of the radius length (Fig. 2).

Absolute wood moisture content has been determined based on the following relation:

$$u = \frac{x}{1 - x}, \quad (3)$$

where: u and x signify the same thing as in the previous relations.

Fig. 2. Measurement of relative wood moisture content

3. Results Obtained

As a result of all measurements and determinations the values of absolute wood

moisture content have been obtained as presented in Table 2.

Absolute wood moisture content of freshly felled common hornbeam wood Table 2

No.	Forest District							
	Mediaș, Șeica Mică		Mediaș, Bazna		Dumbrăveni		Vâlcea	
	u (%)		u (%)		u (%)		u (%)	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
1	73.93	85.87	86.51	131.75	91.63	133.10	70.59	90.48
2	77.76	101.61	101.04	128.83	70.68	96.66	71.60	135.29
3	79.44	104.08	106.36	107.47	76.12	101.01	82.03	129.89
4	75.05	76.68	60.30	127.01	76.58	107.04	74.33	124.72
5	75.78	80.50	108.34	135.29	78.95	131.75	65.22	110.97
6	74.27	108.33	98.23	99.60	78.14	133.64	62.31	110.97
7	72.08	85.18	77.73	98.41	90.12	120.26	75.48	122.22
8	73.23	90.47	75.42	165.25	79.82	104.92	64.92	138.10
9	71.63	73.91	45.93	143.90	78.43	126.76	53.63	124.47
10	76.87	104.08	96.48	150.00	70.76	119.78	57.60	125.23
11	96.74	106.39	-	-	71.55	118.82	71.08	136.41
12	70.18	100.20	-	-	75.29	89.75	60.19	139.52
13	63.26	92.12	-	-	74.09	87.97	72.84	135.85
14	65.08	99.40	-	-	79.43	87.62	70.58	167.74
15	78.60	88.14	-	-	79.76	96.08	60.77	142.72
16	70.32	86.39	-	-	-	-	64.50	142.13
17	74.79	90.11	-	-	-	-	60.89	140.96
18	58.87	94.93	-	-	-	-	61.90	118.34
19	68.53	93.05	-	-	-	-	85.77	145.10
20	78.98	113.67	-	-	-	-	81.63	140.96
21	77.72	121.23	-	-	-	-	85.15	139.23
22	96.83	111.19	-	-	-	-	84.60	135.85
23	79.70	84.33	-	-	-	-	72.16	130.95
24	66.27	82.81	-	-	-	-	64.51	149.38
25	78.04	113.90	-	-	-	-	71.50	134.74
26	80.63	102.02	-	-	-	-	67.80	186.53
27	79.97	108.11	-	-	-	-	58.39	121.48
28	63.47	84.16	-	-	-	-	69.00	150.00
29	74.34	74.21	-	-	-	-	56.81	108.99
30	66.83	78.57	-	-	-	-	65.16	135.29
Average value	74.59	94.17	85.05	126.24	77.18	110,13	68.84	136.85

a – method of determining wood absolute moisture content based on the water quantity from wood as opposed to wood dry mass

b – electric method of determining wood moisture content

The average values of absolute moisture content have been calculated considering the sum of the masses of wood pieces in a green and dry state using relation 1 from point 2.

It can be noticed that the values of the absolute moisture content determined by the two methods vary a lot, the differences being between 19.58% in the case of Șeica Mică from the Forest District of Mediaș and 68.81% in the case of Vâlcea.

The precision of measurements made with the electric humidometer depends on many factors, the most important of which being the uniformity of water distribution inside wood and wood temperature. Most electric humidometers measure wood resistance when electricity passes through. This resistance is great in the case of dry wood and it decreases with the increase of wood moisture content, measurements being more precise in the case of moisture contents situated

below the fibre saturation point. From this point of view common hornbeam is part of the species of broadleaves with scattered pores having a fibre saturation point between 32 and 35% (Beldeanu, 2001). At the same moisture content wood resistance when electricity passes through decreases with the increase of wood temperature and the other way round. The higher the moisture content is, the higher the dependence on wood temperature (***, 2011).

On the other hand, wood moisture content varies within broad limits inside wood pieces. Measurements made with the electric humidometer, in the same transversal section, have revealed, in some cases, differences above 10 – 15%. In the case of freshly felled wood the moisture content is higher towards the periphery of the section than in the centre of the section.

Another important factor which influences freshly felled wood moisture content is the species or the group of species. Thus, hard broadleaves have a moisture content between 60...100%, the maximum moisture content at common hornbeam being approximately 93% (Beldeanu, 2001).

The period of the year when the tree is felled also influences wood moisture content. The present research has been conducted in August and September.

5. Conclusion

The results obtained show that in the case of research and production work where there is a need to determine wood moisture content, it is

highly necessary that this be determined by using method <a>, especially at wood with a moisture content situated above the fibre saturation point with water. The values of absolute moisture content determined by method <a> for freshly felled hornbeam wood are within known limits and they do not exceed 93%.

It is possible that in spring, once vegetation begins, the water content of common hornbeam might be greater and this issue will be approached in a future research.

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RESEARCH CONCERNING HORNBEAM WOOD APPARENT VOLUMIC MASS AND WEIGHT DECREASE

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Abstract: *The paper presents the results of the research conducted with the purpose of determining apparent volumic mass at freshly felled hornbeam wood as well as its weight decrease over a storage period of three months. The results have shown that apparent volumic mass varies according to environmental conditions, tree age where wood comes from and its moisture content. Stored wood weight decrease is due to wood moisture content decrease and it highly depends on weather and on storage conditions.*

Keywords: *common hornbeam, apparent volumic mass, weight decrease..*

1. Introduction

At present, the unit of measurement used for wood converted to cordwood or to lengths of two or three meters is the cubic meter. Moreover, certain beneficiaries verify these categories of wood by weighing expressed by t/m^3 or kg/m^3 . Likewise, for an evaluation of costs and fuel consume at logging and transport the mass unit becomes important (Kruch, 1994). Therefore, it is necessary that the conversion factors be established for the transformations which are made between weight and volume. The physical unit which permits this is apparent volumic mass represented by the ratio between wood mass and volume determined under the same moisture content conditions. Because of the two anatomical elements – wood and bark - there are three different volumic masses: that of wood with bark, that of wood without bark and that of bark (Kruch, 1994). In the present paper by apparent

volumic mass we mean apparent volumic mass of wood with bark.

Wood is a hygroscopic material, its moisture content being influenced at all times by the surrounding environment humidity and temperature, any change in these two elements triggering a change in wood moisture content (Vintila, 1942) and, implicitly, a change in its mass and volume. Therefore, the purpose of the present paper is the determination of freshly felled common hornbeam wood apparent volumic mass and its weight decrease over a storage period of three months under the conditions from the primary platform of felling areas.

2. Research Method

The research has taken place in four forest districts according to Table 1, on the platform of felling areas.

Research venue

Table 1

Species	Forest County Administration	Forest District	Management Unit	Felling Area
Common hornbeam	Sibiu	Mediaş	U.P. I Şeica Mică	504
			U.P. IV Bazna	610
		Dumbrăveni	U.P. IV Valchid	613
	Vâlcea	Râmnicu Vâlcea	U.P. II Goranu	841

In every felling area common hornbeam wood has been converted to lengths of one meter and the volume for each piece has been determined

by the xylometric method and the mass by weighing (Fig. 1).

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Fig. 1. The xylometric method and the weighing of wood pieces

Knowing the mass (m) and the volume of wood pieces (v) the apparent volumic mass (ρ) could be determined for each piece with the relation:

$$\rho = \frac{m}{v} \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}, \quad (1)$$

For each piece, wood moisture content has been determined by using the classical method which presupposes the drying of a wood sample in the oven until its mass remains constant. Thus, wood absolute moisture content will be equal to the ratio of the difference between the sample green and dry mass as opposed to the dry mass of the sample.

During wood storage period its mass decreases due to its drying so mass determinations were made monthly over a period of three months using the wood pieces established at wood apparent volumic mass determination. These were stored under similar conditions with those from the primary platform of the felling area.

3. Results Obtained

Determinations and measurements of freshly felled common hornbeam wood allowed the establishment of apparent volumic mass for each source as well as the weight decrease of wood over a storage period of three months according to Table 2.

Common Hornbeam apparent volumic mass and weight loss

Table 2

Forest District	Age (Years)	Site Quality	Apparent volumic mass (kg/m ³)	Absolute Moisture Content (%)	Storage Period	Weight decrease (%)		
						After ... Storage months		
						1	2	3
Mediaş -Şeica Mică-	65	M	1023	75	5 August – 5 November	16,59	19,54	21,23
Mediaş -Bazna-	80	S	1027	85	8 August – 8 November	8,61	16,38	19,42
Dumbrăveni	80	M	1046	77	10 August – 10 November	8,88	11,63	13,88
Vâlcea	90	M	1003	69	25 August – 25 November	12,05	14,35	15,35

M – medium site quality; S – superior site quality.

Apparent volumic mass depends on many factors, the most important of which being age and environmental conditions expressed by the site quality (Leahu, 1994; Giurgiu *et al.*, 2004). This is confirmed by the results obtained following the present research if we consider wood moisture content. The lowest value of the volumic mass is registered under conditions of superior site quality in Bazna, where moisture content is 85%. Higher values of the apparent volumic mass are registered in the present case, under conditions of average site quality in Seica Mica, Dumbrăveni and Vâlcea. A more rigorous comparison could be made if wood volumic mass is known when the moisture content is zero.

As far as the influence of tree age on wood apparent volumic mass is concerned under similar environmental conditions, it could be said that apparent volumic mass increases with tree age. This increase is mainly determined by the decrease of the average width of the annual ring. The annual ring width determines a significant increase of wood apparent volumic mass as the site quality decreases. (Giurgiu *et al.*, 2004).

Research has emphasized a variation of absolute moisture content between 69% in Vâlcea and 85% in Bazna, forest District of Mediaș in the case of freshly felled common hornbeam wood.

Weight decrease of stored wood is due to the decrease of wood moisture content and highly depends on weather and storage conditions. Thus, Vintilă (1942) shows that wood moisture content in open air is determined mainly by the variation of atmospheric humidity and then by temperature. Likewise, it has been noticed that the effect of one rain on wood moisture content is only on the surface and once the rain has stopped, wood surface releases into the atmosphere the water surplus which it contains. The data

presented in Table 1 are representative for the weather in 2011 and for the storage conditions from the primary platform of felling areas. But it could be noticed that in November wood weight decrease almost stops, the differences between November and October being less than 3% and only 1% in Vâlcea.

4. Conclusions

Considering the results obtained it could be said that freshly felled common hornbeam wood is a heavy wood with densities between 1003 and 1046 kg/m³ at wood moisture contents between 69 and 85% depending on environmental conditions and tree age.

As far as weight decrease of common hornbeam wood converted to lengths of one meter is concerned, this decreases in the first three months from felling by 13.88% up to 21.23% of the initial weight depending on storage conditions and under direct influence of relative moisture content and of air temperature.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF STUMP HEIGHT ON THE COST OF FELLING TREES WITH CHAINSAW

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Abstract: *In this paper we tried to establish the correlation between fuel consumption in felling trees with chain saw and some dendrometric elements of felled trees, taking in consideration as base element the cut surface. The felling costs were determined based on the specific fuel and lubricant consumption, and wage expenses were determined based on the cut surface. The correlation between the felling costs and stump height is explained only in 30%.*

Keywords: *fuel, chainsaw, consumption, stump height.*

1. Introduction

The chainsaws were the first machinery introduced in logging operations. In time they have evolved in terms of handling, efficiency, reduction of fuel and lubricant consumption.

The evolution of fuel consumption in forestry was presented by Löfroth and Rådström (2006), showing the trend of continuous decrease.

Besides the problem of increasing efficiency and reducing fuel consumption in the machinery used in logging operation, another problem of great interest is that of the pollutant emissions reduction (Klvac and Skoupy, 2009). A way to solve this problem could be the use of hybrid machinery because they consume less and therefore they pollute less. (Löfroth et al. 2007).

The recent research led to the discovery of organic fuels and lubricants (Nati and Pasin, 2008), fuels and lubricants that can be used for chainsaws.

Regarding strictly the chainsaws subject, Kruch (1992, 1994) conducted some research on the theme of fuel consumption at tree felling and wood cross cutting. Kruch (1987, 1991) studied also the influence of cutting chain defects and cutting chain wear on the fuel consumption

After analyzing the correlation between the base diameter of the felled trees and fuel and lubricants consumption, Bajic and Danilovic (2003) noticed that this consumption decreases once with the diameter increase.

2. Research method

There were analyzed 261 beech trees in the felling stage, for each tree were recorded: the base diameter, stump diameter, stump height. Next step involved determining the cut surface, surface that was determined by digitizing the images of the stump with AutoCad Map (Enache and David, 2011).

The volume of technological consumptions was determined based on the cut surface and the cut width.

In order to determine the volume of wood that remains in stump, Shorohova et al. (2008), assimilates the stump shape with a truncated cone figure, considering therefore the correct use of known relationship to calculate the volume of this figure.

The cost of felling trees was calculated by summing up the wage expenses and the expenses corresponding for fuels and lubricants.

For the wage expenses we considered a monthly salary of 2000 RON and a average of hours worked in one month equal with 172, resulting an orar salary of 11,63 RON.

The productivity taken in consideration was 7,637 cm²/s and considering that 40% of the time is effectively worked, resulted the effective productivity equal to 3,05 cm²/s.

By dividing the cut surface with the effective productivity we obtain the time fund, further by multiplying this time fund with the orar salary we obtain the wage expenses.

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The fuels and lubricants costs were calculated based on the specific consumption:

- fuel 3,8612 ml/100cm²
- lubricating oil 0,9437 ml/100cm²
- oil blend 0,0724 ml/100cm²

Simple and multiple linear regression analysis was performed with Microsoft Excel, using the Data Analysis package.

3. Research results

The coerrelation coefficients between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees, stump height, base diameter and stump diameter

Table 1

	Wood consumption	Stump height	Base diameter	Stump diameter
Wood consumption	1			
Stump height	0,216407051	1		
Base diameter	0,945140623	0,174825647	1	
Stump diameter	0,968106372	0,220994818	0,973805	1

As we can see in table 1, we have strong direct correlation between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and base diameter, between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and stump diameter and between base diameter and stump diameter (Enache and David, 2011). Next step was the multiple regression analysis between the technological consumption of wood at felling

The correlation coefficient $r = 0,214$, resulted from the analysis of simple linear regression between the cut surface and stump height, indicate the existence of a connection of weak intensity.

The multiple correlation analysis has led to the obtaining of the correlation coefficients presented in table 1 for each of the combinations of variables investigated.

trees and stump height, base diameter and stump diameter. As a result of the regression analysis we obtained the regression table from which can be observed the multiple correlation coefficient $R = 0,968$. This value indicate that in this case we have a strong positive connection. The significance of the coefficients from the regression equation was further analyzed using „t” test (table 2).

Checking the signifiange of the coefficients from the regression equation using „t” test

Table 2

Characteristics	Coefficients	t experimental	t theoretical			Signifiange
			5%	1%	0,1%	
<i>f = 257 degrees of freedom</i>						
Free term	-2957,735	-25,6562	1,96	2,5758	3,2905	-
Stump height	1,3374	0,289223				-
Base diameter	6,11959	0,715705				-
Stump diameter	106,9821	13,02817				very significant

Analyzing the signifiange of the coefficients from the regression equation we can say that between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and stump height there is a positive correlation, there influence is insignificant; between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and base diameter there is a positive correlation, but his influence is also statistically insignificant: between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and stump diameter there is a strong

positive correlation, her influence is statistically significant.

Regarding the regression analysis between the stump volume and stump height, the correlation coefficient value is $r = 0,695$, value that indicate a connection of medium intensity.

The signifiange of the coefficients from the regression equation is verified using „t” test, and is presented in table 3.

Checking the significance of the coefficients from the regression equation using „t” test

Table 3

Characteristics	Coefficients	t experimental	t theoretical			Significance
			5%	1%	0,1%	
<i>f</i> = 259 grade de libertate						
Free term	-13144,2	-3,57261	1,96	2,5758	3,2905	-
Stump height	3579,065	15,56605				very significant

We can see that the value of experimental *t* is higher than theoretical *t* at the probability of transgression equal to 0,1%, the stump height has a significant influence on the volume variation, the stump volume increases with the stump height increasing. The correlation between the

stump volume and stump height is best shown by the equation presented in figure 1 ($R^2=0,813$).

Fig.1. The correlation of stump volume and stump height

Regarding the correlation between the felling costs and stump height (figure 2), the regression equation explain by considering only the stump height less than 30% of the costs variation.

As it was said in the research method, it was considered a monthly salary of 2000 RON and a

number of worked hours equal to 172, resulting an orar salary equal to 11,63 RON.

The effective productivity calculated was 3,05 cm²/s. The expenses with fuel and lubricants were calculated based on the specific consumptions and corresponding prices.

Fig.2. The correlation between the felling costs and stump height

4. Conclusions

The main conclusions that can be set based on the results obtained are as follows:

- The correlation coefficient between the cut surface and stump height, indicate the existance of a connection of weak intensity.
- We have strong direct correlation between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and base diameter, between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and stump diameter and between base diameter and stump diameter
- The multiple regression analysis between the technological consumption of wood at felling trees and stump height, base diameter and stump diameter indicate a strong positive relationship.
- The correlation coefficient between the stump volume and stump height indicate a connection of medium intensity.
- The regression equation explains, by considering only the stump height, less that 30% of the costs variation.

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RURAL TOURISM AS AN EMERGING SECTOR IN BRAN-MOIECIU-FUNDATA AREA

D. FRATU* R. GRUIA**

Abstract: *The present paper proposes to present rural tourism and agri-tourism issues and how they can influence the development of rural areas. In order to sustain the theoretical part, a study case on one of the most representative rural areas of Romania - Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area - was carried out. This study aims at presenting and evaluating the effects of rural and agri-tourism on an area. The presupposition of the authors is that rural tourism can be competitive only if it creates value both for demand and supply side and if the actors of the rural area cooperate their activities. The authors emphasize the role of suitable competences and resources.*

Keywords: *Rural tourism, agri-tourism, tourism development, sustainable tourism*

1. Introduction

The rural tourism is one of the main priorities of tourism development in many European countries. The market for rural holidays is growing at the same time as the future of many rural regions is uncertain, due to changes in agricultural practice or the increasing attractiveness of urban living standards. Rural tourism seems to be an appropriate tool to revitalize the declining rural areas and to ensure their sustainable future by job retention or even job creation, service retention, farm support, broadened cultural provision, landscape and nature conservation or the maintenance of rural arts and crafts as tourist attractions. Rural tourism often provides an incentive for infrastructural development, which then contributes to the growth of other economic activities in rural areas.

It seems to be simple to define rural tourism as "tourism that takes place in the countryside", but this definition does not include the complexity of the activity and the different forms and meanings developed in different countries. According to a broader definition, "rural tourism includes a range of activities, services and amenities provided by farmers and rural people to attract tourists to their area in order to generate extra income for their businesses" (Gunn, 2002). If this broader concept is accepted, rural tourism covers not only farm tourism or agri-tourism (which is generally what rural tourism means for most

people), but also special interest nature holidays, touring in rural areas, and the services include - besides accommodation - events, festivities, gastronomy, outdoor recreation, production and sale of handicrafts and agricultural products, etc.

The development of rural tourism (including active nature holidays or participation in farm activities) is still in an early stage and the profitability of rural tourism is very low in Romania). The presupposition of the author of this paper is that the rural (village) tourism in Romania can be competitive only if it creates value both for demand and supply side and if service providers cooperate in concern of success and the destination competitiveness.

The tourism plays a leading role in the development of many European regions. Sustainable tourism assures the preservation and improvement of regional cultural and natural heritage. The objective of the communion politics covering 2007–2013 is the complete mobilization of tourism for the sake of regional development and creating new work places (World Tourism Organization United Nations Agency (UNWTO).Annual Report - A year of recovery-Barometer 2010).

Although the tourism industry was in recession Worldwide due to the economic crisis, Europe exceeded expectations (with a 6 percent growth) and posted the highest growth in the first four months of 2011.

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Results reflect a delayed recovery in various European destinations and source markets. Destinations in Eastern and Southern Europe performed particularly well. (World Tourism Organization UNWTO PR No.: PR 11058 Madrid 30 Jun 11).

According ITB World Travel Trends Report 2011/12 the European destinations have had a

good year 2011 in touristic sector. The figure below, from 26 countries in Europe covering the year up to July or August, showed an 8.9% increase in overnight stays and a 9.7% increase in international arrivals. In Romania the overnight stays percentage increased with approximately 12 percent (Fig.1)

Fig. 1 Development of foreign arrivals in ETC member countries in 2011

Structural Funds and Cohesion Fund offer necessary support for improving the competitiveness of tourism and quality on a regional and local level.

Infrastructure that is being created for tourism is supporting local development and creating or maintaining work places even in regions that are described by the fading of industry or rural activity or where urbanism is being resurrected. This is why tourism is an important tool for the integration of less developed regions or for allowing them access to equal benefits that accompany economic growth.

Many countries consider tourism as a real and sustainable support for their economic development. The tourism was considered a really chance for Romania. Despite this, the travel and tourism economy contribution to Romanian GDP varied around 2 per cent in the last 10 years.

Tourism industry has an important role in the global economy as an indicator of economic status (Davenport, 2006), it has the role to reduce unemployment, create national income, raise the level of population's welfare etc (Liu, 2006).

Rural tourism is an economically significant sector of the Romanian economy and holds great potential in terms of sustainable rural development. Sustainable development for local communities should aim to improve the residents' quality of life by optimizing local economic benefits, protecting the natural and built environment and providing a high-quality experience for visitors.

We mention that, in the large field of Tourism and Nature or "green tourism", besides ecotourism, the agri-tourism is a complementary activity in the rural development process, which makes the agricultural activity profitable as it combines agriculture and tourism, improves

natural resources, contributes at the rural area socially and economically (Gruia 2000, Gruia, Ardeleanu, 2008). In many developing countries agriculture is vital for sustainable rural development and it is recognized as a main mean for reducing poverty and ensuring economic growth. In this sense, reducing poverty in rural areas depends significantly on sustainable agricultural development (Anonymous, 2003). However, agricultural development should be considered not only by increasing production but also in the sense of developing rural society.

Agri-Tourism is when a native person or local of the area offers tours to their Agriculture Farm and allows a person to view them growing, harvesting, and processing locally grown foods or any product the person would not encounter in their home country.

Rural and Agri-tourism are alternatives to bad practices, not just trips; their purpose is to stop things like dynamite fishing, destruction of forest, wearing out the soil, etc.

Rural tourism is a trip based on the desire to discover nature, with the purpose to meet the host culture and discover its habits, traditions.

Another positive effect of rural tourism is that it helps the local community to increase its income and it offers employment opportunities, without the least damaging effects on the natural environment (Goodwin, 2008).

2. Rural tourism as a tool for development of rural areas and family enterprises

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is the only global international organization dealing with the rules of trade between nations. WTO used rural tourism concept for defining that tourism product "that gives to visitors a personalized contact, a taste of physical and human environment of country side and as far as possible, allow them to participate in the activities, traditions and lifestyles of local people."

According to WTO it is considered as part of rural tourism a wide range of activities like: climbing, riding, adventure tourism, educational travel, sport and health tourism, arts and heritage tourism.

Rural tourism is a trend in Europe and is in a continuous growing. WTO estimates an annual growth of approximately 6% of rural tourism comparing with 2% growth of tourism in general. In a number of Southern and Eastern European countries the growth was strongly, more than

20%, due to some transformations which took place in the countryside and agriculture as a results of recently involved in the European Union.

The specific features of rural tourism are:

- First of all it is concentrated in rural areas.
- Second, it is based on small-scale and traditional activities and enterprises, environmental aspects and heritage.
- Third, it is related to small-scale buildings and settlements
- Fourth, it relies on traditional qualities of the countryside and develops slowly under the control of local people.
- Lastly it reflects the complexity of the rural environment and has several different forms.

In European countries rural tourism became an important segment of tourism. The Euro-Gites conference in 2003 reported that there were more than 200 thousand providers of Farm and Village Tourism registered in Europe, with more than 2 millions beds.

A Euro barometer survey on "Europeans on Holiday" showed that more and more people are interested not only in "sampling" new places but also in discovering different forms of tourism, placing greater emphasis on quality products, on more environmentally and culturally sensitive forms of tourism and on shorter but more frequent trips, while a significant number of Europeans (23%) choose the countryside as the most preferred tourism destination (WTO).

Rural areas and agricultural fields are two concepts that are usually used one instead of another. However, rural areas are multifunctional dynamic systems. They include different land use and activities such as settlement, transportation, industry, forestry, tourism and recreation. With the post-industrial revolution, urbanization and increased leisure time, tourism and recreation activities in rural areas have also increased.

On the other hand, in the restructuring process of economy in rural areas, one of the most obvious effects is the necessity to create job opportunities alternative to agricultural sector. In this respect agro-tourism, as part of rural tourism, is a valued option protecting the rural environment, sustaining small-sized enterprises and providing income and job opportunities.

Agri-tourism, which is defined as 'any tourism or recreation enterprise on a working farm' or 'form of rural tourism whereby paying guests can share in farming life either as staying guests or

day visitors on working farms' can be seen as a new income source for agricultural societies (Busby and Rendle, 2000).

Agri-tourism concept, the popularity of which increases steadily is actually not new and it is known that 25% of farms accept tourists in Romania for about 30 years (WTO).

Within the context of agricultural tourism there are services such as outdoor recreation (hunting, fishing, etc.), educational experiences (wine tasting, cooking classes), entertainment (festivals, etc.), and hospitality services (staying at the farm). In this context, advantages of agricultural tourism can be summarized as follows:

- Helps to protect the agricultural areas, cultivation lands and rural landscape.
- Creates diversity in agricultural pattern and job opportunities in rural areas.
- Provides opportunities for marketing the agricultural products.
- Increases welfare level of local people.
- Establishes social and economic relations between urban and rural dwellers.
- Provides a bridge between rural and urban areas.
- Meets the tourism and recreation needs of urban people.
- Increases the respectability of agricultural activity from the urban peoples' point of views.
- Introducing agricultural activities to urban people is a way to educate urban people in the sense of contribution of agriculture to quality of life and economy.

In addition to the above-mentioned advantages of rural tourism, are the principles determined for tourism industry in the Rio Declaration in 1992 (e.g. protection of ecosystem, harmony with nature, creation of job opportunities for local people). In the context of sustainable rural development, agriculture as a tourism and recreation source can be deemed as an opportunity for rural areas.

3. Romanian rural tourism development. Case study: rural tourism in Bran-Moeciu-Fundata area

The region Bran-Moeciu-Fundata is favorable for spending a unique holiday in one of the most beautiful areas of Romania, where nature is still unspoiled and people still keep a traditional lifestyle. Tourists can be part of their life, get to know their traditions and participate in their activities.

The region Bran -Moieciu-Fundata is famous in Romania for the picturesque area, local tourist attractions, but also because it is the most developed rural tourism area in Romania.

The most famous landmark is Dracula's Bran Castle. The region has earned its international recognition due to the legendary figure of count Dracula, the nearby presence of its castle and the wonderful natural scenery of the Carpathian Mountains.

This Romanian landmark is the key factor in improving of the number of the tourist in this area. Every foreign visitor who arrives in Romania includes in its itinerary the Dracula castle.

The region Bran-Moieciu-Fundata provides the most suitable way to spend quality time for everyone who comes here either for rest or for business, without depending on the season they choose. The area offers the possibility to relax in a very quiet environment, away from the noise and stress of the city, between the hills and Carpathian Mountains, a unique view that tourists will never forget.

On the other hand, Bran - Moieciu- Fundata as a rural settlement which is situated in the Northwest of Brasov metropolitan city and 29 km far away from the city has increasing rural tourism potential.

In figures 2, 3 and 4 we have presented the provinces images extracted from Google Earth.

Fig. 2. Moieciu province, extracted from Google Earth

Fig. 3. Bran province, extracted from Google Earth

Fig. 4. Fundata province, extracted from Google Earth

Due to an underdeveloped and neglected road infrastructure, to the lack of financing resources and to the lack of interest of local and central authorities for tourism development, regions fitted for ecotourism and rural tourism failed to attract tourist, neither foreign, nor Romanian. The situation improved slowly since 1996, after the decision of European Community to finance the rural development (including rural tourism) in Romania through Phare programs and--by the end of 1990s--through SAPARD programs.

4. Evolution of the tourist number of arrivals and of the length of stay in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area

For the last four years, according with the indicators used by specialists in economic domain - growth rhythm (R) and the dynamics index (I) of the growth - the evolution of the tourist number of arrivals and the tourist length of stay respectively, in the area Bran-Moieciu-Fundata, can be appreciated as below :

Table1. The evolution of the number of arrivals in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area between 2008 and 2011

Year	Total	Residents	Non-residents
2008	67490	62554	4936
2009	59756	53535	6221
2010	65214	58896	6318
2011	81527	72914	8613
$\Delta(\text{units})$	14037	10360	3677
R (%)	0.065	0.052	0.204

Source: [one's own according, data from <http://www.brasov.insse.ro/main.php?id=439>]

In the period 2008-2011, the total number of arrivals has increased on average with 0.065 percent per year, representing 14037 arrivals per year. The number of resident arrivals has increased on average with 0.052 percent per year representing 10360 arrivals per year, while the number of non-resident arrivals has increased with 0.204 percent per year representing 3677 arrivals per year.

Fig 5. The evolution of the number of arrivals in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area. Total, residents and non-residents

Source: [one's own according, data from <http://www.brasov.insse.ro/main.php?id=439>]

We can notice that the trend of total tourists and of resident tourists had a similar evolution. Analyzing the tendencies in tourism regarding the number of arrivals, we can notice an oscillating trend: between 2008 and 2009 the trend is descending, while in the period 2009-2011 the trend is ascending. The lines' gradients corresponding to the period 2008-2009 are relatively small representing slow decreasing rhythms.

The lines' gradients corresponding to the period 2009-2011 are big representing accelerate increasing rhythms. Comparing the value corresponding to year 2008 with the value corresponding to year 2011, we can observe that the number of arrivals has increased. The number of arrivals of non-residents had an almost linear evolution; comparing the value corresponding to year 2008 with the value corresponding to year

2011, we can observe that the number of non-resident arrivals has slightly increased.

Table 2. *The evolution of the length of stay in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area between 2008 and 2011*

Year	Total	Residents	Non-residents
2008	2.4	2.41	2.24
2009	2.22	2.26	1.89
2010	2.21	2.25	1.9
2011	2.14	2.17	1.87
Δ (units)	-0.26	-0.24	-0.37
R (%)	-0.037	-0.034	-0.058

Source: [one's own according, data from <http://www.brasov.insse.ro/main.php?id=439>]

In the period 2008-2011, the total length of stay has decreased on average with 0.037 percent per year. The number of both residents' and non-residents' length of stay has decreased on average with 0.034 percent per year, respectively with 0.058 percent per year.

Fig 6. *The evolution of the length of stay in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata area. Total, residents and non-residents*

Source: [one's own according, data from <http://www.brasov.insse.ro/main.php?id=439>]

We can notice that the trend of total tourists, resident and non-resident tourists had a similar evolution. Analyzing the tendencies in tourism regarding the length of stay, we can notice an overall descending trend.

The lines' gradients corresponding to the period 2008-2011 are relatively small representing slow decreasing rhythms. Comparing the value corresponding to year 2008 with the value

corresponding to year 2011, we can observe that the length of stay has decreased.

Sustainable local development strategies

In addition for tourism development in Bran-Moieciu-Fundata region - one of the most beautiful areas in Transylvania, there are some strategies to built-in for rural tourism and to attract tourists, as the followings:

Infrastructure development

Tourists numbers are increasing every year, although tourists are very disappointed with the infrastructure, the roads are in very bad condition, the train is not a very safe alternative. For tourism development the key factor is the actual investment at Ghimbv district nearby of Bran to allow the accessibility by air with low-cost flights. The presence of an airport would have attracted more tourists and would have facilitated the access to this area. A modern airport in the heart of the county is needed urgently in order to increase the number of incoming tourists.

Private owned lands

To attract Romanian tourists there is another strategy: the Municipality sells the parceled land and there is an increasing demand of Bucharest citizens specially, to own land in Bran District on an individual base.

For the last decades, Bucharest citizens especially with high income and education level, have a tendency to own a weekend house and/or a farm house in rural areas of north and west parts of the Brasov city in the Bran – Moieciu - Fundata area.

Entrepreneurial orientation

Rural tourism provides an ideal focus for research into entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial talent because of its growth, the large amount of governmental support it receives through subsidies and the changes of rural population has undergone in the switch from agriculture to rural tourism.

In this region where economy depends on agriculture, the number of landless families is considerably high while the amount of arable land for each household is quite small. High amount of landless families in Bran – Moieciu - Fundata province is explained by the fact that

reversed migration of retired families in the last 20 years. Based on this conclusion it can be claimed that elder inhabitants, who spend their post-retirement days in the village are favorable to develop the agricultural production for tourism industry.

In this district sheep's breeding tradition goes back to centuries ago. With regard to animal production, a sheep's breeding for dairy production is significant.

Sheep's breeding represents the main source of income to a large number of families in the countryside. It is found over a wide area, consisting of almost all of the three Romanian areas.

For many people who grow relatively small number of sheep, farming is an enjoyable activity or a hobby. Local food is often more expensive than that which one can buy at the big stores, but more healthy. Local foods are responsibly-produced at the real costs. Buying local food allows varieties of food to be grown that don't travel well but taste delicious.

The farmers and food artisans will transform a working sheep farm into an open-air gourmet restaurant serving up a banquet of local food.

Educative rural activities

Sheep's breeding activities have been prevalent many years. Not all farmers do this. All farmers do try to educate people who visit their farms about sustainability, and why they make some of the choices they do.

The farmers have also mentored local agriculture apprentices and students and some from foreign countries too, and hope to be able to do more of that in the future. In terms of educating urban people about the challenges facing farmers it's very important for people to see real farms, not just agro-tourist farms.

They will see a place where several generations have done meaningful work, planned, and dreamed and made this land a part of them. The farmers would be very, very happy to see so many people enjoying themselves on his farm.

And also there is significant demand for agricultural tourism and recreation; furthermore this demand is steadily increasing.

However, it is observed that in recent years due to pollution there is a sharp decline in fertile land of this region, where sheep's breeding activities have been prevalent many years.

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Conclusion

Sustainable development is a process having economic, social, cultural and environmental-ecological dimensions. This process is perceived as a development in all respects for both urban and rural societies. Yet, in most of the developing countries rural population is gradually diminishing, notwithstanding the agricultural lands that are losing productivity are increasing.

While this situation primarily results in increasing impoverishment of rural society, it also causes problems such as deforestation, erosion and productivity loss with the misuse of resources. On the other hand, damaging the natural resources emerge problems such as migration, poverty and hunger. These problems primarily affect rural people. Most affected ones by these problems are elder inhabitants, who spend their post-retirement days in the village.

Overcoming these problems would be possible by sustainable planning and management of rural areas in accordance with their resource potential.

Although the tourism industry was in recession worldwide due to the economic crisis, Europe exceeded expectations. Destinations in Eastern and Southern Europe performed particularly well.

Rural tourism is an economically significant sector of the Romanian economy and holds great potential in terms of sustainable rural development which has as purpose to improve the residents' quality of life, to protect the natural and built environment and to provide a high-quality experience for visitors.

Agri-tourism, as a form of rural tourism, combines agriculture and tourism and provides the visitors the chance to share in farming life either as staying guests or day visitors on working farms. In Romania, it is known that 25% of farms accept tourists for about 30 years.

Bran-Moieciu-Fundata region has earned its international recognition due to the legendary figure of count Dracula, the nearby presence of its castle and the wonderful natural scenery of the

Carpathian Mountains. It is a very beautiful area, suitable for the development of rural tourism.

Observing the evolutions in the past four years regarding the number of arrivals and the length of stay, we can conclude that although the number of both resident and non-resident tourists has increased, the length of stay has decreased.

In order to improve tourist satisfaction levels, some strategies to assure sustainable

development are required: infrastructure development and improvement, entrepreneurial orientation, encouragement of educative rural activities and investments in private owned lands.

Rural Tourism and Agri-tourism are better alternatives to other practices, because they promote tourism activities with respect towards the environment.

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THE PROCESS OF MODULARIZATION IN THE SYSTEMIC EVOLUTION

Romulus GRUIA

Abstract: *The paper proposes itself to describe a systemic evolution mechanism by elucidating the modularization process and understanding the application directions, either at a “macro” level, or at a “micro” level, in report with the type of modularized subsystem of the complex system analyzed, module resulted by integronic restructuration and emergent integration. Based on the integronic emergent theory, the paper analyses the modularization dynamic in systemic evolution and the mechanisms of the modularization process which allow the module realization.*

Taking into account the complex systems, as well as the hypercomplex ones, the module is described in the present scientific step as representing the basic „cell” from the point of view of their structure. It is analysed the kind and the place in which the idea of the ecoemergent integronic (synergic, synchronic, syncretic and emergent) is manifested, so that the newly got modular structure of the complex systems may impose the idea of the dynamic of the modularization process as a mechanism in the process of the systemic evolution.

Keywords: *modularization, emergence, integronic, complex system, systemic evolution*

1. Introduction

The dynamic of the system theory has always fascinated many researchers, with a lot of approaches and theories about the subject, not only as for the living systems, but also for the not living ones, or the anthropised ones of all categories, simplified, complex or hypercomplex systems, closed or especially open systems.

A short enumeration shows us the multitude of these preoccupations. In cybernetics, thermodynamics, or biology a series of theories have been developed, among which we mention: the dissipative structure theory, the far-from-equilibrium system theory, the entropy theory, the Strehler energetic theory, the cross link theory, the oxydoreduction theory, the biostructural theory etc. From different perspectives, they deal with the way a (biological, technical – digital, mechanic –, economic, etc.) system processes information and reacts at them, the way they modify themselves or allow modifications in order to optimize their actions, etc.

The aspects regarding the systemic evolution are diversified through different directions, such as : the analyses of the evolution modality of the complex systems (linear or non-linear evolution), the analyses of the emergent interrelations of the matter ontological triad (Substance, Energy, Information), the morphologic analyses of the systemic structures (of the forms) by studying the

complexity, the analyses of the function in dynamic equilibrium of the complex systems (for example of the ecosystems), respectively of the control mechanisms (regulation and self regulation) etc. (Gruiia,R., 2002b; Gruiia,R., Gaceu, L., 3003).

The restructuration dynamics which we are approaching in the modularization process indicates important elements of the systemic evolution, with applications at complex and hypercomplex systems. We remind thus the most important characteristics of a complex system, properties which are geared, in a way or another, in the process we are dealing with (e-bibl.1) : (a) a complex system is not a whole made up of parts, but a whole made up of other wholes; (b) the system components locally interact: no component directly reacts with all the others, but only with the neighbor; (c) the global behavior is independent of the internal structure of the components; (d) the global behavior of the system is well defined.

In this context the dynamics of complex system modularization becomes possible, the made up “module” representing another whole locally interacting, independently of the global behavior and, of course, well defined (well bordered, measured, monitored and controlled). The idea to modularize and modularization constitutes the passing process from a dimension into another one, making, for example, production modules by restructure and concentration, from a special point of view, as well as from an energetic and

informational one, increasingly making evident a clearer and clearer delimitation of the given system areal and perimeter

The theory of the complex system modularization (Gruia, R., 2010 a) represents an ensemble of hypothesis, laws and concepts, organised in a logical step, which describes and explains the systemic process of modularization and its result, respectively of the system redimensioning and emergent integration as an evolutive modality towards a subsystem, which aims to integronic restructure, and, as a result, the systemic evolution.

The concept of systemic evolution has been approached for a long period of time. For example in the theory of dissipative structures Ilya Prigogine (the 60s) was observing that, for the dynamic, complex systems, the disequilibrium represents the necessary condition for development (or the system growth). i.e. far from equilibrium systems. The syntagma „far-from-equilibrium” is in fact the equivalent for nonlinearity. The dissipative structures spread their own energy in order to re-create themselves under new forms of organization, in disorder conditions and confronted with an amplified noise level. These systems own inborn properties to reconfigure so that they may exploit new information. Thus, the open systems exchange energy, matter or information with their environments and which, when they are pushed “far-from-equilibrium” create new structures and a new order.

It is known that the disequilibrium thermodynamics explains these notions, an important part being played by different interpretations given to the second thermodynamics law. The complex systems, with their high degree of organization, seemed to defy the physics laws at the beginning of the 20th century, more exactly the second principle of the thermodynamics, in conformity with which the universe develops in the direction of the entropy growth. It has been neglected for a long period of time the fact that the second principle, in its present statement, is valid only for isolated systems. These systems really develop until the thermodynamic equilibrium with the environment, state in which their entropy is maximum.

For the open systems it is noticed that the disequilibrium is the releaser factor in the systemic evolution, and entropy, as an element allowing the evaluation of the energy degradation from the given system, indicates the degree of

organization (in fact, disorganization) of that system or subsystem. What we propose ourselves is to describe a model by which we may explain the restructuring process passing from disequilibrium to a new dynamic equilibrium, controlled by the entropic factor, through modularization with anti entropic effect. Therefore the idea of the modularization process in the systemic evolution is outlined.

The modularization process has, as a work bases, the emergent integronic theory (Gruia,R.,2009a), which essentially applies the emergent integration principle in direct relationship with the analysis (eMergetic). Here the energy of a form of energy defines the available energy of a transformation or a system (Pillet, G., Odum, T., 1987), which constitutes one of the methodological principles of the theory applications. Starting from these theoretical aspects, the modularization process, by the concept of emergent integronics and, respectively, the principle of emergent integration, approaches the substance, energy and information flows (S,E,I) which go through the systems, from the perspective of the eco-energetic analysis, of cogeneration and eMergetic sustainability.

There is thus defined the restructuring (changing) model and the functioning way of the system modularization process, having as applications of interest especially the more difficult to analyse systems, i.e. complex systems and those with dissipative structures (Gruia, 1998, 2002, Szabo et al., 2005), among which we mention the ecosystems, the agroecosystems and the environment-economy systems.

The basic objective of the paper is therefore linked to the making clear of the modularization process and understanding the application directions, either at a „macro” level, or at a „micro” level, in comparison with the type of modularized subsystem of the analysed complex system, module resulted by integronic restructure and emergent integration, having as a result the systemic evolution.

2. Material and method

The approached method proposes itself to apply the theory of complex system modularization (Gruia, R., 2010a) in order to clear up the complex and/or hypercomplex system evolution, having as a main goal to elucidate the mechanisms of efficient “piloting” (integronic management) of the “module” type

subsystems. There are approached scientific and methodological aspects which sustain this approach: the emergency theory, the general theory of integration, the concept of ecological modernization and others. The method puts into evidence the “modularization process”, sustained by the concept of emergent integration and integronic restructuration, and then it describes a series of aspects concerning the ecologic emergency by systemic eco-modularization, based on the general theory of ecologic emergency integration or of the ecoemergent integronics.

3. Results and discussions

On bases of the theory of the complex system modularization (Gruia, R., 2010 a) one can explain a model of systemic evolution, more precisely, the passing process towards superior forms of organization of the complex and hypercomplex systems, respectively by the „modularization process”. It appears the necessity to approach, from a new perspective, the interrelation potentiality between the complex system elements, in order to point out and quantify these new forms of organization, for the idea of efficient management, or to favorably „pilot” the respective systems, being forced, among others, by the adaptation to the specific conditions of the 21st century (Gruia,1995,1998).

The components of any system being its forerunners, which belongs in fact to a cosmic vision both emergentistic and evolutionistic, impose the idea of a relation between the integrative, change of hierarchic structure manners and the new forms, through the „integration-emergence” dualism, generalised at the ecosphere (Bunge, 1984), (Constantinescu, 1986), (Gruia, 1995). The modularization process is, simpler said, the „releasing gear” of the passing to a higher organised system, to another reality or even to another modulation (Gruia, 2009 a).

All these implicitly indicate applications of the theory too. For instance, from the perspective of the Complexity study (Munteanu, Fl. 1996,2004), it is shown that the applicability of the obtained results allows: the development of the ecologic technologies; monitorization, diagnose and prediction, especially in the zones presenting a high natural and anthropic risk; understanding of the social, economic and political phenomena, in the context of the cohabitation at a planetary level, etc. All the previously mentioned are

totally characteristic to the specific of the open anthropic subsystems or, more concretely said, of the modules of ecological, agricultural and industrial production.

3.1. The modularization dynamics in the systemic evolution

The model of the modularization process may be better understood in its dynamics if we refer to ecosystems (as an example of the complex systems) and to the systemic eco-modularization. At these systems, the bigger the degree of anthropisation is, the more evidently the modularization process manifests itself. A prime effect is restructuration, at the same time with delimitation and more evident pointing out of the system parameter, i.e. emergent redimensioning and integration characteristic to the modularization process (Gruia, 2009 b).

Therefore it results that the integronic restructuration of the complex systems (as, for example, of the agroecosystems), is a process whose dynamics differently develops in function of the modularization level. We are referring on one hand to the level of some mega-ecosystems of the agroecosystem type, concretized by eco-farms as well as large production agro-modules, with not very well determined perimeter, and, on the other hand, to modularization at the level of „mini-ecosystems” of small agro-module type, with well determined perimeter, speaking in fact of production modules in an environment and space totally controlled by man, aspects largely described by the model of modular agriculture (Gruia, R., 2010 b).

One may observe that the modularization process refers to „modularize”, in the idea of „passing” to which are added new meanings from a semantic point of view, i.e. a verb, becoming a basic conceptual notion. To modularize indicates a passing from a dimension to another, making new modules by restructure and concentration, from a spacial (matter, substance) point of view, as well as from an energetic and informational one, with making more and more evident the ever clearer areal delimitation and the given system perimeter. Thus we are referring in fact to the dynamics of the process, to its „modularization” action, respectively to its action to modularize itself and to its result, the idea of „dimensioning” and „redifining” idea being taken over. At the second step there is materialized the notion of „modularization”, i.e. the action of the structuring process and its result, respectively of

redimensioning and emergent integration, aiming to integronic restructuration of the complex systems, with effect of growth in concentration and visibility, with perimetrization more and more delimited, in comparison with the initial stage of complex and diffuse mosaic.

It must be mentioned the fact that, within the modularization process, concomitently increase both the information quantity and quality from the system, i.e. the complex system becomes better organized, more simplified but more labile and dependent on energy. As it is known, complexity is defined as the number of „links” and interactions that may be established between a system subunits, which may be represented as a measure of the number of retroactions (feedbacks) which may be established between the mentioned elements. The modules we are referring to conceptually have a more reduced number of interactions and retroactions, especially those from the production fields of ecologic, biologic and technical, technical and economic nature, as for example the agroecosystems.

From what we have specified, it results the importance of the modularization process in the complex system dynamics, as well as the fact that this process constitutes in itself a necessary instrument in the management of the anthropised ecosystems, i.e. in their efficient and effective piloting. The awareness of the modularization process means an important step for the productive activity of the decades to come, especially if we take into account the climate, ecologic, economic and social provocations of the 21st century (Gruia, 1995, 2002 a, 2009 a).

In the context of what we have presented, we identify a direct relation between system anthropisation and their modularized structure.

THE MODULE, as well as in case of complex systems, but especially in case of hypercomplex systems, represents in fact the basic “cell” from the perspective of their structure, as well as the place where the dynamics of the ecoemergent integronics manifests itself, from the functional perspective of the given areal.

The modular structure of the complex and hyper complex systems implicitly imposes the idea of the dynamics of the modularization process (fig.1), i.e. of the growing flow and integration, having as a result a systemic

development of an evolutive type, from a diffuse and complex mosaic towards an emergent induction one (3S= synchronic, syncretic and synergic), with a result of simplification in detectable parameters, with controlable and monitorizable flows and cycles. Thus it results the finding out of the “new” from a superior level, i.e. the emergence. The passing to another level means the passing of the system to a new, restructured state. At its turn, the resulted module becomes a system with a new structure in dynamic equilibrium, which may, at its turn, when moving away from equilibrium, restart the modularization process necessary to reequilibrate at a superior level. The dynamics of the process goes on, the anthropic systems practically becoming more and more “modularized”, restructure that explains in fact a model of the systemic evolution.

3.2. The mechanisms of the modularization process

As figure 1 shows, there are three moments of reference that a complex or hypercomplex system crosses through the development of the modularization process necessary in the systemic evolution, having as a result the apparition of a perfectly controlled module, with high production capacity and in dynamic equilibrium: flow, integration and reorganization.

Flow : Constructive law

The constructive law (Bejan, A.,2000) underlines the fact that Nature constructs and, in parallel to it, Man also constructs. The constructive law refers to a universal phenomenon from nature: the flow configuration generation. Not only by living organisms, but also by non-living physical structures, flow different fluids: water, air, sap, blood, electric and thermic flows. In their transit, the fluids have the tendency to flow easier, on larger access ways. The law says that, *“in order that a macroscopic system of a finite form may survive in time, its configuration must evolve so that it may offer the best access to the currents that flow through it”*.

Fig.1 – Conceptual diagram concerning the dynamics of the modularization process of complex and hypercomplex systems

The phenomenon which generates flow configurations is like a cartoon, where a frame is replaced by another, in which currents flow easier, and, heat for instance, flows from a volume to a “mouth” point, not in a homogeneous manner, but through a network that successively rarifies itself. The optimum network perfectly looks like a hydrographic basin, which may be the model of work, for example, for energy flow in modularized subsystems. Growth and form is the leading vision, which cannot be doubted. Things have a certain form because they grow in that particular manner, which also represents the pattern to be followed for the growth and form of the modular systems.

We consider that this concept of design in nature is the principle on basis of which are explained and forecast phenomena, processes, natural and anthropized behaviors (but taking into account

the natural manner) and may be developed modules in which circuits of substance, energy and information may easily and efficiently.

Integration : The concept of integronics

Integronics is the science of system coexistence, based on the general theory of integration, which studies the integration processes and their component elements, i.e. integrated systems. The concept of integronics opens new horizons in the research fields due to the synergic effect, more precisely, by coordinating several actions in order to obtain a common result with economy of means. Its tools and mechanisms are comprehensive, they operating de facto in the modularization of the complex systems, especially in comparison with the phenomenon of emergence.

The association between “integration” and “emergence” becomes practically natural for complex systems (example of type of ecosystem)

or for the hypercomplex ones (example of environment-economy type), interrelation which constitutes in fact a principle and a concept to be rediscovered in the process of modularization: the concept of emergent integration. On basis of the principle of emergent integration (Gruia, R., 2003,2005), having the quality of universality, the notion of integration closes the explicative circuit, i.e. in case a system is regulated and, from a functional point of view, is organized, then the system integrated. On the contrary, when the function of the system is disorganized, then the system is disintegrated.

Restructuration : The theory of eco-emergent integronics

The theory of eco-emergent integronics (R. Gruia, 2009 a) is applicable in the modularization process, playing the part of explaining the evolution manner, as well as the superior forms of complex and hypercomplex system organization. It appears the necessity to approach from a new perspective the respective phenomena and processes and the potentiality of the interrelations between the elements of the system, in order to make evident and to quantify these new, superior forms of organization. All these in the idea of favourably „piloting” the respective systems, no matter their size, but characterized by a large complexity. The modularizing process makes the restructuring by inducing emergence, respectively synchronic, syncretic and synergic, resulting, as it has already been precised, „modular units”, i.e. simplified systems under detectable perimeters, with monitorizable and controlable flows and cycles.

Without entering into details, we mention an application of the modularizing process, i.e. in case of the ecosystems arranged by man. They have a simplified structure, with a larger energetic support to maintain equilibrium under the conditions of fulfilling the objective for which they have been created, i.e. a higher productivity (Gaceu,L., Gruia,R., 2003). Even if they structurally differ, man, by profoundly knowing the natural ecosystems, may

permanently perfect the structure of his own ecosystems in the modules he is imagining. An eloquent example in this direction is represented by the agroecosystem modularization, restructure with high potential for the agro-alimentary system of the 21st century .

4. Conclusions

The modularization process indicates the dynamics of flowing and growing integration, having as a result the making of production modules with systemic development of evolutive type, from the state of diffuse and complex mosaic, towards the emergence inducing one (3S= synchronic, syncretic and synergic), the modules thus becoming simplified, in detectable perimeters, with monitorizable and controllable flows and cycles, but with high productivity and efficiency.

In the systemic evolution, the modularizing process is the mechanism playing the part of finding out the apparition of the « new » of a superior level (i.e. emergence), respectively the system turning into a new restructured state; the mechanism continuously functions, the resulted module becomes a system with a new structure in dynamic equilibrium, which may, at its turn, when distancing from equilibrium, restart the modularizing process, necessary to reequilibrate at another superior level. The arranged complex systems may become more and more “modularized” (better controlled, more efficient and effective), restructured, which explain in fact a model of the systemic evolution with applications necessary to the conditions of the 21st century.

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THE INFLUENCES OF (GRASSES AND LEGUMES) MIXTURES AND THE WAY OF THE NITROGEN IMPLEMENTATION ON THE PRODUCTION OF TEMPORARY MEADOWS FROM PREAJBA, GORJ

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Abstract: In the first year of vegetation temporary grassland made no significant difference depending on the mixtures. The application of nitrogen contributed to the differentiation of fodder, remarking the 150 kg/ha N dose fractionation into two halves: 100 kg/ha in spring and 50 kg/ha after the first harvest. In the second year, the rainfall was much lower, causing the obtain of lower production. The two years average yields ranged from 5.80 to 7,27 t/ha d.s.

Keywords: cocksfoot bird`s-foot trefoil, fertilization, timothy, grassland.

1. Introduction

The duration of economical exploitation, normally up to 5-6 years, is constantly influenced by more than one factor, especially the vivacity of component species, and play an important role in this direction, but there are other combined elements, components which have a great contribute (Ionescu I., 2003).

The process of aging and degradation of temporary meadows starts since the third year of vegetation, with the decrease in the ratio of legumes. In the first year of vegetation temporary grassland shall be used only by mowing, method that protect young plants and stimulates their fellowship (Barbulescu C. ș.a., 1991).

If temporary meadow shall be used as a grassland, the first scythe it would be taken in the range in which the grasses with the highest proportion is found between earing and flowering, period in which it is performed the most balanced report between production and nutrient content (Pavel C. ș.a., 1988).

Research carried out want to bring some new items on how do behave two mixes of grasses and legumes, under the terms of the fractional applying of nitrogen fertilizers.

2. The working method

It was located a bifactorial experience by type 2 x 3, at Experimental Center for Grassland culture from Preajba, Gorj county, after subdivided parcels method, in 3 repetitions.

The experienced makers and their graduations are:

The A factor - The mixtures of grasses and legumes

$a_1 = Dactylis glomerata$ 20% + *Festuca pratensis* 20% + *Phleum pratense* 20% + *Trifolium pratense* 40%;

$a_2 = Dactylis glomerata$ 20% + *Festuca pratensis* 20% + *Phleum pratense* 20% + *Lotus corniculatus* 40%;

The B factor - The way of applying nitrogen intake

$b_1 = 150$ kg/ha all in spring;

$b_2 = 100$ kg/ha in spring + 50 kg/ha after the first scythe;

$b_3 = 50$ kg/ha in spring + 50 kg/ha after the first scythe + 50 kg/ha after the second scythe.

In spring, along with the first dose of nitrogen, 50 kg/ha P_2O_5 + 50 kg/ha K_2O have been applied.

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As fertilizers have been used complex 15 - 15 - 15 along with ammonium nitrate. It has been harvested mechanically with mowers.

3. Results and discussions

On average in two years of experimentation (2010 and 2011) have obtained the following most important experimental results.

The analysis of unilateral influence by the mixtures on the production of temporary meadows, it has shown that the association of red clover (40%) with the three grasses (*Dactylis glomerata*, *Festuca pratensis* și *Phleum pratense*, each one with 20%) led to an production of 6,74t/ha d.s. and the association of *Dactylis glomerata* (40%) at the three grasses referred led to a production of 6,10 t/ha d.s. The production minus of 0,64 t/ha, is significantly (Table I)

Table 1
The permanent influence of the mixture on the production of temporary medaows (t/ha d.s.).

Nr crt.	The mixture	The production t/ha d.s.	%	The difference / Mt.	The significance
1	a ₁ - <i>D.g.</i> 20 % + <i>F.p.</i> 20% + <i>Ph.p.</i> 20% + <i>T.p.</i> 40%	6,74	100	-	Standard
2	a ₂ - <i>D.g.</i> 20% + <i>F.p.</i> 20% + <i>Ph.p.</i> 20% + <i>L.c.</i> 40%.	6,10	100	- 0,64	0

DL 5 % = 0,52 t/ha d.s.
DL 1 % = 0,86 t/ha d.s.
DL 0,1 = 1,61 t/ha d.s.

Analyzing the separate influence of the nitrogen application mode on the temporary meadows production, has result that at the application of N150, in spring, in a single treatment, have been obtained 6,14 t/ha d.s. (standard).

By nitrogen dose fractionation on two treatments (N100 in spring and N 50 after the

first scythe) has been obtained the biggest production of 6,96 t/ha d.s.

The percentage rise in relation to the first variant is 13%, and the rise of production is 0,82 t/ha d.s., verry significant.

By fractionation of nitrogen in 3 equal halves, have been obtained 6,17 t/ha d.s., with an minus of 0, 03 t/ha d.s., insignificant (table 2).

Table 2

The separate influence of the nitrogen implementation on the temporary meadows production (t/ha d.s.)

Nr. crt.	The application of nitrogen (kg/ha)	The production t/ha s.u.	%	The difference /Mt.	The significance
1	b ₁ - 150 in spring	6,14	100	0,0	Standard
2	b ₂ - 100 in spring+ 50 after the first scythe	6,96	113	0,82	* * *
3	b ₃ - 50 in spring+50 after the first scythe + after the second scythe	6,17	101	0,03	-

DL 5 % = 0,37 t/ha d.s.
 DL 1 % = 0,51 t/ha d.s.
 DL 0,1 = 0,70 t/ha d.s.

The third table contains experimental data relating the interaction between those two factors experienced (a mixture of grasses and legumes and nitrogen dose fractionation).

At the association of 3 grasses (20 % from each) and *Trifolium pratense* (40 %) productions have ranged from 6,42 t/ha d.s. (a₁b₁) to 7,27 t/ha d.s. (a₁b₂). At the association of grasses (60%) with *Lotus corniculatus* (40%) yields ranged from 5,80 t/ha d.s. (a₂b₃) to 6.65 t/ha d.s. (a₂b₂).

The maximum output, of 7.27 t/ha d.s. was made in the version with 60% grasses și 40% *Trifolium pratense*, in wich the nitrogen dose was fractionated into two halves (N 100. in spring, N 50 after the first scythe). The lowest production of 5.80 t/ha d.s. was recorded in the version with 60 % grasses and 40% *Lotus corniculatus*, in wich the dose of N was split up into three halves (N50 in spring, N50 after the first scythe and N50 after the second scyth).

4.Conclusions

The mixture between grasses (60%) and *Trifolium pratense* (40%) gave a bigger production of 0,64 t/ha d.s. to the mixture of grasses (60%) and *Lotus corniculatus* (40%).

The fractionation of nitrogen in 2 halves (N 100 in spring and N 50 after the first scythe),

has led to a rise in production of 0,82 t/ha d.s., very significant, compared to the full application of nitrogen in spring. The fractionation of nitrogen reduces the risk of environmental pollution.

For production is recommended the mixture composed from *Dactylis glomerata* (20%), *Poa pratensis* (20%), *Phleum pratense* (20%) and *Trifolium pratense* (40%) and dose fractionation of nitrogen in second halwes. In this way you get sustainable production from temporary grassland in Subcarpathian area of Oltenia.

Table

The combined influence of the application mode of nitrogen with grasses and legumes mixture on the temporary grassland production (t/ha d.s.)

Nr. crt.	The mixture	The way of nitrogen application	The production t/ha	%	The difference / Mt.	The significance
1	Legumes 60% + <i>Trifolium pratense</i> 40% a ₁	b ₁ 150	6,42	100	0,0	Standard
2		b ₂ 100 + 50	7,27	113	0,85	*
3		b ₃ 50+50+50	6,54	102	0,12	-
4	Legumes 60% + <i>Lotus corniculatus</i> 40% a ₂	b ₁ 150	5,86	100	0,0	Standard
5		b ₂ 100 + 50	6,65	113	0,79	*
6		b ₃ 50 + 50 + 50	5,80	99	-0,06	-

DL 5 % =

0,73 t/ha d.s.

DL 1 % =

1,01 t/ha d.s.

DL 0,1 =

1,40 t/ha d.s.

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BIODIVERSITY OF ALGAE IN RIVER MIRUSHA

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Abstract: Algal diversity is considered at the levels of richness of species and of higher taxonomic ranks and as the variety of habitats algae dominate and their functional importance in the processes they mediate. The geographical distribution of algae indicates substantial differences in species richness and degree of endemism in different regions. We revealed an algal diversity consisting of 114 algal species in Mirusha River, which belongs to five(5) divisions..

Keywords: biodiversity, algae, analysis, river, Mirusha.

1. Paper sections and font styles

According to our research, algal diversity is significantly influenced by changes in the environmental parameters. We can use this contiguity in bioindication methodology.

However, the major parameters used in bioindication are individual for each species, while the reaction of the entire community is left unseen.

Algae are excellent indicators of water-quality conditions, notably nutrient and organic enrichment, and also are indicators of major ion, dissolved oxygen, and pH concentrations and stream microhabitat conditions. The autecology, or physiological optima and tolerance, of algal species for various water-quality contaminants and conditions is relatively well understood for certain groups of freshwater algae, notably diatoms. However, applications of autecological information for water-quality assessments have been limited because of challenges associated with compiling autecological literature from disparate sources, tracking name changes for a large number of algal species, and creating an autecological data base from which algal-indicator metrics can be calculated. A comprehensive summary of algal autecological attributes for North American streams and rivers does not exist.

Algae can be found in all aquatic habitats. In most streams and rivers, algae are the most

diverse assemblage of organisms that can be sampled easily and identified readily to species or variety (Stevenson and Smol, 2003). Algal species are excellent indicators of water quality and environmental change (Patrick, 1948, 1977; Dixit, Smol, and others, 1992).

The main objective of this study was to reveal algal diversity in the Mirusha as a basis for taxonomic, chorological, and ecological analysis. We consider the algal assemblage of the river Mirusha as a system reflecting the sum of ecological variables and their dynamics in a typical river of Kosovo.

2. Material and methods

The samples were collected at 4 sampling stations along the river Mirusha in the spring of 2011.

Water samples were collected in 500 ml glass bottles, 10 cm beneath the water surface, using standard methods (Hindak,1978). Conductivity, pH, salts, TDS (Total Disolved Salts), were measured in situ using mobile instruments (HACH), O₂ were measured with mobile instrument such as oxygenometer (Hana Instrument) and nutrients (N, P, Si) were analysed by standard methods (DEV,1981).

Epilithon was brushed from the stones with toothbrush and the upper layer of epipelton was pipetted off with a vacuum suction system

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(Sladeckova,1962). Epiphyton was sampled with the substrate and palced in the plastic bottles .

The algae were examined using a Leica microscope, with a digital camera Fujifilm, which filmed the algae directly from the sample.

3. Diatoma cleaning

Clenaing of diatom frustules , preparation of permamnent slides and determinations follow Krammer & Lange-Bertalot (1986-2001).

Algal identification was done according to the keys:*Cyanophyta*: Elenkin 1938, 1949; Starmach 1966.*Bacillariophyta*: Kramer, Lange-Bertalot 1986, 1988, 1991a, 1991b

Euglenophyta: Starmach 1983; *Chlorophyta*: Komárek and Fott 1983; Pascher 1984,1985.

4. Results and discussion

The composition of algoflora of river Mirusha it is to much diversified. We identified 114 taxa, which belongs to 5 divisions : Cyanophyta, Bacillariophyta, Xanthophyta, Euglenophyta and Chlorophyta.

Dominate the Bacillariophyta with 75 taxa, then Cyanophyta with 18 taxa, Chlorophyta with 14 taxa, Euglenophyta with 10 taxa and Xanthophuyta with 2 taxa.

Division Bacillariophyta is represented through its highest number of species and

intraspecific taxonomic varieties, among which are Nitzschia-13 species, Navicula - 11, and Surirella-6.

From the representatives of filumi Cyanophyta most rich in species is gender Oscillatoria, with 4 taxa, the representatives of which constitute about 22.22% from the total number of Cyanophyta.

Algae flora of the river is characterized by a big variety of Chlorophyta with 13 taxa, where dominating gender is Closterium with 3 taxa, and Scenedesmus 3 taxa.

At division Euglenophyta dominating gender is Euglena and Trachelomonas with 3 species, followed by the representatives of the gender Phacus -2 species.

Representative of Bacillariophya , found at all locality are Cocconeis placentula var. lineate, and Cymbella helvetica, while at Cyanophyta is Oscillatoria mirabilis.

It was determined 38 algal bioindicators in the river.

Phytoplankton diversity and productivity are strongly related to water quality (e.g., Moss, 1988) as well as to biotic factors (Scheffer, 1998). Singh (1965) stated that temperature, pH, alkalinity and phosphate have been emphasized to be significant factors for controlling distribution of Cyanophyceae which is also corroborated with the present study.

Table 1.Determined algae in the river Mirusha during summer season 2009

	Division CYANOPHYTA	Level of Saprobity	LOCALITIES			
			1	2	3	4
116	Total number of algae					
1	Anabaena plantonica Brunnth.		1		1	
2	A. oscillarioides Bory			1		1
3	Chroococcus varius Al.Br.					1
4	Chroococcus dispersus (Keissler) Lemm.		1			
5	Dactylococcopsis acicularis Lemm			1		1
6	Gloecapsa sp.			1		
7	Lemanea annulata (Rotalge)Vergr.		1		1	
8	Microcystis grevillei f.grevillei (Hass)Elenk.			1		
9	Merismopedia tenuissima	β				1
10	Nodularia spumigena Mert.		1			
11	Oscillatoria mirabilis Böcher		1	1	3	3
12	O.nitida Schkord					
13	O.plangtonica Wolosz.			1		
14	O.rupicola Hansg.			1		

15	<i>Phormidium ambiguum</i> Gom.	β		1		3
16	<i>Rivularia dura</i> Roth.		1		1	
17	<i>Stigonema hermioides</i> (Kütz.)Born et Fla.		1	1	1	
	Division BACILLARIOPHYTA					
1	<i>Achnanthes hungarica</i> (Grunow) Grunow	o	1		1	
2	<i>A. coarctata</i> (Bréb.) Grun.	x	1	1		
3	<i>Achnanthidium minutissimum</i> (Kütz.)Czarneck		1		1	1
4	<i>Amphora lybica</i> Ehrenberg		1	1		
5	<i>A. normani</i> Rabenhorst	o	1		3	3
6	<i>Aneumastus stroesei</i> (Ostrup) Mann			1		
7	<i>Cocconeis pediculus</i> Ehrenberg	o- β		1		3
8	<i>C. placentula</i> var. <i>lineata</i> (Ehrenberg) Cleve		3	1	5	3
9	<i>Craticula accomoda</i> (Hustedt) Mann	o- β	1			3
10	<i>C. cuspidata</i> (Kützing) Mann	o			3	1
11	<i>Cyclotella ocellata</i> Pantocsek			1		1
12	<i>Cymatopleura solea</i> (Brébisson) W.Smith	β			1	1
13	<i>Cymbella affinis</i> Kützing	o- β	3		3	3
14	<i>C. helvetica</i> Kützing	o	3	1	3	3
15	<i>C. minuta</i> Hilse ex Rabenhorst		1		3	
16	<i>Diatoma ehrenbergii</i> Kützing		3		5	3
17	<i>D. moniliforme</i> Kützing				3	
18	<i>Epithemia adnata</i> (Kützing) Brébisson				3	
19	<i>Fragilaria capucina</i> Desmazières	o- β	3	1		
20	<i>F. ulna</i> (Nitzsch) Lange-Bertalot				1	
21	<i>F. ulna</i> complex <i>oxyrhynchus</i> Lange-Bertalot		1			1
22	<i>Frustulia vulgaris</i> (Thwaites) De Toni	o	1	1	1	
23	<i>Gomphonema carolinense</i> Hagelstein				1	
24	<i>G.grovei</i> M.Schmidt		1		1	1
25	<i>G. micropus</i> Kützing			1	1	
26	<i>G. minutu</i> (C.Agardh) C.Agardh				1	1
27	<i>Gyrosigma acuminatum</i> (Kützing) Rabenhorst	β	1		1	
28	<i>G. scalproides</i> (Rabenhorst) Cleve				1	1
29	<i>Hippodonta capitata</i> (Ehrenbg.)Lange-Bertalot					1
30	<i>Luticola goeppertiana</i> (Bleish) Mann		1			1
31	<i>L. mutica</i> (Kützing) D.G. Mann				1	
32	<i>Meridion circulare</i> (Grev.) C. Ag.	o	1		1	
33	<i>Navicula capitatoradiata</i> Germain			1		1
34	<i>N. cryptotenella</i> Lange-Bertalot				3	3
35	<i>N. cryptocephala</i> Kütz.	α				1
36	<i>N. lanceolata</i> (Agardh) Ehrenberg		3		3	3
37	<i>N. radiosa</i> Kützing	o- β		1		3
38	<i>N. recens</i> (Lange-Bert.) Lange-Bert.	o- β	1			1
39	<i>N. species aff radisafallax</i> Lange-Bertalot		1			
40	<i>N. tripunctata</i> (O.F.Müller) Bory		3			3
41	<i>N. trivialis</i> Lange-Bertalot		3		3	
42	<i>N. tuscula</i> Ehr.	o- β		1		1
43	<i>N. viridula</i> var. <i>rostellata</i> (Kützing) Cleve		3		3	
44	<i>Nitzschia acula</i> Hantzsch in Rabenhorst			1		
45	<i>N. capitellata</i> Hustedt		3		3	
46	<i>N. constricta</i> (Kützing)Ralfs		1			3
47	<i>N. closterium</i> (Ehrenberg)W.Smit			3		1
48	<i>N. dissipata</i> (Kützing) Grunow	o- β			3	3
49	<i>N. elegantula</i> Grunow in Van Heurck					3
50	<i>N. eglei</i> Lange Bertalot			1		
51	<i>N. fonticola</i> Grunow	o- β			3	
52	<i>N. levidensis</i> (W.Smith) Grunow		3			
53	<i>N. litoralis</i> Gruow			1		1

54	<i>N. linearis</i> (Agardh) W.Smith	o-β	1			
55	<i>N. pusilla</i> Grunow					1
56	<i>N. sigmoidea</i> (Nitzsch) W.Smith	β		3		3
57	<i>Pinnularia microstauron</i> (Ehrenberg) Cleve	o-x	3	1		
58	<i>P.microstauron</i> var. <i>brebisonii</i> (Kützing)Mayer	x	3	1		
59	<i>Planothidium ellipticum</i> (Cleve) Round		3	1		
60	<i>Planothidium lanceolatum</i> (Brébisson) Round		3			
61	<i>Reimeria sinuata</i> (Greg.) Kociolek & Stoermer			1		3
62	<i>Rhoicosphaenia abbreviata</i> (Ag.)Lange-Bertalot	x-o	1		1	1
63	<i>Sellaphora pupula</i> fo. <i>rostrata</i> (Hustedt) Bukhtiyarova				1	
64	<i>Stauroneis smithii</i> Grunow	x-o	1			1
65	<i>Surirella angusta</i> Kützing	o		1		
66	<i>S. brebisonii</i> var. <i>kuetzingii</i> Krammer & L-B.			1		3
67	<i>S. minuta</i> Brébisson in Kützing	o	1		3	3
68	<i>S.ovalis</i> Breb.	o	1		1	
69	<i>S.patella</i> Kützing			1	1	
70	<i>S.robusta</i> Ehrenberg				1	1
72	<i>Synedra acus</i> Hustedt		1	1		1
73	<i>S.nana</i> Meister				1	
74	<i>S.ulna</i> Kützing		1			1
	Division XANTHOPHYTA					
	<i>Vaucheria sessilis</i>			1		
	<i>Characiopsis naegelii</i>				1	1
	Division EUGLENOPHYTA					
1	<i>Euglena acus</i> Ehrenb.	β		1		
2	<i>E.minima</i> Fr.	o	1	1		
3	<i>E.oblonga</i> Lemm.		1			1
4	<i>Phacus orbicularis</i> Hübn.	β				
5	<i>Ph.pusillus</i> Lemm.			1		1
6	<i>Trachelomonas affinis</i> Lemm.		1			1
7	<i>T. bituricensis</i> Ehrenberg			1		
8	<i>T.oblonga</i> Lemm.	β	1			
	Division CHLOROPHYTA					
1	<i>Cladophora glomerata</i> Kützing	β			1	1
2	<i>Closterium moniliferum</i> Nitzsch	β		1		1
3	<i>C.praelongum</i> Bréb.		1		1	
4	<i>C.prunum</i> Bréb.			1		
5	<i>Desmodesmus perforatus</i> (Lemm.) Hegew.			1		1
6	<i>Microspora floccosa</i> (Vauch)Thuret.				1	
7	<i>M.elegans</i> Hansg.		1	1		
8	<i>Oedogonium vochinense</i> Lazar					1
9	<i>Pleurococcus naegeli</i> Chod.		1			
10	<i>Scenedesmus quadridens</i> Meyen	β		1	1	
11	<i>S. acutus</i> Meyen	o-β	1			1
12	<i>S. ellipticus</i> Corda	o-β	1		1	
13	<i>Spirogira</i> sp.					

Legend: o-oligosaprobic level, β - betamesosaprobic level, α - alphamesosaprobic level, p-polisaprob level.1,3,5 – Relative abundancy level.1,3,5 – Relative abundancy

5. Conclusions

On the basis of algoflora analysis of the river Mirusha, we can conclude:

-Higher diversity of algae in summer season.

-During the study period (summer season 2010) we identified 114 algal species.

-In river Mirusha (during summer season) dominate diatoma with 74 species.

-Bioindicator species are 39, dominate, oligosaprob and betamesosaprob species with 11 taxa, followed by oligosaprob with 10 taxa.

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DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL TOURISM

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Abstract : *Rural tourism or agro-tourism is a unique form of tourism services on people who love culture and peasant art, offering near spending family holidays in rural households the opportunity to eat foods with high biological value and also the opportunity to join the hosts to collection or production of traditional food. To the peasant farm host, rural tourism is a source of income obtained using household products, increasing the economic capacity of household and from the perspective of foreign tourists, use this form of tourism, near the promote the national tourism abroad, rural tourism is a form of "export" version of rural households obtained food products.*

Keywords : *rural tourism, agro-tourism, the peasant farm, hostel, tourist.*

1. Rural tourism or agro-tourism. Concepts, principles, complexity

Before 1989 in Romania we can not speak of Tourism, this form of tourism taking into being after 1989, although in Europe this form of tourism was booming in the last decade of the twentieth century.

New branch of traditional tourism, rural tourism has the advantage of turning spaces rustic, natural resources, without major infrastructure investments, and cultural heritage, while the agricultural products produced on farms are used by tourists, thus making a financial profit.

By use of buildings in rural areas and work without aggressive environmental elements, rural tourism contributes directly to local development in rural areas, the flow of tourists and biological products used as raw materials for food tourists, is a major component in the development of a country's territorial, recognized by the countries like France, Germany, Austria and Ireland.

In addition to raising living standards in rural areas, rural tourism contributes to the preservation and transmission across generations of inherited traditions and culture, reducing the phenomenon of migration from rural to urban areas by stimulating investments in rural and through benefits of legislation in the field.

Due to these economic benefits offered by social and demographic development of rural tourism, the legislature came and covered some financial and fiscal incentives for the development of rural tourism in areas with tourism potential in Romania: mountain areas, the Danube Delta and Black Sea.

Over the time, there were numerous ways conceptual delimitation of rural tourism, some authors speak about agro-tourism, ecotourism or green tourism, but all theoretical approaches have in common the idea of defining forms of exploitation of natural resources within households native or newly built, but respecting the local architecture and the firm for the purpose of tourism.

As defined by the World Tourism Organization, rural tourism is "... a form of tourism that includes any tourism activity in rural areas organized and led by local people, valuing local tourism resources - natural, historical cultural, human - and equipment, tourist structures, including pensions and agro farms".

According to the team led by Professor Puiu Nistoreanu from ASE Bucharest, rural tourism "(...) includes all tourist activities carried out in the village (rural) areas beyond the coastal and mountain resorts reached"[1, p.187-188], while in work led by Professor Gabriela Stănculescu rural tourism is defined as "a concentrated form on destinations in rural areas, having a specific functional structure of accommodation and service heterogeneous"[2, p. 180].

Returning to the definition of the World Tourism Organization, as noted in the literature, this definition meets the specific features that characterize rural tourism activities, such as: location in rural areas, building tourism product in the functional characteristics based on the world rural (contact with nature, traditions, traditional practices), conservation of rural infrastructure, rural lifestyle preservation.

Given that one of the requirements to practice sustainable rural tourism is to preserve the

essential elements of rural, rural tourism definition must take into account several factors such as: the psychological dimension (based on human need to enjoy rest and recreation) social dimension (caused by contact with the rural), geographic size (related to landscape configuration that favor or limit the development of tourism activities), and not least the urban dimension (the organization of space, settlement size, the facilities, comfort and infrastructure) [3, p. 349-350].

From the above definitions, detach that rural tourism is dependent on the environment, which is the subject and scope of activity and development of tourism, natural resources while providing necessary.

Given this relationship of dependency, environmental protection and development is sine-qua-non condition for tourism, for any change produced to environment, how small, can generate reducing or even canceling harm natural resources and tourism potential of the area question.

is a relatively new term and refers to various forms of travel, directly related to agricultural activities and / or buildings that have purpose, role, functions in agriculture[2, p. 14].

From this perspective, agritourism is a special form of rural tourism and it is based on the countryside and the peasant household of accommodation, meals, entertainment and their related bulletins.

This form of rural tourism is practiced by smallholders in rural areas as a secondary activity to activity in their household (agriculture and livestock) as the main income generating activity.

Please note that activities and lodging provided to tourists is a secondary activity and the presence of host / hosts in the same living space with tourists, hosts tourists by providing living space surplus, disposed or arranged specifically for such activities without constituting a building housing separate hosts.

Although for some authors, agritourism and rural tourism are synonymous terms, we think the two are different notions, that have in common rural areas where the tourist develop their activities, but agritourism requires further use and promotion of biological agricultural products and promoting cultural heritage.

Based on this relationship between the two concepts, we consider that the definition captures all the elements that define specific agritourism we met in a scientific material

published in the journal *Studia Universitatis Vasile Goldis West University of Arad*, according to which agritourism is that action to move a person in a rural unpolluted, picturesque, with a specific agrarian completed by stay for a period of at least 24 hours in the farm, eating local food and nonfood products, and cohabitation, observation, assistance and co-participation in local social community, by enabling the entire compliance action[4, p. 163].

Production from specific foods consumed in tourism activity in their own host of peasant farming, rural tourism activity is high profitability and lack of trade margins and value added tax applied to food products consumed by tourists made also the prices of services Agro to be below the other forms of tourism.

The term green tourism used mostly in the Community, was originally used to refer to activities that were outside of tourist dedicated areas, and using colors to associate certain activities practiced by tourists such as winter sports – white tourism or holiday travel sea – blue tourism. Based on color symbolism, green was chosen because of synchrony with the countryside, with nature.

Based on color, green tourism was defined as an activity practiced in areas of provincial tourism, but also in sparsely populated coastal areas less involved in tourism activities, as in mountain areas that had no particular destination on winter sports, as at present to conclude that green tourism is stuck in rural communities who are in space or near national parks, natural parks or nature reserves[3, p. 352].

Ecotourism is a form of green tourism, marked by the practice to the unspoiled wilderness of human intervention, the main motivation for tourists is the observation and appreciation of nature and local traditions related to nature and the tourist action must preserve and protect nature so that the negative impact on the tourist presence and socio-cultural environment will be minimal.

2. Legislative regulatory of agro-tourism in Romania

Without having an official and continuous character, the casual visitor accommodation in their own home, especially in rural areas and from the shoreline, was practiced since the mid-twentieth century in our country, but only in 1967-1968 were made first rural tourism actions

organized within the network of national tourism.

Based on specific Romanian village, with reference to elements of rural tourism, by the Minister of Tourism nr.297/1972 Research Centre for international tourism has identified and proposed to introduce the domestic and international tourism has a number of 118 villages, as by the Minister of Tourism experimental nr.744/1973 be declared as "tourist villages" for national and international practice areas tourism following locations, in different counties covering all Romanian province : Letești - Arges county, Fundata and Sirnea - Brasov county, Sibiel - Sibiu county, Tismana – Gîrlău county; Mirighiol and Crisan - Tulcea county, Racos - Timis county, St. George – Tulcea county, Bogdan Vodă - Maramures county; Vatra Moldoviței - Suceava county, Poiana Sărată- Bacau county, Vaideeni - Valcea county.

Not an year had past from the efforts made to promote Romanian tourism villages, and hence the Romanian tourism at international level, and the Decree nr.225/1974 denied accommodation by foreign individuals domiciled in Romania, as well as land available to foreigners for installation of mobile accommodation. Failure of mandatory liability offenses attracted a fine of 5,000. to 15,000 lei, finding violations and imposing fines for the representatives of the executive committee of the People's Councils and the Ministry of Interior officers and NCOs.

Until 1989, the Decree nr.225/1974 exception recognized by the former regime, has created a breach in the tourism system by including in folklore and cultural programs of the Carpathians-Bucharest O.N.T. five villages declared tourist villages, which were promoted internationally by contracting with various foreign companies.

Amid a centralized economy and agriculture cooperatives organized by the state, which own and manage land with crops, until 1989 there was virtually no family farm, rural tourism essential, so that only after restitution of land to former landowners and strengthening private property in rural areas can be no question tourism development in Romania.

An important step for developing rural tourism in Romania was made in 1994 when the state passed a policy to support individuals and family associations, authorized by law, which provides tourist hostels or private farms located in rural

mountain areas over 500 m altitude, in the Danube Delta and Black Sea.

Benefits and tax concessions granted to promote rural tourism by Government Ordinance nr.62/1994 [5] refers to tax breaks to small and medium business, even if the legal conditions required for this, and also the following forms of support:

- provision by local councils of available land owned by them, for the construction or development of areas and farm guesthouses Agro;
- prioritizing the installation of telecommunications lines;
- specialized technical assistance from the Ministry of Tourism;
- Promoting the agro advertising guesthouses and farms belonging to individuals and family associations approved for rural tourism in tourist promotion materials of the ministry and presenting them with actions taken to promote foreign tourist information offices of the Ministry of Tourism;
- exemption from income tax for a period of three years of the guesthouses and agritourism farms are authorized to provide travel services.

The legislator also comes out expressly by the Government Ordinance nr.62/1994 differences for the recruitment category agro tourist guesthouses and farms, the legal definition of features based tourism as a form of rural tourism.

Thus, if pensions are tourist accommodation structures for housing and meals, with a capacity between 3 and 20 rooms, operating in public housing or independent buildings, private farms have the same basic elements, and a characteristic element: providing food tourists is made with fresh products and traditional own resources or local.

By Law no.145/1994 approving the Government Ordinance nr.62/1994 [6] facility tax was extended to exemption on income tax for up to 10 years.

Year 1994 is the year of establishment of the National Association of Rural, Ecological and Cultural known by the abbreviation ANTREC with an important role in promoting rural tourism, member of European Federation of Rural Tourism (EUROGITES).

Most of the ANTREC objectives were achieved, the association has been a promoter of

sustainable rural tourism. Among the objectives achieved include:

- identifying and disseminating tourism potential of rural areas;
- training through seminars, workshops and training of entrepreneurs in rural tourism exchanges in the country and abroad;
- publishing newsletters and magazines about rural tourism in Romania,;
- the establishment a database with farms and rural tourism in Romania pensions and services;
- advertising campaigns through media touristic guesthouses and farms;
- participation in national and international fairs to promote the Romanian rural tourism;
- creating a system of online booking in Romanian rural tourism, which currently operates on the association's website.

Evidence of the role of promoter ANTREC is assumed that in 1998, with the assistance of EU funds, is published and promoted international first catalog of farms and agro guesthouses in the country, bringing together a number of not less than 736 locations.

The legislature returns in 1997 and repeal Government Ordinance nr.62/1994 and adopt a new Ordinance establishing facilities for rural tourism development, Government Ordinance nr.63/1997 [7] respectively and currently in force, after approval by Law 187 / in 1998[8].

Changes to the new law regards on the extension of facilities for rural tourism development in any rural area, without the express geographical limitation from earlier legislation, and more expansion facilities include agro touristic pensions and guesthouses located in villages and communes belonging to the cities and municipalities.

Also, it must be said that previous facilities are maintained, indicating that income tax exemption applies agro tourist guesthouses and guesthouses, with an accommodation capacity of up to 10 rooms including, plus tariff grant used by individuals for electricity, methane gas and telecommunications services used by the agro touristic pensions and guesthouses can accommodate up to 5 rooms including.

As a form of organization of rural tourism activities may be organized either as an individual, the family business or company, in whatever form granted the same facilities.

The legislature uses the terms of guesthouses and rural locations, maintaining the characteristics of the touristic pensions, agro farms respectively from the previous legislative

act, with restriction, to agro-touristic pensions case, for food to be used for feeding tourists to its production of the host household.

By law approving Government Ordinance nr.63/1998 legislature comes and make some changes and clarifications. Thus, the category of facilities provided, mention priority connections to electricity, water, gas and sewer, since not all rural communities are public utilities and connection costs are substantial, while tourists have provided comfort under the same conditions for all pensions from a certain category of classification.

Exemption from income tax, income that is maintained on the same period of 10 years, which commences from the date the pension classification, choice of facilities no longer period left to the owner, because the legislature intended that this facility to newly established benefit pensions, and not claimed by the owner according to their financial interests.

If a boarding house or facility agrotourist received exemption from income tax, ie income, but rural tourism outgoing transition before a period of less than twice the period of exemption, the owner must repay state budget or local budgets income tax that the corporation was exempt for the entire period that benefited from this facility.

Also in order to attract investments for infrastructure development of rural tourism, but also increases the comfort of tourists, the legislature has provided by law approving ordinance loans with preferential interest for a maximum of 10 years, interest incurred by the beneficiaries of loans of half in the interest of the banking market.

Since it is the granting of new banking facilities that are privately owned banks, the difference in interest rate to banks is granted bank lender under Government Ordinance nr.63/1998 funds Ministry of Tourism.

By law approving Ordinance nr.63/1998 legislature includes pensions in the agro tourist guesthouses, both forms of accommodation with the same capacity - up to 10 rooms and 30 seats - and the same location - the people or buildings housing independent. The element that distinguishes them is to provide tourists with some of the food products produced by itself, in agrotouristic pensions case.

Basically, by including the category of agrotouristic tourist guesthouses, classification maintained also through the Order of the National Tourism Authority nr.61/1999,

legislature comes, indirectly, declare agritourism as a specific form of rural tourism, but rural and agro pensions are regulated separately by tourist pension and rural tourism, because there are similar concepts, but they are identical up to a certain point, where from starting separators elements.

Starting with the Government Decision nr.1328/2001 [9] in the legal regulations it is not meet about notion of rural locations, legislator using the concepts of pension urban and rural pension, while changing the criteria for the classification of units of accommodation-reception.

And yet, ANTREC maintain the notion of rural locations, as of September 2004 to change the criteria for agro pensions harmonizing European legislation in this area code. Changing the classification criteria was to include, in addition to the classification system maintained daisies previously classified in relation to functionality guesthouses and Breakfast Family, rural locations, pensions romantic (offers tourists a unique atmosphere in terms of the natural environment, of architecture and decoration), fishing and hunting hostels, hostels for skiing, boarding wine hostels.

Referring to the facilities for agro-touristic pensions must remember that by mountain law no.347/2004 [10] was introduced a special category boarding mountain agro-touristic pensions, and to support rural tourism in mountain areas, the legislature has regulated, apart from tax benefits recognized to agro-tourism through Ordinance Government no.63/1998, exemption from income tax and land tax for 5 years after construction, if their accommodation capacity not exceeding 20 seats.

This feature was eliminated by modifying the Law of the mountain but so far there is not any financial incentives for rural tourism regulated by special law, except as provided by Government Ordinance nr.63/1998.

3. Conclusions and recommendations

Reported the potential of agro-tourism in Romania, believe that the regulations and the interest at national level are minimal, given that most European countries put particular emphasis on rural tourism development, see, among others, and a solution recovery.

Agro-tourism as a form of rural tourism is a factor of rural development, promoting

Romanian values and traditions, capitalizing the farms.

Given the social and economic development of rural tourism, consider the problem of rural development through tourism is a problem as acute as it is necessary to be solved.

Since the basic cell system is rural farm, rural tourism development strategies should aim at developing agriculture and rural socio-cultural environment, so that in addition to products of farming and housing in rural areas, owners of boarding agro tourism can provide appropriate services.

Interacting of rural tourism, rural tourism and rural development across Europe resulted in legislative and administrative interest for farm development in particular and rural development in general.

Since in the Romanian legislation is legislation granting facilities for rural tourism, taking the Italian model, we consider that the development of a framework law covering all aspects (organizational, financial and administrative division of Romania's provinces reported on) needed to develop tourism in Romania is more than necessary.

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ASPECTS REGARDING PHYTOSANITARY TREATMENTS APPLICATION SPECIFIC TO THE CONCEPT OF ECOLOGICAL FARMING IN ORCHARDS

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Abstract: *Development of ecological farming is one of the fundamental guidelines in developed countries, especially in the European Union. Intense use of synthetic pesticides in agricultural practice is one of several factors that have caused progressive degradation of the environment over recent decades. Ecological fruit farming represents an alternative production, based on the rational exploitation of nature. As part of ecological farming, has the same objective and is based on the same principles.*

Keywords: *ecological fruit farming, clean active substances, biological control.*

1. Introduction

Around 1920 the idea arose when the practice of ecological farming industrial society began to replace the rural. Thus in Europe have differed in chronological order, **three trends**: biodynamic, organic and biological farming.

Biodynamic farming is based on the natural laws of life and unity of soil-plant-animal-man, the greater importance being given "vital forces". Its luminaries were Rudolf Steiner and Ehrenfried Pfeiffer in Germany.

Davidescu (1994) argues that biodynamic farming is characterized by the use of nine biodynamic preparations that are made from herbs (yarrow, chamomile, dandelion, valerian, nettle, oak bark), manure and silica, which are used mixed with water in very small quantities per hectare.

Organic farming emerged in England after the Second World War and based on exclusive use of organic fertilizer. This trend attributed humus a fundamental role in biological balance and soil fertility. The founder of this trend was Albert Howard, who in "Agricultural Testament", published in 1940, stresses the disadvantages monocultures, disappearance of small farms, the use of mineral fertilizers and the role of associated crops (grasses, legumes) and soil fertility in ensuring plant resistance to pests.

In the same period in Austria, Hans Peter Rusch propose a method of organic-biological agriculture, based on the observation that in nature plants and slurry waste is biodegradable and come to fatten the ground without anyone to

incorporate into the soil. This trend is adopted in Switzerland by Hans Müller.

Biological farming was promoted after the Second World War (70 years) by consumers and physicians concerned with the effects of food on human health.

More in the last two or three decades have developed awareness of responsibility towards the environment, formed several organizations (1972, IFOAM) producers aiming to promote biological farming.

In this context, ecological fruit farming developed as part of biological farming. Development of ecological farming is one of the fundamental guidelines in developed countries, especially in the European Union due to increasing concerns for improving the quality and safety of the food chain and develop an ethic of sustainable use of resources in agriculture.

The main direction for improving the phytosanitary treatment application technologies and appropriate technical equipments is treatment quality increasing by making **clean work processes** that lead to environmental rehabilitation and obtain healthy products.

Intense use of synthetic pesticides in agricultural practice is one of several factors that have caused progressive degradation of the environment over recent decades. Although it proved effective in combating agricultural pests and diseases, and recent research have focused primarily on environmental aspects and quantities of harmful chemical residues in food, ground water and soil.

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Quick installation of the phenomenon of resistance of pests to pesticides chemical and environmental degradation require research and promotion of selective and biodegradable pesticides.

New stringent international regulations restricting the use of chemical pesticides, eliminating many effective products on the market, will seriously limit the options based on efficiency / cost of beneficiaries and users will be able to opt for less toxic products or use synthetic pesticides natural or safe.

Searches in improving phytosanitary treatment of different plant types are permanent. Thus, **a new direction is the ecological phytosanitary treatments with active substances derived from plants, plant debris, or less polluting substances.**

2. Trends in development of fruit farming in Romania

Romania's climate and soil culture provides favorable conditions fruit trees and shrubs, widespread species, depending on their biological requirements throughout the country in the field to altitudes of 800-1000 m above.

Heritage fruit trees, consisting of orchards and nurseries in the '80s totaled 290.000 ha, representing 2% of the agricultural area of the country. Today, heritage fruit trees is greatly reduced, the total area cultivated with fruit trees in 2005 was 142.300 ha. Annually, new surface formed with various tree species is approximately 2000 ha, while declining plantation area is about 30 times higher. Orchards structure by age is shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Orchards structure by age

Competitiveness of fruit farms largely depends on the ratio of production for fresh consumption and for industrial processing.

If and when the plantations reached adulthood this report lies in favor of production for fresh

consumption - for plantations under 10 years, the ratio is 90% -10% for the age group 10-20 years, report is 80% -20% and between 25-30 years old plantations ratio is 75% - 25% - for plantations in decline, the ratio is reversed in favor of production for processing, at least 50% of total production.

Development trends on fruit farming, experts support the idea that fruit production should not increase due to the increase of areas, but the yield per unit area.

Given the economic importance of fruit, horticulture development programs in our country include priority measures and actions. Of these, the first place is **to promote trees ecological cultivation techniques and technologies.**

The Sustainable Development Strategy of Romania "Horizon 2025" states that Romania will promote agriculture in a multifunctional role, which can gradually face the European and world market in which to practice farming methods that protect the environment and be able to provide quality products and safe food and animal population.

One of the objectives of sustainable development and complex strategy is to support **ecological farming** and protection measures and environmental protection and preservation of natural environment.

The crop production sector in general and fruit farming in particular, the strategy provides positive developments by 2025 compared with 2004, as follows:

- will increase the fruit trees area with about 23%, and vineyards with about 11%;
- consumption of fruit and vegetables will increase and the variety of species and varieties will be diversified, with emphasis on fruit from shrubs crops;
- increase fruit production, with about 43%, vegetable field with about 26% and grapes with around 61%;
- ensure equal access of agricultural producers of the plant facilities to be granted as a result of EU accession.

In Romania, the number of entrepreneurs engaged in ecological farming is increasing, according to a recent study of the National Federation of Ecological Farming (NFEF). According to NFEF, ecological farming attracts more investors as a result of up to 400% profit obtainable from ecological crops.

3. Peculiarities in ecological orchards

Ecological fruit farming represents an alternative production, based on the rational exploitation of nature. As part of ecological farming have the same objective and is based on the same principles.

Some of the objectives of ecological farming, as defined by the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements of (IFOAM), refers to:

- obtain high nutritional value of agricultural products in sufficient quantities;
- application of working methods compatible with the environment ("by nature"), rather than attempt to dominate nature;
- avoid any form of pollution that may result from agricultural techniques;
- farmers insurance of satisfactory living conditions, adequate wages and a safe working environment.

Principles of ecological farming is based on thorough knowledge of production systems the most of local resources, to minimize economic and environmental risks, integrating traditional knowledge with science in all fields of biology. These principles are: preservation of soil fertility - to feed the soil to feed the plant, environmental protection, abolishing the use of synthetic chemical fertilizers and pesticides, disease control, pest and weed prevention methods and respect for consumer health.

It was found that intensive culture systems increase the risk of disturbances in the ecological balance of ecosystems. It is therefore necessary remodeling of the current ecological type of progress in horticulture, to ensure environmental protection. This need not mean traditional culture systems, but rather the practice of modern technology, based more on biological processes yields, the virtues of the phenomenon of photosynthesis and increased use of solar energy efficiency, quality and humificare decomposition phenomenon, mainly on organic fertilization and cover crops associated pedoameliorative in orchards, on integrated prevention and control systems, mainly biological, the application of other methods of mechanization and irrigation, finally, the integration of regional intensive fruit growing agroecosystems sustainable and competitive. For it is necessary to extend the cultivation of varieties with resistance to pathogen attack, stress conditions, varieties

grown in different ecological zones to allow full expression of genetic potential that possesses variety, especially in terms of production.

Soil works are expected in **ecological fruit farming** which least disturb the soil microbial activity and ensure the maintenance structure. The plow, one of the most commonly applied soil tillage in orchards should not be buried deep horizons to not "live" on the surface, which would harm the soil biological activity. Fresh organic matter (plant residues, green manure, organic fertilizers fresh) are not incorporated into depth, but superficially, to be subject to prior humificări aerobic and may be limited as the number of passes with heavy equipment to avoid soil compaction, the negative effect on the structure, aeration and on its biological activity.

To prevent these negative phenomena in orchards is the separation of traffic lanes for crossings only aggregates, so the number of mechanical interventions on soil is minimized. The application of integrated, rational means for combining chemical and biological, mechanical and physical methods use agro, allowing reduction of environmental pollution. Given all this, more and more scientists consider necessary to develop new concepts for alternative crop development technologies, aimed at reshaping the current type of progress, in accordance with the requirements underlying their harmonization with the laws of nature.

Fertilization in ecological fruit farming should be based on organic fertilizers, limiting fertilizer use only minerals to balance the mineral nutrition to the needs of species and soil nutrient balance. Fertilization should be based on continuous monitoring of agro-technical properties of soils, soil supply levels correlate with the requirements of trees, establishing differentiated in terms of how fattening system, doses and ages fertilizer management. The fertilizer should be differentiated according to species, variety, rootstock. In terms of fertilization, it is considered necessary amplification research in the following areas:

- monitoring the status of land supply and nutritional status of trees in order to establish optimal values and application of differentiated fertilization;
- develop new fertilization schemes with organic fertilizers and organo-mineral humus content to increase and maintain an intense activity of the biocenosis build;

- use of leguminous green manure in young plantations, - replacement of synthetic chemical fertilizers with substances considered "biological" (EU regulations);
- generalized use extraroot fertilization that improves the nutritional status of trees in critical periods, with minimal environmental impact.

4. Biological control of pests and diseases

The International Organization for Biological Battle (I.O.B.B.) defines biological control using living organisms and their biological activity products in order to regulate pest populations.

Extension of biological pest control, is one of the perspective direction of development of plant protection, especially to reduce and eliminate pollution phenomena that can produce chemicals. Conservation and natural activation control population densities of pests must be based on a profound knowledge of all factors and links biocenotic.

In ecological fruit farming weeds are not considered "enemies" to be fought but rather a resource that must be managed correctly. Weeds compete with trees in plantations and, undoubtedly affects their productivity. This competition occurs in certain critical periods of plantation development. Outside these periods, weeds can have important beneficial effects, providing surface protection and soil biological activity stimulation by root exudates released.

To avoid plantation invasion by unwanted weeds, place emphasis on preventive aspects such as: execution of plowing in the early spring, soil grassing for permanent use. In general, at present there is a clear trend of "greening" activities that depend on the environment.

The basic principle of the concept of biological control is the balance biocenotic that the population of a species (prey, host) is conditional on other species (predators, parasites and pathogens). But this balance is swinging, is dynamic and can be disrupted by some agrotechnical practices and plant protection. Therefore it is necessary to create favorable conditions for entomophags. Wiackowski (1971) attaches great importance to so-called prophylactic biological methods, meaning the entomophags concentration methods in the culture emphasizes particularly useful supplementary food (nectar of flowers, pollen and sweet secretions of insects), intermediate

hosts, and places wintering and generally entomophags concentration methods (culture in strips of alfalfa and other agro-technical and organizational measures).

The main **methods of biological control** of pests in agricultural systems are:

- zoophags use (predators and parasites);
- microbiological control (pathogenic microorganisms);
- genetic methods (autocidics);
- pheromones;
- **spraying with biological substances.**

Zoophags are very different and highly specific for different pests. In addition can own to develop spontaneously as a result of numerical growth of the host (pest). This means that what is natural resources can renew themselves. In recent years improved methods have been developed for mass multiplication of species of zoophags. Of great interest are zoophags species which acquired resistance to some pesticides and thus can fit better in combat.

Hormones and pheromones as regulators of growth, development and behavior of insects, are chemical messengers, have no toxic action itself. As transmitters of information disturbing development program at certain times and they provide a great selectivity. Hormones have a different mode of action. Immediate mortality by treating a culture medium is relatively low, but survival is very low the next phases, reduce fecundity of females, increase the percentage of sterile eggs, which ultimately leads to a high efficiency. But this effectively protects crops later than usual treatment with an insecticide. Pheromones are substances excreted by insects in the surrounding atmosphere and determine the behavior and other forms of activity of the body. Unlike self-professed hormones secreted by endocrine glands and which function, work full body insect pheromones secreted by exocrine glands and other relations of relations between individuals in the population. During the past 25 years genetic methods for suppression or eradication of harmful insects have become reality. Genetic suppression of insect pests is unique among genetic pest control methods, it involves the release genetically modified insects to combat the same species, so these methods are autocides. It is a method based on the idea of self-destruction of harmful species, but by measures applied by man.

An attractive aspect of biological battle as a method of insect control is economic. Although this method requires substantial initial investment

for equipment and labor, they are paying generous benefits to results.

Microbiological products have also progressed significantly. Use of entomopathogenic viruses as preparations formulated has great potential for use. 320 viruses were isolated from more than 250 species of insects and mites, of which 38 were experienced in fighting insects.

Technology of the application of microbiological plant protection means should be developed according to the most sensitive stage of the pest and to ensure ingestion of the product by the insect. For many products microbiological methods have developed long interaction of microbes with insects.

Mixtures of biological products and especially those selective also allow dose reduction of biological and chemical product, a better storage of entomophags and avoid or delay in the existing races.

In so far as it will develop products subject that can be maintained over time, these products will expand much more. Microbiological successes in combating allow frequent use of these solutions to combat inside integrated systems.

An important role in combating have substances acting on critical processes and behavior. These substances are actually more selective nature and thus allows to recover and to activate entomophags in the cultures are used.

Bioproducts are made using biological means microorganisms useful crop plants or based on natural compounds (plant extracts, called suggestively "botanicals"). Due to their biological nature, bioproducts have a complex action on crop plants, the correct term is not used in the bio plant protection, but the bio-agricultural use. Already become a classic example, illustrating this complex action is that of bio-based antagonistic fungi of the genus *Trichoderma*. Biofungicides approved as a series of bio proved to be stimulating plant growth and the stimulation of plant growth was found to be due to biofungicide intervention in plant nutrition.

Using bioproducts is an important direction in current agriculture because it has advantages:

- reduce environmental pollution and food;
- avoiding pest populations resistant to combat treatments;
- the use of unqualified staff under total security (both crop plants and for the user);

- sustainable use of resources useful so far unexploited agricultural systems.

Clean phytopharmaceuticals preparations obtained from plants

The extract is a preparation obtained from cold. Plant parts, chopped, put in contact with water 12-24 hours. Flask may be shaken several times, then filtered.

Infusions or teas are prepared from fresh or dried plant material, fresh shredded by pouring boiling water over it, then cover until complete cooling and filter.

Decoction or broth. First plant material is soaked in water for 24 hours at room temperature, covered, then simmer for 20-30 minutes content. After cooling filter.

Doughs are fermented juices with a wide range of use. Chopped plant material is placed in containers placed in a sunny, ventilated and protected from rain. Pour water, leaving a space foam fermentation capture. Container boards covered with a grill. Shake daily. 2-3 weeks after fermentation ends (stops foaming, obtaining a dark liquid).

Natural phytopharmaceuticals preparations to **remove** pests are presented in table 1.

Natural phytopharmaceuticals preparations that **kill** pests are presented in table 2.

5. Conclusions

- The ecological fruit farming was developed as component part of biological agriculture; the development of biological agriculture is one of the fundamental guidelines in developed countries and in particular in the EU due to growth interests for improving the safety of the food chain and the development of ethical and sustainable use of resources in agriculture.
- Considering the economic importance of fruits, the fruit farming development programs in our country include measure and priority actions.
- One of the objectives of sustainable and complex development of the strategy "Horizon 2025" is to support ecological agriculture and conservation measures and the protection of the environment and preservation of natural ambient.
- The soil tillage proposed in ecological fruit farming are those which cause the least soil microbial activity and ensure the maintenance of its structure.

- The fertilization in ecological fruit farming must be based on organic fertilisers, mineral fertilizers with the limitation of using only for balancing nutrition needs mineral species and mineral elements from the soil's balance sheet.
- In ecological fruit farming the weeds are not considered "enemies" which must be disproves, they are resources which must be managed correctly; the weeds can have significant benefits, ensuring protection of the surface of the soil and a stimulating biological activity by exudates tufts released.
- The main methods of biological control of pests in agricultural systems are: use predators and parasites; combating microbial (pathogen-free); genetic methods (autocidices); pheromones and biological substances for aspersions.
- Biopreparations are biological means completed on the basis of microorganisms useful plants or on the basis of natural compounds (herbal extracts).
- The clean clean phytopharmaceuticals preparations obtained from plants are: extracts, infusions or teas, decoctions or broth and doughs.

Table 1

Preparation	Pests
Semi dough fermented of nettle (<i>Urtica dioica</i> , <i>U. urens</i>), 2%	leaf lice and mites
Nettle extract, 100%	leaf lice
Lump of eagle fern or fern field (<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>), 10%	leaf lice (aspidinofilicina, tuiona filicic acid)
Lump in the fern forest (<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i>), 10% (vegetație) și 100% (repaus)	lice lice tested and woolly in fruit trees
Extract of fern forest, 100%	woolly lice in apple
Vetricia infusion of flowers (<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>), 25%	lice leaf and root, apple and plum worm, worms ground (essential oil based tuiona)
Lump of pieplant leaves (<i>Rheum rhabarbarum</i>), 50%	leaf lice and caterpillars (oxalic acid)
Infusion of condurași (<i>Tropaeolum majus</i>), 100%	woolly lice in apple (sulfur and antibiotics)
Tomato leaf extract (<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>), 100%	albilița (solanine and essential oil from leaves)
Lump of wormwood (<i>Artemisia absinthum</i>), 100%	caterpillars (with essential oil and azulene tuiona, bitter substances - absintina, absintiina, artemitina)
Decoction of wormwood, 100%	albilița and apple worm
Infusion of marjoram (<i>Origanum vulgare</i>), 25%	lice tested in houseplants

Table 2

Preparation	Pests
Pyrethrins, extracts of pyrethrum flowers (<i>Pyrethrum cinerareaefolium</i>)	aphids, Colorado potato beetle, thrips, cicadas, white flies (chrysanthemum esters)
Rotenone, extract from the roots of tropical plants (<i>Deris eliptica</i>)	gadfly on pastureland
Cyasia tropical plant wood extract (<i>Quassi amara</i>)	many pests, including the house and stable flies (bitter substances, quassina and tannins).
Tobacco juice (<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> or <i>N. rustica</i>)	hairy caterpillars, woolly lice (alkaloid nicotine)
Alcoholic extract of leaves of castor (<i>Rhus typhina</i>)	some leaf lice and caterpillars (over 70 bioactive substances, hexahidrofarnesilacetona)

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IMPORTANCE OF PREDATOR SOIL MITES DIVERSITY IN DAMAGED AGRICULTURE FIELDS RESTAURATION

Minodora MANU

Abstract: *The damaged agriculture fields are characterized by a decreased fertility and low plant productivity. One of the less studied tools for their ecological restoration is soil fauna diversity. Soil is the most favorable habitat for predatory mites. The structure and function of soil mites biota could be modified due to the chosen cultivation method. The paper presents scientific arguments for the role of soil mite's diversity as a bioindicator tool for agroecosystem's ecological reconstruction. A comparative study made in two types of ecosystems from Insula Mare a Brăilei, Romania, demonstrated that in arable fields, soil mites diversity decreased significantly, in comparison with a natural ecosystem.*

Keywords: *agroecosystem, biodiversity, fertility, mites, productivity.*

1. Introduction.

The soil fertility is considered to be a characteristic due to the nutrients flow, existence of pathogens, herbivores and mutualism species, to the favorable environmental factors [2, 9]. But the most important factor is the presence of the soil fauna. The soil fauna is represented by animals which spend their whole life or only a part of their biological cycle in soil. In soil fauna are included invertebrates with important role in vegetal material decomposing (soil mites), participating to the soil formation (influencing its fertility) and indirectly to the productivity of cultures. Through activity of different trophic components from soil web, the edaphic fauna provided over 75% from total assimilated energy by the plants [1, 10, 24].

Chemical pollution of agricultural soils (irrational use of synthetically pesticides, fungicides and to synthetic fertilizers) increased importance given to soil mites. All these anthropical interventions (including the intense exploitation of agricultural soils) determine quantitative (density) and qualitative (diversity) modifications, in comparison with natural ecosystems. The chemical pollution affects the mites soil fauna directly and indirectly. The directly effects are associated with pollutants transmission on trophic chain, from biotic compartment to another. The indirect effects are the decreasing or missing of food resources for mites (microfauna), modifications of organic matter and microclimate [4, 5, 6, 17, 18, 27].

On the other hand, soil biological responses to climate changes are complex, and have been

considered in a realistic, multifactor framework. Climate changes can influence soil microarthropod community abundance and composition directly by altering soil microclimate and indirectly by altering resource availability and the composition of the soil food web. Increased temperature (which is one of the aridization causes) and other climate factors may indirectly influence soil microarthropod communities (as soil mites) through changes in plant physiology or community structure which can alter resource availability and microhabitat conditions [8, 11, 14, 16].

On soil habitats, recultivation measures should fulfill a twofold task: prevent aridization (erosion, leaching of nutrients) and stimulate biodiversity with all its consequences for sustainability of ecosystem functions and nature protection. The fast establishments of a gramineous vegetation cover, which have bioretention capacities, determine an increasing biodiversity of soil mites, perhaps due to the creation of high habitat diversity or to provide enough islands for spontaneous natural succession. Because of its role as promoter of ecosystem services (e.g., soil fertility, carbon sequestration, water infiltration), soil mites should be considered in the assessment of risk associated with climate change and intensive use of the soil resource [15, 17, 18, 19].

All these scientifically argues demonstrated the importance of soil mites as bioindicators of natural or damaged ecosystems (as agriculture fields).

2. Material and methods

In soil mites sampling we take into considerations some ecological criterias, as: the minimum studied area by 100 sq.m. and the minimum 10 samples in order to provide the statistical assurance. The soil samplings were collected randomly (taking account of the environmental factors heterogeneity), with MacFadyen soil core, by 5 cm diameter. The sampling was made till 10 cm depth. 40 soil samples were collected. Two populational parameters were analysed: numerical density (ind./sq.m.) and species diversity (number of species). The statistical analysis (abundance plot) was conducted with the aid of the BioDiversity Pro 2.0 software, designed and developed by Neil McAleece and provided by The Natural History Museum, London.

In order to compare the structure of predatory mites populations (Acari-Gamasina), two types of ecosystems were analysed: natural grassland and agriculture field from Insula Mare a Brăilei, in period 2005-2006. Insula Mare a Brăilei is situated on the lower course of the Danube, in Brăila district. The natural grassland (N 44°87'19.40"; E = 28°05'86.10"), was characterized by the following vegetation species: *Lemnetum minoris*, *Elodeetum nuttallii*, *Scirpo-phragmitetum*, *Typhetum angustifoliae*, *Typhetum latifoliae*, *Typhetum laxmannii*, *Sparganietum erecti*, *Sclerochloa-Polygonetum avicularis*, *Hordetum murini*, *Cynodonto-Atriplicetum tataricae*, *Tanaceto-Artemisietum vulgaris*, *Ambrosietum artemisiifoliae*, *Conietum mculati*, *Bolletetum nigrae* and *Sambucetum ebuli*. The vegetal associations were *Hordeetum murini* Libbert 1932 em. Pass. 1964, *Agropyretum pectiniformae* (Prodan 1939) Dihoru 1970. The agriculture field was cultivated with *Zea mays* L. (N: 44° 78' 99,1"; E: 28° 00' 65,5") [29].

3. Results and discussions

In our study from Insula Mare a Brăilei, the soil was tilled. This cultivation technique determines modification on soil horizons, decreasing the quantity of organic matter, which is the favorable habitat for the predator

soil mites. The organic matter is the main trophic reservoirs for the edaphically fauna. Many other researchers demonstrated, that the structure (biodiversity) and function of soil mites biota could be modified due to the chosen cultivation method. Periodic tillage and planting continually reverts the tilled area to an earlier stage of ecological succession.

Physical disturbance of the soil caused by tillage and residue management is a crucial factor in determining soil biotic activity and species diversity in agroecosystems. As a proper solution to these cultivation techniques is "alternative" or sustainable agriculture. Weed control or mulching are optimal methods used in agricultural field restoration [12, 13, 25] (Table 1).

In investigated areas from Insula Mare a Brăilei, the species diversity had different values. 16 predatory soil mites were identified (14 in grassland and 2 in arable field), with a total numerical density by 16.800 ind./sq.m. (16.000 ind./sq.m. in grassland and 800 ind./sq.m. in arable field) (Table 2)

A square meter of an organic temperate agricultural soil may contain 1000 species of organisms with population densities in the order of 10⁶/sq.m. for nematodes, 10⁵/sq.m. for microarthropods and 10⁴/sq.m. for other invertebrate groups [2].

The role of mite's diversity in soil processes was demonstrated by many specialists. They contribute in nutrient cycling as well as in soil structure [1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 17, 18, 23, 24, 26]. As a result of the relation between mites activities and ecosystem processes could be the improvement of the soil fertility and affect plant primary productivity.

Analysing the abundance plot, the graph revealed differences between mite communities from the investigated ecosystems. The highest values of numerical abundance were recorded on mite communities from grassland, while the lowest were observed on invertebrates from arable field. (Fig. 1). The grassland's mite communities are represented by some species with the highest number of individuals: *Hypospis aculeifer* (14), *Rhodacarellus kreuzi* (9) and *Olopachys vysotskajae* and *Parasitus sp.* (each 5).

Table 1

Soil characteristics and ecological effects on different cultivation methods.

Cultivation techniques	Soil	Ecological effects
Tillage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - disturbs at least 15–25 cm of the soil surface; - replaces stratified surface soil horizons with a tilled zone more homogeneous with respect to physical characteristics and residue distribution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lost of nutrients by leaching, - less organic matter, - the decomposer food chain is bacteria-based, - decreased soil organisms and plant diversity, - exposure to predation.
No-tillage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specifically low porosity resulting from the particle-size distribution and mainly the presence of low-activity clay, - high bulk density values, an indicator of high soil compaction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - more nutrient conserving, - the decrease in pH and organic matter content, - macrofaunal abundance, richness and diversity were significantly lower than in natural grassland, - favors the development of fungi, - restrict root system development and crop growth.
Sustainable or 'alternative' agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - availability of organic material, - erosion control, - good porosity and water flow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - water conservation, - increased fertility, - greater biological activity, - soil carbon sequestration, - favorable microclimate, - complexity of food webs, - protect soil life and its diversity.

Fig. 1. Abundance plot for the identified mites species from the investigated ecosystems.

Due to the natural process of ecological restoration, in grassland, the soil is richer in organic matter (due to the characteristic vegetation), in comparison with monoculture. These species are easily adapted to soil dryness, due to their wide trophical spectrum (predators), to their mobility and to the possibility of

migration in soil till 20 cm [17, 18]. These species were identified in other type of ecosystems, where the soil is characterized by a small quantity of organic matter and decreased humidity, as: shrubs, adjacent area of cliff, urban parks and spoilt areas [20, 21, 22, 23].

Table 2

Soil mites identified in Insula Mare a Brăilei.

Species	Grassland	Arable Field	Biogeographical distribution	Habitat
<i>Pergamasus quisquiliarum</i>	•		Europe, South America	Arabe field orchards, compost, humus
<i>Pergamasus barbarus</i>	•		Central Europe	Soil, moss, humus, litter.
<i>Pergamasus sp.</i>	•			
<i>Parasitus krepelini</i>	•			Compost, humus, moos, litter
<i>Parasitus sp.</i>	•			
<i>Epicriopsis horridus</i>	•		Europe	Soil
<i>Arctoseius semiscissus</i>	•		Europe	Litter, humus, moss, meadows
<i>Rhodacarellus kreuzi</i>	•		South-East Europe, Central Europe, Russia	Humus, moss, soil, litter.
<i>Geholaspis longispinosus</i>		•	Europe	Litter, humus, soil detritus, moss, lichens, ant-hills, nests, dung.
<i>Macrocheles decoloratus</i>	•		Europe, Asia	nests
<i>Olopachys vysotskajae</i>		•	East Europe	
<i>Hypoaspis aculeifer</i>	•		Europe, Asia, North America	Grassland, heathland, sand dunes, seashore, moss, nests, coal shale, arable field, farm animal waste, stored cereal products, decaying vegetation
<i>Pachyseius humeralis</i>	•		Europe	Grassland, arable field, mine, decaying vegetation
<i>Zercon romagniolus</i>	•		Central and South Europe	Soil substrates, wood detritus, moss, rocky slopes, screens
<i>Trachytes aegrota</i>	•		Europe	Decaying vegetation from forest
<i>Uropoda sp.</i>	•			
Total no.of ind./sq.m.	16.000	800		

Table 3

Comparative species diversity and numerical abundances of predatory soil mites from agroecosystem and natural ecosystem.

Country	Agroecosystem		Natural ecosystem	
	No. ind./sq.m.	No. of species	No. ind./sq.m.	No. of species
Germany	5000	7	10000	15
Latvia		104		141
Argentina	987	14	2737	15
Romania	8000	23	15900	35

Other specialists from the world have recorded different values of these two populational parameters, in relation with types of studied ecosystems (agriculture field and natural area). The highest values of numerical abundance and of species diversity was recorded in natural ecosystems, in comparison with agroecosystems [6, 7, 15, 17, 18, 21, 22, 28] (Table 3).

The study made in Romania demonstrated the biodiversity of predatory mites is influenced by the soil management system. The species number and the numerical abundance were more increased in natural ecosystem. On agriculture fields the species number of identified mites and their densities are decreasing significantly, from 16.000 ind./sq.m. to 800 ind./sq.m.

4. Conclusions

The plant productivity and the soil fertility are the important characteristics for agriculture fields. These characteristics are influenced by the soil fauna (including the mites), directly or indirectly. This paper suggests that the microarthropods are extremely sensitive to land management practices. The chosen cultivation method could influence the structure and function of soil biota. The biological activity of these invertebrates and their diversity in optimal environment represents a natural tool to restoration the undisturbed soil ecosystems. On the other hand, even the presence or absence of specialized species, the modifications on populational parameters (species diversity, numerical abundance) could be biondicators for the natural or damaged agriculture soils.

In Romania, the edaphically studies concerning the soil fauna from agroecosystems is poorly developed. We consider that soil mites researches from agroecosystems will be an important tool for ecological restoration of the damaged agriculture fields in the future.

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ASPECTS REGARDING THE TECHNICAL-ORGANIZATIONAL PROBLEMS IN THE AGRICULTURAL TRANSPORTS

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Abstract: Each year in Romania, in a first phase, 80...100 million tons of agricultural products and materials are transported, for which an adequate material base has to be ensured. With respect to a monthly average of 8...9 million tons, in September and October 20...25 million tons of agricultural products require transport, for which large material values are made available (means of transport, fuels, lubricants etc.), as well as important human resources. The permanent of transport requirements, a correct choice of transport and manipulation means represent essential factors for normal working processes in agriculture, which aspects are approached in the present paper.

Keywords: agricultural transports, seasonality, production dispersion.

1. Introduction

The large volume of required work, the important energy consumptions as well as the characteristics of agricultural transports call for up-to-date information regarding all these aspects, in order to keep transport from becoming a restricting or even a negative factor of agricultural production. It has been estimated [1] that in Romania transports require about 30% of the labour volume in agriculture, and that in other countries their weight is even greater [2].

The material base of agricultural transports consists of tractor-agricultural trailer type aggregates, which between November and May cover over 70% of transport requirements. From June to October the base agricultural transport consists of motor vehicle type means, as tractors are implied in other agricultural works too, and as the dry soil allows for field mobility this type of aggregates too.

A correct assessment of transport needs in agriculture must take into consideration a series of requirements, factors and characteristics due to which these are considerably different from transport in other economical fields. On the other hand appropriate organization of agricultural transport is strongly influenced by the size of the agricultural enterprises, the structure of production, applied working technologies etc. In choosing transportation means dispersion of production in the field must also be considered, soil compression by the vehicle wheels, tractor and motor vehicle

working capacity with respect to road resistance, type adherence to the soil etc.

Neglecting some of the specified factors may disturb normal development of transport and implicitly lead missing optimum periods for different agricultural works.

2. Soil structure and sizes of agricultural enterprises

In 2009 [3] the agricultural surface of Romania was divided in to land use categories and pedological-climatical and relief zones, as shown in table 1.

Although the lands of zone III represent about 50% of those of zone I, total transport requirements of zone III formers are much lesser than of those of zone I. This is based on the fact that almost 50% of zone III are pastures, for which transport activities concern only small amounts of materials and products.

Farming (tillable) lands and meadows zone III are on shapes, or access to these implies sloping routes, which influences transport capacity of the employed means. In these cases smaller capacity trailers are indicated which can be attached to a larger range of tractors.

The types of agricultural sites, their number and the surface occupied by each type in 2009 are presented in table 2 [3].

It is obvious that at the level of peasant farms land is excessively fragmented. The selling and buying processes of farming land will soon increase the current average of 2.5 ha for a site;

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this will positive consequence on the results of agricultural work, transport included. On the other hand, currently site sizes of family associations, agricultural companies and

commercial agricultural companies allow for a far better organization of all activities connected to agricultural production.

Table 1

Agricultural land structure, th. ha

Crt. no.	Land use category	Surface/ area	Agricultural land structure on zones		
			I	II	III
1.	Tillable	9338.0	5818.1	2761.2	758.7
2.	Pastures	3578.4	721.3	1329.2	1527.9
3.	Meadows	1493.7	60.5	481.9	951.3
4.	Vineyards	298.4	172.1	117.7	8.6
5.	Orchards	289.0	67.7	134.3	85.0
6.	TOTAL	14997.5	6841.7	4824.3	3331.5

Table 2

Types of agricultural sites in Romania

Crt. no.	Type of site	Number of site	Total occupied area, ha	Average area of a site, ha
1.	Peasant farms	2 598 749	6 576 459	2.5
2.	Family associations	16 346	1 862 341	114.0
3.	Agricultural companies	4 052	1 812 835	447.0
4.	Commercial agricultural companies	1 171	1 918 389	1638.0
5.	Public domain agricultural sites	-	2 827 526	-

3. Work volume and seasonality of agricultural transports

Considering the data of table 1 and those of [3], the quantity of vegetal agricultural products and other materials which are the object of primary transports over a year are summarized in table 3. The fact has to be pointed out, that only most important groups of products and materials have been comprised in this table, so that the resulting total may be considered a minimum value.

Typically, the quantity of primary transported products is by 30...50% greater than computed in table 3.

If this quantity of products and materials were uniformly distributed over the entire year (as industrial transports are distributed) a monthly amount of about 6,210,000 tons would have to be transported.

The greatest transport demands (about 90.6%) are determined by corn cereals, fodder plants, industrial plants (sugar beet, tobacco, chicory), potatoes, vegetables, natural fertilizers and other materials.

On the other hand corn cereals (33%) fodder plants (22%) and natural fertilizers (20%) hold

each such a weight of the transport requirement, have strongly defined characteristics and are transported over sufficiently long periods of time (3...4 months), thus justifying the development and use of specialized means of transport.

Due to the seasonability of agricultural production, transport requirements vary very much for different periods of the year, as shown in Figure 1 [4].

It can be noted that the average yearly demand of agricultural transport represents only 31.8% of the maximum demand (in September). Further, the minimum monthly demand (in March) represents only 3.1% of that of September.

In order to transport the 19.5 million tons (this being a minimum value, its real level may be 50% greater), in September over 76,000 trailers should be available. (Average load capacity of a trailer is of 3.5t, a trailer completes about 3 runs daily, being considered optimum for transport for about 25 days).

Considering that between June and October tractors are intensely employed for other agricultural works too, the need involving other motor vehicles in agricultural transport becomes

obvious (lorries or with trailers, or lorries and semitrailers) [6].

4. Influence of cultures structure and working technologies

Establishing the plant species to be grown in an agricultural year on a given site is an extremely complex problem involving many factors to be considered. Besides the requirement of ensuring a certain sequence of cultures and of

considering the pedological-climatical needs of plants it is also useful to find appropriate solutions for products and materials transport [5].

Subsequently by analysing the technologies for the main plants grown in Romania it was established that the most significant transport requirements concern in all cases natural fertilizers, main and secondary production and other necessities (chemical fertilizers, seed water and pesticides etc.), which may even be occasional.

Fig. 1. Seasonability of agricultural production and transport requirements

Table 4 gives average amounts of products and materials to be transported for a hectare planted

with one of the analyzed species, even indicating the direction of transport (to or from the field).

By correlating the data in tables 3 and 4 even the national requirement of agricultural transport can be established.

It can be established that, in the case of correct application of technologies, the major weight of

transports to the field is held by organic fertilizers. But these fertilizers are applied only to a small extent, due both to their lack and the difficulties in distributing them in the field.

Table 3

Vegetal agricultural production, thousands of tons

Crt. no.	Plant species	Main production	Secondary production	Period of transport
1.	Cereals	18 183.8	10 000.0	15.06-15.10
2.	Vegetables for beans	76.1	25.0	01.07-30.09
3.	Textile plants	9.3	10.0	01.08-15.09
4.	Oil plants	874.1	1000.0	01.08-30.09
5.	Industrial plants	2763.8	500.0	01.09-20.10
6.	Medicinal and aromatic plants	6.3	25.0	15.05-30.07
7.	Potatoes	2 846.7	-	01.09-10.10
8.	Vegetables total	2 568.8	500.0	15.05-20.10
9.	Green and yellow melons	611.1	-	15.07-15.09
10.	Silo fodder	19 406.0	-	15.05-25.10
11.	Grapes	1 032.7	-	15.08-15.10
12.	Fruit	1 462.4	-	15.06-20.10
13.	Chemical fertilizers	479.0	-	01.09-15.04
14.	Natural fertilizers	16 945.0	-	15.08-15.03
15.	Other materials	3 000.0	-	01.01-31.12
16.	TOTAL	70 245.1	-	-

Table 4

Amounts to be transported, according to technology, to/ ha.

Crt. no.	Culture	To the field		From the field		General total		Total without natural fertilizers	
		Natural fertilizers	Other materials	Main products	Secondary products	To the field	From the field	To the field	From the field
1.	Barley	30	1.25	3	2	31.25	5.05	1.25	5.05
2.	Wheat	30	1.25	3	2.1	31.25	5.15	1.25	5.15
3.	Sunflower	30	0.95	2.5	1.5	31.95	4.05	0.95	4.05
4.	Maize	45	1.35	10	3	46.35	13.05	1.35	13.05
5.	Sugar beet	40	1.15	30	10	41.15	40.05	1.15	40.05
6.	Potatoes	40	3.65	25	-	43.65	25.05	3.65	25.05
7.	Soya	20	0.75	1.5	-	20.75	1.55	0.75	1.55
8.	Vegetables-fields	60	1.85	40	5	61.85	45.05	1.85	45.05
9.	Fruits	40	5.05	20	7	45.05	27.05	5.05	27.05
10.	Grapes	30	5.55	15	5	35.55	20.05	5.55	20.05
11.	Plants used for silage	25	0.95	50	-	25.95	50.05	0.95	25.95
12.	Hay	10	-	8	-	10.05	8.05	0.05	10.05

Sugar beets, potatoes, vegetables, chopped fodder, grapes and fruit excepted, for which transport to and from the field are equal, for the other cultures transport to the field is 4..6 times

greater than from it. By excluding natural fertilizers, in all cases transports from the field of the main and secondary production are much larger than those to the field. It can be noted that it would be

necessary to diversify the offer of transport means, in order to minimize expenses under this heading.

5. Influence of production dispersion

The agricultural products have to be collected from a large area and transported to a destination within or outside the site at distances ranging between 1 and 20 km.

Table 5 presents some considerations with regard to this aspect, based on type and average size of agricultural sites.

Assuming the ideal situation, when the whole site surface forms a single square unit, table 5 gives the distances to be covered by transport means in the field, in order to collect the products.

Table 5

Distances to be covered by transport means in the field

Crt. no.	Type of site	Average area	Ideal dimensions	Transport on field	Transport to farm	Average number of cultures
1.	Peasant farms	2.5	0.16x0.16	2...3	1...2	6...7
2.	Family associations	114	1.05x1.05	80...100	3...4	5...6
3.	Agricultural companies	447	2.12x2.12	300...400	7...8	4...5
4.	Agricultural commercial companies	1638	4.05x4.05	1200...1500	10...12	4...5
5.	Public agricultural sites	-	-	-	-	-

It can be noted, that for commercial agricultural companies these distances can exceed 1 000 km, and considering that some cultures are cropped in several stages, these distances multiply correspondingly.

Field mobility of transport means generates too specific problems for the manufacturer:

- agricultural transport vehicles must be able to move in the fields (reduced load, sometimes attentive protection of plants);
- small distances make loading - unloading times at least as important as running speed is less important than for long distances.

6. Conclusions

Knowing as accurately as possible characteristics of agricultural transports, the quantity of products and materials to be transported at any time /moment of the year allows for work organization able to avoid disturbances in this particular sector of economy, subjected anyway to numerous risk factors (storms, low temperatures etc.).

Thus agricultural or motor vehicle type means of transport will be employed, ensuring in due time the required amounts of

field and lubricants, as well as human resources able solve this problem.

Further elements are highlighted essential for design and manufacturing, concerning working capacity, road resistance, tire adherence to soil, correct forming of transport aggregates by correlation of traction forces etc.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE OPTIMIZATION OF THE ROMANIAN FARM SIZES

Gh. BRATUCU* I. CAPATINA*

Abstract: *The paper opens with a presentation of the current structure of tillable ground in Romania, highlighting the current average area of a private farm, i.e., 2.28 ha. Taking into consideration this quite serious situation, the author examines two ways of establishing optimum dimensions for farms, firstly from the viewpoint of the possibilities of achieving effective rotations of crops, and secondly from that of profit capitalization. The analyses are carried out for farms producing cereal and technical plant crops.*

Keywords: *agricultural structures, farms, agricultural profit rate.*

1. Introduction

The design of rational farm sizes has to start from the concrete regional and local circumstances in Romanian agriculture, considering also the experience of other countries and the current requirements regarding organizing, management, production, productivity and efficiency in agriculture.

The *magnitude of the farm* describes its production capacity, determined by the volume of production resources and by their degree of use, and represents the qualitative aspect of farm economic activity and the level of production intensity.

The *farm size* refers to its quantitative aspect that has to allow for a rotation of crops and combination of branches, has to allow for the implementation in production of current technology, of mechanization [2].

The significantly share of farms smaller than 3 ha can be easily noticed representing 73% from the total of individual farms. The share of farms larger than 3 ha chemical treatment, irrigation etc. can be made in economical conditions. The farm size has to create the framework for a normal unfolding of all factors related to agricultural activity. Thus, in regard to mechanization of agricultural works, farm size has to allow for employing tractors and high technology and capacity implements. Also, rational alternation of crops is not possible on small areas [1].

Consequently to the enforcement of the Law of Land Reclamation, land ownership in Romania has the structure indicated in table 1.

The dynamic of private farm structure highlights mainly a dispersion of dimension (size), of both propriety and farm. Table 2 presents the current situation of the main types of private farms in Romania.

Table 3 presents the situation of individual farms in Romania, grouped into categories of size (dimensional aspect), ha (27%) consists of 16% farms of 3.0...5.0 ha, 7.15% farms of 5.0...7.0 ha, 3.5% farms of 7.0...10.0 ha and only 0.26% farms larger than 10 ha.

2. Optimum farm sizes from the crop alternation viewpoint

A rational crop alternation for field plants in plain regions is organized into at least 4 groups of cultures, each on a surface varying from 10 to 100 ha.

Achieving optimum size farms, adequate crop alternations and rotations holds multiple advantages. It is known for example, that after a crop of perennial vegetables the soil keeps approximately 80 kg nitrogen to the hectare, thus yielding 675,000...900,000 kg ammonium nitrates for a surface of 1.5...2.0 million ha. Production of these fertilizers requires about 300 million m³ of methane gas, and the energy corresponds to about 0.1...0.15 million tons of petrol [3].

Following implementation of a crop-in-rotation (perennial vegetables), the total corn production on 1,000 ha podsol soil will be about 30% greater than in the case of a mono-culture.

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Research has shown that the most efficient crop rotations have the duration of over 3 years, what requires a farm size able to ensure such a rotation. The production gain for 1 kg fertilizer in 3 to 5 year crop rotations is 3 to 4 times greater than for monocultures or for the alternation of maximum 2 cultures, typical for small size farms.

Table 1

Specification	Agricultural surface [thousand ha]	%	Tillable surface [thousand ha]	%
Total country	14.793	100	9.341	100
- Public and private state owned sector:	4.457	30	1.876	20
- Private sector, of which:	10.336	70	7.480	80
- individual farms	6.673	65	4.165	55
- family associations	1.782	17	1.585	21
- agricultural and commercial companies	1.881	18	1.795	24

Table 2

Specification	Number	Average size [ha]
Individual farms	3,557,270	2.28
Family associations	15,150	116
Agricultural and commercial companies	4,009	447
Commercial companies	372	235

Table 3

Specification	No. of Indiv. Farms [th]	Aver. Surf. [ha]	Number of individual farms [th], categories of size [ha]						
			<0.5	0.5-1.0	1.0-3.0	3.0-5.0	5.0-7.0	7.0-10	>10
No. of Indiv. farms	3.557	2.28	234	1083	1280	570	254	125	9
Weigh [%]	100%	-	6.59	30.46	35.98	16.03	7.15	3.53	0.26

Table 4

Production profile	Pedo-climate zone	Optimum dimensions
Cereals and technical plants	- plain - hills	500...1000 100...300
Vegetable cultures	- adequate for intensive vegetable growing	30...50
Fruit tree breeding	- adequate for intensive fruit breeding	50...100
Winegrowing	- adequate for intensive winegrowing	50...100

Based on these considerations it can be estimated, that from the point of view of crop rotations related to culture structures and pedo-climate zones, the optimum dimensions for agricultural farms in the vegetal sector are those of table 4 [5].

Table 5 shows the optimum dimensions for zootechnical individual agricultural plantations by animal species, breeding systems, in heads/ farm.

Taking these aspects into consideration, optimum dimension design of individual farms is not only important, but also imperative.

The current sizes of peasant farms (in average about 2.28 ha), but also those of family associations (average 118 ha) and agricultural companies (average 447 ha) are far from those

estimated as corresponding to the requirements of an efficient agriculture.

Table 5

Production sector	Breeding system	Optimum dimensions
Milk cows	- regular farming	5...10
	- intensive	100...200
Meat pigs	- regular farming	100...200
	- intensive	1,500...2,000

Table 6

Agricultural zone	Capitalization possibilities in various farms						
	10ha	60 ha	80 ha	120ha	300 ha	500 ha	1000 ha
Irrigated plain	1760	10552	14069	21104	52759	87932	175864
Non-irrigated plain	1093	6557	8743	13115	32788	54646	109292
Non-irrigated hill	929	5575	7433	11150	27875	46458	92916

Table 7

Type of 80 ha farm	Capitalization possibilities of net profit [thousand lei]					
	36.65		24.9%		16.6%	
	Per farm	Per ha	Per farm	Per ha	Per farm	Per ha
Irrigated plain	14069	176	9840	123	6560	82
Non-irrigated plain	8743	109	6115	76	4077	51
Non-irrigated hill	7433	93	5199	65	3466	43
EU	27056	338	18924	236	12616	158

Table 8

Farm dimension	Production value [th. Lei]		Expenses [th. Lei]		Profit [th. Lei]	
	Total	Per ha	Total	Per ha	Total	Per ha
50	29500	590	23500	470	6000	120
100	65000	650	46500	465	18500	185
500	330000	660	220000	440	110000	220
1000	700000	700	425000	425	275000	275
1500	997000	666	650000	433	347500	231
2000	1300000	650	875000	437	425000	212.5

3. Optimum dimension design of private farms considering capitalization possibilities

The only alternative to high interest bank loans available to farmers consists in capitalization by high rates. As the joining process of Romanian farms will have to take the same course as in EU countries, it is helpful to consider the capitalization rates characteristic to various stages of this process in these countries. Thus for 1959-

1971 the capitalization rate was 35.6% of the net income (I. stage), for 1971-1980 of 24.9% (II. stage) and for 1981-1990 of 16.6% (III. stage) [6].

Considering the budget of income and expenditure devised for one complex hectare destined for vegetal culture (the cultures taken into account were: wheat, barley, corn, sunflower, soybeans, beans, sugar beet and autumn potatoes) it follows, that the net income is of 39,520 lei/ha in the irrigated plain agricultural zone, of 24,560 lei/ha in the non-irrigated plain agricultural zone

and of 20,880 lei/ha in the non-irrigated hill agricultural zone [4].

Table 6 presents the capitalization possibilities of profit (net income) in Romanian private farms of various dimensions, similarly to the first stage of capitalizations in EU countries (35.6%). The adopted dimensions are the reference ones employed in the computations published by the competent EU structures.

It can be noticed, that for the 10 ha farm the accumulated capital is of 1.760 million lei/year in the irrigated plain agricultural zone, of 1.093 million lei/year in the non irrigated plain agricultural zone and of 0.9292 million lei/year in the non-irrigated hill agricultural zone.

At the same time, for the 60 ha farm the accumulated capital is of 10.552 million lei/year in the irrigated plain agricultural zone, of 6.557 million lei/year in the non-irrigated plain agricultural zone and of 5.575 million lei/year in the non-irrigated hill agricultural zone etc.

The first investment possibilities of the accumulated capital occur in the over 80 ha farms, that have the possibility of purchasing in one year a tractor, a plough and a disk-harrow.

On the other hand, a comparison of the capitalization values for an 80 ha farm in Romania with an EU one, considering the three agricultural zones and capitalization rates, yields the results given in table 7 [7].

It can be noticed, that since the net annual income of Romanian 80 ha farms is 2...4 times smaller than that of a similar EU farm, capitalization possibilities will also be accordingly slimmer. Practically, in Romania at the current level of income, only farms larger

than 300 ha can look at reasonable capitalization possibilities.

4. Conclusions

1. With regard to the rotation of crops, farms need to be of sizes larger than 100 ha (for cereal and technical plant crops).

2. With regard to capitalization possibilities, the sizes of farms have to exceed 300 ha.

3. Joining of farms in order to achieve adequate sizes is a process requiring a long period of time, during that Romanian agriculture will yield particularly weak results.

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INFLUENCE OF THE HARVESTING MACHINE TYPE OVER POTATO TUBERS MECHANICAL INJURIES

I. CAPATINA* Gh. BRATUCU**

Abstract: This paper presents the results of experimental research regarding the potatoes tubers mechanical injury after harvesting. The research was conducted in autumn 2011 on a plot planted with potatoes in Cernat from Covasna county. At the harvesting work was used three different types of potatoes harvesting machine manufactured in Germany. The probes consisted in about 100 tubers from each machine bunker, which were calibrated according to the norms, and then they were sorted in order to identify the mechanical injuries. The potatoes were from Riviera variety. After harvests there were about 10...14 % injured tubers. In the paper are made clarifications regarding the causes of these injuries.

Keywords: potato, mechanical injury, harvesting.

1. Introduction

The potato is a staple food, both in Romania and at global scale. Its content of nutrients and vitamins recommend it for use in various food recipes, available for consumers of all ages. Higher productions on hectare and climatic conditions of specific areas in Romania have made the potato a principal product for the existence of a large number of farmers. At the same time the potato proved to be a vegetable product particularly sensitive to fluctuations of temperature and humidity, soil physical and chemical characteristics and especially to a lot of diseases and pests.

In the twentieth century, the area cultivated with potatoes increased continuously. Annual potato production in developed countries increased from 30 million tons in the early 60s to 85 million tons in recent years. According to a FAO study entitled "Potatoes in the 1990s", potato production in developing countries which recorded a 3,6 % annual rate is expected to increase by more than 5 % per year, especially in Asia, Africa and Latin America.

The technologies and equipment used in potato production and primary processing follow the idea of ensuring a quality product under ecological aspect and with total low costs. It turns out however, that most of the existing potatoes on the market contain harmful elements, are sick and degraded from the use of inappropriate

technologies and equipment for their production, conditioning or for their processing.

2. Material and method

In this paper are presented the results of experimental researches conducted to determine the influence of the potato harvesting machine type over the quality of the tubers. For this was used three types of potatoes harvesting machines produced in Germany by the Grimme company: the self propelled harvester on two rows Grimme SE 170-60, the semi-carried harvester on two rows Grimme SE 150-60 and the semi-carried harvester on single row Grimme SE 75-40.

Figure 1. Manual potato calibration device

The measurements consisted in studying three buckets (about 100 tubers) of potatoes from the

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each harvesting machine bunker. The studied potatoes were from the same variety (Riviera) and on the same plot (similar soil characteristics). To determine the tubers injury degree, the potatoes, were first split in size classes accordingly with STAS (25, 28, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, > 70 mm) using a manual calibration device (Figure 1). For each size class the tubers were checked and divided into three categories: good, superficial injured and injured in depth.

From the analysis of the potatoes characteristics obtained and processed by different technologies and existing equipment can

be detached proposals for selecting the best of them, at which it can be analyzed the points where improvements may be made, leading to elimination of the causes of physical degradation of the potato.

3. Results and discussions

The results of the experimental researches made on each potatoes harvesting equipment were written in tables (table 1,2 and 3) to emphasize the percents of injured tubers on each equipment type.

Table 1.

Tubers situation harvested with Grimme SE 170-60

Nr. crt.	Dimension class, mm		Tubers status			Total number of potatoes on dimension classes, pieces	Share, %
			good,	Superficial injured	injured in depth		
1.	Under STAS	25	0	0	0	0	0
2.		28	0	0	0	0	0
3.	For seeds	35	0	0	0	0	0
4.		40	3	1	0	4	3,22
5.		45	8	1	1	10	8,07
6.		50	10	1	0	11	8,87
7.	For consumption	55	15	0	1	16	12,90
8.		60	18	0	0	18	14,52
9.		65	22	2	1	25	20,16
10.		70	19	3	0	22	17,74
11.		> 70	13	5	0	18	14,52
Total number of potatoes, pieces			108	13	3	124	
Share, %			87,10	10,48	2,42		

Table 2.

Tubers situation harvested with Grimme SE 150-60

Nr. crt.	Dimension class, mm		Tubers status			Total number of potatoes on dimension classes, pieces	Share, %
			good,	Superficial injured	injured in depth		
1.	Under STAS	25	0	0	0	0	0
2.		28	0	0	0	0	0
3.	For seeds	35	0	0	0	0	0
4.		40	1	0	0	1	0,85
5.		45	3	0	0	3	2,56
6.		50	13	1	1	15	12,82
7.	For consumption	55	7	1	0	8	6,84
8.		60	15	2	0	17	14,53
9.		65	16	1	0	17	14,53
10.		70	25	3	1	29	24,79
11.		> 70	21	5	1	27	23,08
Total number of potatoes, pieces			101	13	3	117	
Share, %			86,33	11,11	2,56		

Table 3.

Tubers situation harvested with Grimme SE 75-40

Nr. crt.	Dimension class, mm		Tubers status			Total number of potatoes on dimension classes, pieces	Share, %
			good,	Superficial injured	injured in depth		
1.	Under STAS	25	0	0	0	0	0
2.		28	0	0	0	0	0
3.	For seeds	35	0	0	0	0	0
4.		40	0	0	0	0	0
5.		45	0	0	0	0	0
6.		50	5	2	0	7	6,2
7.	For consumption	55	11	0	0	11	9,74
8.		60	18	2	0	20	17,70
9.		65	28	1	0	29	25,67
10.		70	24	4	0	28	24,77
11.		> 70	15	3	0	18	15,92
Total number of potatoes, pieces			101	12	0	113	
Share, %			89,38	10,61	0		

For a better comparison of the obtained results it was made a graphic (figure 2) in which are expressed the values of the superficial, in depth and total injuries, in percents for each type of potatoes harvesting machine used in the research.

From the graphic we can see that at the harvesting equipment SE 75-40 there are no tubers injured in depth. At all three equipments, before the tubers reach the storage bunker, the tubers are placed to a sorting band, usually served by four persons. Although each equipment had

four persons for the sorting operation, the potatoes flow at the SE 75-40 harvesting equipment is smaller because it harvests on a single row against the other two equipments which harvests on two rows.

Also it can be seen that the percent of superficial injured tubers is almost identical for each one of those tree potatoes harvesting equipments which means that the difference of total injured tubers is given by the number of tubers injured in depth.

Figure 2. Variation of the tubers injury degree depending on the harvesting equipment type

From the observations made in the working time of this equipments has been established that the most of the in depth injured tubers is due to the inaccurate adjustment of the working depth of the cutters, trough the working process of the equipment having place only superficial injuries.

4. Conclusions

- Total percentage of injured tubers that reach the potatoes harvesting equipment bunker is different for each equipment type according to the percent of in depth injured tubers.
- The percent of in depth injured tubers depends mostly by the skills and attention of the sorting band operators.
- The potatoes harvesting machine with a lower working capacity can have a better tubers injuries percentage from the bigger and more efficient equipments. The formulae and tables are written by means of a specialized graphics editors.

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Microbiological quality aspects of the composting process of sludge result from municipal wastewater treatment plant

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Abstract: *Considering that the use of sludge in agriculture must be considered estimates sludge quality and microbiological quality parameters evolution during its composting process, the objective of this study was to obtain health biosolids harmless sludge cost through efficient technology aerobic digestion and assess potential threats to soil contamination with pathogens concentrated in sewage sludge, in order to avoid possible consequences that might have on state land and staff sanogenetic manipulator. Can be avoided difficulties clear justification about the impossibility of using sludge as fertilizer, based on technical issues - noncompliance chemical and microbiological quality. In this way, motivating the choice of storage as the back end can not be accepted by the absence of a clear will from the experts in agriculture to take over the sludge.*

Keywords: *fermented sludge, aerobic composting, pathogens*

1. Introduction

Activated sludge arising from urban wastewater treatment plants can be processed to obtain an organic compost produced can be used as fertilizer in cultivation of flower species. Pathogenic organisms may be present in products submissive to composting, making compost itself can contain pathogens and constitute a health risk. To avoid this problem, activated sludge must be free of pathogens that are a major risk factor for humans. Directive 86/278/EEC [5] and MEWM Order 708/2004 [6], limit the application of treated organic sludge to the land through the control of heavy metals and priority hazardous substances, without taking into account the load of pathogenic bacteria. Currently, the Romanian legislation does not standardize content limits bacterial compost which can be used in agriculture, but is considered only total microbial load (Probable Maximum number of germs / g). Sludge to be used as fertilizer must be stabilized by an anaerobic fermentation process followed by thermal stabilization in order to comply with conditions imposed by STAS 4076/88. In

Romania, the issue of sewage sludge is regulated by Order no. 344 of August 16, 2004. These include the approval of the technical environment, particularly soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture. (A) Several studies (Tremier, A., 2005, Suthar, S., et al., 2008, Lillenberg, M., et al., 2010) have provided evidence that the existing range of organic waste, sewage sludge composting capable of producing a quality product that can be used as fertilizer and soil amendment because of its organic matter content can vary from 50% to 70% of the total solids (Banegas, V., et al 2007, Lillenberg, M. , et al., 2010). Compost is a biologically active material, the bulk of organic origin which can vary in texture. Lately the U.S. has increased interest in using compost" value added" or the compost amended with fertilizers with microorganisms that suppress disease and other products that stimulate plant growth. Council of Canada uses compost as a soil amendment and a valuable chance for recovery of all organic waste.

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2. Materials and methods

Anaerobic digestion experiments followed pathogen reduction efficiencies at temperatures of 39° and 36 ° C and retention time of 15-16 days, compared with control - temperature 32 ° C, TRH = 12 days. Anaerobic digestion bioreactor used in these experiments is a bioreactor "Biostat A Plus", with automatic pH, temperature, homogenization and the possibility of destruction of the foam. All these parameters are set and controlled automatically by a computer.

Fig.1. bioreactor ,, Biostat A Plus,,

Working parameters of bioreactor were: pH = 7 ± 0.05; stirring = 150 rpm. Testing period was 16 days at 39° C, 15 days at 36 ° C and 12 days at 32 ° C.

Mixed biomass sample consists of fermented sludge from WWTP Pitesti was analyzed microbiologically standardized indicators STAS 4706/88 total coliform and faecal coliform bacteria, which are mesophilic microorganisms that grow at 35°C.

Determination number of total coliform bacteria / cm³ and number of faecal coliform bacteria / cm³ according to STAS 3001/91 and accepted quality STAS's 4076/88 for use in agriculture. In carrying out residual sludge compost was used (mixture of primary sludge with biological sludge) anaerobic fermented and dried (combine the aerobic treatment with anaerobic in order to obtain efficient processes and an increase of cleaning).

Compost (obtain at the Experimental Research Station Albota) was examined microbiologically

(Laboratory of Microbiology at the University of Craiova) aiming at the level of contamination on microbiological indicators: total coliform (TC), faecal coliform (FC), total streptococcus (ST), fecal streptococcus (FS), presence or absence of agents enteric pathogens: Shigella spp, Salmonella spp, Staphylococcus aureus and Candida albicans fungi. Bacteriological analysis subsist in the current analytical methods for determining the level of bacteriological pollution and to establish potential risk for human and animal health community.

The methodology used was designed to determine: Probably Number of CT (total coliforms), MPN/g; Probably number of thermotolerant coliform CF (faecal coliform) MPN/g; ST bacteria Number of urge probably (total streptococci) MPN/g; Probably number of SF bacteria (faecal streptococci) MPN /g. Complementary methods of analysis were used to establish pollution levels bacteriological compost, with reference to identification of the pathogenic bacteria of the genus Salmonella/25g presence, the presence of bacteria of the genus Shigella/25g; presence of bacteria of the genus Staphylococcus aureus/25g; presence of bacteria the family Enterobacteriaceae(genera objected to the composition of coliform germs)/25g. Fecal coliforms were analyzed using MacConkey agar and Salmonella sp. and Shigella sp. agar were analyzed using Salmonella / Shigella agar ®.

All plates were incubated for 48 hours at 37°C (Fig. 2).

3. Results and discussion

Microbiological test results are presented in Tables no.1, 2, 3 and illusted in graphs number 2, 3, 4.

Table no.1
Quantitative estimation of aerobic mesophilic heterotrophic bacteria, total coliform, faecal coliform and faecal streptococci in fermented sludge samples (for 16 days at 39⁰ C) / gdw

Sample	Moisture g%	Aerobic mesophilic bacteria CFU/gdw	Total coliform CFU/gdw	Faecal coliform CFU/gdw	Faecal streptococcus CFU/gdw
NP	1.83	5.3×10^7	8.4×10^4	7.8×10^4	6.9×10^5
NF ₄	2.06	4.2×10^7	4.7×10^3	2.0×10^3	5.1×10^4
NF ₈	2.33	1.4×10^7	5.2×10^3	1.2×10^3	1.7×10^3
NF ₁₂	2.17	7.9×10^6	1.9×10^3	1.4×10^3	1.2×10^2
NF ₁₆	2.14	3.1×10^6	2.3×10^3	0	3.6×10

Fig. 3 Estimation of faecal pollution indicators

Table no. 2
Quantitative estimate of mesophilic aerobic heterotrophic bacteria, total coliform, faecal coliform and faecal streptococcus in samples of primary sludge and sludge fermented (15 days to 36⁰ C) / gdw

Sample	Moisture g%	Aerobic mesophilic bacteria CFU/gdw	Total coliform CFU/gdw	Faecal coliform CFU/gdw	Faecal streptococci CFU/gdw
NP	2.38	1.3×10^7	1.1×10^5	1.0×10^4	4.6×10^4
NF ₆	2.22	1.1×10^8	5.3×10^3	1.6×10^4	1.2×10^4
NF ₉	3.19	2.8×10^7	4.9×10^3	6.4×10	6.8×10^2
NF ₁₃	2.41	1.6×10^7	3.2×10^3	1.3×10	1.9×10^2
NF ₁₅	2.70	2.4×10^6	1.7×10^3	0	4.5×10

Fig. 4 Estimation of faecal pollution indicators

Tabel nr.3

Quantitative estimation of aerobic mesophilic heterotrophic bacteria, total coliform, faecal coliform and faecal streptococcus in samples of primary sludge and sludge fermented (12 days to 32⁰ C) / gdw

Sample	Moisture g%	Aerobic mesophilic bacteria CFU/gdw	Total coliform CFU/gdw.	Faecal coliform CFU/gdw	Faecal streptococci CFU/gdw
NP	2.17	1.5 x 10 ⁷	3.0 x 10 ⁴	3.5 x 10 ⁴	2.7 x 10 ³
NF ₄	2.40	2.9 x 10 ⁷	3.0 x 10 ⁴	2.1 x 10 ³	5.2 x 10 ²
NF ₇	1.28	5.9 x 10 ⁶	3.0 x 10 ³	1.8 x 10 ³	2.7 x 10 ³
NF ₁₂	3.86	5.1 x 10 ⁵	2.3 x 10 ³	1.3 x 10	3.4 x 10

Fig. 5 Estimation of faecal pollution indicators

The analysis results can be appreciated as anaerobic digestion performed at a temperature of 36 ° C has the best efficiency in reducing faecal coliform, EPA standardized indicators of pathogenicity. Faecal coliform disappear after 13 days of digestion. In the fermentation experiment conducted at 39 ° C, faecal coliform are destroyed after 16 days of experiment. In the blank experiment, conducted at 32 ° C for 12 days at the end of retention period, total coliform residual titer was 1.3 x 10³ CFU/USG. In Fig. 6 can be observed several aspects of microbial colonies grown on culture media.

Fig. 6 Skin culture media plates used to determine faecal coliform

It is found that the sludge used in preparing compost biosolids belongs to class A (according

to U.S. EPA 503) as it meets the following requirement: the density of faecal coliform in the composted sludge must be less than 1,000 MPN per gram of total solids. According to U.S. EPA 503 regulation requires a minimum temperature of 55 ° C for a period of 23 hours to produce so-called biosolide Class A, Class A biosolidele valuable as a fertilizer without restrictions on the use of agricultural [2]. Following the determinations made, it is found that the initial compost pathogens were present in a proportion of 11x10³ (Table 4) compared to their presence in the final composted material which reached the value 2x10².

As the Romanian legislation does not standardize content limits bacterial compost which can be used in agriculture, but is considered only total microbial load (Probable Maximum Number of germs/g), microbiological determinations carried out on compost, by tracking the level of contamination with total coliform (CT), faecal coliform (FC), total streptococci (TS), faecal streptococci (FS), presence or absence of agents enteric pathogens: Shigella spp, Salmonella spp recommendation their use as indicators for estimating the quality of compost as possible biofertilizers. Analyzing the microbial load on the types of bacteria in compost can be observed the following: faecal coliform (FC) MPN / g were identified at levels <20, Escherichia coli, MPN/g was identified as values < 20.

Table no. 4
Microbiological indicators in sample stabilized compost, MPN/g

Experimental version	Total coliform / dm ³	Faecal coliform / dm ³	<i>Escherichia coli</i> / dm ³	Total streptococci / dm ³	Faecal streptococci / dm ³	Total number of aerobic bacteria (CFU) / cm ³	Notes
Final compost	11x10 ³	< 20	< 20	< 20	< 20	4 x10 ²	Salmonella, Shigella, stafilococcus, yeasts and molds = absent
Initial compost	2 x 10 ²	<20	<20	absent	<20	2 x10	absent

4. Conclusions

In a study on fermented sludge and compost the following conclusions:

- The process of composting, although sterilizing effect of all potentially pathogenic bacteria, may still be considered as one of the most effective methods for decontamination of waste products for soil fertilization.
- Thermal reactions with biological processes occurring in anaerobic sludge fermented during processing by composting lead to a reduction or discontinuation of total mesophilic aerobic bacteria (from 5.3×10^7 at 3.1×10^6 after 16 days at 39°C ; 1.3×10^7 to 2.4×10^6 after 15 days at 36°C , from 1.5×10^7 to 5.1×10^5 after 12 days at 32°C) and the destruction in a short time probably the number of coliform bacteria (12 days and 13 days at 39°C to 36°C).
- Based on the results we can say that application of compost derived from sewage sludge can be recommended in the horticultural, without risk to soil condition and proper behavior of man.

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RESEARCH CONCERNING THE POSSIBILITY TO REDUCE FUEL AND LUBRICANTS CONSUMPTION AT FELLING OF SPRUCE WITH MECHANICAL CHAINSAW HUSQVARNA

A. CIUBOTARU* GH. D. MARIA**

Abstract: *The paper presents results of research conducted by authors on the definition of areas of use of mechanical saws Husqvarna 242 and 365, to the spruce felling where fuel and lubricant consumption is minimal. This analysis took into account the need to reduce pollution at felling trees in forest ecosystems with mechanical chain saws, knowing about these machines, the consumption of fuels and lubricants, can greatly damage, especially soil and water quality of surface or underground*

This research showed that between the consumption of fuels and lubricants and diameter breast height of trees are highly significant correlations which allowed the definition of areas with minimal consumption of fuel and oil, therefore with minimal pollution, for each mechanical chainsaw analyzed.

Keywords: *forest ecosystem; pollution; mechanical chainsaw; felled trees*

1. Introduction

Mechanical chainsaws are the basic equipments, which is done cutting wood in forest exploitation, equipped with engines with two stroke and internal combustion. Locations where this equipment it is used are the forest cutting area and the landing area.

Given that mechanical saws are equipments polluting for forest ecosystems should be established for each chainsaw working condition who is with minimal consumption of fuels and lubricants, therefore who is the chainsaw who produced minimal pollution.

Pollution of forest ecosystem with these machines is result of burning fuel (gasoline) and the consumption of lubricants (oil and lubricating mixture). It should be noted that the lubricants, used for fuel mixture and lubrication of the cutting device, are ejected into forest.

Consumption of fuels and lubricants to mechanical chainsaws for cutting wood in logging activity in a year in our country, estimated based on general consumer norms, have the following values: 10 million liters petrol, 4,5 million liters of lubricating oil and 0,2 million liters of oil for mixture with gasoline.

In these conditions our research sought to identify the recommended areas for felling of spruce trees (*Picea abies*), with mechanical chainsaws Husqvarna 242 and Husqvarna 365, so

that consumption of fuels and lubricants to be minimal.

2. Characteristics of the researched area

The research was located in three cutting area in the mountain area from Vâlsan valley, at altitudes between 1,150 and 1,600 m, on slopes with an average declination of 30 degrees. In this cutting area was applied clear cutting and thinning. Trees stand composition, in all cases, was 10.Mo.(spruce). Characteristics of cutting area and wood marks are given in table 1.

Table 1

Characteristics	Cut area:		
	1	2	3
Type of cutting	Thinning	Clear cutting	Thinning
Cutting area, ha	7,3	3,5	11,5
Number of trees	700	917	790
Mean diameter breast height, cm	25	40	30
Mean height of trees, m	23	27	22,5
Volume of mean tree, m ³	0,47	1,21	0,72
Total volume, m ³	329	1.114	567

3. Methodology

For determination of fuel and lubricants consumption at felling of spruce was used a mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 365, 65.1 cm³ cylinder capacity, power of 3.4 kW and a usable length of 42 cm blade and a mechanical saw Husqvarna 242, cylinder capacity of 38.2 cm³ of 1.5 kW power output of the blade length of 30 cm.

Was measured the amount of gasoline and lubricating oil consumption for felling each tree included in the test group. Measurement was made using a graduated cylinder with 1 ml accuracy.

Each felled tree was measured the diameter breast height, the stump diameter, the height, the depth and the angle of notch and the width of hinge. For these measurements were used: caliper, roulette and rapporteur.

Diameters at breast height has been classified as category from 2 to 2 cm, and stumps diameters was calculated as the average of two perpendicular diameters and reported like integer values.

Characteristics of felling and notch are shown in figures 1 and 2.

Cutting area surface, to extract notch, was measured by their assimilation with a circular segment. To calculate areas was used equation (Bobancu et al., 1974):

$$A = \frac{d_c^2}{4} \left(\frac{\pi \cdot \varphi}{180} - \frac{\sin \varphi}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Meaning of terms is shown in figure 3.

Hinge surface area was equated with that of a rectangle and back cut area was calculated as the difference between the area of stump and summed areas of the notch (S1 and S4 in fig. 2) and the back cut area.

Consumption of fuels and lubricants were analyzed by expressing them in the unitary consumption form, in ml/m³ (Ciubotaru, 1990).

4. Results

The research conducted was intended, in a first step, analysis of correlations between the stump diameter, the cutting area of felling and diameter at breast height. As shown in the graphs in figures 4 and 5 are highly significant correlations expressed by coefficient of determination (R² having higher values that 0,86).

Fig. 1. The felling characteristics: 1– notch; 2– hinge; 3– back cut.

Fig. 2. Types of notch and the surfaces cut: a- Humboldt notch; 2- block notch, S1,...4- the surface cut; - angle of notch.

Fig. 3. Characteristics of the stump for calculation of cutting area: dc - diameter of stump; a_t - notch deep; \square - hinge width; φ -

The values of coefficient of determination justify analysis of fuel and lubricant consumption in correlation with diameter breast height of trees.

By using Husqvarna 365 mechanical chainsaw, the correlation between the consumption of gasoline and lubricating oil are significant (fig. 6 and fig. 7), with coefficients of determination values 0.87 and 0.89 respectively. For Husqvarna 242 mechanical chainsaw values of coefficients of determination are 0.88 and 0.86 respectively.

To establish favorable working condition, respectively low pollution, for felling trees spruce, with these two types of machines, in the graphs from figures 10 and 11 was represented correlation between trees diameter at breast height and the difference of fuel consumption and difference of oil consumption. The difference was calculated by subtract the consumption realized by chainsaw Husqvarna 242 and consumption realized by chainsaw Husqvarna 365. Positive values indicate a range of differences of consumption, respectively diameters at breast height favorable for using mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 242, and negative values indicate a range of differences of consumption, respectively diameters at breast height favorable for using mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 365.

Fig. 4. Correlation between stump diameter and diameter breast height

Fig. 5. Correlation between the surface cut and diameter breast height

Fig. 6. Correlation between diameter at breast height and the gasoline consumptions of mechanical saws Husqvarna 365

Fig. 9. Oil consumption at the felling of trees with Husqvarna 242

Fig. 7. Correlation between diameter at breast height and the oil consumptions of mechanical saws Husqvarna 365

Fig. 10. Correlation between diameter at breast height and the difference of fuel consumptions with mechanical saws Husqvarna 365 and Husqvarna 242

Fig. 8. Gasoline consumption at the felling of trees with Husqvarna 242

Fig. 11. Correlation between diameter at breast height and the difference of oil consumptions with mechanical saws Husqvarna 365 and Husqvarna 242

5. Conclusions

The research shows that for spruce stand between diameter at breast height and stump diameter is a highly significant correlation. This conclusion justifies analysis of the consumption of fuels and lubricants in conjunction with diameter at breast height of marked trees.

Correlations between diameter at breast height and the consumption of fuels and lubricants felling expressed graphically using the second degree polynomial regression. For each case values of diameter at breast height, for minimal value of consumption of fuel and oil, are 20 ... 40 cm for mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 242 and 40 ... 80 cm for mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 365.

For definition of diameters areas where fuel consumption and oil consumption are minimal was analyzed the differences in consumption made by the two types of mechanical chainsaw for which measurements were made. Analysis showed that these differences can be expressed by a linear regression. This show that recommended used area for mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 242 is for tees with diameters at breast height less than 45 cm. and for mechanical chainsaw Husqvarna 365 for diameters at breast height larger than 45 cm.

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EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH REGARDING THE RESISTANCE FORCE OF VEGETABLE PRODUCTS IN THE CUTTING PROCESS USING DIFFERENT TYPE OF KNIVES

L.G. CIULICĂ*

Abstract: *This paper presents the determination of the cutting resistance force in the cutting process of certain vegetables. The role of this paper is to highlight the influence of the knife edge geometry on the cutting force. To achieve this were performed experimental measurements consisted of cutting samples of plant product using a single edged knife and a double edged knife, both with the same cutting angle, respectively 30°. The determination of the optimum cutting angle for different variety of vegetables will lead to a lower energy consumption required for the cutting processes.*

Keywords: *cutting resistance force, vegetables, cutting knives.*

1. Introduction

The sharpness of a cutting instrument is a fundamentally important parameter in all cutting applications. It strongly influences the forces generated and energy required during the cutting process, the life of the cutting edge, and the surface finish or quality of the cut surface.

The sharpness of a blade is a key parameter in cutting soft solids, such as foodstuffs or elastomeric materials.

Despite the lack of standardization, there are many industries in which blade sharpness plays an important role and affects not only the cutting process, but often has a direct influence on human life.

A number of studies have considered the effect of cutting blade geometry on the forces generated during a cutting operation. McGorry examined the effect of blade angles (ranging from 20_ to 50_) on cutting tool grip forces and moments exerted by professionals during two different meatpacking operations and found that blade angle did not have a significant affect on these measures.

However, this finding is in disagreement with the work of Moore et al. who found, while cutting sugar beet, that the cutting force increased as the wedge angle increased.

Studies that have examined the effect of the cutting tool tip radius have found that as the radius increases, the cutting forces also increase.

The above studies highlight the need to accurately determine blade sharpness across very different fields of science and engineering.

The fact that there is no standard definition, measurement or protocol to quantify the sharpness of a cutting instrument is largely due to the complexity and diversity of variables associated with cutting edge profiles. However, a recent international standard addresses sharpness and proposes an edge retention test for cutlery. This standard specifies the sharpness and edge retention of knives which are produced for professional and domestic use in the preparation of food of all kinds, specifically those knives intended for hand use. [1]

The stiffness curves of sharp blades identify typical characteristics of the cutting process, i.e., initial indentation, steady state cutting etc. and are thus a useful way to examine the cutting process.

These curves are easy to produce once the cutting forces and blade displacements are available and could be used in most cutting applications to identify the different stages of the cutting process.

However, the blunt stiffness curves identify initial indentation but thereafter change significantly with respect to the sharp case and fail to identify any recognizable stages of the cutting process.

This is due to the random nature of cutting with blunt blades in which the substrate can buckle under the blade combined with tearing

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and possibly many other local non-linear events such as wrinkling. Although difficult, it would be very interesting to develop a method to examine the initiation and growth of the cut in front of the blade tip for both sharp and blunt blades.

This could be achieved by mounting a microscope and camera onto the blade and moving the substrate relative to the blade (rather than moving the blade as in the case here). [1; 2]

2. Material and Method

By performing experimental research in the laboratory were made some comparisons between cutting resistance force obtained from certain plant products such as potatoes, belonging to different varieties, thus highlighting their influence on the process of cutting. For experimental measurements in laboratory

conditions were used different potato varieties, namely Rudolf, Destiny and Arizona.

For the determination of cutting resistance was used a special stand created by Zwick / Roell. This equipment works with software called Test Expert, which stores data in its Windows operating system for acquisition, visualization and data analysis. One of its most important ability is to store one of the measures procedures and have immediate access to it. A determination can be defined by two windows: one by imposing the parameters, and the other one by defining the way to view the results (graphs, tables).

The knives are presented in figure 1 and 2, and are single and double edged with a sharpening angle of 30° .

Fig. 1 Graphic representation of the single edged cutting knife with the sharpening angle of 30°

Fig. 2. Graphic representation of the double edged cutting knife with the sharpening angle of 30°

The cutting of tested products was performed using these knives with the blade thickness by

1.4 mm. For each variety of potatoes were tested five potatoes for each knife in part.

Fig.3. Aspects from the experimental research

3. Results and Discussions

vegetables used in the experimental researches were displayed in table 1.

The experimental research results for those

Table 1

Potatoes variety	Type of edge	Knife sharpening angle [°]	Cutting resistance force [N]				
			Rudolph	Single edge	30°	63.59	57.64
Destiny	81.23	63.31	55.45			75.16	78.72
Arizona	40.88	67.74	54.59			61.44	48.37
Rudolph	Double edge	49.82	39.99	44.68		45.14	45.85
Destiny		61.86	52.87	88.37		77.25	57.57
Arizona		39.75	44.63	45.86		34.53	43.76

The results obtained from experimental measurements were processed as a graph (fig.4).

The graph shows that the lowest cutting force (41.70 N) was obtained for Arizona potatoes

variety for the double edged cutting knife, and the higher cutting force (70.77 N) was obtained for Destiny potatoes variety for the cutting single edged knife.

Fig.4. Cutting resistance variation

It also can be observe that higher values were obtained for the Destiny potatoes variety which had the higher values in both cases. For the single edged cutting knife were obtained the lowest cutting force for all types of potatoes.

4. Conclusions

1. Following the experimental measurements it can be seen that the cutting resistance force is lower for the double edged cutting knife compared with the single edged cutting knife

2. For the same type of potatoes was obtained smaller values for the double edged cutting knife in contrast with the single edged cutting knife.

3. For an optimal energy consumption is recommended to use the knife with double edge to obtain the minimal cutting force.

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EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH REGARDING THE CUTTING RESISTANCE FORCE OF CERTAIN VARIETIES OF POTATOES

L.G. Ciulică*

Abstract: *In the paper are presented the results of experimental researches regarding the resistance force of different varieties of potato during the cutting process. At these experimental determinations were used six different types of potatoes which were cut with the same double edged knife with the sharpening angle of 30°. The role of this paper is to show which of these selected varieties of potatoes present a minimum resistance force at cutting. This fact is important for their further processing, causing the variation of cutting force and thus the energy consumption for their processing.*

Keywords: *cutting process, knife, potatoes.*

1. Introduction

The potato was first cultivated in Peru and Bolivia and it was used by incase the 2000 years before the arrival of Spanish explorers. In the early 1500s the spanish explorers led by Pizaro discovered potatoes in Ecuador. From here, the explorers brought the potato to Spain, Italy and France, the latter rejecting the potatoes at first.

In the twentieth century, the area cultivated with potatoes increased continuously. Annual potato production in developed countries increased from 30 million tons in the early 60s to 85 million tones in recent years. According to a FAO study entitled ``Potatoes in the 1990s``, potato production in developing countries which recorded a 3.6 percent annual rate is expected to increase by more than 5 percent per year, especially in Asia , Africa and Latin America.

This increase is caused both by improvements in productivity they bring to these countries, but also due to increased area cultivated with potato. FAO report states that potato production in Asia increased by 136 percent from 1961 and by 140 percent in Africa. It also states that the second largest potato growing after Russia is China, and the third is Poland.

The potato is a staple food, both in Romania and at global scale. His content of nutrients and vitamins recommend him for use in various food recipes, available for consumers of all ages. Higher productions on hectare and climatic conditions of specific areas in Romania have

made the potato a principal product for the existence of a large number of farmers. At the same time the potato proved to be a vegetable product particularly sensitive to fluctuations of temperature and humidity, soil physical and chemical characteristics and especially to a lot of diseases and pests [1].

In many food processes it is frequently necessary to reduce the size of solid materials for different purposes. In this case, size reduction may aid other processes such as expression and extraction, or may shorten heat treatments such as blanching and cooking. Comminuting is the generic term used for size reduction and includes different operations such as crushing, grinding, milling, mincing, and dicing. Most of these terms are related to a particular application, e.g., milling of cereals, mincing of beef, dicing of tubers, or grinding of spices [2, 3].

During the processes of peeling and cutting, intracellular oxidizing enzymes are released. In addition the surface of the vegetables is exposed to the air and to contamination by bacteria, yeasts and moulds.

Therefore elevated respiration/transpiration rates and metabolic activities of spoilage microorganisms are the main reasons for shortened shelf-life [4].

2. Material and Method

For the determination of cutting resistance is used a special stand created by Zwik / Roell which is presented in figure 1.

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Fig. 1 Zwick /Roell stand for cutting resistance determination

This equipment works with software called Test Expert, which stores data in its Windows operating system for acquisition, visualization and data analysis. One of its most important abilities is to store one of the measures procedures and have immediate access to it. A determination can be defined by two windows: one by imposing the parameters, and the other one by defining the way to view the results (graphs, tables).

The equipment is composed from the frame 1 in which is mounted the drive mechanism of the knife holder, the knife 3, a control panel 2 and a device for vegetables application 4.

The knife used for this experimental determination is presented in figure 2, and is double edged with a sharpening angle of 30° .

Fig. 2 Graphic representation of the single edged cutting knife with the sharpening angle of 30°

For experimental measurements in laboratory conditions were used different potato varieties, namely Rustic Ecologic, Cumidava, Christian, Roclas, Kronstad, Tâmpa.

The cutting of tested products was performed using these knives with the blade thickness by 1.4 mm. For each variety of potatoes were tested ten potatoes with this cutting knife.

Fig.3. Aspects from the experimental research

3. Results and Discussions

After measurements, the experimental research equipment displays the results in the form of graphs representing the variation of cutting

resistance depending on the depth covered by the cutting knife.

An example of such a graphic is presented in figure 4.

Fig.4. Variation of cutting resistance for the Tâmpa variety potatoes

Analyzing the graphs from figure 4, it can be observed the mechanism of cutting operation, characterized by the existence of two stages. By applying shear force on one axis (transverse), on this direction the material will be required to compression. In the first step under cutting blade action, in the mass of sample material develops a state of efforts, its cellular tissue will be elastic deformed. In the second stage, characterized by reaching a critical value (on the chart the

maximum variation curve), causing cracks, which quickly spreads and branches, phenomenon that is evidenced by low levels of effort, after which the process is repeated until the total separation of slice. Action the knife in material is accompanied by plastic deformations of cellular tissues, which is destroyed and produce a certain amount of release cellular juice, which will have lubricating qualities. Complete separation of the splinter material, is characterized by a sudden

decrease of the values force that drives the knife.
The experimental research results for those

vegetables used in the experimental researches were displayed in table 1.

Table 1

Potatoes variety	Probe	1	2	3	4	5
Rustic Ecologic	Cutting force [N]	41.47	59.93	64.42	45.53	54.14
	Diameter [mm]	39.75	44.63	45.86	34.53	43.76
Cumidava	Cutting force [N]	61.86	52.87	88.37	77.25	57.57
	Diameter [mm]	49.40	49.90	48.93	52.92	52.62
Christian	Cutting force [N]	53.67	40.87	45.94	44.28	43.39
	Diameter [mm]	49.82	39.99	44.68	45.14	45.85
Roclas	Cutting force [N]	48.42	43.98	49.32	52.90	46.59
	Diameter [mm]	44.70	48.42	50.48	48.81	45.82
Kronstad	Cutting force [N]	41.77	57.07	71.40	74.29	41.90
	Diameter [mm]	40.57	45.80	41.75	49.27	40.70
Tâmpa	Cutting force [N]	57.88	47.40	39.31	48.53	44.50
	Diameter [mm]	49.61	45.40	47.60	48.23	49.97

The results obtained from experimental measurements were processed as a graph (fig.5).

For graphical representation of these results was calculated the average values for each type of potatoes variety and also, the medium diameter. Thus for the Rustic Ecologic variety the value for medium cutting force was 53.09 [N] and the average diameter was 41.7 [mm], for the Cumidava variety the medium value was 67.54 [N] and average diameter was 50.75 [mm], for the Christian variety the calculated value was 45.63 [N] and average diameter was 45.09 [mm],

for Roclas variety the value was 48.24 [N] and average diameter was 47.67 [mm], for Kronstad variety the medium value was 57.28 [N] and the average diameter was 43.61 [mm], and for the Tâmpa variety the calculated value was 47.52 [N] and the average diameter was 48.16 [mm].

The graph show that the lowest cutting force (45.62 N) was obtained for Christian potatoes variety and the higher cutting force (67.54 N) was obtained for Cumidava potatoes variety.

Fig.5 Variations of cutting resistance force for different potatoes variety

4. Conclusions

Following the experimental measurements it can be seen that the cutting resistance force depends on the cutting section, so that with increasing cutting section, increase their resistance to cutting. But, the cutting resistance force may vary depending on the internal structure of the material, like in the case of Kronstad potatoes variety which presented a higher cutting force 57.28 [N] even if the cutting section was quite small 43.61 [mm], compared with other values obtained.

The knowledge of cutting resistance for these vegetables can be used to optimize knife parts of food industry equipments used in their processing.

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RESEARCH CONCERNING MEAT INDUSTRY'S BY-PRODUCTS CAPITALIZATION

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Abstract: *In this study it has been tried to reveal the health benefits of soy protein meat preparats due to their content in easy assimilated proteins and for their contribution in reducing risk of osteoporosis. The meat preparats were furnished by some illustrative production units in the county Suceava, some obtained by traditional means, other by modern technologies and recipes.*

Keywords: *meat products, MDM, soy protein, quality properties*

1. Introduction

The manufacture of new products with real health benefits is a recent problem and in the same time is the result of accepting idea that nourishment has a major role in preventing and/or treating illnesses. This new concept motivating the development of new foodstuffs have mobilized a great number of production units and organizations with the purpose to assure food safety, health risk, rapport risk-benefits, efficiency and toxicity evaluation, sanitary settlements.

Also, for producing and marketing these new products, it is important establishing quality control rules and health efficiency.

The major feeding role is that of furnishing proper nutrients in satisfactory quantity for metabolic organisms' needs and beside all these, consumers' satisfaction due to their sensorial attributes. Foodstuffs also contribute to maintaining health, optimal development and reducing the risk of falling-ill [1,2].

Claims on reducing risks of illnesses were officially recognized in USA since 1993. Thus, it was documented evidence about the correlation between foodstuffs' or diet foods' nutrients and some illnesses, such as: foods with high calcium level reduce the risk of osteoporosis; low carbonated fat and cholesterol content for heart diseases; polyalcohol presence for decays risk. The main conditions for a product to be foodstuff are:

- To be salubrious;

- To have nourishing value;
- To possess proper sensory qualities, elements that define food value.

Nourishing value for a food product is determined by nourishing substances composition: proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, vitamins, mineral salts, and the relation between components, their quality, digestive using degree, and the way in which it satisfies the organism's requirements. Nourishing value differs from a food product to another in regards to its origin, variety, developing conditions, processing technology and can be evaluated by biological or chemical methods [4].

The nourishing researcher Strimska F developed a nourishing value indicator using just 10 components from food product, resulted from chemical analysis: proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, Ca, P, Fe, vitamins: A, B₁, B₂, C.

The energetic value refers to food components' property of producing combustion energy: proteins, carbohydrates and lipids and it is taking account by energy quantity determined in standard conditions for 1 gram of each product: 4.1kcal for 1g of proteins and carbohydrates and 9.3 kcal for 1 g of lipids.

Mechanical, physical, chemical, biochemical processing, with the purpose of obtaining finished products, create sensible modifications regarding chemical composition, with an implicit influence on nourishing and energetic value, by proteins, hydrocarbons, lipids, vitamins and mineral salts losses. Processing techniques have

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different influences on chemical components' losses: refining and drying produce significant losses compared to freezing of foodstuffs. For both processing technologies it is important to have processing guiding, working regime and technical parameters. Also, there is positive influence coming from processing technologies: germination, lactic fermentation, etc. It is important how much the influence of each processing on food results in nourishing value, for best precautions to minimize losses [2].

This study points out some considerations about the energetic value comparison between meat products (beef, pork and poultry) and corresponding products on MDM (mechanically deboned meat) [3, 5, 6]. In detail, to underline the effects of using vegetable protein and MDM in pre-cooked and meat products, taking into account the quality and functional properties of this kind of proteins.

2. Material and Methods

For the experiments were used meat products from important meat-processing plants from Suceava, some of them made by beef and pork meat and others by poultry and by soy and MDM addition.

In the laboratory were applied standard chemical methods for analysis:

- 105°C etuve drying for humidity determination;
- Kjeldahl method for total protein evaluation;
- 550°C ashing for mineral salts determination;

- Soxhlet method for lipids' extraction and for hydrocarbons' determination was made 100% difference (humidity plus proteins plus lipids plus ash plus hydrocarbons make 100).

As apparatus, Gerhardt unit was disposed for both mineralisation and distillation for total protein and potentiometric titration with calibrated electrode for equivalent point of HCl 0.1 N titration; Selecta etuve for humidity, Selecta automatization unit for Soxhlet method using petroleum ether as solvent and 150°C evaporating temperature; Carbolite ash furnace.

The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided.

3. Results and Discussions

The following tables present indicators' values obtained by chemical analysis for examined samples. It was also determined NaCl content for its influence on water content, on texture, on time storage and healthy influence (cord diseases).

Use clear ideas, short sentences, and standard terminology. Special characters, symbols, and measure units must comply with the standards in use.

Table 1 points out values for pre-cooked and poultry – MDM meat products. With few exceptions the products present energetic value over 200 kcal/100 g product, which means an important energy for organism. Plus, the positive influence of vegetable protein or poultry protein – more assimilable and digestible for age categories: children and ageing population.

Table 1

Energetic value for pre-cooked and poultry – MDM meat products

Assortments	Physical –chemical parameters				Energetic Value [kcal/100g]
	NaCl [%]	Water [%]	Lipids [%]	Protein [%]	
Fried poultry sausages - freezed	2.10	63.41	17.18	14.08	234
Poultry Kebab	2.25	69.35	14.77	12.96	202
Mortadella – sausage	1.75	71.88	5.48	13.92	122
Nuggets - poultry	1.84	68.71	10.16	13.80	165.5
Hamburger - MDM	1.75	71.12	12.45	12.89	177.3
Meat pie – poultry	1.76	72.16	8.76	13.62	147.1
Sausage Delice – poultry	2.43	59.51	17.98	12.97	232.8
Saucisse - poultry	2.13	60.84	18.71	13.81	243.7

Table 2 shows superior values for this kind of meat products because of their superior content in lipids and protein. Also their lipid content

and pork origin of meat means bigger attention over intensive consumption.

These salami were obtained after long maturation with mould suspensions at high

humidity and low temperature – controlled parameters. It points out high values of lipids and also proteins content that leads to values of over 470 kcal/100 g product, even 509 kcal/100 g product at Sibiu salami (table 3). Due to the processing technology these products have better sensory qualities such as aroma, taste, texture, aspect.

The sausages analyzed demonstrate also good values for energetic value and good balance between lipids and protein content (table 4). The NaCl content is too close to the 3.0 % limit value accepted by present legislation.

Table 2

Energetic value for beef and pork salami

Assortments	Physical –chemical parameters				Energetic Value [kcal/100g]
	NaCl [%]	Water [%]	Lipids [%]	Protein [%]	
Bucuresti – salami	2.31	59.84	24.19	11.17	284.82
Mix Mortadela	2.27	64.11	16.51	11.09	213.40
Dry salami	3.0	47.31	24.23	18.48	315.54
Victoria salami	2.51	66.19	20.09	11.05	243.42

Table 3

Energetic value for mould ageing salami

Assortments	Physical –chemical parameters				Energetic Value [kcal/100g]
	NaCl [%]	Water [%]	Lipids [%]	Protein [%]	
Sibiu	3.05	28.21	45.29	18.01	509.35
Ghiudem	3.07	33.66	42.81	15.39	475.62
Babic	3.15	33.21	43.17	15.51	478.36
Taranesc	2.91	29.11	43.89	17.31	490.18

Table 4

Energetic value for assortments of sausages

Assortments	Physical –chemical parameters				Energetic Value [kcal/100g]
	NaCl [%]	Water [%]	Lipids [%]	Protein [%]	
Cluj	2.98	51.73	15.63	23.96	260.16
Special	2.97	49.73	22.90	19.57	307.27
Cabanos	2.63	49.01	26.36	16.83	329.20
Ardelenesti	2.47	50.44	24.37	19.19	320.12
Smoked	2.88	46.99	28.52	18.49	354.62

4. Conclusions

Using the proteins with modified structure (either chemical or enzymatic methods) and unconventional sources proteins to achieve one or another purpose:

- degradation reaction blocking (Maillard or Lysine-Alanine type compounds);
- proteins' functional properties improvement;
- proteins' digestibility intensification.

Majority of proteins have hydrophilic aminoacids at molecule surface (Lysine, Glutamine, Serine) and hydrophobic aminoacids (Phenilalanine, Valine) at molecule interior. Adding hydrophobic groups at molecule surface by chemical modifications there were obtained structural modifications and also hydrophobic areas.

Obtaining vegetables proteins for food industry consists also in functional properties'

improvement: dispersability and solubility intensification, heat treatment resistance improvement, elasticity intensification for a better finite form development.

Using vegetable proteins or MDM for pre-cooked or meat products leads to solubility

improvement and proteic dispersions viscosity rising and also emulsion and foaming capacity improvement. Plus, don't forget the health benefits of using vegetable instead animal proteins, soy bean effects concerning phytohormones' action.

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STUDY ON QUALITATIVE AND OPERATING INDICES OF M-1464 MACHINE FOR CHOPPING AND SPREADING ON THE SOIL OF PLANT DEBRIS

P. DALADIMOS¹, M. BADESCU¹

Abstract: *Analysis of plant debris choppers necessitate research in order to improve the working process of the machines for cutting and chopping plant debris and making optimum their use, research that are not sufficiently highlighted in the literature. In this sense, by the research that will be carried out we will be able to determine the type or types of active bodies (knives) the best suited to fit machines for cutting and chopping plant debris so to have a range as large as possible of plant debris that must be cut, chopped and scattered on the surface of the soil. At the same time it will be set the optimal working speed running of the rotors with knives, which equip the machines for chopping plant debris, so that the qualitative indices to meet the conditions imposed on the operation of cutting, chopping and scattering on the surface of the soil plant debris, according to two parameters: the working speed of the aggregate tractor-machine for cutting and chopping plant debris and the quantity and type of plant mass subject to cut and chop.*

Keywords: *chopping machine for plant debris, degree of chopping, working speed*

Introduction

Being a priority by the share which has in our country in all agricultural works, the question of land release of plant debris by cutting, chopping and uniform distribution of the chips on the surface of the soil become objective of applicative scientific research.

The chopping of plant debris resulting from agricultural activities, after the main products harvest, as well as spontaneous vegetation destruction on cultivated or fallow lands, represents an important step in the technological process of establishing agricultural crops.

The works on the land release of plant debris are management practices of particular importance, because of the effect they have on the quality of subsequent works of preparation of the ground for the creation of new cultures.

The main purpose of cutting, chopping and uniform distribution of the vegetal chips on the surface of soil on the agricultural land is to create appropriate conditions for performing at a higher quality level of ploughings and achieve maximum work capacity for ploughing aggregates. By ploughing, plant debris crushed is incorporated into the soil and through their decay is an enrichment of the soil with nutrients.

The study of the working process of chopping machines of plant debris and leave them on the ground by scattering, allowed to define the constructive and working parameters of the chopping rotors and scattering on the soil of plant debris from other features that contributes to the achievement of uniformity in length of the chips and uniform scattering on the ground, leading to the optimization of the working body type and the process of chopping and scattering of the aggregate composed of 65 HP tractor and machine for chopping plant debris.

In this way experimental research will concentrate in particular on the determination and analysis of those factors that influence sensitively the degree of chopping and scattering uniformity of chips and less on constructive elements who have found so far solution in the concept of the machines for chopping plant debris. In the category of factors with decisive role on the degree and length of chopping and on distribution uniformity of vegetal ground remnants, are the following:

- type of chopping and scattering knives;
- the revolution of the rotor mounted with chopping and scattering knives;
- working speed of the aggregate tractor and chipper plant debris;

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- mass and density of the plant remnants, and the height thereof, existing on the aggregate working surface.

In order to obtain conclusive results allowing further interpretation of the influence factors on the qualitative indices, which have significant weight on the working process of the machine for chopping plant debris, the experimental tests will be performed on some machines which are in series manufacture or are part of farms equipment in Romania.

Material and method

Experiments were carried out in 2009 with a machine for chopping plant debris type M-

1464, produced by s.c Poliprod s.a from Târgu Secuiesc.

M-1464 has a working width of 2.4 m and a mass of 700 kg and is working in aggregate with a 65 HP tractor with a rotor speed of 1600 rpm.

For experiments, for the purpose of achieving higher revolution than normal rotor with knives, set by equipment manufacturer, it has developed a set of wheels with corresponding belt, which were mounted in place of the existing ones. In this way it has obtained the rotor revolutions: 1800, 2000 and 2200 rpm.

Technical characteristics of Poliprod machines are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Type of machine	Working width (m)	Dimensions of gauge working (m)			Machine weight (kg)	Rotor revolution (rot/min)	Power requirement (CP)
		Lenght	Width	Hight			
M-1461	1,6	1,4	2,0	0,7	400	1600	25-35
M-1460	1,9	1,35	2,25	0,85	465	1600	25-35
M-1464	2,4	2,475	2,635	1,2	700	1600	35-45
M-1404	2,7	2,475	2,93	1,3	960	1600	35-45
M-1402	3,0	2,475	3,220	1,3	1040	1600	35-45
M-1406	3,1	2,707	3,45	1,26	1060	1600	58-70
M-1401	4,5	2,51	5,0	1,55	1880	1600	80-100

Fig. 1 Machine type M cutting plant debris

Fig. 2 Types of knives used at Polyprod machines

Results and discussions

From the analysis on the operating indices of the machine for chopping plant debris in the world resulted that the revolution of the rotor is between 1600 and 2000 rpm, therefore, all experiments shall be carried out with rotor

speeds from 1600 to 2000 rpm. The results of trials are listed below.

Degree of grinding vegetable remnants using different types of knives mounted on rotor chipper is shown in table 2.

Table 2

Culture characteristic	Working speed (km/h)	Rotor revolution (rot/min)	Chopping degree		
			Knife type		
			universal Y	palette	upright
Maize Vegetal mass 12250 kg/ha	3,83	1600	80,3	80,9	75,2
		1800	81,4	81,8	75,8
		2000	84,2	83,4	76,5
		2200	85,6	84,7	77,9
	7,68	1600	79,8	79,2	72,4
		1800	80,4	80,9	73,1
		2000	80,92	81,2	74,2
		2200	83,4	82,6	74,7

Data analysis from table 2 shows:

- the degree of chopping for both types of plant mass is higher at 3,83 km/h and smaller at 7,68 speed km/h. For a speed of 3,83 km/h using universal knives, type Y at the culture of maize, the chopping degree is in the range of 80,5% and 85,6%, while at the speed of 7,68 km/h values are between 79,8% and 83,4%.
- universal knives type Y and type palette makes the chopping by about the same intensity, in particular an easy advantage in favor of Y-type knives. In comparison with these upright knives

have a chopping degree well below those obtained with knives of type Y or palette. The values for the degree of chopping obtained by upright knives are between 72,4% against 80,5% 79,8% to 87,7% obtained with knives of type Y and type palette.

Experimental values for fuel consumption of aggregate tractor and machine for chopping plant debris, using different types of knives mounted on the rotor machine have been determined through Flowtronic apparatus. These values are presented in table 3.

Table 3

Culture characteristics	Viteza de lucru (km/h)	Rotor revolution (rot/min)	Fuel consumption (l/h)		
			Type of knives		
			universal Y	universal Y	universal Y
Maize Vegetal mass 12.250 kg/ha	3,83	1600	5,4	6,0	4,9
		1800	5,9	6,3	5,01
		2000	6,1	6,9	5,10
		2200	6,5	7,2	5,8
	7,68	1600	8,2	8,9	6,1
		1800	8,4	9,0	6,5
		2000	8,8	9,6	6,8
		2200	9,1	9,8	7,1

The data presented in table 3 will allow highlighting the following conclusions:

- necessary fuel consumption increases with speed, at all kinds of the experienced knives and is influenced by the shape of knives.
- at a speed of 3,83 km/h at chopping plant remnants from the maize crop the fuel consumption is:
 - 5.2-6.4 l/h at Y-type knife;
 - 5.8-7.2 l/h to type palette knife;
 - 4.9-5.6 l/h at knife type upright.
- at a speed of 7.68 km/h for chopping plant debris fuel consumption was:
 - 8.0-9.1 l/h at knife type Y;
 - 8.8-9.8 l/h to type palette knife;
 - 6.1-7.1 l/h at knife type upright.
- the lowest fuel consumption at all speeds is with upright knife as compared to the other two types of knives, consumption is much higher.

The bottom line is that the speeds 3,83-7,68 km/h, the upright knife requires a fuel consumption between 4.9-7,1 l/h, palette knife type requires a fuel consumption 5.8-9,8 l/h, and Y-type universal knife requires a consumption of 5.2-9.1 l/h.

Fuel consumption increases with increasing chipper impeller revolution. For example at culture of maize and at aggregate speed of 3,83 km/h, with the rotor machine equipped with Y-type knives at an 1800 rpm, fuel consumption is 5.9 l/h. under the same conditions to an idle speed of impeller of 2000 RPM is consumption 6,1 l/h and speeds of 2200 rpm fuel consumption is 6.5 l/h. For example at a speed of 3,83 km/h, when the rotor is equipped with Y-type knives, the maize crop fuel consumption 5,4-6,5 l/h.

Corroborating the results obtained on the preliminary experiments of the types of knives, one can say that in terms of index chopping and

fuel consumption that defines the process of chopping plant remnants, best behaves in crop of maize, knife type Y.

Determination of the influence of various factors on the qualitative indices

The results obtained from the measurements were grouped in tables, depending on the test conditions established on the basis of which it could interpret the quality of the work done by a machine for chopping plant debris in different conditions.

It is known that the on the qualitative indices of chopping process a major influence has the speed of the aggregate consisting of tractor and chopping machine, the revolution of the rotor and the type of cutting bodies with which it is equipped, as well as the characteristics of the plant material subjected to chop.

Influence of working speed on the qualitative indices at maize culture

Results of measurements on the influence of working speed on the qualitative indices in a culture of maize are shown in table 4.

Fig. 3 Land aspect after chopping maize stalks

Table 4

Vegetal mass quantity (kg/ha)	Rotor characteristic -revolution (rot/min) - type of knives	Working speed (km/h)	Quality indices (%):		
			Chopping degree	Cutting degree	Uniformity of the cutting height
6500	1600 Knives type Y	3,83	83,9	98,3	94,6
		4,16	83,6	98,5	94,2
		5,78	83,2	97,6	93,8
		6,17	82,7	97,3	93,6
		7,68	82,1	97,1	92,7
	1800 Knives type Y	3,83	84,5	98,7	94,8
		4,16	84,8	98,8	94,4
		5,78	85,2	97,9	93,8
		6,17	85,6	98,1	93,7
		7,68	85,8	95,6	93,2
8.500	1600 Knives type Y	3,83	82,5	98,1	93,4
		4,16	82,1	98,0	92,8
		5,78	81,4	97,6	92,1
		6,17	81,8	97,4	91,4
		7,68	80,7	97,2	91,2
	1800 Knives type Y	3,83	82,8	98,7	94,5
		4,16	82,9	98,5	93,4
		5,78	81,8	98,8	93,1
		6,17	81,2	98,1	92,7
		7,68	81,4	97,6	92,6
12.250	1600 Knives type Y	3,83	81,4	97,8	91,7
		4,16	80,8	97,5	91,3
		5,78	81,7	97,4	90,5
		6,17	81,2	96,8	90,2
		7,68	80,4	96,4	89,1
	1800 Knives type Y	3,83	83,5	98,2	92,4
		4,19	83,7	98,6	92,8
		5,78	83,9	98,8	92,8
		6,17	84,1	97,8	93,1
		7,68	84,2	97,9	93,3
6500	2000 Knives type Y	3,83	85,66	98,18	95,4
		4,16	85,18	98,10	94,8
		5,78	83,9	97,9	94,7
		6,17	82,84	97,5	93,5
		7,68	82,18	97,3	92,6
	2200	3,83	87,9	98,2	95,8
		4,16	87,5	97,8	95,2

	Knives type Y	5,78	86,4	97,6	94,4	
		6,17	86,2	97,4	94,1	
		7,68	85,3	96,5	93,7	
8500	2000	3,83	84,58	97,8	94,9	
		4,16	84,74	97,6	94,5	
		5,78	83,62	97,1	93,4	
	Knives type Y	6,17	82,68	96,8	93,2	
		7,68	81,78	96,9	92,1	
		3,83	87,1	98,1	94,7	
	2200	4,16	86,9	97,3	94,3	
		5,78	86,7	96,9	93,6	
		Knives type Y	6,17	85,8	97,1	93,1
			7,68	85,1	96,2	92,3
	12250	2000	3,83	84,2	96,5	93,3
			4,16	84,36	96,4	92,8
5,78			83,42	95,8	92,4	
Knives type Y		6,17	82,64	95,3	92,1	
		7,68	80,92	95,1	90,7	
		3,83	85,7	97,9	93,2	
2200		4,16	85,5	98,1	93,5	
		5,78	84,3	97,3	92,6	
		Knives type Y	6,17	83,8	96,5	92,4
			7,68	83,4	96,2	91,7

Analysis and interpretation of the results presented in table 4 leads to the following conclusions:

- on qualitative indices resulting from the process of chopping at maize culture, major influences have the working speed (tractor and chopping machine), chopping machine rotor revolution and the amount of plant mass subject to chop;

- the influence of speed on the qualitative indices shows that with the increasing speed of the aggregate decrease quality indices values. So at a speed of 3.83 km/h, and a chopped mass of 6500 kg/ha, with an idle speed of 1600 rpm, chopping degree is 83.9% while under the same conditions but at a speed of 7.68 km/h, the chopping degree is 82.1%. Index on the cutting plants varies within the limits of 98.3 at 3.83 km/h and the speed of 97.1% 7.68 km/h. Additionally index of the uniform cutting height is between 94.6% at speed 3.83 km/h and 92.7% at 7.68 km/h speed. Same findings are valid and if the aggregate works in crops with higher yields and the revolution of the rotor is different;

- the influence of rotor revolution of the chopping machine on the qualitative indices

shows that working with the increasing revolution qualitative indices values increase. So, for example for a stalks mass of 8500 kg/ha and a speed of 3.83 km/h, the chopping degree is 82.5% rotor revolution of 1600 rpm, 84.58% at 2000 rpm and 87.1% at 2200 rpm. Working in the same conditions the cutting plants index is 98.1% at rotor revolution of 1800 rpm, 97.8% at 2000 rpm and 98.1% at 2200 rpm. In the same working conditions the cutting plants index is 98.1% at rotor revolution of 1800 rpm, 97.8% at 2000 rpm and 98.1% at 2200 rpm.

Similar conclusions about the influence of chopping machine impeller revolution can be drawn for different vegetal masses of crops (corn stalks) per hectare and for other work speeds.

Index on uniformity of cutting height is 93.4% at 1800 rpm, 94.9% at 2000 rpm and 94.7% at 2200 rpm. Instead for a speed of 7.68 km/h chopping degree is 80.7% at 1800 rpm, 81.78% at 2000 rpm and 85.1% at 2200 rpm. Degree of cutted plants, under the same working conditions is 97.2% at 1800 rpm, 96.6% at 2000 rpm and 96.2% at 2200 rpm and cutting height variation is 91.2% at idle speed of 1800 rpm,

92.1% at idle speed of 2000 rpm and 92.3% at 2200 rpm.

- with regard to the influence of corn stalks mass to the ha on the qualitative indices shows that with the increase of the quantity of stems at ha, the values of the indices fall. Thus, a rotor machine idle speed 1800 rpm and working speed 3,83 km/h, the degree of chopping is 83.9% at a plant mass of 6500 kg/ha, 82.5% when working in a culture of maize plant with a total mass of 8500 kg/ha and 81.4% for a vegetal mass of 12.250 kg/ha.

Conclusions on experimental trials with M-1464 machine

Regarding the chopping degree

- the degree of chopping for both types of plant mass is higher at speed of 3.83 km/h and less at speed of 7.68 km/h. Thus, at speed of 3.83 km/h using universal knives, type Y at the culture of maize, the chips are in the range of 80.5% and 85.6%, while at 7.68 km/h values are between 79.8% and 83.4%.

- universal knives type Y and type palette make the chopping by about the same intensity, in particular an easy advantage in favor of Y-type knives. In comparison with these knives type upright obtain a chopping degree with values well below those obtained with knives of type Y or palette. The values of the degree of chopping for upright knives are between 72.4% and 80.5% against 79.8% to 87.7% obtained with knives of type Y and type palette.

Regarding the influence of the working speed on the qualitative indices it is found that

with the increasing working speed of the aggregate decrease quality indices values. So at a speed of 3.83 km/h, and a chopping mass of 6500 kg/ha, with a rotor revolution of 1600 rpm, chopping degree is 83.9% while under the same working conditions but at a speed of 7.68 km/h, the chopping degree is 82.1%. Index of the cutting plants varies within the limits of 98.3% at 3.83 km/h and 97.1% at 7.68 km/h speed. Additionally index of the uniform cutting height is between 94.6% at a speed of 3.83 km/h and 92.7% at 7,68 km/h. Same findings are valid and if the aggregate works in crops with higher yields and the rotor revolution is different.

- cutting degree of plants maintains at close values for all working speeds, rotor revolutions and the stalks production;

- Quality index on uniformity of cutting height have values between 97.4% at 3.83 km/h and stalks production of 5825 kg/ha when the rotor machine revolution was 1800 rpm. In the same way but with a production of 7500 kg/ha, uniformity of cutting height values are 97.1% at 3.83 km/h speed and 9.7% at 7.58 km/h. Similar trends of falls in the values of the index of quality regarding the uniformity of cutting height is found when the rotor machine revolution changes from 1800 rpm at 2000 rpm and 2200 rpm. Value quality index on uniformity of cutting height is higher at low speeds and less at high speeds, the highest obtained at rotor revolution of 2200 rpm.

As regards fuel consumption, shows that it increases with increasing of chopping machine rotor revolution.

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STUDY OF THE ANGLE OF ASCENT OF THE PRODUCT IN A ROTATING CYLINDER SIEVE UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF VIBRATION

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Abstract: *This paper presents the results of the practical definition of elevation angle of the granular mixture - grains of pea in a rotating drum sieve at angular vibration of the working body in the vertical plane.*

Key words: *cylindrical sieve classifier, bulk products, mechanical vibrations, angle of elevation of a material*

1. Problem formulation and its relation to important scientific and practical tasks.

Machines with rotating cylindrical sieves are widely used in food-processing industry for separation, classification, calibration of any bulk solids. These machines are: centrifuges, ovens, dryers, refrigerators, mixers, granulators, screens, drum calibration machines, tumbling drums, machines, sifting and assorting friable materials etc. Prominent feature of the machines of this type is that they can realise connection of technological processes in them, for example, granulation and drying, grinding and classification.

A literary review and experimental researches show that given type of equipment is used insufficiently because of lack of exact theory of motion of a granular material in rotating cylinders and methods of calculation of optimal modes and geometrical parameters of the machine.

In the papers [1, 2] a new theory of motion of the granular mass is presented and a positive influence of mechanical vibrations on increase of efficiency of separation in a horizontal drum-sieve due to increase of the area of useful sieve surface is proved. It resulted in the necessity for practical studies of this process.

The purpose of the article is practical confirmation and researches of increase of area of effective cylindrical sieve surface due to the use of vibration. Determination of dependence of change of value of area of effective cylindrical sieve surface from the angle of elevation of material at the different volumes of loading of the drum that rotates.

Researches were held using a pre-production model of separator with cylindrical steel stamped sieve designed for calibration of grains of green peas (Figure 1). Experimental Stand contains in its structure: a welded basic frame - 1, a drive basis - 2, a bar of supporting frame - 3,

springs - 4, pass drive transfer - 5, a drive reducer - 6, an electric motor - 7, a centrifugal vibrator - 8, a bunker - 9, a set of perforated cylinders - 10, a set of rubber coated rollers - 11, a set of trenches for unloading - 12, an electronic tachometer - 13, a device for repair and maintenance - 14.

In construction of the pre-production model the drive basis - 2 is fixed to the crossbar of the support frame - 1 by means of bar - 3 and springs - 4 under the regulated angle of slope to horizon. The drive basis consists of two parts similar on design and connected by a threaded connection.

There is the drive that consists of the electric motor - 7 and the reducer - 6 at the front. Reducing gear by means of the special pulley and pass *transmission* - 5 transmits torque to the pulleys whose axes are fixed on the conducted platens - 11 of the perforated cylinders - 10. Roller bearings - 11, in turn, are fixed in the front and rear parts of the drive basis - 2.

The torque from the conducted pulleys is transferred to the rubber rollers put on the second end of each axis with the conducted pulley. Through friction transfer rollers are joined with the extreme ring of the separating cylinders and turn them. Each cylinder consists of two extreme rings and the steel cylindrical frame covered with a steel or copper sieve with the corresponding size of closets. The size of closets diminishes with the increase of diameter of cylinder, the sizes of cylinders are such, that they are located one in another. Each cylinder is hung by one extreme ring on two rubber rollers pressed on the bearings, the axes of which are firmly fixed to the front of the basis of the drive.

1 - a welded basic frame; 2 - a drive basis; 3 - a bar of supporting frame; 4 – springs; 5 - pass drive transfer; 6 - a drive reducer; 7 - an electric motor; 8 - a centrifugal vibrator; 9 - a bunker; 10 - a set of perforated cylinders; 11 - a set of rubber coated rollers; 12 - a set of trenches for unloading; 13 – an electronic tachometer; 14 - a device for repair and maintenance.

Fig. 1 - *Experimental Stand*

From above this extreme ring is pressed against the third leading roller, which is fixed in this position.

The back part of the basis of the drive is executed symmetrically to the front part, cylinders are fixed similarly here. The rollers of forward part of the basis which press extreme rings of cylinders and the rollers of back part corresponding to them are connected by means of special platens that pass a torque between rollers. Platens have hairy surface, which is pressed to the sieve surface of each separating cylinder from above. Hopper is fixed to the back part of the base and directs initial mix into the least on diameter

cylinder. Troughs for exit of each fraction are set under each cylinder and form the block of troughs which fastens in the bottom part of base frame.

In order that particles of a product were not under influence of centrifugal force when handling cylinders and the mode "with a collapse" was provided, it is necessary to use admissible turns for each cylinder. Thus, the condition when force of weight equals on size to centrifugal force should be satisfied. In this case the particle of a mixture will not rise higher than the horizontal axis of the drum circle.

According to [1] we can determine the value of speed and angular velocities of the cylinders, depending on their diameters. The data we put in the table 1.

Table 1.

Value of radius, turns and angular speeds of cylinders

r, mm	125	205	285	365
n, rpm	84,855	66,260	56,196	49,657
ω_B, c^{-1}	8,886	6,939	5,885	5,200

Calculated values of n, in practice, are received by varying the diameters of conducted pulleys under pass transmission on each cylindrical sieve.

In construction of the pre-production model change of the angle of inclination to the horizon at the expense of turning of the working body on a bar and hanging by its other end on shorter or longer springs is foreseen.

Vibrations generated by the centrifugal vibrator is angled, the axis of rods is their center, rocking of working body occurs in a vertical plane at a certain angle, as it is shown in Figure 2.

For the experiment we used the smallest

sieve cylinder with a diameter of 250 mm. Fixation of the data about value of an angle of ascent was carried out with different amounts of loading the drum at the uninterrupted separation mode of 50 kg of grains of green peas. Thanks to the rounded shape chosen product is ideally suited for the imitation of coarse friable food mass. The volume of loading of the drum was provided by continuous supply of the product. Fixing of the values was performed using the special scale put on glass (Figure 3), which is attached to the hopper so that the range of the base sieve cylinder coincided with the scale.

Fig. 2 - The scheme of reception of fluctuations

Scale photographing took place at the time of stabilized influence of fluctuations on the angle of elevation of segment of the product so that the picture displayed the end point of a segment of the product.

Photos in electronic form were placed on the pages of the file of software package AutoCAD. The size of the photo was edited so that the circular scale on photo was precisely imposed on the same drawn scale, that was executed in 1:1 scale. The line tangent to surface of grains of segment which formed a chord of a

segment of the product was drawn on the scale. An angle between the vertical radius of the cylinder and a perpendicular to the chord - is the angle.

The frequency of the engine speed vibrator was replaced with a rheostat and measured by a tachometer. The amplitude and the frequency were defined by change of weight and frequency of the engine rotation. The frequency of turns of the vibrator engine was changing by means of rheostat and measured by tachometre.

Fig. 3 - The scale, which determines the angle of the segment of the product

Table 2.

The value of elevation angle of the material β in a rotating sieve cylinder depending on the frequency ν and the amplitude of oscillations at 1/3 filling of the drum with the product

Value of the oscillation frequency ν , Hz	Value of the oscillation amplitude A, m								
	0,0005	0,001	0,002	0,003	0,004	0,005	0,006	0,008	
20	5,0	4,8	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,8	5,0	5,2	
21	4,6	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,2	4,4	4,6	4,8	
22	4,1	4,0	3,8	3,7	3,8	4,0	4,1	4,8	
23	4,1	3,6	3,6	3,6	3,6	3,6	4,1	4,8	
24	4,1	4,0	3,8	3,7	3,8	4,0	4,1	4,8	
25	4,6	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,2	4,4	4,6	4,8	
26	5,0	4,8	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,8	5,0	5,2	
27	6,0	5,8	5,6	5,4	5,6	5,8	6,0	6,0	
The value of elevation angle of the material β , degrees									

Table 3.

The value of elevation angle of the material β in a rotating sieve cylinder depending on the frequency ν and the amplitude of oscillations at 1/4 filling of the drum with the product

Value of the oscillation frequency ν , Hz	Value of the oscillation amplitude A, m.								
	0,0005	0,001	0,002	0,003	0,004	0,005	0,006	0,008	
20	15,7	15,3	15,3	15,4	15,6	16,5	18,5	18,9	
21	13,6	12,3	12,3	12,2	13,5	16,6	16,4	18,6	
22	12,4	7,3	6,7	7,2	6,7	7,3	14,6	18,9	
23	12,3	6,1	6,1	6,1	6,1	6,1	12,1	18,6	
24	12,4	7,3	6,6	7,3	6,7	7,45	14,5	18,6	
25	13,4	12,3	12,5	12,4	14,4	15,4	16,4	18,8	
26	15,6	15,5	15,4	15,5	15,7	16,7	18,8	18,5	
27	18,3	18,2	18,9	18,8	18,4	18,8	19,2	18,7	
The value of elevation angle of the material β , degrees.									

Fig. 4 - Experimental dependence of the elevation angle of the material β on the frequency ν and the amplitude A of oscillations at 1/3 filling of the drum with the product.

Fig. 5 - Experimental dependence of the elevation angle of the material β on the frequency ν and the amplitude of the drum oscillation when it is loaded on 1/4

Reducing in loading of the drum leads to increase of the angle and a sharper separation of an optimum zone from other values. The optimal parameters of vibrations for a minimum value

during the separation of pea grains with the different volume of drum loading are included to the table 4.

Table 4.

The optimal parameters of the oscillation for a minimum angle β .

Drum loading	Amplitude, m	Frequency, Hz.	Angle β_{\min} , deg
at 1/3.	0,001 – 0,005	22 – 24	3,6 – 4,1
at 1/4.	0,001 – 0,005	22 – 24	6,1 – 7,3
at 1/5.	0,001 – 0,005	22 – 24	8,2 – 10,5

An increase in the projection of an effective sieve surface on a horizontal plane in percentage have been defined with the graphic

method in the software package. The results are presented in table 5.

Table 5.

Increasing of the area of effective sieve surface depending on the volume of the drum loading when it rotates with the use of vibration

Volume of the drum loading	1/3	1/4	1/5
The angle β_{\max} , deg. without vibration	15,363	23,827	29,463
The angle β , deg. at vibration	3,6	6,1	8,2
Percent of increase in the efficiency of sieve surface	3,6	8,6	14

It is necessary to note that with reduction of volume of the drum loading the effective area of a cylindrical sieve increases.

Conclusions: The increase of the area effective cylindrical sieve surfaces due to vibration is confirmed and studied. Dependence of change of the value of area of effective cylindrical sieve surfaces on the elevation angle of the material is established at different volumes of loading of the rotating drum.

Prospects of the further studies in the given direction.

In a prospect it is necessary to define speed of moving of friable material along the axis of the sloping revolved cylinder at influence of vertical vibrations and to get equalization for determination of the productivity of oscillation cylindrical sieve classifier.

In the long term it is necessary to define speed of moving of a loose material along an axis of the inclined rotating cylinder at influence of vertical fluctuations and to receive the equation for definition of productivity of a vibrating cylindrical sieve classifier.

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MODERN EQUIPMENT USED FOR THE CONDITIONING OF MEDICINAL AND AROMATIC PLANTS BY WASHING

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Abstract: Natural conditions in Romania are favorable for obtaining adequate quantities of plant material, from the wild flora and also from the introduction of scarce species. The quality of medicinal and aromatic plants is influenced by the active ingredients content, the method and optimal timing for the harvest, and also by the processing technology (conditioning, storage and industrial processing). Conditioning, carried out immediately or during the harvest in order to remove impurities and foreign bodies from the product, is done with different types of equipment, based on the processor requirements.

Keywords: conditioning, impurities, medicinal and aromatic plants, washing.

1. Introduction

- *The role and importance of medicinal plants*

In terms of medicinal plants, Romania's resources are very diverse. From the existing data, over 3,600 species of superior plants exist, of which only 10 ... 12 % are used in scientific and traditional Romanian medicine.

Medicinal and aromatic plants are obtained by gathering different species and varieties of nutritional value and/or with pharmaco-dynamic properties from the spontaneous flora, and by the cultivation of traditional and others adapted from the spontaneous flora.

Although plants have been valued for their medicinal and aromatic qualities for centuries, synthetic products of the modern era have exceeded their importance for a while. Despite this fact, a return to the natural products is noticed, medicinal plants constituting a healthy therapeutic remedy, in contrast to drugs obtained synthetically.

- *Types of medicinal and aromatic plants grown in Romania*

Until 1990, the area cultivated with medicinal and aromatic plants in Romania was 65,000 ha, but later on, when significant areas of farmland were returned, the cultivated area and export of these products has known a significant decrease. The evolution of areas cultivated with medicinal and aromatic plants in Romania is shown in Figure 1 [3].

Some of the medicinal plants grown intensively in Romania are: coriander, poppy, caraway, and fennel. Other medicinal plants are cultivated on small surfaces, such as calendula, basil, thyme,

wormwood, alecost, Echinacea, Herb Robert, mint, lavender, sage etc. Besides these medicinal plants there are species of the wild flora that were introduced or are being introduced in the culture (angelica, valerian, yarrow, wood avens, cumin, Lady's Mantle etc.) [2].

Fig. 1. The evolution of the surface cultivated with medicinal and aromatic plants in Romania [thousand ha.]

Medicinal and aromatic plant species that are grown with very good results constitute an important source of raw materials for the extraction of active ingredients and essential oils, of a particular value for the drugs and pharmaceutical industry, for the cosmetics industry (perfumes, creams, detergents) and for the food industry (flavors, dyes, spices).

2. Materials and method

Medicinal plants are represented by annual, biennial and perennial species, whose products – vegetable raw materials (Figure 2) – represented by: flowers (flores), leaves (folium), herb or the

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whole aerial part of the plant (herba), fruit (fructus), seed (semen), roots (radix), rhizomes (rhizoma), tubers (tuber), bulb (bulbus), bark (cortex) and buds (gemmae) find different uses.

Fig. 2. Vegetable raw materials of medicinal plants

The quality of medicinal and aromatic plants is influenced by the content of active ingredients, the method and optimal time of harvest, as well as by the processing technology (conditioning, storage and industrial processing). Pedoclimatic factors have a considerable influence on the formation and accumulation of active principles and the growth and development of medicinal and aromatic plants.

• *Sources of contamination of the medicinal plants:*

1. Plants with similar characteristics as the medicinal and aromatic plants, harvested from the wild flora. This source of contamination can lead to the compromise of the product and is generally caused by failing to respect the technical planning which establishes and identifies the species to be harvested;

2. Impurities or foreign bodies that may originate from the same species, represented either by parts of plants, other than those required or by desired parts, but of inadequate quality;

3. Anorganic substances (dust, sand, soil) resulting from the harvest, transport and storage of the medicinal and aromatic plants;

4. Heavy metals (Pb, Cd, As etc.), which may contaminate the plant product;

5. Microorganisms that can grow if certain conditions of temperature and relative humidity are not met in the storage areas.

• *The operation of conditioning by washing and the modern equipment used*

After harvesting, the different parts of medicinal plants are directed on a particular flow, according to the purpose of use, namely retail market for immediate consumption and distribution to the processor. Each of the destinations of use requires a certain way of preparation, either brief or more complex, known as *conditioning*. Conditioning operations depend on the species, its destination, the degree of technical equipment and they vary in number, manner and duration of execution.

Conditioning, carried out immediately after harvest consists in the removal of impurities and foreign bodies from the product's mass. The equipments used for conditioning the various plant organs of herbs are diverse and manufactured by different manufacturers. A special type of conditioning is needed by the underground parts of the medicinal plants (roots, runners, bulbs, tubers etc.), which undergo a sequence of operations carried out in a well established order. The washing is preceded by the peeling and longitudinal or transversal segmenting operations, depending on the species and the equipment used. Over time, washing equipments that operate on different constructive principles were developed all over the world, some of them being listed below.

Heuling Maschinenbau GmbH from Germany produces the equipment shown in Figure 3, used to wash underground parts of medicinal plants (roots, bulbs, tubers).

Fig. 3. Heuling Vegetable Washer [1]

Heuling Vegetable Washer washes root vegetables without intervention and effort. The washing cycle is intensive, yet gentle. In the washer, the contents are sprinkled with fresh water while being tumbled gently during the wash cycle lasting from 3 to 5 minutes (depending on the type of soil to remove). The waste drains straight away from below the machine. The elongated perforations in the washing drum have been stamped from the inside out.

This process strengthens the washing drum and leaves a smooth inner surface that protects the vegetables or fruits from damage. The contents are discharged whilst the drum turns by rotating the retaining panel on the discharge side. The batch is funneled out of the washing drum into a waiting crate or onto a conveyor for sorting [2].

Technical specifications of this equipment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Available models for Heuling Vegetable Washer

Specifications	Type 815	Type 1400
Drum length/ Drum diameter	815 mm/ 850 mm	1400 mm/ 850 mm
Batch weight	circa 150 kg	circa 250 kg
Drive Standard	Geared - motor 380 V	Geared – motor 380 V
Drum speed	9/ 18 rpm	9/ 18 rpm
Overall length	1520 mm	2105 mm
Width/ Height	1000/ 1930	1000/ 1930
Loading height/ Discharge height	1500/ 650	1500/ 650
Number of water jets	4	7
Water pressure	4...8 bar	4...8 bar

Another equipment used for cleaning different parts of medicinal plants (leaves, rhizomes, tubers etc.) is produced by Machinefabriek Eillert BV in Netherlands and is presented in Figure 4.

GWB washing mashine is suitable for both heavy kinds of vegetables as well as for both fragile varieties.

Fig. 4. *GWB Washing Mashine* [4]

Because of the continuous washing process the washing machines can easily be integrated into production lines. The transport speed of the product (length of stay in the washer) can be adjusted. The machines are available in single or multi-stage washers and can be supplied in various lengths, widths and versions (for different capacities). So there is a choice between a belt outfeed, type **GWB**, or vibration sieve, type **GWT**. At the outfeed vibration sieve the

vibration motors are built sideways and therefore fall outside the product flow [5].

Because of the open, hygienic construction (e.g. removable stainless steel end covers of the nozzle pipes) the machine is easy to clean.

Another manufacturer of equipment used in the food industry for washing plant products is **DP Food Technology** in Italy. This company produces the **Ortoget 6500** equipment, which is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Ortoget 6500 Washing Machine [6]

This linear machine is constructed entirely in stainless steel inox, in accordance with EC regulations. It consists of a belt that conveys the crop into the chest which is then immersed into a tub where, in the central section, it is subjected to a shaking action (adjustable).

The chest remains partially immersed up to its adjustable waterline. It is sprayed from above by a series of jets, also adjustable, connected to a high capacity pump with adjustable pressure, which directs the jets through both the shower heads and the power jets. The pump is fitted with

an internal extractor with a metallic mesh filter and by-pass shutters for the direct connection to the water supply.

KRONEN GmbH from Germany is one of the leading suppliers for the food industry which develops and produces single and special machines as well as complete processing lines for cutting, washing, drying, peeling and packing of food. Technical specifications of the GEWA3800V ECO Washing Machine are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 6. GEWA3800V ECO Washing Machine [5]

Table 2

Technical specifications of the GEWA3800V ECO Washing Machine

Length/ Width/ Height	3830 mm/ 1280 mm/ 1540 mm
Infeed/ Feeding Height	1073 mm
Discharge/ Outfeed height	820 mm
Total Power	5.6 kW
Voltage	3~400 V N/PE
Frequency	50 Hz
Total Water Volume	745 l
Weight	560 kg

GEWA3800V ECO Washing Machines (figure 6) offer perfect solutions for a various scope of application. Products as for example vegetables, lettuce, herbs and fruits are

circulating through the entire water volume of the washing tank and can be effectively and carefully washed thanks to the rotary helical washing system. This feature has decisive advantages:

- The compact models with a small footprint allow a reduction of water consumption;
- Movement and distribution separate the product perfectly which allows better water contact during the washing. This leads to a gentle and effective cleaning process;
- The helical water flow system takes most products quickly and gently under water. It is not necessary to use mechanical devices to allow product immersion.

Heavy dirt particles (like small stones) and sand are removed from the product flow and settled separately in the sand trap, at the bottom of the wash tank. Thus the sand particles cannot return to the product flow.

Another equipment produced by KRONEN GmbH is GEWA5000V ECO Washing Machine, shown in Figure 6.

GEWA 5000V ECO Washing Machine (figure 7) with vibration outfeed (product outfeed over vibration screen) is efficient for lettuces, vegetables, herbs and fruit. The benefits of the vibration outfeed are:

- The vibration outfeed is optimally suited for vegetables, salads, fruits, herbs and many more;
- Eccentric motors produce vibrations, which are transmitted into a linear movement of the long lasting stainless steel outfeed screen;
- Depending on product, if the vibrating plate perforation has adequate hole sizes, vibration discharge can be used to product pre classification. This way, smaller particles that can fall through the holes are separated, allowing a better end product quality.

Technical specifications of the GEWA5000V ECO Washing Machine are presented in Table 3.

Fig. 7. GEWA5000V ECO Washing Machine [5]

Table 3

Technical specifications of the GEWA5000V ECO Washing Machine

Length/ Width/ Height	5145 mm/ 1590 mm/ 1600 mm
Infeed/ Feeding Height	1073 mm
Discharge/ Outfeed Height	825 mm
Total Power	10.7 kW
Voltage	3~400 V N/PE
Frequency	50 Hz
Total Water Volume	1400 l

All water used here will directly be guided to the main GEWA waterflow. This way, the used water in the GEWA tank will be continuously replaced by fresh water. Excess water will overflow at a specific area at the pump tank.

3. Conclusions

- Medicinal and aromatic plant species that are grown with very good results constitute an important source of raw materials for the

pharmaceutical, cosmetics and perfume industries, food industry, both in Romania and abroad.

- Under the current conditions, when it is necessary to ensure food safety for the consumer, conditioning and appropriate processing of medicinal and aromatic plants, conducted according to quality standards can meet this requirement.
- Providing the most modern equipments for conditioning and further processing of medicinal

and aromatic plants, as well as raising the level of training and specialization of staff will contribute to obtaining competitive products on foreign markets.

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MODERN EQUIPMENT USED FOR CONDITIONING BERRIES

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Abstract: Conditioning, carried out immediately after, or during the harvest consists of removing impurities and foreign matters from the product. Impurities may be organic (from the same species) or inorganic (sand, dust, soil). In order to comply with quality standards imposed by law, different constructive types of separation equipment have been developed. From fan to laser sorting by color, technologies and conditioning equipment experienced a dynamic growth during the last years.

Keywords: bilberries, conditioning, equipment.

1. Introduction

• The role and importance of bilberries

The bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus L.*) is one of the most powerful of all foods, and this member of the blueberry family has shown great promise at treating and preventing a number of serious medical conditions.

The bilberry bush grows wild throughout the forests and meadows of many parts of Europe and western Asia, and also in the Rocky mountain regions of North America. The bilberry is closely related to the blueberry, cranberry and the huckleberry, and it shares the health benefits of those related fruits [1].

Bilberries are darker in color, and usually appear near black with a slight shade of purple. Their blue-black pigment is the result of anthocyanosides, a type of flavonoid responsible for stabilizing collagen structure [3].

Bilberries, or wild blueberries, have been shown to have the highest Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity rating of more than 20 fresh fruits and berries.

The antioxidant properties of bilberries were shown to be even stronger than those of cranberries, raspberries, strawberries, plums, or cultivated blueberries (figure 1).

One of the most important benefits of bilberry consumption is the ability to enhance the vision. The bilberry plant is also thought to play a role in keeping blood vessels healthy. The compounds contained in the bilberry, notably the anthocyanosides, have been shown to help fortify blood vessel walls, thereby aiding circulation and increasing blood flow.

In addition to these important benefits, bilberry is quite an effective treatment for sore throats and also was often used as a treatment for diarrhea. In addition, however, the leaves of the bilberry bush are thought to have their own unique healing properties [2].

Bilberries obtained from the spontaneous flora contain a number of components of particular interest in the food and drug industry, because of their active principles content. Whether manually or mechanically harvested, a number of organic impurities (leaves, twigs etc.) remain in the fruit and they have to be removed.

In order to meet the quality standards required by legislation, processors use different constructive types of separation equipment to remove the impurities remaining after the harvesting operation.

Conditioning, carried out immediately after, or during the harvest consists in removing the impurities and foreign matters from the product. Impurities may originate from the same species and are either different plant parts, other than those required, or the desired parts, but of poor quality. In turn, foreign matters are divided into: organic (represented by fragments from other

Fig. 1. Cellular antioxidant activity [2]

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species – for example weeds or weed seeds) and inorganic (dust, soil, pebbles etc.).

Depending on the technical equipment available, conditioning can be performed manually or mechanically.

• **Equipment used for conditioning bilberries**

Lakewood Process Machinery (LPM) manufacturer is a global leader in processing equipment for all types of fruit and vegetables. Lakewood Process Machinery provides standard equipment for harvesting, processing, sizing, sorting, weighing, washing, packaging etc., often providing innovative solutions to the challenges

faced by crop producers and processors. For the past three decades Lakewood Process Machinery has been a leader within the small fruit industry, offering a full line of packing and processing equipment to the berry industry. Some types of conditioning equipment produced by this company are listed below [5].

✚ **Stick Eliminator** (figure 2) separates and removes sticks and large debris from product flow. The product is conveyed through custom-turned aluminum scalping rollers. It falls through the roller bed, while sticks and debris are carried over the rollers to a partitioned trash conveyor.

Fig. 2. *Stick Eliminator* [5]

✚ **Air cleaner Model 14130** (figure 3) is ideal for separating small berries, leaves, loose stems and unwanted debris from the main product flow in a grading line. Berries are fed onto the inclined conveyor either directly or into an optional metering hopper. They are conveyed up and discharge off the upper end, falling through the air stream onto the secondary lower take-a-way conveyor that exits to the right. Lighter berries, leaves, and debris follow the air stream into the overhead cage where it is conveyed out to one side via two conveyors. The first conveyor carries out the berries while the second conveyor carries out lighter sticks or leaves.

✚ **Fresh Berry Destemmer Model 12300** (figure 4). Berries are fed into the conveyor. As blueberries move along the bed, the destemming rods grab hold of the stem and gently tugs it out leaving the berry unharmed.

Fig. 3. *Air cleaner Model 14130* [5]

Fig. 4. *Fresh Berry Destemmer Model 12300* [5]

The stems fall beneath the bed while the destemmed berries move along to the next step in the process line. As they land on the stainless open mesh conveyor belt a percentage of stems will protrude through the mesh. The stems that extend below the bottom of the mesh will be

pulled off the berries as the conveyor travels forward across the shear bars mounted under the bed. The overhead rubber fingers will re-orient the berries, thus exposing more stems to the shear points as they travel forward on the conveyor.

✚Laser sorting by color is also a separation method used to remove organic impurities remaining after harvest and also for separating and removing harvested fruits that do not comply in terms of harvest maturity. Manufacturers such as Buhlergroup have developed several variants of such equipment, an example being the SORTEX EIC (figure 5).

With cultivated varieties, most extraneous vegetable matter (EVM) is extracted by mechanical pre-cleaning equipment prior to sorting. As a result the sorting process is primarily concerned with identifying discoloured berries and, of course, eliminating any residual EVM. Wild berries undergo a similar process but extraneous vegetable matter contamination is at a higher level than with cultivated varieties. The challenge at the sorting stage therefore is to extract a higher level of EVM such as pine needles, stems, leaves and stick fragments. So the sorting process focuses on both color and shape.

Fig. 5. SORTEX EIC [4]

The SORTEX E optical sorting machine sorts extraneous vegetable matter primarily by shape but is also successful in identifying color defects. Blueberries, whether discolored or unripened, can show green or yellow and raspberries, similarly, can be white, pink or brown. InGaAs technology performs a vital function in identifying plastic or wood fragments, cardboard and both light and dark coloured stones. By combining enhanced InGaAs technology, bichromatic cameras and shape recognition it is uniquely capable of ensuring the safety of the product [4].

Benefits of using this equipment are: hygienic operation and easy cleaning; detecting and removing small and subtle color defects and most foreign material; detecting and removal of problematic foreign material; a very stable solution giving flexibility in defect detection.

✚Binder is another equipment manufacturer offering constructive solutions to the most

diverse applications. Binder provides sieving and separating systems for freshly picked and cut leafy vegetables over dried herbs through to dried fruits and tuber vegetables.

Binder has developed a special rotating drum-type sieve (figure 6) to separate fine dust and sand from various products.

Fig. 6. Rotating drum-type sieve [6]

Equipped with a spraying bar on the inside of the drum, this machine is also used in the food industry for the treatment of raw materials.

The rotational speed and inclination, and therefore also the throughput capacity during operation are infinitely adjustable. For the food industry, the plant is made entirely of stainless steel. Depending on the material to be sieved, various sieve attachments such as e.g. wire mesh or perforated plates are used. Automatic cleaning of the sieving area using a rotating brush is available as an accessory. The sieved off fine fraction is collected in a large collecting basin.

3. Conclusions

- Modern agricultural processing equipments for fruit and horticulture products are developed under higher standard for quality and help the bilberry growers to improve their harvest productivity.
- The latest technology by optical sorting used to remove organic impurities increases productivity, improves quality and reduces labour costs. By

combining enhanced InGaAs technology, bichromatic cameras and shape recognition the quality of the product is ensured.

- All the equipments developed by different manufacturers are intending to ensure the highest product quality, providing sieving and separating systems for freshly picked to frozen fruits.

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PRELIMINARY RESEARCH REGARDING THE IMPACT OF MUSTARD FLOUR ADDITION IN BREAD

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Abstract: *The paper presents a preliminary study of mustard flour incorporation in bread regarding the organoleptic characteristics. Mustard flour at level of 10% was used in whole wheat flour for bread production to improve the quantity and the quality of protein. The breads were subjected to sensorial evaluation. The sensory evaluation by using single-phase process it showed a decrease in textural characteristics compared with the control sample.*

Keywords: *mustard flour, bread.*

1. Introduction

Wheat bread is one of the most commonly consumed food products in the world. Fresh bread usually presents an appealing brownish, crispy and crunchy crust besides pleasant aroma. [2]

Bread is a staple food that reaches the mass consumer of everyone. The average bread consumption per person in Romania is of about 330 grams every day, or 120 Kg per year. The consumption of white bread is still the preference in Romanian families, making up 70% of all bread consumed. [6]

White bread contains 2.6 percent sugar, 46.7 percent starch, 1.9 percent total fat, 8.4 percent total protein, 1.7 mg per 100 mg vitamin and 5 percent glutenin. [13]

Bread as a functional food is such a way to give consumers informed or not the benefits of nutrients such as natural proteins from spices.

Nowadays spices are extensively studied in order to explore their therapeutic, nutritional and technological potential and to clarify the controversy in accepting many "traditional" as scientific truth. Spices enhance the taste or appearance of bread so the direct contribution of flavor but also by their antimicrobial effect. In addition contain various health beneficial ingredients such as antioxidants.

Mustard seeds are composed of protein (23-30%), fixed oil (29-36%), carbohydrate (12-18%) together with minor constituents including minerals (4%), essential oil (glucosinolates, 0.8-2.3%), phytin (2-3%) as well as phenolic compounds and dithiolthiones [4]. The large amount of protein of around 30% for whole

mustard seeds and flours appears satisfactory, for growth and development.

In study wheat flour was replaced with defatted mustard flour at 5, 10, 15 and 20% incorporation levels in biscuits preparation. For sensorial evaluation it was found that the sample containing 15% defatted mustard flour scored highest in most of the attributes including overall acceptability. In the same study, the nutritional analysis showed a considerable improvement in protein, ash, crude fiber and carbohydrate content. [12]

Processes for the preparation of protein isolate from mustard by different treatments to reduce anti-nutritional constituents have been developed and patented. [1, 3, 5, 8, 10]

The goal of our research was to examine the possibilities of improving the quality of wheat flour based bread by supplementing the basic recipe with defatted mustard flour. Mustard flour was used for bread fortification due to its high protein content and quality and considerable proportion of other biologically active compounds (mainly isomers of sinapic acid which are the predominant antioxidant, soluble dietary fiber [4]) exerting numerous health beneficial effects.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Wheat flour 650 type, compressed baker's yeast (Pakmaya), salt and sugar was purchased from the local market. Mustard flour was purchased from the shop with natural products.

According to information provided by manufacturer to get this flour was required prior

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conditioning of mustard seeds and their subsequent degreasing by cold pressing and finally grinding broken.

2.2 Equipment

Were used the equipment of bakery products laboratory (Food and Tourism Faculty from Braşov): fixed bowl spiral mixer model 50 Silver, SQ 10 divider, round molding machine with tapered bearing surface, long shaped machine model RO-CR-600, fermentation cabinet Telbo and electric oven.

2.3 Bread making procedure

A single-phase process was used for bread preparation. In first experiment all ingredients, inclusively mustard flour, were mixed and kneaded. In the second experiment, classic dough was re-kneaded after fermentation time with 10% mustard flour.

For both experiments was prepared a blank sample.

For first experiment, dough was prepared on a flour weight basis, for 3000 g flour, 1650 ml water (55%), 90 g compressed baker's yeast (3%), 45 g table salt (1,5%) and 300 g defatted mustard flour (2E-PROD, Romania).

The compressed baker's yeast has been dissolved so distribution of yeast cells in dough mass is uniformly to ensure a homogeneous fermentation. To reactivation of compressed baker's yeast is mixed with sugar (1/5) and water and rested for 10 min. Salt has been used as a solution of 20% concentration.

Ingredients were mixed and kneaded in a 50 Silver spiral mixer for 3 min at slow speed and 5 min at fast speed and rested for 35 min at 32 °C while covered with a textile material to avoid drying and to achieve the fermentation. After the dough has fermented it is loaded into a divider that cut the dough into pre-determined weights and then pre-molded in a round molding machine where the dough piece take spherical shape and the moisture from surface from dough piece are removed. Then dough pieces were rolled mechanically in RO-CR-600 molder where dough piece are turned and fed into pressure board where it takes cylindrical shape; air is passed through the board. Four dough pieces were placed on oven trays and proofed at 32° C in a fermentation cabinet aiming to increase the dough volume (versus the initial volume of the dough). Next, dough pieces were intended with knife sharp slightly moistened in water by a

quick move to avoid cracks in the surface crust during baking and then baked in an electrical oven. Baking process was performed at fixed oven temperature of 220° C for 35 min. After baking, breads were allowed to cool down for 45 min at room temperature.

In the second experiment, dough was prepared with the same ingredients except mustard flour which was added after 35 min of fermentation. Fermented dough was re-mixed with mustard flour for 5 min at fast speed and re-fermented for 15 min at 32°C. After that the dough was divided and pre-molded, four dough pieces were rolled and placed on oven tray. The oven tray was placed in fermentation cabinet for 20 min and baked for 30 min at 220°C. Control samples were prepared without the addition of mustard flour.

Fresh breads were tested for color, smell, crumb appearance, taste and flavor.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Influence of mustard flour addition in dough

Usually, the kneading of the dough helps to produce bubbles of equal size evenly distributed throughout the dough.

For first experiment the mustard flour addition did not adversely influenced the mixing parameters by comparison with control sample. Dough present uniform black particles, a good consistency and the smell were pleasant.

Fig.1. Dough during mixing (first experiment)

For the second experiment the fermented dough was mixed at fast speed with mustard flour because at slow speed dough does not lead. Mustard flour embedding in dough mass has made more difficult by comparison with first experiment. Even so, the dough structure after mixing was satisfying.

Fig.2. *Dough during re-kneading with mustard flour (second experiment)*

To make comparison a control sample was made. Fig.3 present a picture with control sample (second experiment) during re-fermentation time and as can be seen textural descriptors are optimize and characteristics and features for this product.

Fig.4. *Control sample during re-fermentation (second experiment)*

Baked control sample presented a high quality standard of appearance, texture, and flavor as can be seen in Fig.5.

Fig.5. *Control sample after baking process (second experiment)*

Fig.6a. *Dough proofing in first experiment*

Fig.6b. *Dough fermentation in second experiment*

In first experiment, during the fermentation time the increase of dough volume was insignificant. A possible cause for this disadvantage was probably the inhibition of compressed baker's yeast by isothiocyanates which is formed by the action of myrosinase enzyme on glucosinolates.

In second experiment even if the volume of the dough during fermentation increase to three times, after re-mixing with mustard flour and re-fermentation the dough volume decreases. The addition of mustard flour after fermentation aimed to allow the yeast to ferment sugars so mustard flour does not to inhibit yeast activity. For both experiment, during proofing time, dough volume has remained constant.

Fig.7. *Baked bread in second experiment*

3.2 Organoleptic characteristic of bread with mustard flour

The most important flavor compounds are formed during baking, when heat reaction, such

as the Maillard reaction and caramelisation, take place.

Table 1. *Organoleptic properties of samples from experiments*

<i>Recipe</i>	<i>Sensorial attributes</i>	<i>Samples</i>		
		<i>Control sample (direct method)</i>	<i>First experiment (direct method)</i>	<i>Second experiment (direct method with re-kneading)</i>
- 3000g flour; -1650 ml water (55%); - 90 g compressed baker's yeast (3%); - 45 g table salt (1,5%); - 300 g defatted mustard flour (10%).	Crust appearance	-without wrinkle and crack -shiny, thin, crispy; - yellowish brown color ;	- with wrinkle and crack; - uniform but mat color with black points; - crispy; - color intensity was reduced;	
	Crumb appearance	-fine and uniform pores; - elastic; - soft texture; - airy;	- no porosity; - without volume increasing; - chewy texture; - unbaked; - dense, crumb moistness; - black particles from mustard flour;	- small and uneven pores; - elasticity significantly reduced comparatively with control samples but more evident related to first experiment; - partial baked;
	Taste	-pleasant, and characteristic; - without foreign odor;	- easy and pleasant taste of mustard; - sharp odor;	
	Flavor	-characteristic and pleasant;	- pleasant with mustard flavor;	

As shown in Fig.7. bread crust obtained in second experiment was cracked and in section does not present porosity. Crumb bread was sticky and non-aerated. All variants of bread supplemented with mustard flour have a small volume. The porosity aspect is significantly affected by mustard flour addition.

As can be seen mustard flour incorporation in bread using direct method influence negatively the volume, elasticity and porosity.

4. Conclusions

To 10% supplement of mustard flour in bread sensory attributes related to odor are not reduced compared with control sample. It can be feel a pleasant mustard aroma. As well, at this percentage the mustard flour has an important contribution to nutritional value of bread, especially on protein content. Using the direct

method, bread quality decreases therefore research should be continued to optimize a manufacturing process of bread with mustard flour added.

Due to the important properties of isothiocyanate in mustard flour (antimicrobial effect studied by several researchers [7, 9, 11]) adding this flour in dough by direct method has disadvantages concerning bread quality. For these reasons, future goals are:

- (a) bread production by biphasic method;
- (b) bread production by three-phasic method;
- (c) use of modern methods by adding cultures of microorganisms;
- (d) replace compressed baker's yeast with baking powder;
- (e) use of an inexpensive method for myrosinase enzyme inactivation from mustard flour.

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THERMAL ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN THE BREWERY

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Abstract: *The heat energy requirement for brewing forms a substantial part of production costs. It is the job of the brewer to use energy as efficiently as possible to keep these costs as low as possible. One must therefore expect a total energy usage for beer production of 170-230 MJ thermal energy/hl. The greatest user of heat energy in the brewery are the brewhouse department. In this department, the most important plant is boiler plants.*

Keywords: *thermal energy, steam, evaporation, heat price.*

1. General Considerations

In the boiler water is converted to steam which can be used to perform work. Steam has a considerably higher heat content than the water and can be easily transported. To produce steam a fuel is required. Nowadays the fuel most commonly used are petroleum oil and natural gas, but other fuels are also economically advantageous for various reasons.

The thermal value of a fuel is amount of heat which is released on burning a defined amount. The upper thermal value (combustion heat) is the theoretical greatest possible value. The steam is produced in every combustion process and it condenses on cooling. The condensation heat produced is difference in energy between the upper and lower thermal values. Payments are always based on the upper thermal value. The lower thermal value is the amount of heat which is released when the steam produced during burning is cooled to 20° C but is still present as water vapour.

However, the upper thermal value is used for calculating the amount of fuel required.

From the economics point of view a very important figure is the heat price. This shows how much kWh or MJ costs in the end. It is determined from the following formula.

$$\text{Heat price} = \frac{\text{Price of the fuel per t or m}^3}{\text{Heat value of the fuel}}$$

The result is expressed in price/MJ or/kWh. However this result does not give any information about the extent to which the boiler can actually convert the energy in the fuel to heat energy-and this is also very important with regard to the cost. The ratio of these two numbers is called the boiler efficiency.

The important available heat price (or net heat price) is obtained as follows:

$$\text{Available heat price} = \frac{\text{Heat price}}{\text{Boiler efficiency}}$$

Thus the available heat price shows exactly how much money one MJ or kWh finally costs for production purposes. Naturally, the available heat price is always greater than the heat price because the boiler efficiency is less than 100%. Modern brewery boilers partially condense the exhaust gas and therefore achieve-related to the lower heat value- efficiencies above 100%.

If one intends to evaporate water in the boiler, one should know more about the properties of steam.

2. Steam and boilers

When water is heated to boiling point and additional heat is then supplied, steam is produced. The temperature at which water boils is called the boiling point. The boiling point depends on the pressure and increases with increasing pressure.

a) Heat of evaporation

To convert water into steam, heat is required to evaporate it. The heat of evaporation is the amount of heat necessary to convert 1 kg of water to steam at the same temperature. For example, to convert 1 kg water at 100°C and at the normal pressure oh 1 bar to steam at 100°C, 2257,9 kJ = 2257,9 Ws = 0,6272kWh = 539 kcal is needed.

The heat of evaporation depend on the evaporation temperature and the pressure. With increasing temperature and increasing pressure it becomes increasingly smaller. At the "critical steam pressure" of 221,2 bar = 374,15 °C no further heat of evaporation is needed. The boiling water is converted directly to steam.

b) Wet steam

The steam produced during boiling is called wet steam. It has the same temperature as the boiling liquid and still contains about 20% water. As soon as the heat of evaporation has been supplied completely one speaks of dry saturated steam which can be led off. However, as soon as the temperature drops it condenses again and loses a considerable amount of its heat content. During condensation the heat for evaporation is set free again.

c) Superheated steam

In order to be able to move the steam without loss, the saturated steam is heated further to

300°C by supplying additional heat (Fig.1). Such steam is called superheated steam. Its large heat content makes it possible to convey it over long distances without much loss of energy. Heat transfer, despite the high temperature, is relatively poor.

One therefore tries to keep the heating surfaces as small as possible and to introduce the steam into the heat exchanger as saturated steam. For this reason condensate is often sprayed into the superheated steam shortly before it enters the heat exchanger to remove the superheating.

Fig.1. Heat content of steam

Enthalpie = Enthalpy; Dampfdruck = Steam pressure; Flüssigkeitswärme = heat in liquid; Verdampfungswärme = evaporation heat; Überhitzungswärme = superheating heat; Kritischer Punkt = critical point.

d) Hot water

It is also possible to distribute heat in a different way by heating the water under pressure to 160 to 170 °C without allowing it to boil. This very hot water can then be transported and used for boiling. In this case one speaks of hot water boiling (or hydroboiling). It is advantageous to be able to use the full heating potential for heating. In addition the management of condensate and its control is no longer necessary.

Disadvantageous is the substantially large pipe diameter and the higher pump performance needed to transport liquid water instead of gaseous steam.

Classification of boilers

Boilers, in the sense of the boiler regulations, are closed containers or arrangements of pipes which produce steam at higher than atmospheric pressure for use outside the boiler.

Boilers are classified, according to the operating pressure (high and low pressure boilers), according to the type of fuel (coal, oil, natural gas, electric), according to the type of water circulation (natural and forced), and according to the medium flowing through (fire-tube and water-tube boilers).

The most important operating data of a boiler plant are the capacity in t of steam per hour, the furnace output in MW per hour, the operating overpressure in bar, the steam temperature in the boiler at the superheater outlet, the water temperature at the boiler inlet, the fuel (type and heat value in kJ/kg or m³) and the water capacity.

Types of boiler structure

Basically there are two types of boiler construction:

- fire-tube exhaust gas-tube boilers and
- water-tube boilers.

Fire-tube exhaust gas-tube boilers - in these the combustion occurs in a fire-tube and the exhaust gases pass through exhaust gas tubes.

The fire-tube and the exhaust gas-tubes are both located in the water chamber. Because of their great water content these boilers are also called large water space boilers. In the form of two fire-tube boilers these large water space boilers have been used for many years very successfully for steam production in breweries. Double fire-tube boilers are still built today, with modern designs for outputs of up to 30 t of steam/h.

Nowadays most boilers in breweries are three pass boilers.

This term is used because the flame and exhaust gases pass through these boilers in three flow paths. The heat exchange surfaces available are thereby used optimally. The advantages of the large water space boilers are considerable:

- because of their large water content they are very robust and can compensate for inequalities in rates of use.
- because of their large evaporation surfaces they supply relatively dry steam.

Water-tube boilers

In contrast to fire-tube boilers these have water and steam in the tubes. These tubes form the outside of the furnace chamber. Water-tube boilers are built for medium and high outputs up to more than 30,000 kW and operating pressures of up to 180 bar.

High speed steam producers

High speed steam producers are a special type of water-tube boiler in which water is forced by pumps through heating coils and as a result evaporated in the shortest possible time (2 to 10 min). With water-tube boilers a distinction is made between natural flow and forced circulation boilers.

In natural circulation boilers the less dense steam/water mixture rises upwards whilst the water in the cooler part sinks downwards. This results in a natural circulation in the water

chamber of such a boiler which is operated at a pressure of up to 180 bar.

In forced circulation boilers the water is circulated by a pump. The pump circulates the boiler water from the steam separator through the heated tube system and thereby brings it to the boiling temperature set by the boiler pressure.

Three pass boilers - most breweries have one or more three pass boilers of various sizes which can be switched on according to the energy needed. The boiler consists of a horizontal, well insulated sheet steel cylinder (Fig.2). At one side of the boiler is the fire-tube (2) at the front end of which the burner (3) is installed. By means of this the gas/air or oil/air mixture is burnt in a large flame in the fire-tube. Water flows around the fire-tube and the water level is maintained at a constant level above the fire-tube by high performance water level electrodes. The direction of flow of the exhaust gases produced is reversed in the rear direction changing chamber (4) and it sent to the front of the boiler again through a bundle of exhaust gas tubes (5) forming the second path. In a front direction changing chamber (6) the direction is reversed again and the exhaust gas is now led to the rear of the boiler again – third.

3. Energy recovery

It is advantageous to use the energy released from the fuel as completely as possible within the brewery.

For this purpose:

- the feed water is preheated in an economizer by cooling the exhaust gas,
- the steam is superheated to make it transportable, and
- the waste heat is used to heat up the condensate.

Exhaust gas temperature

A closed condensate return system only operates if the plant is always under pressure. Then the plant must run 365 days a year. The efficiency of the boiler depends on the number of starts, and the operating and use times.

Fig. 2. Three pass boiler
 a- side view, b- top view, c- front view,
 1-boiler wall, 2-fire-tube, 3- burner, 4-rear direction changing chamber, 5- exhaust gas tube bundle (2nd pass), 6- front direction changing chamber, 7-exhaust gas tube bundle (3rd pass), 8-steam valve.

Example 1:

A boiler with a large capacity and a water temperature is switched on on Sunday to steam the air filter for wort aeration. Most of the heat is produced for no useful purpose. The efficiency in this case is almost 0%.

Example 2:

A high speed steam producer with two stages (6 t/h and 12t/h) is operated in a brewhouse in which 50 hl/h is evaporated. In this case it can happen that the boiler is continuously switched on and off, low output, high output, etc.

The result of this is that during ventilation of the flow paths, which is necessary to avoid explosions, the hot combustion gases are removed unused. The efficiency is less than 50%. In most cases the nominal efficiencies are related to optimal operating conditions. Consequently average efficiencies greater than 85 % are rarely obtained.

a) Economizer (Eco)

The combustion gases are still very hot when they leave the boiler. So as not to lose this heat serpentine pipes are installed in the space immediately behind the boiler and the boiler feed water is led through them in a counterflow.

The hot exhaust gas, still at about 260 to 300°C, is thereby cooled to about 180 to 130 °C whilst the boiler feed water is heated to above 100°C (Fig. 3). The boiler efficiency can be increased to above 95 % in this way. Such an exhaust gas water preheater or economizer (Eco for short) is

connected directly to the boiler or fixed by flanges in the exhaust gas pipe.

Fig. 3. Economizer (principle)
 1- exhaust gas inflow; 2- exhaust gas to chimney

b) Superheater

In the superheater the temperature of the steam is raised above the saturation temperature. This increase in temperature has the following advantages:

- the water carried with the steam out of the boiler is vaporized,
- the dry steam can be transported over long distances with little cooling and without condensing.

Superheaters are constructed with one or more stages and consist of smooth pipes bent in a serpentine shape.

The exhaust gas flowing past on the outside supplies additional heat to the steam in the pipes and superheats it to 250 to 300 °C.

c) Return of condensate

The condensate also contains a considerable amount of heat which can be recovered. The condensate, which is under pressure, is still above 100 °C, sometimes considerably above this. By returning the condensate, at 140 to 180°C, to the boiler about 10 to 12 % of this heat energy can be recovered. For this it is necessary to have a closed return system since as soon as the condensate is no longer under pressure it expands to reach 1 bar = 100 °C and evaporates without any useful effect.

4. Steam engines

Earlier it was customary for every brewery to have its own steam engine in which some of the steam was used to produce rotational movement. Using a decorative flywheel an electric generator was driven and this more or less provided all the brewery's own energy requirements. Such steam piston engines can nowadays be admired in brewery museums. Only about 12 to 14 % of the energy contained in the fuel was converted in these machines to mechanical movement energy (mechanical efficiency).

The largest part of the energy in the steam can not be converted to rotational movement and occurs as heat energy (waste steam or hot water). Later, instead of steam piston engines, steam turbines were used in which, by means of a rotor, a continuous rotation was obtained instead of the to and fro movement of the steam engine. Such turbines can still be encountered in a few breweries. To use heat energy as economically as possible, the following types of processes were developed.

Non-condensing operation - in this process the steam expands in the machine until it reaches atmospheric pressure and then escapes unused. Such a process is completely uneconomic and little used nowadays.

Counterpressure operation - the pressure on the steam is reduced only to 2 to 3 bar and it can be used for boiling and heating purposes.

Condensation operation - the steam is condensed. Its volume therefore decreases and as a result a vacuum of 0.1 bar is produced.

This increases the drop in pressure and consequently the mechanical efficiency. Basically it must be said that the use of steam powered equipment to provide an internal supply

of electricity is more rarely found in breweries nowadays. It is more advantageous where low cost fuel is available as an incentive.

Nowadays combined heat and power plants are more commonly used.

5. Combined heat and power plants

Instead of the old steam operated machines, combined heat and power plants (CHP) are increasingly encountered. The name "power station" leads one to suppose something rather greater than it is.

The most important part of a combined heat and power plant is a gas motor which burns the natural gas or crude petroleum oil supplied to it and uses the energy to produce a rotational movement. In principle therefore a motor car engine is also a combined heat and power plant.

An electricity generator is attached to the gas motor and, producing a voltage of 380 V, it runs in parallel to the supply network and provides a substantial part of the internal electricity needs or, if the internal needs are small, it can supply electricity to the public network.

Temporary electricity requirement peaks can thus be covered. However, use of a gas motor simply as an electricity generator can not be justified since the electricity provided is much too expensive.

It only becomes of interest when the heat from the motor can also be fully utilised (heat and power plant).

The basic idea behind the heat and power plant is to employ the kinetic energy obtained from the energy in the natural gas by converting it to electrical energy and to use the heat produced in the form of hot water in the brewery.

It can be expected that of the 100 % amount of energy in the natural gas, about 96 % can be used i.e 33 % by conversion to electricity and 58 % as heat (hot water or steam) together with 5 % from radiation from the motor which can also be used for heating.

In order to be able to use the heat energy released efficiently it is usually recovered in two stages using:

- a high temperature water circuit at about 140°C and,
- a low temperature water circuit at about 65 °C,

and the corresponding storage tanks.

The high temperature water circuit at about 140 °C corresponds to a pressure of 3.5 bar.

This hot water can be used directly for heating (hot water boiling) or the pressure is first reduced, producing steam, which similarly can be used for heating and boiling.

When this steam is used for boiling, it loses its heat content and condenses. To keep it in the form of steam additional energy must be supplied. This can be done by heating, or by increasing the pressure by compressing the condensing steam vapour.

6. Conclusions

Consequently a combined heat and power plant comprises the gas motor with an electricity generator, and low and high temperature water circuits with storage tanks.

Installation of heat and power plants in breweries to cover a substantial part of their own energy requirements is an important step towards reducing energy costs.

The plant is connected parallel to the supply network or in "isolated operation" which can be very advantageous in many countries. In the case of large plants using gas turbines one speaks of "power-heat-coupling".

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THE PROCESS OF MANUFACTURING BROWN MALT BY THERMOPLASTIC EXTRUSION

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Abstract: *The process of drying sprouted barley to manufacture brown malt is a component of the technological flow of beer manufacturing which involves high amounts of thermal energy. Thermoplastic extrusion constitutes a thermo-mechanical operation, consequently, energy is transferred to malt both as heat and as mechanical energy. The mechanical treatment consists in shearing stress, to which stirring, compression and expansion is added. The thermal treatment consists in heating involving bio-chemical transformation, cooling, or both.*

Key words: *malt, drying, thermoplastic extrusion, heating.*

1. Introduction

The operation temperatures with thermoplastic extrusion reach no more 220°C, and the duration of the treatment is of only some tens of seconds, in contrast to the traditional method of drying brown malt, which lasts a long time, thus involving high thermal energy consumption.

The process of drying green malt in beer manufacturing is fairly complex, involving high heat consumption. As a result of the classic drying process, the moisture content decreases from 45% in green malt to 1,5% in brown malt.

The temperature the drying air must reach is of approximately 120 °C, while, to manufacture 1 ton of malt, the heat consumption lies between 5231 and 6696 KJ, for which an amount between 189 and 230 kg of conventional fuel is needed. On the other hand, the drying process lasts approximately 10 hours in the 2-grate dryer.

However, the amount of energy required when using thermoplastic extrusion to manufacture brown malt is lower by 15 to 25 percent.

The process of thermoplastic extrusion includes the following unit operations:

- **Mixing:** where mostly mechanical energy is involved, its use being to obtain a homogenous structure of the material (as a rule made up of several components), so that each component's concentration will be uniformly spread in the mixture.

- **Heating:** where mostly thermal energy is involved, so as to have certain bonds within the molecules of the product modified; in this case, mostly thermal energy is involved, so as to have

certain bonds modified within the molecules of the treated product.

- **Extrusion,** consisting in applying an amount of pressure on the product to have it pass through a die.

As a result of the action of temperature and force applied in the course of treatment, the final product will acquire certain features, particularly in point of texture, taste, colour and other functional characteristics.

The structural modifications of the extruded product will be influenced by the temperature reached and the duration of the process within the extruder, thermoplastic extrusion being also considered a HTMT (High Temperature Medium Time) process, with consequences on the nutritional and sensorial level.

2. Extrusion-General Information

2.1. The Operating Principle of the Extruder

In the food processing industry, the extruder can be considered a complex biochemical reactor, which operates at high temperatures, with low down-time, high operation pressure and inside which high shearing stress is exerted.

In its complete structure, an extrusion equipment is made up of the following components: the mixer, the extruder itself, the body of the helical conveyor or screw and the operating conveyor.

- *The mixer's* function is to make the mixture homogenous before it is put through the stages of extrusion and of preconditioning by steaming it at constant air pressure and temperature.

- *The extruder itself* is made up of the body, the conveyor/screw, the die, the cutting tool and the reduction gear box.

The body of the extruder can be cylindrical or cylindrical-conical, manufactured of parts that can be easily put together, covered by a steam jacket and a water cooling jacket.

On the inside part of the body's walls, longitudinal ribs are milled, so as to increase the

friction coefficient between the material and the containing body and to intensify the process of mixing the processed material, namely, malt.

The operating helical conveyor or conveyors can be of different types and have three areas: the feed area, the melting area and the pumping area, as shown in (Fig 2.1)

Fig. 2.1 The basic diagram of an extrusion equipment.

The feed area's function is to take over and transport the material. This area operates at air pressure and its function is to get the mixture homogenized and the air eliminated from the material.

In this segment of the equipment the heating unit does not operate and the materials do not undergo transformations at the granule or molecule levels.

The melting area, which operates at low and medium pressure, is the area where the temperature rises and the material is plasticized/softened.

In the same section, the most important physical and chemical transformations affecting the raw materials undergoing extrusion take place. These are: gelification of starch, coagulation of proteins and others.

The pumping area is the section where air pressure and temperature are highest, and where the material, which has now turned to smelt, continues to be pushed towards the extrusion head. In this area, the material behaves like a non-Newtonian fluid, being subject to a flowing process similar to the one taking place in a screw pump.

The extrusion head is placed at the far end of the section of maximum pressure and temperature. The holes can be cylindrical, rectangular or ring shaped. After being discharged from the extruder, the material expands, the pressure suddenly dropping, while the last moisture in the material finally

evaporates, which brings about distension of its cylindrical and concentric layers.

The electrically actuated cutting tool cuts the material as required.

Fig. 2.2 The shapes of the extrusion head hol

2.2 Extruders used in beer manufacturing for drying malt.

The double screw extruders have seen a boost of their area of application in the food processing industry, as they allow a closer process control and a higher flexibility. The two screws can rotate in countermove or in parallel move, as can be seen in (Fig. 2.3 a and b).

In addition, depending on the way the oven is fitted in, the screws can be set separately, tangentially or in an interlocked manner.

Fig. 2.3. The direction of the screws' movement in a double screw extruder (adapted after Benbow and Beidgewater, 1993)

Fig. 2.4. Types of contacts between the screws in a double screw extruder .

In (Fig.2.5)the Clextral Extruder BC-45 is shown.

Fig. 2.5. The Clextral double-screw extruder: Overall view

1- frame; 2- die; 3- guide and the guide's actuation system; 4- cooling system; 5- heating system reaching 300°C temperatures in 10 minutes; 6- damper system; 7- reductor; 8- dispenser pump; 9- direct current motor; 10- fan; 11- water injector; 12- solid feed dispenser; 13- second water injector; 14- independent modules; 15- collar plate; 16- granulating cutter.

The equipment is mounted on a frame (1) fitted with a sliding system is (3). A direct current motor (9), cooled by a fan (10), sets the two screws into motion the two grooved screws. Between the motor and the crankshaft, a speed reducer is fitted (7).

A damping system (6) placed before the crankshaft enables it to take over the forces the screws transmit axially, forces produced by the pressure gradients emerging along the crankshaft.

There is also a grease gun to keep the rotating mechanical pieces (reductor, damping system) greased, and a double-screw-volume batcher (12), which feeds the malt to the extruder, while a proportioning pump regulates the humidity content of the

mixture in the extruder by injection (11). Another loading can be made through the feed orifice (13). A granulating cutting tool can be fitted to the die to have the extruded malt scraped out continuously. This extruder is a double-screw equipment, whose screws are interlocked, as can be seen in (Fig. 2.6)

Fig. 2.6. View of the double screws of the Clextral extruder

1- body of the extruder; 2- screws interlocked

3. Factors influencing the extrusion process

3.1 Pressure and temperature

The line plotting temperature in the extruder (Fig.3.1) points to a slow rise of the temperature in the segment next to the feeding area of the extruder and a sharp rise to the highest value before passing into the die. The temperature curve will be influenced by: the constructive features of the extruder; the temperature level in the jacket; the rotational speed of the screws; rate of malt feed; water content in malt.

The malt warm-up inside the extruder is brought about by the dissipation of mechanical energy throughout the viscous flow, dependent on the material's rheological features and the intensity of friction, while additional supply of heat is provided by the jacket heating.

Fig.3.1. The temperature curve for the thermoplastic extrusion AB-preconditioning; SC-extrusion; CD-expansion on leaving the die due to moving from high pressure in the compression area to air pressured- drying by detent after swelling; EF-cooling down to 60°C and lower.

3.2. The advance rate of the material inside the extruder

We consider the exclusively linear flow of non-Newtonian fluid material onto the direction of the screw's windings. Inside the extruder three flow rates occur, which result in the general rate ensuring the material's flow, i.e., the advance rate of malt inside the extruder.

The three flow rates are:

with each other;

- The transport rate, Q_T , which results from the difference of velocity between the rotating screw's surface and the stationary cylinder,
- The pressure rate Q_P , which is opposed to the flow (counter-current) and is caused by the overall pressure in the die,
- The outflow rates also opposed to the flow and caused by the overall pressure in the die.

The Q_T and Q_P rate operate on and along the surface of the flute between the windings, while the Q_S operates on the gap between the screw and the cylinder. The resulting (general) rate will be $Q = Q_T - Q_P - Q_S$.

Taking into consideration that the Q_S is negligible, due to the low nip at the winding's ends and the cylinder, Q will amount to: $Q = Q_T - Q_P$

Fig.3.2. The flow rate curves in spread-out section

The flow rate curves in spread-out section are presented in (Fig.3.2).

The relative velocity V_R between the cylinder and the screw can be decomposed along two directions, thus the transport velocities result, V_T , along the flute of the screw's winding, its sense being opposed to the screw's rotating direction, and velocity V_a , perpendicular to the screw's winding.

Fig.3.2. Relative velocity V_R and the decomposition along two directions, resulting V_T and V_a

The rate will result from the relation:

$$Q = \frac{1}{2} \pi^2 D^2 h \sin \varphi \cos \varphi n - \frac{\pi D \sin^2 \varphi h^3 dp}{12 \mu dt} \quad (1)$$

Taking into consideration that all along the length of the pressure area $d/L = P$ an increase of pressure occurs, from 0 to P (pressure at die entrance), Q will become:

$$Q = \frac{\pi^2 D^2 \sin \varphi \cos \varphi}{2} n - \frac{\pi D \sin^2 \varphi h^3}{12 \mu L} P \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the two components of the rate will be:

$$Q_T = \frac{\pi D^2 h \sin^2 \varphi}{4} n, \quad Q_P = \frac{\pi D h^3 \sin^2 \varphi}{12 \mu L} P \quad (3)$$

Hence, it results that the transport flow Q_T does not depend on the value of the pressure, but it will increase relative to the raising of the number of turns; the pressure flow Q_P is proportional to the pressure produced in the extruder and inversely proportional to the viscosity μ of the mass of material. In addition, the flow Q_P rises proportionally with the third power of the fillet's height. The total rate Q will depend on the screw's dimensions (D, H, L), on the operating regime (n, P) and the viscosity of the mass, μ .

3.3. Pressure and temperature inside the extruder

In the main three areas of the extruder there is: air pressure in the first area; ~80 bar pressure in

the medium pressure area and ~150 bar pressure in the area in the proximity of the expansion head. The temperature inside the extruder is ensured either by heat supply as compressed steam or by electric power (Joule effect or magnetic induction) into the jacket of the screw's body.

3.4. Standing time of the material inside the extruder

This variable is important for reaching the optimum temperature. When the standing time is too short, the transformations of the main components of the mixture (starch, proteins) are not carried through; when the standing time is too long, the fluidity of the mixture diminishes and the extruder clogs up.

The standing time can be regulated by modifying the rotation speed of the screw or by adapting the diameter and, especially, the geometry of the screw's windings.

4. Conclusion

Thermoplastic extrusion has been largely developed lately, turning out to be a promising cost-effective technological development for the food processing sector.

The optimum extrusion parameters are characteristic for each type of mixture. The main parameters which can be monitored are those pertaining to the extrusion process itself (temperature, pressure, hydration) and those linked to the constructive features of the extruder (spiral walk, pitch of the screw, rotation speed, the screw's profile, the screw's diameter).

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CLIMATE CHANGES OF THE EARTH AND SOLUTIONS FOR THE REDUCTION OF THE AGRO-ZOOTECNICAL PRODUCTION , THROUGH THE ”MODULAR AGRICULTURAL” MODEL

A. R. Gruia A.T. Bogdan

Abstract: *The ideas that may offer solutions to the climate changes and/or the „avalanche” of techno-economical and scientific changes are very important in nowadays research. The modular agriculture is a step and a model in this direction. Through an original interpretation and a sum of concepts, the paper underlines the importance of a holist vision for the evolution of complex systems, such as those from agriculture and food. Thus it is identified a direct report between system anthropisation and their modularized structure. At the level of agroecosystems we meet macro-modularization based on the principles of sustainable agriculture, and micro-modularization in case of agriculture in space and controlled environment.*

The paper reveals existent or perspective applications of the agro-zootecnical production based on the principles of modularized technologies. There are described also the evolution directions of modular agriculture in view of counteracting the diminishing of agro-zootecnical productions, under the perspective of the ever more acute lack of fertile agricultural soil. The conclusions of the paper aim at the technological and managerial adaptation in order to obtain agro-food products in specific production modules, complex systems which take into account previewed climate changes and the prognosis of world development on Earth or even in space.

Keywords: *modularization, agro-modules, desertification, vertical farms, ecosystem, holism, emergence, integronics.*

1. Introduction

As it is known, pollution is the main reason for climate changes, with all known or yet unknown negative repercussions. That is why researchers from all over the world try to calculate the amount of pollution the 21st century population can afford, so that they may preserve the temperature growth under safety limits.

A scenario of the Meteorological Institute of Great Britain considers that the CO₂ emissions should get to zero until 2050, to maintain the average global temperature rise under 20C. But the reality is worse, so other scenarios show that the biggest quantities of carbon dioxide, issued from human activities, will attain the maximum in the 2010-2020 decade, and will get to zero only in the year 2100. It must be mentioned that all these evolutions depend on technological reorientation i.e. antipollution, including the use of geo-industry for CO₂ absorption from the atmosphere.

Climate modifications especially caused by pollution have a direct effect upon agriculture and food. It is known that gas production with greenhouse effect as a consequence of human

activity, but also produced by plants, may generate big enough CO₂ accumulation to generate temperature growth with an average of over 20C. That means that in several zones the temperature (in Europe for instance) may rise with 40C, which might produce a maximal concentration of equivalent from the atmosphere of CO₂ of 450 ppm (in comparison with 400 ppm presently), which would lead to extreme meteorological phenomena, to the proliferation of the greenhouse effect, to the modification natural bio-geo-chemical cycles, to a potential crises of fresh water, to the extension of diseases in case of animals, to the disappearance of traditional crops etc.

Under these conditions there are previewed prognoses which show that up to 30 % of the actual surface may be „devoured” by desertification. The greenhouse effect implicitly leads to iceberg melting, having as a result, the growth of sea and ocean levels, i.e. to inundation of the ground. Thus will be flooded many coastline and low altitude zones, which will also reduce the present agricultural surface [8].

The environment and its contribution becomes therefore more and more precarious, which

makes the situation more difficult for the decades to come, especially in the situation in which it is forecast that the year 2050 will reach 10 billion inhabitants on Earth, i.e. 3 to 4 billions more "mouths to be fed" than in the. But even in situation of stagnation at this moment, the classic agriculture (including its sustainable side), in order to feed the extra people from the demographic evolution to come, 1 billion new hectares of culture would be needed. As in the present more than 80% of the fields are already cultivated, as well as taking into account that a part of them will be more and more used, not for food cultures, but for energetic ones (the reserves of hydrocarbons, as it is known, being more and more limited), the situation might become very dramatic. This fact will impose to destroy woods in order to gain more land, which will have negative incalculable negative consequences for the natural environment. Therefore, we may consider that one of the most serious problems of the future will be the acute lack of land meant to agriculture and animal breeding [8,14,15].

That is why researchers from all over the world are looking for new manners to solve the food problem under the conditions of ever more acute lack of agricultural land, as it has been previously mentioned, but also for energy and water [3,4,5,6,7,9]. If for energy the researches are more advanced, and those linked to fresh water seem to be solved, taking into account the reserve of salted water, what is worrying is the bases of classical agriculture and, at the same time, the prime richness of the planet, i.e. the lack of fertile soil for food and fodder production, as well as, more frequently, the competition between cultures for food with the energetic. Therefore it is to be previewed that classical agriculture to be completed and, here and there, replaced with something else, with new solutions and the respective technologies.

In our opinion, as frame solutions we consider essential the following two: on one hand the superior valuation of the mountain areal, where pedoclimate conditions and, implicitly the temperatures will become optimal for agriculture, and, on the other hand, agriculture in a controlled environment and space. For both variants we have the certitude that activity optimization will be linked to the process of modularization.

2. Work Methodology

In our opinion, the study of complex and hyper complex systems (Cs/HCs) may generate viable

applications and solutions in order to solve the food problem of the 21st century. Beginning with the Ecoemergent Theory (Gruia, R., 2002) and, more recently, with the General Theory of Ecologic Emergent Integration or the Theory of the Ecoemergent Integronics (Gruia, R., 2009), there are approached, from a new perspective, the phenomena, processes and potentiality of interrelations between the elements of the analyzed systems, to reveal and quantify new, superior forms of organization in order to optimally "pilot" the complex and/or hyper complex systems, where the nonlinear evolution makes the problem be more complicated.

The Theory of Ecoemergent Integronics (EEI) is the ensemble of hypothesis, laws and concepts, organized in a logical approach, which describe and explain the system coexistence and the study of their integration processes and of their composing elements (integrated systems), respectively a change form of an evolutive and integrative type, of the interrelations between living organisms and their life environment, including the relations of man and his natural and social environment, having as results the achievement of something totally new and with the apparition of new properties, of a superior. The emergent integration characterizes a system as a whole and that composing elements do not have.

3. Agroecosystem modularization

In the context of what has been presented we identify a direct relation between the system anthropization and their modularized structure. At the level of the agroecosystems we meet the macro-modularization based on the principles of the sustainable agriculture, and we meet micro-modularization in case of agriculture in space and controlled space. In the first case we practically refer to large agro-zootechnical units and to eco-farms up to the level of the peasant. As for the micro-modules we speak about little well shaped units, of the green house, solarium type, the compactized ones of agro-food production, or capitalization.

THE MODULE, not only in case of complex systems, but especially in case of hyper complex systems, represents in fact the "cell" of structural base, as well as the place where is manifested the dynamics of ecoemergent integronics, from the functional perspective of the given areal.

The modular structure of the Cs and HCs implicitly imposes the idea of the dynamics of

the process of modularization (fig.1), i.e. of the dynamics of flow end growing integration, having as a result a systemic development of evolutive type, from the state of diffuse and complex mosaic, towards the one to induce emergence (3S= synchronic, syncretic and synergic), with result of simplification in detectable perimeters, with monitorable and controllable flows. Thus results the elucidation of apparition of the “new” of superior level, i.e the emergence. The step to another level means the passing of the system to a new restructured state. At its turn, the resulted module becomes a system

with a new structure in dynamic equilibrium, which may, at its turn, when distancing from equilibrium, enter again the process of modularization necessary to reequilibrate to a superior level (fig.2). The dynamics of the process goes on, the anthropic systems practically becoming more and more “modularized” (more organized in the sense of preestablished objectives), restructure that explains in fact a model of the systemic evolution.

Fig.1 – Conceptual diagram concerning the modularization process of complex and hyper complex systems

Fig.2 – The dynamics of the process of complex and/or hyper complex system modularization, based on the mechanism of ecoemergent integronics
S(M)-substance (material); E-energy; I-information; Cs-complex system; HCs-hyper complex system; M-module

What results from the graphic from diagram 2 is the fact that, besides material (substance), energy is higher and (quantitatively and qualitatively) higher, necessary to sustain the new modules with pronounced anthropised control, which imposes a superior organization of the new module in direct relation with the idea of ecoemergent integronics.

Food crises present nowadays in many in course of development countries, but also the dark spectrum given by climate changes, impose new models of agriculture, in general, and of its agronomic, zootechnic, veterinary, of food processing etc. components, in particular. The implication of scientists, of researchers in the field, becomes crucial for technical-economic and judicial solution of grievous problems. Concomitantly, it is necessary for the governments and politicians to become conscious and unite to solve the paradigms of globalization and climate changes specific to the 21st century and implicated in building a modern, competitive

agriculture, structured with respect for sanitary and natural environment.

Agriculture becomes a strategic provocation for the decades to come. It is previewed that in approximately four decades the world food demand will double. That is why it must be found a model of agriculture which may feed 9-10 billion people, as it has already been mentioned.

3.1. Agro-Modules

Taking into account climate changes and demographic evolution at the world level, we consider to be very important the agroecology principles and percepts for the elaboration of new agricultural models. That is why it becomes efficient and especially effective the understanding of agriculture and food development based on production modules well defined by the principles of modularization process, which we synthetically call: agro-modules.

The agro-module represents the conventional measure unit to determine the proportions of a complex system of the „environment-agriculture-food” type, respectively of the agroecosystem and food system type, which ensures the execution of their production function in dynamic equilibrium, through structure and own regulation and self-regulation mechanisms.

We consider that the models offered by sustainable agriculture represent „the rocket launcher” in an evolution of classical agriculture towards another form of agriculture. As it is known, sustainable agriculture aims in principle at the elimination of the present disequilibrium

and fulfillment of a concordance between Environment and Economy, respectively, as for the present paper, between man’s activity in the agro-food field and the sustainability of this technical-economical activity by the natural environment through the so-called „externalities”

(goods and services of the environment „labor”) [14,15,16,17].

Therefore, the management of a complex system can not and must not be reduced to Substance (S) or material, but it will be reconsidered in being more complex, by a more evident opening towards Energy (E) and Information (I) [8,18,19,20]. Piloting in this case will be not only more efficient from an economic point of view, but will become effective in comparison with the system [1,2,10,11,13]. Thus it is made the first step towards the understanding of the production modules as complex systems (agro-modules), including "mini-ecosystems" or micro-modules producing food in controlled environment and space, when in the environment appear major pedoclimatic modifications.

3.2. Modular Agriculture

Besides present agro ecosystems, one may imagine agro-modules, as complex systems to produce food, having as dates of entering the system dynamic conditions of climate and demographic change previewed for the decades

MODULAR AGRICULTURE is the branch of primary food production which includes operations and methods to cultivate plants, mushrooms or to breed animals in "modularized" complex systems, the activity going on from a technological point of view in a controlled environment and space, and, from an economic

It must be mentioned from the very beginning the fact that, unlike classic agriculture, meaning first of all cultivating the land, modular agriculture of the future will also presuppose the existence of land, but most of the technologies are especially meant to supply for the absence of soil through different culture environments and sophisticated control equipments. The teams of specialists collaborate and continuously imagine different applications, which may be based on the principles of modular agriculture [12].

Without entering into details, we exemplify a series of applications. Thus, to understand the components of the described model and the solution for the reduction of agro-zootechnical production consequently to climate changes, a

series of examples of modular agro-food systems and technologies may be given: hydroponic vegetable cultivation, the use of soil "replacements" as cultures in sand, gravel, sawdust, shavings or vermiculite (mineral substances), together with different culture environments (water, air), all being coordinated and controlled with modern equipment; the breeding of the rainbow trout in vivieras in sea waters, the sturgeons breeding in mountain waters, i.e. in "tunnels" on breeding basins specific to trout etc. The complexity of the problem imposes an analyses referring to the methodology and typology of forms from modular agriculture (table 1).

to come. Ecoemergent integronics, at conceptual level, leads to understanding different totally new agricultural forms, as for example the model of Modular Agriculture. The efforts of the researchers from tradition countries have developed in time systems of agriculture in controlled environment and space (greenhouses, solariums, tunnels, vivieras etc.). They represent composing parts of a whole with own functioning and which, in our opinion, constitute in fact modules of integration and emergence, which may be applied especially for vegetal production (especially horticultural), but also for certain mushrooms species, or terrestrial or aquatic animal species (special zootechny). The evolution of these modular systems, restructured and with stressed anthropised control, having a dynamics of diversification and efficacy, through their multiplication, it is de facto imposed a new model of agriculture for the future, whose definition may be synthesized as it follows.

CLASSIFICATION ELEMENTS OF MODULAR AGRICULTURE

Nr. crt.	CRITERIA	CLASSIFICATION	OBS.
1	AFTER THE FORM OF AGRO-MODULES	Horizontal Modules	- ex. tunnels
		Vertical modules	- ex. towers
		Modules with variable geometry	- different combinations
2	AFTER THE DEGREE OF CONTROL	Uncontrolled modules	- practically agro-ecosystems from classic agriculture, which depend on natural climate and on bad weather
		Semi-controlled modules	- systems which presuppose the presence of soil and biocenoses of soil (greenhouses, solariums)
		Totally controlled modules	- dependence on water, energy (especially electric) and on culture environment
3	AFTER THE PRODUCTION TYPE	Vegetal production modules	- generally from the horticulture field
		Mushroom production modules	- ex. pleurotus
		Animal production modules	- generally small animals, birds, pigs, other species in future too
		Aquatic production modules	- aquaculture, pisciculture
4	AFTER THE MODULE SIZE	Micro-modules	- with the potentiality of developing the future ecopolises, but also peasant farm transformation into micro-enterprises
		Medium modules	-important economical level
		Macro-modules	- large efficiency and effectiveness, on large natural areals, with acceptable production conditions

Among the main development directions of modular agriculture, we consider, summarizing, the following tendencies:

1. Organization of modular production of vegetables and fruit, the mushroom one, but also in pisciculture and aquaculture, in small animal breeding and poultry or pigs. The tendency is to include most species in „modular technologies”, in which the anthropic control degree increases, from the microclimate level up to the situation when production may be achieved in a controlled environment and space.
2. It is to be noticed the tendency to pass from agro-ecosystems with a certain anthropisation degree, to agro-modules, to a certain type of modularized mini-ecosystems for agricultural

production (micro-modules), as complex 100% controlled systems;

3. There are defined solutions to counteract the lack of fields, which is foreseen in the 21st century: the idea of rising agricultural cultures and animal farms up to vertical farms built inside big cities. On these real ”agricultural towers” and/or „vertical farms” of the agricultural skyscrapers one may imagine agro-modules where may be planted all kinds of vegetables and fruit, mushrooms, respectively may be bred fish, shrimps, poultry, pigs etc.
4. The future of the food systems imposes the problem of certain constraints of the nourishing system including on space ships. These things may be solved on the bases of the principles of modular agriculture model.

4. Conclusion

Modular production systems apply when in the environment appear major modifications, consequently to profound climate changes and especially in case of lack of fertile soil necessary to produce food.

Ecoemergent integronics, at conceptual level, leads to the understanding of certain totally new agricultural forms, as for example the model of modular agriculture.

"Agricultural towers" or the rise of agricultural cultures and of animal farms to vertical farms, as well as agro-food skyscrapers inside big cities, represent the proper solution for the 21st century conditions. More than that, the applications of the agro-modules may also be extended to spaceships in the perspective of special colonization.

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CUTTING OF MULTI-LAYERED PRODUCTS IN FOOD INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Most food products and some packaging materials are laminated, or have inclusions that are different structural and mechanical properties. Feature cutting multi-layer materials - increase efforts at resistance movement knife to approaching blotches. The technique of cutting research, conducted modeling the blade in multilayer products, conducted experimental research. In the results obtained a number of mathematical models of cutting in the form of second order differential equations that allow to determine the cutting force and speed of the blade in the product.

Keywords: cutting, food, packaging materials, multi-layer materials, force, mathematical modelling.

1. Introduction

The food cutting process used in the food industry may serve as a bypassing operation of division of raw material and semi-finished products to pieces of specified shape and size during formation, batching and milling. Cutting may be as a final operation of product making. The front look and the quality of product surface depend on the quality of its execution.

Foodstuff can be homogeneous (a sugar beet, meat without a bone, confectionery weights etc.), and also multilayered, or with impregnations [1,2,4]. Layers or impregnations are strongly connected with the basic volume of a product, but considerably differ the structurally-mechanical properties. For example, it are meat products which have layers from sinewy fabrics, a skin and bones. Vegetables which have a strong external cover.

And many packing materials which consist of layers (cardboard, paper, synthetic fiber, skin) which differ in structure.

The analyses of scientific papers showed that the methodologies for directly detecting the power of cutoff cutting is missing and don't let using the gained results during calculation and construction of cutting equipment.

For determination of cutting power we conducted math and physics modeling. This allowed to determine the main parameter of cutting process – the power of cutting in dependence with the blade speed in the product and mechanical property of the product.

2. Analytical research of the cutting

2.1. Modelling of cutting of homogeneous products.

Let's take a look at the mechanism of cutting process. Let's compose a differential equation which describes the blade movement in the product.

In case of cutting of a homogeneous product on edges forces operate:

- Cutting F_r
- Friction

$$G = C + k_1 V = C + k_1 \frac{dy}{dt} \quad (1)$$

- Inertia

$$P_i = ma = m \frac{d^2 y(t)}{dt^2} \quad (2)$$

C, k_1 - factors, which characterize friction;

y, V, a – moving, speed and edge acceleration in the product.

Let's write the differential equation of movement of an edge in the product.

$$F_r + G + P_i = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (3)$$

$$F_r + (C + k_1 \frac{dy(t)}{dt}) + m \frac{d^2 y(t)}{dt^2} = 0$$

Having solved the equation (3), we receive the equation for definition of force of cutting depending on speed of the edge and properties of the product:

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$$F_r = \frac{k_1 \frac{dy(t)}{dt} - e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}} (C + V_{oy} k_1) + C}{e^{\frac{k_1 t}{m}} - 1} \quad (4)$$

Capacity of cutting:

$$N = F_{rm} \frac{dy(t)}{dt} \quad (5)$$

F_{rm} the maximum force of cutting.

During cutting force and power of cutting equipment calculations it is necessary to know the specific power of cutting as relation to the power of cutting to the length of the cut L.

$$F_{sr} = F_r / L, \text{ H / M} \quad (6)$$

Having experimental meanings of specific power of cutting the effort of cut off cutting by lamellate flat knife is being determined.

The detailed analysis of the equation (5,6) it is shown in works [1, 3].

To determine the cutting power with the usage of received math models we developed experimental rigging [1] (fig.1). It is simple by construction and safe while using. On the end of the dragonflies 2 blade 4 is placed. Blade during dragonflies falling cuts product 7, which is secured in the fixator 8. Blade speed and its reserve of kinetic energy is easily changed in the wide limits. For this the dragonflies is flinging from various angles, and the placement of load 3 is being changed.

Blade speed:

$$V = R \sqrt{2 \frac{\sum P_i r_i}{J} (1 - \cos \beta)} \quad (7)$$

P_i – weight of every detail of dragonflies, r_i – distance from the center of the weight of this detail to the axes of dragonflies; β – angle out of which dragonflies is hurling; R – dragonflies length; J – inertia moment of all dragonflies details. The results of the modeling are undertaken to define the rational regimes of food products cutting. Cutting power is determined by formula (4). The specific cutting power F_{sr} to the blade length is calculated (5). The results are presented on the fig. 2 and 4.

Fig. 1. The scheme of the device for cutting process research:

1 - plate; 2 - dragonflies; 3 - load; 4 - blade; 5 - pointing hand; 6 - scale; 7 - product; 8 - product fixator.

Reduction of the cutting force is happening at the expense of lessening of product deformation under blade edge under its high speeds. It's typical for all viscid, elastic and plastic products.

For comparatively tight and frail products continuous increasing of cutting force at blade speed growth is observed.

The results gained are valuable for determination of work regimes for cutting equipment. Usage of them in practice allows to lower the energy cutting costs, reduce deformation of products and increase the quality of the cuts.

The application of the results of modeling allow optimize the process for many food products. Besides determination of rational cutting regimes with the help of developed methodology it is possible to determine the consistency of the product. The consistency together with other indicators allows evaluate the product quality.

2.2. Modelling of cutting of non-uniform products.

Feature of cutting of non-uniform products which have impregnations or a cover, it is short-term an operating (instant) force, which operates at edge approach to the cover:

$$F_M = B e^{-bt} \quad (5)$$

The equation of movement of an edge for such products:

$$F_r + G + P_i + F_M = 0 \quad (6)$$

Change of instant force is shown on fig. 3. Graphically it is represented as quickly falling down dependence, time of its action $0 - t_1$ it is much less movements of blade in a product.

The differential equation of movement of an blade:

$$F_r + (C + k_1 \frac{dy(t)}{dt}) + m \frac{d^2 y(t)}{dt^2} + B e^{-bt} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Having solved the equation, at entry conditions ($t=0 \Rightarrow x(0)=0, V(0)=V_0$) we receive value of moving (8), speeds of blade (9) in a product and force of cutting (10).

Change of force of cutting, if cover is presenting, was confirmed experimentally. According to the equation (4) it is received force of cutting of meat with a sinewy layer. The layer was on an input or an exit of an blade from a product. Force of cutting of separately sinewy

layer is so small, that was not fixed by devices. But at cutting of meat with a layer average force

of cutting increases at layer placing on an exit of an blade from a product (fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Dependence of specific cutting power from the blade moving speed in the product during cut off cutting:

1 – crumb of hot bread; 2 – crumb of bread after cooling for 6 hours; 3 – cheese; 4 – sugar beet; 5 – scab bread; 6, 7 – meat (pork) under temperature 5° C and -5°C.

Specific force of cutting, kN/m

Fig. 3. Dependence of force of cutting of meat on placing of a sinewy layer:

1 – without the layer; 2 – the layer on an input in the product; 3 – the layer on exit of the blade from a product.

Fig. 4. Dependence of specific force of cutting of porous polyfoam on speed of cutting:

1 – a cover on an edge input in the product; 2 – on an exit of an edge from the product.

$$y(t) = \frac{m(1 - e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}})(V_0 k_1 + C + F_r)}{k_1^2} + \frac{k_1(B(1 - e^{(bt)}) + bt(C + F_p)) - mb(bt(C + F_r) + B(1 - e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}}))}{(mb - k_1)k_1 b} \quad (8)$$

$$V(t) = \frac{e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}}(V_0 k_1 + C + F_r)}{k_1} + \frac{k_1(Bbe^{(-bt)} + b(C + F_p)) - mb(b(C + F_r) + \frac{Bk_1 e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}}}{m})}{(mb - k_1)k_1 b} \quad (9)$$

$$F_r = \frac{Vk_1 mb - Vk_1^2 + e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}}(-V_0 k_1 mb + V_0 k_1^2 - mbC + Bk_1) + k_1 C - k_1 B e^{(-bt)} - k_1 C + Cbm}{e^{-\frac{k_1 t}{m}}(mb - k_1) + k_1 - mb} \quad (10)$$

Adequacy of the received models is confirmed and for not food product. For example, presence of a thin polymeric layer on a packing paper increases force of its cutting at 20-50 times under condition of film placing on an blade exit.

To receive exact results for foodstuff difficult as they do not possess constant properties. Therefore as a subject of researches of cutting multilayer materials we used a modelling body

– porous polyfoam. The cover role is carried out pasted by a film. Polyfoam on the structure - an is viscous-elastic body, as well as the majority of foodstuff. Dependence of effort of its cutting on a cover arrangement (fig. 4) is received.

The cover arrangement on an exit of an edge from a product increases force of cutting in 50 times in relation to a case when the cover settles down on an edge input in a product or is absent. The work spent for cutting of directly cover, in this case is very small. But, if the cover is located on an edge exit, she creates resistance to product deformation at blade introduction. Thus on a lateral surface of an blade the big pressure operates, and there is a great strength of a friction.

Fig. 5. Change of pressure N on a knife surface: 1 – product; 2 – cover; 3 - blade

It is experimentally confirmed, that the greatest resistance to blade movement arises at its maximum approach to a cover. In case of cutting of a modeling body, this distance makes 0.5 – 1 mm. For example, average force of cutting of a modelling body at a thickness of polyfoam of 0.5 mm 82 kN/m, at a thickness have made of 2 mm - 83 kN/m, 20 mm – 85 kn/m (at speed of an edge of 5 m/s). Such law explains exponential dependence of instant force F_M on cutting time t .

On the basis of the aforesaid it is drawn a conclusion, that the product structure influences force of cutting. Presence of a cover and its arrangement on an exit of an edge from a product considerably increases force of cutting, therefore so to cut a product irrationally.

Let's consider rational ways of orientation of blade for various types of cutting of products with a cover .

At normal cutting the cover should be on an edge input in a product. Thus the knife easily cuts a cover, and further it does not interfere with product deformation.

The correct arrangement of a knife at cutting under a corner also allows to lower effort of cutting. In the beginning the cover, and behind it a product great bulk is cut.

At cutting by a disk knife under the scheme, if axis of rotation of a knife is placed over product, the cover in the beginning is cut. If the rotation axis is below a cover - there is an additional friction.

Similarly product orientation gets out at cutting tape teeth a knife. It is necessary to notice, that the increase in lateral loading at a knife surface leads to a curvature of a teeth and a deviation of a knife from a correct direction of movement. The product thus is considerably deformed.

3. Conclusions

1. Force of cutting of products with a cover or impregnations, and also quality of a surface of a cut depends on an arrangement of a cover concerning blade movement.
2. Mathematical models of movement of an blade in homogeneous and non-uniform products on structure. Models allow to define forces, rational modes and ways of cutting was received.
3. Performance of the resulted recommendations for choice orientations of the cutting tool at cutting multilayered products allow to provide high quality of cutting at low expenses of energy.

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SCIENTIFIC FOUNDING AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE RAPID TECHNOLOGY OF YEAST SEMI-FINISHED PRODUCTS WITH USING THE INDUSTRIAL AFTERPRODUCTS OF THE PROCESSING THE POTATO RAW MATERIAL.

S. ILDIROVA, S. POPOVA

Abstract: *In the article scientifically grounded and developed speed-up technology of zymic intermediate product with the use of afterproducts of processing of potato. Factious composition of the second potato raw material is investigational after freezing. The rational mode and duration of low temperature treatment of afterproducts of processing of potato is offered. An optimum method and mode of drying of the mashed potatoes is developed. The speed-up method of receipt of zymic test is described with the use of dry potato addition.*

Key words: *bakegoodss, zymic to the intermediate product, speed-up technology, afterproducts of processing of potato, dry potato addition, low temperature treatment, radiation drying*

1. The actuality of the topic.

The analysis of the modern market of food stuffs in Ukraine shows that every year the quality decline of products due to wide distribution of using chemical improvers and conservatives is observed [1,2,3]. So how bakery products in Ukraine are the basic food stuffs [4], and their quality do not always meet the requirements, the necessity of creation of the new technologies of high quality bakery products has occurred. It should be noted that the process of dough formation takes much time on the bakery industry plants, which leads to the considerable expense of time, so the creation of rapid technology will considerably allow to shorten time of preparation of bakery products. Also, the problem of the creation of non-waste technologies is an open issue in terms of building of the resource-saving technologies of Ukraine [5].

For this reason, nowadays the creation of principle new rapid technologies of the bakery productsproductionwith using natural raw material is an actual problem.

The analysis of literary sources rotined that the last years got wide distribution development speed-up technologies of production of bakegoodss due to introduction of additional ingridients or additional operations. One of the most widespread directions in this area there is a search of natural sugar replace got from starch, because the necessity of production of sacchariferous matters grows quick, than their

production, that in the end results in appearance of deficit and price increase on traditional sugar [6,7].

Development of this direction is explained by that rapid technology allows to establish the baking of wide assortment of products even on the small medium-size factories, because the modern bakery productsproduction means the variety of small bakeries, Confectionery shops, supermarkets. This technology allows to react operatively on the market requirements in consumers satisfaction of fresh products, it is also allowsto control quality, safety of the bakery products on the stage of semi-finished preparation, to create new bakeries with a brief technological cycle.

Therefore the subsequent development of the scientific researches in the direction of rapidbakery productsproduction with the usage of secondary plant materials for improving the quality of bakery products and rational usage the industrial after products is very topical these days.

2. The purpose of the study.

The purpose of our work is the scientific grounding and development of the rapid technology of yeast semi-finished products with using the industrial afterproducts of the potato processing.

The purpose of this work foresees the development of rapid technology of yeast semi-

finished products due to adding the afterproducts of potato processing to the compounding thus, to improve the high-quality indexes of the flour products and to make the technological process of their production more intensive.

Figure 1 it is offered the model of technological process of getting the dry potato additive from the secondary products of potato processing, which determines the strategy of subsequent researches.

Fig 1. A model of technological process of getting the dry additive from potato.

The given model of technological process foresees the use of afterproducts of potato processing (subsystem of C), which gives the possibility to use the second raw material rationally, and also to start the development of principally new technology for getting sweetener from the starched raw material. Subsystem B includes the grinding and adjusting the motion of the technological process of getting the dry potato additive. Subsystem A determines the possibility of using the dry potato additive in the technology of food production, particularly in the technology

of yeast dough production removing sugar from compounding

Consequently, the review of literary sources has confirmed the expediency of upgrading the quality of bakery products, the intensification of the technological process of their production on the basis of the using the untraditional raw material and rational using of the second natural resources.

But, the using of new raw material creates the necessity of evaluation of the chemical composition and its change during the previous treatment and preparation for the subsequent application; studying its physical, chemical and

technological properties; and also the researching of influence the got dry potato additive on the components of dough with the purpose of development the effective technology of its use.

During the studying this subject it was marked that today the afterproducts of potato processing are used in starch productions technology, and also for feeding the cattle. But, in national and foreign literature it was not found the technology of production the dry potato additive which is produced in quality of natural sweetener got from the starched plant materials.

So that we conducted the series of experimental researches for the scientific grounding of new method for recycling the secondary raw materials for getting the dry additive and its subsequent usage in food production technologies, particularly for yeast wares.

Determinations of technological parameters and modes of getting the dry potato additive from the second starched raw material were conducted in a few stages.

On the first stage the technological parameters of the pretreatment of the second raw material was determined. At first the

hydromechanical treatment of the potato after products was conducted, then it was grounded down to puree the mass. During the growing of the starched raw material the color changing is observed, it is related to oxidation of the polyphenoloxidase and co-operating the starched polysaccharides with air oxygen. In common practice for the oxidizing reactions prevention the previous treatment of product ascorbic or lemon acids is used, and also the method of sulfatation of product is used also.[8,9]. In this work the method of previous treatment was used by solution of lemon acid.

On the second stage the temperature parameters of the treatment with the purpose of maximal accumulation of sugars was determined. It is known that under the low temperature treatment there is a considerable accumulation of sugars due to the process of hydrolysis of starch, that is why the determination of treatment and temperature interval duration is a necessary.

Freezing was conducted at the following temperatures: -40°C, -18°C and -5°C with the purpose of setting time that is enough for maximal accumulation of the sugar. The results of this research are given on the figure 2.

Fig 2. The dynamics of accumulation of the reduced sugars during the cooling treatment.

According to the conducted experimental researches which results are represented on the figure 2, we can see, that under the influence of low temperature treatment, the amount of sugar grows swiftly. It is necessary to notice that the oscillation of the temperature range considerably influences on intensity of accumulation of sugars,

which depends on the time of low temperature treatment. So in an hour in conditions of the shock freezing there was the swift growth of the amount of the reducing substances. Then their amount became stabilizing and continued to be in a stable value. At the temperature -18°C the same amount of sugar appeared later, in 2 hours. Then

it stabilized also, and at the temperature -5°C the amount of the reducing substances did not attain the maximal value for three hours.

Consequently, the using of shock freezing vehicle or low temperature section on the line of processing the potato afterproducts is advantageous from the point of energy maintenance.

Subsequent researches related to the determination of the factious composition of sugar, which appeared during the low temperature treatment. The researches was conducted by the method of high effective liquid chromatography on the device of Shimadzu LC20 Prominence. The results of them are shown in the table 1.

Table 1. The concentration of the optically active carbohydrates in the potato solutions

Carbohydrate	Secondary products of potato processing		Dry potato additive	
	Concentration C, %	Mass m, gr	Concentration C, %	Mass m, gr
saccharose	29.84	0.3916	0.83	0.04248
fructose	5.41	0.0710	28.98	1.47578
maltose	–	–	40.16	2.04473
glucose	64.75	0.8499	29.98	1.52650
dextrin	–	–	<0.05	0.00241
together:	100.00	1.3125	100.00	5.0919

The principle technological scheme of the experiment anticipates that after establishment of duration and temperature of the previous technology of production the dry potato freezing and determination of the factious composition of appearing sugars, it is necessary to choose the rational mode of drying of the obtained mixture.

The next stage of the research were the series of experiments for the scientific grounding of the method of dry potato additive production which was obtained from of the potato recycling.. In fact the using of the frozen product is not really convenient for the small and middle-size factories. The dry products are also more convenient for keeping and have longer due term.

The conducted review of the methods of pasty products drying, which is given in the first section in more details, permitted us to choose the drying puree from the potato wastes, the method with the radiation warming. So that in our case the large number of reduced sugars is appeared as a result of the previous freezing of the product, which promotes the sticking of the product on a hot metallic surface during the conductive drying. The complication of the removal such a product from the surface, as our experimental researches showed, predetermines the low quality of it. That is why we chose the radiation method of drying the puree in an immobile thin sphere on the fluoroplastic surface that prevents sticking [10].

The change of the product moisture and its temperature field was investigated, thus these

tests carried out separately. For determination of the moisture change with an interval in one minute, a plate with the product weighed on the analytical electronic scales of SNUG II-300 with exactness 0,01 gr. Every test carried out to stopping the change of the mass. According to the method of drying to the permanent mass [11] the moisture of product before and after drying was determined. In this case the grinded product was drying in the drying closet SNOL 3,5.3,5.3,5/3,5 I2, that is equipped by the automatic regulator of the temperature, at $130\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The examination of the temperature field of the product was conducted without the periodical weighing while the thermocouples were set up. All the experiments have been conducted three times, the results were averaged.

Based on the experimental data, the charts of drying speed of drying and temperature were built in the different points of the product (thermograms).

On figure 3 there are drying and speed of drying charts for the potato puree made from recycling left overs with different levels of the heat steam density.

Experiments were carried out at a temperature of air in the premises $19-21^{\circ}\text{C}$, initial moisture content of the product 317%, unit load of product on Fluor plastic plate 2.33 kg/m^2 .

Curves with a speed of drying constructed by graphical differentiation of curves drying. Analysis of the curves shows that the drying

process is taking a place in three stages - heating (small convex to the upper horizontal axis of the plot at the beginning of curve), linear changes in moisture content and the falling speed of drying. The value of critical moisture content, which separates the second and third periods, lies within

the range 122,1-132,9% according to density of heat flow IR radiation. Most long curves on dry land is a linear change of moisture content, during which, together with a plot of heating, removing mostly the free moisture.

Fig 3 – Curves of drying (1-3) and drying rate (1'-3') mashet from potato waste at different values of the density of heat IR- radiation flux:
1, 1' – 1625 W/m²; 2, 2' – 1250 W/m²; 3, 3' – 875 W/m²

As shown by curves, the intensity of drying greatly depends on the density of heat flow. Thus, while increasing it from 876 to 1625 W/m² length of the process is reduced accordingly from 51 to 33 minutes. Acceleration of drying in this case occurs mainly in the period of linear change in moisture content. Thus, the constant drying rate in this period increased correspondingly from 7.92 to 12.8% / min. In view of that, this intensification of the process achieved by reducing the height of the block heaters from 0.096 to 0.051 m for the same values of the electric power, it is clear reduction while specific energy consumption and increase performance settings proportionally reduce the length of the drying process. It means that with position indicators above the optimum is the least possible for technical reasons, the distance between the block heaters and products.

A different kind of influence of increasing the density of heat flow on product quality. So, at

875 W/m² final product has a uniform cream color, there are no zones of burning product. In 1250 W/m² at the periphery of the product layer appears circular area about 15 mm wide with a dark color characteristic of caramelization at the appropriate temperature for the product in this area.

Even larger sizes this area accepts with 1625 W/m². This shows that the heterogeneity of the density of heat flow for a given experimental setup in horizontal planes. This heterogeneity, judging from the burning area increase with decreasing distance between the product and unit heaters, also changes in the vertical direction.

The next stage of the research was the development of accelerated technology pastry with dry potato supplements.

The proposed way to prepare dough from the previous activation of yeast environment will significantly reduce the adaptation of yeast to

environmental conditions and intensify the process of fermenting dough.

The method of pastry with dry potato additives were carried out as follows.

The activation of yeast realized when temperatures are 30-32°C for (18-20) • 60 seconds for the prepared potato dry additive is injected into pre-dissolved yeast. After activation injected recepturnoyi balance of water, flour, margarine and

conduct during kneading (10-15) • 60 seconds, then precooked dough left to ferment for (60-90) • 60 seconds at 30-35°C in the process is carried out smashing dough for several times. Dough should be split, forming, baking, cooling and packaging.

The performed research allowed the complex research to substantiate prescription composition of pastry with dry potato additives (table 2).

Table 2. Compounded composition pastry

Name of raw materials	Costs of raw materials per 100 kg of product
Flour	64100
Dry potato additive	3400
Pressed yeast	1900
Grease component	2900
Soult	1000
Dry egg powder (chicken egg)	3400
Water	25800

Thus, the following conclusions can be made: A new method of processing recycled plant material, and conducted experimental research allowed to develop a rapid method of preparing

dough with a prior activation of yeast. Form the basis for the production of bakery products with reduced time dough formation to 35-40%.

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RESEARCH IN OBTAINING OF COSMETICS AND BEAUTY CARE BASED ON VEGETABLE OILS FOR SUN PROTECTION

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Abstract: *The paper's research shows progress and results for new sunscreen products. They had to consider new formulations for a tan activator and another painkiller after beach.*

It is known that exposure to the sun enables our the skin to produce Vitamin D a nutrient needed for strong bones. Although UV radiation is only 5% of the solar spectrum, they are the biggest contributor to the skin's genetic damage, causing premature aging as well as increasing the risk of skin cancer.. There are three types of UV radiation: UVA, UVB and UVC, the latter being stopped by the ozone layer.

The main differences between UVA and UVB radiation is the fact that UVB is present between ours 10-16, affect the epidermis, causing sunburns and heatstroke while UVA rays penetrate deep into the skin reaching the dermis, causing skin aging and solar allergies, which are constant throughout the day and year.

Studying ancient Egyptians , it was discovered that they were protecting their skin from strong sunlight using natural oils.

Starting from this, were analyzed and selected a number of natural oils formulated to two products: an oil tan activator and a soothing after-sun oil, both containing a mixture of vegetable oils, oil extracts and essentials oils.

Keywords: *vegetable oils, sun protection factor, volatile oil*

1. Introduction

They studied a number of fatty oils with high content of essential fatty acids and fat soluble vitamins. These oils can be assured of Hofigal own production, price and quality so as to be optimal compared to other similar products.

The rating system for sunscreens specifies a Sun Protection Factor (SPF) value, which can be thought of as a time factor for the protection of skin compared to exposure without any protection. For example, if a person would show visible erythema (sunburn) after five minutes of exposure, application of a sunscreen with SPF eight extends that time to five minutes times the protection factor of eight, or forty minutes. Study were performed to evaluate ultraviolet (UV) absorption ability of volatile and nonvolatile herbal oils used in sunscreens or

cosmetics and express the same in terms of sun protection factor (SPF) values.

2. Materials and Methods

The *in vitro* SPF is determined according to the spectrophotometric method of Mansur *et al.* Hydroalcoholic dilutions of oils were prepared, and *in vitro* photoprotective activity was studied by UV spectrophotometric method in the range of 290-320 nm. It can be observed that the SPF values found for nonvolatile oils were in between 2 and 8; and for volatile oils, in between 1 and 7. Among the fixed oils taken, SPF value of olive oil was found to be the highest. Similarly among essential oils, SPF value of peppermint oil was found to be the highest.

3. Results and Discussion

In Table no.1 are given values for some volatile and nonvolatile oils. The study will be helpful in the selection of oils and fragrances to develop sunscreens with better safety and high SPF. Oily vehicles are more

effective for producing a uniform and long-lasting film of sunscreen on the skin, and their emollient properties protect the skin against the drying effects of exposure to wind and sun.

Table 1. The herbal oil and SPF value calculated spectrophotometrically

Name of herbal oil taken	SPF value calculated spectrophotometrically
Olive oil	7.5
Coconut oil	7.1
Hemp oil	6
Macadamia oil	6
Sesame oil	4
Jojoba oil	4
Peppermint oil	6.6
Lavender oil	5.62
Eucalyptus oil	2.62
Tee tree oil	1.7

Milk Thistle Seed Oil (*Silbum marianum*)

The Milk thistle oil is considered as the one of the rich source of the natural vitamin E and its derivatives. Beside this type of substances it contains also special kind of flavonoids (flavonolignans) which contributes to high anti-

oxidant potential of the oil and protection of the skin supporting its regeneration. Thus Milk thistle oil is suitable especially for the cosmetic and pharmaceutical preparations intended for sensitive and irritated skin like in new born babies, children, people suffering from atopic eczema, psoriasis, diabetic patients etc.

Tab.2. Fatty Acids Pattern of Silybum marianum Seed Oil

Tocopherol Content (ppm)	Tocopherol Composition %			
	α -T	β - T	γ - T	δ -T
260	84.5	9.9	5.4	0.2

The unsaponifiable matter of milk thistle oil is about 1% of the composition.

This fraction is rich in phytosterols, known as the anti-aging agents and agents of skin hydration.

Table 3. Whole Sterols Pattern of Silybum marianum Oil

Total Sterol Content (mg/100g)	Sterol Composition %						
	Chole sterol	Campe sterol	Stigma sterol	Sito sterol	Isofuco sterol	7stigma sterol	Avena sterol
600	0.9	6.1	6.8	57.4	2.9	20.4	5.5

The major component of Milk thistle oil is linoleic acid, well known also as the “essential” polyunsaturated fatty acid from group of omega-6 fatty acids. . Beside the triglycerides part of oil, in virgin oil we can find a significant amount of (about 5% w/w) of mono- and diglycerides which increase the total oil polarity. This property is very important for the spreadability of the preparations made of Milk thistle oil. Polar oils in general have a much better ability to act as the carriers of biologically active substances. Their behavior in the skin is closer to sebum properties than the behavior of paraffinic oils. Due to these facts Milk thistle oil exhibits some excellent properties as the part of dermatological preparations.

Hemp Seed Oil (*Canabis sativa*)

Hemp is an excellent vegetable oil. Thanks to its content in omega 3 and 6 it has a composition similar to skin lipids and vegetable oils are among the richest in essential fatty acids. Moisturizing, regenerating and revitalizing oil is especially useful for dry, mature, irritated, tired or dehydrated skin. We also find it in composition of hair care cosmetics, which brings brilliance and strength of hair. Hemp Oil provides essential fatty acids in maintaining healthy and flexible cell membranes, with good results in treating chronic allergies and inflammatory skin disease. Has the ideal ratio of essential fatty acids omega 6 and omega 3, thereby supporting cellular metabolism. Terpenes in the composition of hemp oil have anti-inflammatory effects, vitamin E is found here as variants of alpha-tocopherol and gamma-tocopherol.

Carrot oil (*Daucus carota*) it is an oil soak rich in vitamins. Carrot oil can help protect the skin from the sun’s UV rays, and also help sunbathers to get the bronze tan they desire. Carrot Oil also acts as a natural tanning enhancer, producing a visibly golden tan in a short amount of time. It is

antioxidant, velvety elasticizant, radiant, refreshing.

Marigold oil (*Calendula officinalis*) is recommended for sensitive skin care, hypersensitive, with redness or couperose, for soothing properties, softening and toning. Marigold flowers contain protein substances, volatile oil, saponins, glycosides, carotenoids, xanthophylline, flavonoids, yeast, mucilage, vitamin C, organic salts. Some of the substances, in combination with the high resin content, provide Marigold with its' powerful anti-inflammatory action. It is a good remedy for inflamed skin and for a range of microbial and parasitic infections. Ideal of healing cuts, scrapes, lacerations, surgical wounds and scars, small infected wounds, animal bites and scratches.

Useful for skin conditions such as acne, shingles, chickenpox, dermatitis, eczema sores, impetigo spots and other systemic fungal, bacterial and viral conditions. An effective aid to healing minor first degree burns, such as sunburn. The active principles from marigold stimulates blood flow to tissues causing a more rapid regeneration thereof.

Sea Buckthorn oil (*Hippophae rhamnoides*)

Sea buckthorn oil is rich in lecithin, mineral salts, essential fatty acids, phyosterols and flavonoids, vitamins. Thereby, provitamin A prevents depigmentations caused by aging, Vitamin E, the most valuable natural antioxidant, develop good protection against free radicals, Vitamin F is a mixture of essential unsaturated fatty acids that nourish the skin and prevents dehydration .

Sea Buckthorn oil has multiple benefits in the area of restorative and anti-aging skin care. Natural antioxidants and essential fatty acids help reverse damaging effects of sun radiation and minimize long term effects of sun exposure, like wrinkles, dryness, dark spots reduce skin

inflammation, promote natural skin restorative processes . The oil is well tolerated by any type of skin and provide long term anti-inflammatory, restorative and revitalizing action.

There have been two new products for sunscreen, tanning oil and soothing oil

Tanning Oil

Description:

Recommended for skin already accustomed to the sun. Provides an rapid and uniform tan, maintaining skin elasticity. Natural beta-carotene present in the formula accelerates skin tanning and gives a golden tint. Thistle oil and hemp oil with high content of essential amino acids are protective and soothing. It's recommended for dark skin or, already tanned skin only to enhance tanning.

Usage:

Apply a thin layer all over the body exposed to solar radiation. Reapply frequently and plentiful (especially after bathing, as if sweating or toweling). Prolonged exposure to sunlight is dangerous, do not stay too long in the sun even if you use a sunscreen . The product does not contain UV filters.

Aftersun oil

Description:

Active protection against premature skin aging. Oil was designed with a special formula that quickly regenerates the skin after sun exposure. The oils, rich in Vitamin E neutralize free

radicals and prevents premature skin aging. The high content of lipids from the natural oils quickly rehydrates and maintain skin elasticity. The oil softens the skin and maintain.

4. Conclusion

Excessive sun exposure is a serious health threat. Do not expose babies and young children to direct sunlight.

Benefits for tanning oil: fixes and enhances tan, maintain skin elasticity.

Benefits for aftersun oil: Pour a small pool into the palm of your hand. Clasp the hands together to warm the oil and spread over the hands. Gently massage into the skin working up the body towards the heart.

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STUDY REGARDING THE EVOLUTION OF HEAVY METALS IN CARBONATED DRINKS AT STORAGE

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Abstract: *The aim of this work was to determine the content of heavy metals form different kinds of carbonated and to observe the evolution of migration of heavy metals in carbonated drinks at storage and transport. We studied four types of carbonated drinks for the content of certain metals as Fe, Cu, Cd, Pb, Al and Mn. The test was made at 4°C and at 22C for the carbonated drinks in the shop. For purposes of this study used modern methods and equipment were used. They allow to determine with accuracy the content of various substances in food and beverages. The results of experimental work showed increased content of various metals. This is the result of migration, which is different for different carbonated drinks tested. During the preservation period of products in metallic packages, lead and cadmium migration from the packaging material into product takes place with a rate directly proportional with increasing of storage time.*

Keywords: *carbonated drinks, migration, metals, cans.*

1. Introduction

Metal is the most versatile of all packaging forms. It offers a combination of excellent physical protection and barrier properties, formability and decorative potential, recyclability, and consumer acceptance. The two metals most predominantly used in packaging are aluminum and steel.

Aluminum. Commonly used to make cans, foil, and laminated paper or plastic packaging, aluminum is a lightweight, silvery white metal derived from bauxite ore, where it exists in combination with oxygen as alumina. Magnesium and manganese are often added to aluminum to improve its strength properties [1]. Unlike many metals, aluminum is highly resistant to most forms of corrosion; its natural coating of aluminum oxide provides a highly effective barrier to the effects of air, temperature, moisture, and chemical attack. Besides providing an excellent barrier to moisture, air, odors, light, and microorganisms, aluminum has good flexibility and surface resilience, excellent malleability and formability, and outstanding embossing potential. It is also an ideal material for recycling because it is easy to reclaim and process into new products. Pure aluminum is used for light packaging of primarily soft-drink cans, pet food, seafood, and pretreated closures. The main disadvantages of aluminum are its high cost compared to other metals (for example, steel) and its inability to be welded, which

renders it useful only for making seamless containers.

The primary purpose of food packaging must continue to be maintaining the safety, wholesomeness, and quality of food. The impact of packaging waste on the environment can be minimized by prudently selecting materials, following EPA guidelines, and reviewing expectations of packaging in terms of environmental impact. Knowledgeable efforts by industry, government, and consumers will promote continued improvement, and an understanding of the functional characteristics of packaging will prevent much of the well-intentioned but ill-advised solutions that do not adequately account for both preconsumer and postconsumer packaging factors [2].

For drink cans, the top is usually referred to as a Stay-on Tab (SOT), enabling the opening tab and pierce-open end section to be retained on the can. The SOT end has largely superseded the traditional ring-pull end.

All ends for processed food cans have a number of circular beads in the center panel area to provide flexibility. These allow the panel to move outwards, as internal pressure is generated in the can during the heating cycle of the process and so reduce the ultimate pressure achieved in the can. During the cooling process, this flexibility permits the center panel to return to its original position.

Ends for beer and carbonated drink cans do not require the above feature as the can's internal

pressure is always positive. The plate thickness and temper have to be appropriate to the level of carbonation of the product and, if applicable, pasteurization treatment; otherwise excessive internal pressure may cause can ends to peak or distort [3].

2. Storage and distribution

Both processed and empty cans should be stored in controlled conditions. Condensation that can lead to corrosion (see Section 5.10) is a major issue if inappropriate combinations of container temperature, air temperature and air humidity are allowed to occur. The risk of condensation at a given set of storage conditions can be predicted using psychrometric charts. Historically, the use of tempering rooms to avoid sudden changes of temperature has been recommended. Where the risk is severe and climate control difficult, e.g. shipping across the equator, the use of desiccants within secondary packaging might be considered. Warehouse storage should ensure that there are no draughts, windows are closed and air movement is minimized e.g. door flaps. Stretch-wrapping of pallets and shrink-wrapping of trays help to reduce the risk of condensation as well as the accumulation of salt-laden dust which is hygroscopic and can effect rusting. Efficient stock control will serve to minimize the risk of corrosion [4].

Coastal canneries are particularly at risk from corrosion due to airborne salt from sea spray. Extra precautions may be necessary, e.g. externally lacquered can components. Can ends are frequently externally lacquered to provide extra protection against external corrosion, particularly at the top edge of the double seam. Paperboard divider sheets or pallet layer pads are often re-used and salt residues can accumulate leading to rusting and possible perforation of double seams. Paper should be within the recommended pH and salt (chloride and sulphate) content range. Freezing of filled cans should also be avoided to prevent deformation of cans due to ice expansion.

Absence of water is important to minimise external corrosion and also to prevent ingress of bacteria through the can seams. For example, shipping containers and any building used for storage should be water-tight.

Pallet systems used for transporting cans should restrain the load in a manner that minimises the risk of damage during distribution.

This may involve using a frame on top of the pallet, straps and/or shrink-wrapping/stretch-wrapping.

The pallets themselves should have the correct performance specification and be in good mechanical condition. Protruding nails can present a food-safety risk by can puncture; it is also bad practice to use staple guns in close proximity to finished cans for the same reason. The moisture content and chemistry of pallet wood and other secondary packaging materials should be suitable to prevent corrosion issues.

Can specifications should include the axial loads that they can sustain, which enables makers to advise on maximum stacking heights for storage of finished goods, to prevent compression failure of lower can layers in the pallet stack. Warehouse practices should ensure even distributions of weight on supporting pallets. Containers should be held off the floor, and away from walls, to prevent moisture build up. Division of stocks into smaller units will aid in ventilation [5].

The shelf life of canned foods is determined by a variety of factors but all relate to deteriorative reactions of some form or another, either those introduced during production or processing activities or those occurring during storage. In order to understand these processes better it is important to be able to define shelf life more exactly. Shelf life can be defined in two ways: minimum durability and technical shelf life.

- *Minimum durability* is defined as the period of time under normal storage conditions during which a product will remain fully marketable and will retain any specific qualities for which express claims have been made. However, beyond this point the food may still be satisfactory for consumption.

- *Technical shelf life* is defined as the period of time under normal storage conditions after which the product will not be fit to eat.

In general, the shelf life of a can will depend upon the product, the can specification and the storage conditions in which it is held. Every can is a unit of sale and as such each and every can must comply with the legislation relevant to it [6].

For this reason, and because of the many variables associated with the product, from the grower through to the retailer, it is very difficult to assign a specific shelf life to any product. The experience of the packer is most critical in arriving at sensible conclusions. Overall, however, due to the many different factors

affecting shelf life, it is often impossible to predict, and tests with the actual product are the best course of action.

3. Materials and methods

Samples

Analyses were conducted periodically throughout seven months of storage on four different brands of carbonated drinks (A, B, C and D brand). One part of samples was stored in a refrigerator (4 °C) or in a thermostatic chamber (22 °C).

Procedures

Heavy metals content. Prior to heavy metals concentration determination, 40 ml of carbonated drinks were withdrawn from cans. Containers and laboratory materials were washed with warm, diluted nitric acid and subsequently rinsed with double distilled water (conductivity=0.055 mS/cm). Carbonated drinks sample was placed in ultrasonic water bath to eliminate carbonation(60 min. at 45Hz, T=20 C, P=100%) and then 5 ml of degassed beer were diluted to 50 ml with 1 % nitric acid (in double distilled water). After wards, the sample was placed in the auto sampler cup and shortly of ICP-MS AGILENT SERIA 7500ce.

4. Results and discussions

The study shows that aluminium from cans contributes to the transfer of the total aluminium, particularly if they are deformed and containers have been stored for long periods of time.

The paper allows to observe that for maintain a minimum contamination of product with metals, the drinks shall consumed in the first five months after preparation and packaging.

Fig.1.Variation of Mn content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

In the figure 1 it is observe the evolution of Mn content migration from all samples tested at storage.

Fig.2. Variation of iron content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

In the figure 2 it is observe a significant increase of iron content of the sample A compared to other samples during the whole period of storage.

Fig.3. Variation of Cu content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

In the figure 3 it is observe a major change in the copper content from sample B compared to other samples tested storage over time.

Fig. 5. Variation of Zn content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

In the figure 5 it is observe a major change in the Zn content from sample D compared to other samples tested storage over time.

Fig.4. Variation of Cr content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

In the figure 4 it is observe a major change in the Cr content from sample A compared to other samples tested storage over time.

In the figure 6 it is observe a major change in the Pb content from sample A compared to other samples tested storage over time.

Fig.6. Variation of Pb content in foodstuff – Juice- during storage

To this end, constantly made research on the migration of heavy metals and low molecular weight substances from packaging in product.

Perhaps some of the substances detected in beverages were available even in the raw materials used for their production. However, for most metals tested ii is observe their presence in the drink, after a period of storage in aluminium containers, and an increase of 2 to 5 times.

5. Conclusion

In recent years, one of the most important factors, allowing for rapid implementation of the various food and beverage is their safety as regards the interaction between food and packaging.

This shows very clearly that the source of contamination is the process of packaging and storage in that package.

The article published research results for the migration of manganese, iron, copper, chromium, zinc and lead.

In all studied samples migrated quantities of substances are below normal. The overall migration is also underweight required within the EU food and drink. The dependence of increasing the concentration of test substances in the beverage from the time of its storage container is almost linear. This allows for a particular type of beverage container and used to predict the amount of migrated substance after some time.

A drink in the content of chromium, iron and manganese is high. Even the lowest level of manganese in the product at time of storage of the beverage in the container when beverage type A can be seen most rapid increase in concentration. This means that the package has increased migration of manganese in the product.

In most samples studied migration agents increased on average between 2 and 3 times its concentration. This is obviously due to the presence in the packaging material of the packaging, substances such as manganese, iron, copper, chromium, zinc and lead.

The data obtained allow determining the conditions under which drinks are safe for consumers.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE DYNAMIC OF HAEMATOLOGICAL INDICES IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES ON WISTAR RATS

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Abstract: The researches were performed on male Wistar rats diabetised with Streptozotocin and treated with Eridiarom and Diavit (original phytotherapeutic products). In the diseased group treated with Eridiarom the number of erythrocytes reverted from $8.21 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ (3 months) to $8.52 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ (7 months); with Diavit from $8.48 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ (3 months) to $9.08 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ (7 months). Haemoglobin increased from 14.99 g/l (3 months) to 16.64 g/l (7 months) under treatment with Eridiarom; with Diavit from 15.85 g/l (3 months) to 19.1 g/l (7 months). Hematocrit, was 40.15 % (3 months) and 42.95 % (7 months) under treatment with Eridiarom; with Diavit was 43.07 % (3 months) and 44.93 % (7 months).

Keywords: experimental diabetes, rats, Eridiarom, Diavit, erythrocytes, haemoglobin, hematocrit.

1. Introduction

In our research, we observed the haematological modifications in rats in which we had experimentally induced diabetes using Streptozotocin and identified existing correlations between the data we collected, experimentally observing the animals for 7 months. Experiments are meant to provide new therapeutic information, to serve as an alternative to the current insulin and sulphamide based treatment of diabetes.

Eridiarom is a natural fruit concentrate of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. (bilberry), from the spontaneous flora, obtained through original procedures that allow preservation of main active components, and by adding meritose, starch, lactose, gelatine, magnesium stearate and talc. It is rich in vitamins (C, provitamin A, PP, B₁, B₂, E), mineral salts (K, Ca, P, S, Mg, Mn, Fe), natural principles, antocianosides, phytoncides, tannins, vegetal acids (myristic, palmitic, quinic), pectins, polyphenols.

Diavit is a natural fruit concentrate from *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. (bilberry) and *Hippophae rhamnoides* L. (common sea-buckthorn) from the spontaneous flora, obtained through original procedures that allow preservation of main active components, and by adding meritose, starch, lactose, gelatine, magnesium stearate and talc.

2. Materials and Methods

The research was conducted on 4 groups of Wistar rats, males, 6 months old, average mass of 150 grams over a period of 7 months. Animals were injected with 4 g/100g/body Streptozotocin to induce diabetes.

Periodically blood samples were collected for automated haematological exams.

The groups were composed as follows:

Group I - 8 animals clinically healthy, not diseased and untreated (healthy group).

Group II - 8 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin, treated with 2.7g/head/day Eridiarom.

Group III - 8 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin, treated with 3g/head/day Diavit.

Group IV - 8 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin and untreated.

The maintenance conditions, microclimate as well as the food were standard for the rats.

Every two months, blood samples were collected from all animals, the determinations being automatically processed in the clinical laboratory. When inducing diabetes, collecting the haematological samples and euthanizing the research animals we complied with all the current deontological and animal protection norms and regulations. The samples were collected in special recipients, transported on ice and processed immediately.

The obtained data were statistically processed and graphically represented.

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3. Results and discussions

1. RBC (erythrocytic anaemia)

Acute anaemias are especially owed to some posttraumatic internal or external haemorrhages, to some bad coagulation disorders – as in the case of the coumarin and melilot intoxications – to some massive bleeding – gastric and esophagogastric ulcer (in pigs), aneurism rupture or some severe haemolysis – as in the water intoxication.

Initially, anaemia is normocytic normochromic, later to become macrocytic hypochromic, especially in the case of external haemorrhages, when the iron ion cannot be recycled.

Chronic anaemias, in their final phase, are microcytic. They are due either to repeated bleeding (ulcers, haematemesis, metrorrhagia, hematuria), or to certain parasitic diseases: haematopinosis in cattle and pigs; ostertagiasis, coccidiosis, esophagostomosis in cattle, syngamosis in Gallinaceae.

Based on the nature of the anaemia, on the disorders in the production and destruction of the red blood cells, the following major types can be distinguished:

1. Haemolytic anaemia

The destruction of erythrocytes (haemolysis) may occur intravascularly and extravascularly.

Haemolysis is characterised, among others, by jaundice, hyperbilirubinemia, urobilinuria, hypersideremia or splenomegaly. If haemolysis is intravascular and severe, haemoglobinuria can also be noticed.

2. Aplastic anaemia

This is probably the most frequently met type of anaemia in animals: normocytic normochromic anaemia. It is probably associated with thrombocytopenia (bleeding diathesis) and leucopenia (predisposition to infections).

3. Deficiency anaemias (hypochromic, microcytic)

a/- Iron deficiency anaemia: neonatal (piglets, calves, puppies, young minks) excess of phytate in their food (bran), excess of phosphate in food (bran, eggs, milk, cheese); hypochlorhydria gastropathies; malnutrition, malabsorption; repeated gestation; iron deficiency etc.

b/- Copper deficiency : deficiency in food or experimental deficiency;

c/- Selenium deficiency – in pigs;

d/- Cobalt deficiency – enzootic marasmus in bovines = deficiency in B12 vitamin

e/- B12 vitamin deficiency in pigs; B6 (exp.) deficiency in dogs and pigs; niacin deficiency in carnivores; riboflavin deficiency in dogs;

f/- Protein deficiency: especially in pigs and birds

Fig. 1. Graphic representation of the dynamics of erythrocytes and of the standard deviation in groups treated with Eridiarom comparatively with studied groups

The slightly anaemiating trend of streptozotocin-induced diabetes can be seen (Fig. 1) in the diseased and untreated group, whose values are: after 3 months- $8.57 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, after 5 months – $7.79 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, and after 7 months – $7.64 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ as compared to the

average of the control group. We can also see here, in the diseased group treated with Eridiarom, a comeback in the number of red blood cells from $8.21 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at 3 months, to $8.49 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at 5 months, and respectively $8.52 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at 7 months (slightly increasing).

Fig. 2. Graphic representation of the dynamics of erythrocytes and of the standard deviation in groups treated with Diavit comparatively with studied groups

The slightly anaemiating tendency of streptozotocin-induced diabetes can be seen (Fig. 2) in the tendency of the diseased and untreated group whose values are: after 3 months $8.57 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, after 5 months it was $7.79 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, and after 7 months it was $7.64 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$, as compared to the average of the control group. We can also see here, in the diseased group treated with Diavit a comeback of the number of red blood cells from $8.48 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at three months, to $9.22 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at 5 months, and respectively $9.08 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ at 7 months.

2. HGB (HAEMOGLOBIN)

Haemoglobin is synthesized by the red blood cells during their formation, in the bone marrow. It serves to carry the carbon dioxide from the organs (heart, muscles) to the lungs, but especially to carry oxygen to all the body tissues. The normal values of haemoglobin range between 14 and 18 g/L.

The drop in haemoglobin values not associated with the drop in the number of red blood cells is called anaemia; the main cause of anaemia is iron deficiency. As a result of this deficiency, the haemoglobin synthesis decreases, and the red blood cells will be hypochromic and microcytic. In haemolysis, the associated jaundice is caused by the bilirubin metabolite and by the circulating haemoglobin that might cause kidney failure.

At a smaller scale, it appears that haemoglobin A combines with glucose that binds in a certain site, thus creating the **HbA_{1c}** (glycosylated or glycated haemoglobin) compound. As the glucose concentration increases, the percentage of HbA turned into HbA_{1c} increases, too. In diabetic patients, where the glucose has very high values, the compound also tends to have high values, its percentage being representative for the level of the blood glucose due to the 50-55-day lifespan of the red blood cells.

Fig. 3. Graphic representation of the dynamics of haemoglobin and of the standard deviation in groups treated with Eridiarom comparatively with studied groups

Evidently, the haemoglobin presents the same tendency as the red blood cells, that is an increasing tendency in the treated groups from 14.99 g/l at 3 months to 15.61 g/l at 5 months and 16.64 g/l at 7 months under the Eridiarom treatment; equally obvious is the decreasing

tendency in the diseased group from 14.39 g/l at 3 months to 12.88 g/l at 5 months, preserving the anaemic status, while at 7 months it reaches a value of 14.08 g/l, at the lower limit of the normal value (Figure 3).

Fig. 4. Graphic representation of the dynamics, of haemoglobin and of the standard deviation in groups treated with Diavit comparatively with studied groups

Evidently, the haemoglobin presents the same tendency as the red blood cells, that is an increasing tendency in the treated groups from 15.85 g/l at 3 months to 16.67 g/l at 5 months and 19.1 g/l at 7 months under the Diavit treatment, exceeding the upper limit of the average; equally obvious is the decreasing tendency in the diseased group from 14.39 g/l at 3 months to 12.88 g/l at 5 months, noticing that the organism starts to recover and compensate the lack of treatment, reaching at 7 months a value of 15.78 g/l, under the value of the control group and the lower limit indicated by literature (Figure 4).

3. HCT (HEMATOCRIT)

It is expressed by the volume of the red blood cells in a certain blood sample, as compared to the sample volume, in percentage. The hematocrit is an analysis performed within the hemogram, its value being used to determine

the erythrocyte indices: Mean Corpuscular Erythrocyte Volume (MCEV), Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin (MCH). The hematocrit together with these erythrocyte indices is useful to determine the differential diagnosis of different types of anaemia.

Pathological increases are rarely encountered, when large quantities of water are lost due to sweating, fever, vomiting (dehydration), or when the disease is characterized by the rapid increase of red blood cells (polyglobulia).

Pathological decreases are observed in cases of anaemia, blood loss or when consuming large quantities of liquids before blood sampling. The hematocrit, together with the red blood cell count and the measurement of haemoglobin help setting a more accurate anaemia diagnosis.

Fig. 5. Graphic representation of the dynamics, of hematocrit and of the standard deviation in group treated with Eridiarom comparatively with studied group

The normal values of hematocrit, according to the literature, are between 35 and 52%. In the control group this value was of 42.573 % ± 1.280 %.

The hematocrit has an obvious decreasing evolution (Figure 5), for the diseased group, from 33.09% at 3 months to 31.62% at 5 and 7 months as compared to the healthy control group, even if

at 7 months is recorded a 38.07 %±1.380% value, below the average of the control group. The hematocrit dynamics in the case of the group treated with Eridiarom is within accepted limits throughout the entire treatment: 40.15% at 3 months, 41.48% at 5 months and 42.95% at the end of the treatment (close to the values of the healthy control group).

Fig. 6. Graphic representation of the dynamics of hematocrit and of the standard deviation in groups treated with Diavit comparatively with studied groups

Due to the anaemia and haemoglobin enhancing evolution, the hematocrit presents an obvious decreasing evolution in the diseased group from 33.09% at 3 months to 31.62% at 5 months, as compared to the healthy control group. It is however noticed that the body recovers in time, seeing that at 7 months the value of the hematocrit is of 38.07%. The hematocrit averages in the group treated with Diavit are within the acceptable limits throughout the treatment: 43.07% at 3 months, 45.61% at 5 months and 44.93% at the end of the treatment, exceeding the values of the healthy control group. (Figure 6)

4. Conclusions

Results of the haematological parameters:

It is known that the values of the erythrocytes in the groups treated with Eridiarom and Diavit were close to the values of the erythrocytes in the healthy group. In the case of the group treated with Diavit, they exceeded the maximum acceptable limit after 7 months. In the diseased and untreated group, the value of the haemoglobin was at the minimum acceptable level or even under its average value, whereas in the groups treated with Diavit it exceeded the maximum acceptable level after 7 months.

In the group treated with Eridiarom throughout the entire time of the experiment, the hematocrit was above the minimum acceptable level, just as in the case of the Diavit-treated group. In the diseased and untreated group, the hematocrit was below the minimum acceptable level, getting to be a little over this limit after 7 months.

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HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE PANCREAS IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES ON WISTAR RATS

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Abstract: *The research was conducted on male Wistar rats diabetised with Streptozotocin and treated with Diavit (original phytotherapeutical product). The untreated diabetic group presented a general regressive hypoplasia. Sinusoidal capillaries were retracted from the islet region and the cytoplasm had a secretory deficit. The dominant phenomena noticed in the islets of Langerhans within the Diavit-treated group after 7 months were: hypertrophy, hyperplasia, cellular proliferation (α and β) and vascular proliferation.*

Keywords: *experimental diabetes, rats, histopathological modifications, Islet of Langerhans, Diavit.*

1. Introduction

In our research, we observed the histopathological modifications of the pancreas of rats in which we had experimentally induced diabetes using Streptozotocin and identified existing correlations between the data we collected, experimentally observing the animals for seven months. Experiments are meant to provide new therapeutic information, to serve as an alternative to the current insulin and sulphamide based treatment of diabetes.

Diavit is a natural fruit concentrate from *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* (bilberry) and *Hippophae rhamnoides L.* (common sea-buckthorn) from the spontaneous flora, obtained through original procedures that allow the preservation of main active components, and by adding meritose, starch, lactose, gelatine, magnesium stearate and talc.

2. Materials and Methods

The research was conducted on 4 groups of Wistar rats, males, 6 months old, average mass of 150 grams over a period of 7 months. Animals were injected with 4 g/100g/body Streptozotocin to induce diabetes.

Periodically blood samples were collected for automated haematological exams. The groups were composed as follows:

Group I -7 animals clinically healthy, not diseased and untreated (healthy group).

Group II -7 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin, treated with 2.7g/head/day Eridiarom.

Group III - 7 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin, treated with 3g/head/day Diavit.

Group IV - 7 animals experimentally diseased with Streptozotocin and untreated.

The maintenance conditions, microclimate as well as the food were standard for the rats.

At the end of periods, respectively after 3 and 7 months, 2 individuals of each group were euthanized, collecting their pancreas. Pancreas samples were fixed in formalin, then embedded in paraffin, sectioned and stained individually, using Tricrom Goldner and Haematoxylin-Eosin staining protocol. Pancreatic sections were examined and photographed under an optical microscope, with different lenses to enable the detailed identification of histopathological modifications occurred during the 7 months of experimenting.

In the euthanizing process were observed all the applicable norms imposed by the current standards.

3. Results and discussions

1. Histopathological modifications of the pancreas in the group treated with Diavit

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Fig. 1. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 3 months Goldner Trichromic's Stain 400 x*

In the section in Fig. 1, we can see cells containing a well-defined, rich cytoplasm, suggesting the presence of an increased secretory phenomenon. The volume of the cells is significantly increased on account of the cytoplasm and the nuclei are vesicular with karyoplasm containing numerous chromosomal particles, suggesting a significant multiplication process.

A cauliflower-like growth of Langerhans islets occurs, promoting the proliferation of α - and β - cells located in sinusoidal capillaries, pseudolobular and cord-shaped. Pancreatic acini

are also very voluminous with the secretory pole of cells well defined, showing an increased secretory activity.

The section in Fig. 2 represents the non-secretory part and a part of the exocrine component of the pancreas. We can see the hyperfunction of the parenchyma, of the glandular acini with a large lumen, with an increased quantity of zymogene secretion. In the hypofunction portion, acini have a smaller lumen, with less pancreatic secretion (zymogene), consisting of fine grains. Hyaline thrombi are agglutinated and homogeneous.

Fig. 2. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Goldner Trichromic's Stain 400 x*

Fig. 3. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Goldner Trichromic's Stain 400 x*

In Fig. 3, we can see large cells in hypersecretion. We can see well-defined vessels accompanying secretory capacities of cells. The

nucleus is surrounded by hyperfunctioning dilated nucleoli.

Fig. 4. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Goldner Trichromic's Stain 400 x*

This image (Fig. 4) represents the relation between blood vessels and Langerhans cells. We can see their positioning into columns, in an intimate relationship between capillaries and cells. There are very similar to the positioning of sinusoidal capillaries of the liver.

In Fig. 5, we can see the multiplication of the nuclei and the somewhat anarchic development around capillaries, which entitles us to say that this is the commencement of the Langerhans islet

regeneration. Also, we can see the cell division in the parenchyma of Langerhans cells, indicating a recent multiplication by great contiguity of the nuclei. The position of the nuclei in the functional parenchyma, with a group of nuclei clustered around the vessel, shows us a primary cell multiplication activity. The random placement of the nuclei in the perivascular area determines the cell multiplication process.

Fig. 5. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Hematoxylin-eosin stain 400 x*

Fig. 6. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Goldner Trichromic's Stain 400 x*

In Fig. 6, we can see Langerhans islets with strong cell hyperfunction. The nucleus of these cells is increased. We can also see groups of cells under secretory stimulation, with a vitality indicated in the nucleus-cytoplasm ratio in favour of the nucleus. The cytoplasm is rich too, with a large number of granulations and secretory vesicles, mainly positioned around nuclei. Vessels and capillaries (haemolyses of red blood cells transforms into hyaline thrombi) determine

the increase of vascularization, enabling the apparition of new vessels. In practice, a vascular proliferation is noted as a result of the Diavit effect on the morphology of Langerhans cells.

The exocrine pancreatic tissue presents enlarged acini, with a large quantity of secretion. Diavit has stimulatory effects on the pancreatic secretion, the pancreatic cells presenting a strong morphological hyperfunction.

Fig. 7. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Hematoxylin-eosin stain 200 x*

Fig. 7 represents a section where a pancreatic interlobular duct is observed. Acini are full of pancreatic secretion; the nucleus is hypertrophied with abundant secretion, with well accentuated zymogene granulation. The cells are high, the nuclei are vesicular and large.

Proportional to the lobular area, the area of the Langerhans islet appears much enlarged; instead of one islet we can see 2 to 3 islets on the lobular area. The cytoplasm is well-defined (Fig. 8), the nucleus cytoplasm ratio in favour of the cytoplasm indicating an increased secretion.

Fig. 8. *Islet of Langerhans of Group III treated with Diavit 7 months Hematoxylin-eosin stain 400 x*

The dominant phenomenon on Langerhans islets, in the group treated with Diavit for 7

months is: **hyperplasia, hypertrophy, proliferation of γ and β cells in the islet area.**

2. Histopathological modifications of the pancreas in the untreated diabetic group

*Fig. 9. Islet of Langerhans of Group IV Diabetes
3 months Hematoxylin-eosin stain 200 x*

*Fig. 10. Islet of Langerhans of Group IV Diabetes
3 months Hematoxylin-eosin stain 400 x*

Fig. 11. *Islet of Langerhans of Group IV Diabetes
7 months Tricom Goldner stain 400 x*

Fig. 12. *Islet of Langerhans of Group IV Diabetes
7 months Tricom Goldner stain 400 x*

In nearly all the sections of the diseased group, presented in the above figures (9-12), we can see a regressive hypoplasia in Langerhans islet cells, in general. On the merits of this general hypoplasia of Langerhans cells, we can perceive a substantial reduction of sinusoidal capillaries of the islet area. The cytoplasm is reduced, with a deficit in the secretory capacity.

The positioning of Langerhans cells in the pancreatic lobules remains the same from 3 to 7 months, without existing in the pancreatic lobules in a normal number. The structure of the endocrine component in Langerhans islets is

more compact, the pseudolobular positioning is faded, α and β cells are no longer differentiated.

The nucleus-cytoplasm ratio is off-balance, as we can observe an atrophy of cells, nuclei becoming more corpuscular, compact and the cytoplasmic area being considerably smaller. We can see a reduction in the number of α and β cells and simultaneous a significant atrophy of the type β cells.

At 7 months the diseased group is characterized by: **hyperplasia and cell involution, with proliferating nodules.**

3. Histological aspects of the pancreas in the healthy control group

Fig. 13. *Islet of Langerhans - Healthy Control Group*
Hematoxylin-eosin stain 200x

In Fig. 13, we can see a number of 1 or 2 Langerhans islets on the pancreatic lobule, which is normal from morphological point of view, well circumscribed, the ratio between α and β cells

being between 1/2 - 1/5, also normal from a morphological point of view. The aspect is sinusoidal between the pseudolobules.

Fig. 14. *Photo of a histologically normal structure of the pancreas*
Hematoxylin-eosin stain 400x

In Fig. 14, the nucleus-cytoplasm ratio is in favour of the cytoplasmic component and the vesicular nuclei are well defined, with uniformly

disposed karyoplasm in the nucleus mass. The acinus lumen in the exocrine side is well defined, with cells placed around the secretory lumen.

4. Conclusions

1. The group treated with Diavit

In the group treated with Diavit cells contain a well defined, rich cytoplasm, suggesting the presence of an **increased secretory phenomenon**. The cellular volume is significantly increased on account of the cytoplasm and the nucleus is vesicular with karyoplasm containing numerous chromosomal particles, indicating an **increased multiplication process**.

In some of the areas we can see a cauliflower-like growth of Langerhans islets with **proliferation of α and β cells**, positioned at the edge of sinusoidal capillaries, pseudolobular or cord-shaped.

Pancreatic acini are also very voluminous with a well defined secretory pole of the cells, showing an increased secretory activity.

Vessels and capillaries lead to enhanced vascularization so that, later, new vessels can appear, hence indicating a **vascular proliferation**.

The dominant phenomena in Langerhans islets for the group treated with Diavit noted after 7 months are: **hyperplasia, hypertrophy, proliferation of β and α cells in the islet area and a clear vascular proliferation**.

2. Untreated diabetic group

We can notice regressive hyperplasia, in general, progressing from 3 to 7 months, with a substantial reduction of sinusoidal capillaries from the islet area while the cytoplasm is reduced, presenting a deficit of the secretory capacity.

The conjunctive tissue becomes visible and covers vast islet portions. The structure of the endocrine component in Langerhans islets is more compact, the pseudolobular positioning is faded, and α and β cells are no longer differentiated.

The nucleus-cytoplasm ratio is off-balance, as we can observe an atrophy of the cells, nuclei becoming more corpuscular, compact and the cytoplasmic area being considerably smaller.

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CUTTING POTATOES AND FAT CONTENT OF FRIED SLICES

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C. CSATLOS**

Abstract: *The paper presents an important step of technological process of fried potatoes: cutting in slices of potatoes tubers. Cellular structure of potatoe is broken during slice cutting. A low quality of cutting process has negative influence on fried slices fat content. There is presented the importance of a correct cutting because it has a major impact in quality of finished good.*

Keywords: *potatoes, slices, cutting, knives, fat.*

1. Introduction

Raw potato, either from the potato storage or directly from the supplier, is processed into a white potato. White means that the charge is free from foreign bodies, the peel and any tubers unsuitable for production. This change occurs with the peeling and examination based upon the quality requirements of the processed product.

The potatoes tubers dosing determines the flow-rate of the whole line. All preceding and subsequent processes must be adapted to the set dosing capacity.

The conveying of the peeled and examined potatoes to the cutting equipment is to be done as carefully as possible.

Due to the high demands and exactness necessary to maintain standards, it is necessary to be mindful of the proportion of water poured into the deep fryer. In this case, for the adjusting of this quantity, an awareness of the existing moisture or dryness of the currently potato lot is necessary.

The stock container for the dose must be sized and controlled in such way that, on one hand, no product destruction is to be expected and, the potatoes should pass the stock container quickly and be kept moist by continuous fresh water spraying.

Refining step is characterized by the changeover of the raw, flat or v-cut potato slices to the baked crisp. The change occurs through deep-frying. The original crisp is therefore improved to the half finished product by seasoning. [1]

Raw, washed and partially dried slices go to the deep fryer to be steadily deep-fried in hot edible oil. In addition, the water from the potatoes slices

is evaporated. If the finished crisp leaves the deep-fryer, a certain water amount and oil amount remains in or on the crisp-determined by a defined moisture content or fat content.

2. Technical requirement

The slice thickness is a major parameter which has a basic influence on the different quality criterions of the finished product.

The variance of the slices thickness has to be reducing to a minimum, therefore the highest attention and precision is necessary with the setting of the knife distance. A steady slice thickness is a precondition to the processes of washing, blanching and deep-frying with a high process quality can run, to avoid moisture variations and also high Acrylamide values. The thicker the potato crisps, the higher the Acrylamide content. Hence, extremely thick crisps face a big problem, because the side coats are stressed stronger thermally until the core is totally fried through.

On the other hand, thin slices lead to undesirably high fat values, depending on the base quality of the potato. Nevertheless, it can be necessary to reduce the thickness of the slices on a low measure, to counteract the building of bubbles in difficult potato lots. [2]

Besides the above mentioned quality parameters the crisps piled density also depends on the slice thickness. Therefore variations within the slices thickness also have consequences on the bag filling amount. Furthermore too thin crisps lead to an increased break percentage. These facts clearly shows that a good balance must be found between regarding setting of the knife blade distances in the operative process.

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2.1. Product supply in a cut basket

The type of loading influences the cut quality and capacity. It must be assured that the nodules fall separated and successively in the cutting basket. This is achieved by the rotation direction of impellers. The procedure is to be performed to the installation recommendations of the manufacturer. A successive and secondary supply decreases the jumping of the potatoes in the cutting basket. No nodules in the cutting process are thereby edged out, the multiple first cuts are reduced, so that less small parts and skew slices are created. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. *Cutting machine*

The potatoes slide about in a chute in the cutting basket, in addition, receiving a twist and are taken by the impeller.

Fig. 2. *Detail impeller and carried along nodule*

The rotary impeller generates a centrifugal force by its rotation, by which the potato is pressed to the outside of the basket, collected by the paddle and is led to the cutting gap.

The speed of the impeller must be steady and be high enough to generate the required centrifugal strength and cutting strength and to guarantee the suitable flow. (Fig. 2)

The impeller blocks which keep the potato along the outer wall of the cutting basket must be checked regularly for precise stationing. All 4 edges of the blocks can be used by rotation of the block. The “working edge” may not be worn.

2.2. Fresh water addition (per cutting basket)

To prevent the built up of starch and small parts, a steady fresh water flow must be guaranteed in the cutter. The rotation of the impellers pushes the water against the inside of the cutting basket to wash starch away and to serve as a lubrication medium. It is recommended to spray the water by a hollow cone nozzle which is placed concentric in the basket.

The washing away of the already cut slices of the outer walls of the baskets with water prevents the backwater of the slices directly after the knives what can lead to damage of the slices.

For the application only fresh water should be used, because process water considerably decreases the standing time of the blades.

2.3. Dimension of the cutting equipment

An overloading of the basket must be prevented. If a cutting basket is overloaded by too many potatoes, small parts, first slices and skew slices occur. Regular overloading during filling and repeat blockage leads to pre-mature damage and the failure of the cutting parts and the gear. Therefore, one should be sure that sufficient space exists within the cutting equipment. An additional cutting basket which is used for a knife change guarantees a steady product stream. If all available heads are in the long-term application, it can come while taking out a head for the purpose of knife change to an overstressing of the other heads what generates the already above mentioned mistakes again.

3. Results and discussions

The interval between the changing of the knives in the cutting basket must not exceed a

period of two hours. The measurement of the potato slices thickness must occur directly after the knife change and between changes everything 20-30 minutes.

Suggestions for the correction values (knife distance) are depending on the starch content of potatoes and they are presented below:

Table 1

Starch content, g	Knife distance
From 500 - 450	Demand value – 0,05 mms
From 450 - 400	Demand value + 0,05 mms
From 400 - 350	Demand value – 0,10 mms

According to potatoes quality (kind, dry substance) and condition of the slices (riffles, rough surface, wedge cuts, defective slices, torn slices) the change interval of the knives must be shortened. Sharp knife blades guarantee a smooth cut. The blades are subjected to permanent wear.

The potato crisps which were produced with worn knives show a rough surface and are inclined to have a considerably higher percentage. They lead to skewed, demand and rough slices, which tend to raise the Acrylamide value. Also wedge cuts are to be avoided.

The wear degree depends very much on the cleanness of the potatoes. If sand or little stones are carried into the cutting process, the wear speed increases greatly.

If strong riffles, indentations, skew slices or increased first slices appear in the slices, this can point to worn blades. Knife fixtures, knife heads require a regular care. The pass-pencils are to be checked with the setting if for correct measure and be adjusted if necessary or exchanged.

The condition of the blades in a very active cutting basket must be evaluated constantly with the help of a slice control indirectly. Dull and poorly aligned knives, worn tracks and rough inner walls are to be avoided.

Potatoes slices are fried in vegetable oil (sunflower oil or palm oil). Fat content pending on cutting quality and potato slice thickness:

Table 2

Crt. No	Slice Type	Fat Content, %
1	v-cut	38,2
2	v-cut	38,87
3	v-cut	38,92
4	v-cut	37,12
5	v-cut	37,4
6	straight	36,67
7	straight	36,39
8	straight	35,58
9	straight	36,36
10	straight	35,67

4. Results and discussions

Potatoes slices surface has a straight or v-cut (crinkle cut) surface, pending on knife shape. A crinkle cut slice will always be higher than

a straight one because of the knife shape. If the crinkle cut potatoes slices would be thinner, the slices will broken because of the poor resistance of the geometrical shape. A thin potato slice has lower fat content than a v-cut one. (Fig. 3)

After leaving the deep fryer, the crisp normally have a fat content of 30% - 40%. The quality can be achieved through continuous comparison of the test parameters against an authoritative value

(“perfect crisp” or “golden standard”). Provided that it is not regulated the minimum point values of the quality of the deep-fried raw bodies are to be reached.

Fig. 3. Fat content pending on potato slice type

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FREE FAT ACIDS AND ACRYLAMIDE CONTENT RELATED TO POTATO CHIPS PRODUCTION

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C. CSATLOS**

Abstract: *The paper presents aspects related to Free Fats Acids and Acrylamide forming during the technological process of fried potatoes. Free Fats Acids and Acrylamide develop and their content grow pending on different aspects of frying process. There are presented possible causes which contribute to the rise of the Free Fats Acids. Acrylamide content grows pending on raw material quality and technological process parameters*

Keywords: *Free Fat Acids, Acrylamide, Sugars, Asparagine, oil.*

1. Introduction

A pleasant fried taste, which is created primarily by a molecular modification due to the Maillard reaction is an essential character of the crisps. It is developed primarily in the last phase of the deep-frying process.

Refining step as part of the technological process of fried potatoes slices is characterized by the changeover of the raw, flat potato slice to the baked, spicy crisp. The change occurs through deep-frying. The original crisp is therefore further improved to the half-finished product.

2. Technical requirement

2.1. Oil quality

Consequently significant deterioration in the quality of the oil will adversely affect the quality of the finished product in appearance and taste. Unfortunately, the oil decomposition is an undesirable side-effect resulting from the deep-frying process. Besides, volatile as well as non-volatile decomposition products form. The non-volatile products concentrate in the oil and can be normally discharged only by absorption by the fried good. Some also deposit on walls and form scab formations which are to be removed with alkaline cleaning mediums. The volatile components dissolved in the released steam. The Free Fat Acids (FFA) standard is used for the regulation of the quality of the oil. In fact, only one part of the decomposition products is collected with this value.

By decomposition progress which occurs during the deep frying process of the oil the FFA

value increases continuously in the deep-frying medium. A good production run and a suitable edible oil consumption lead in turn to respectively good Turnover (=Ratio of the frying fat discharged with the product to the content of the whole oil system) the FFA rises up to a well-balanced working condition (Steady State). This lies generally with 0,15-1,20%. Within this range, the new origin and the discharge of the decomposition substances keep in balance. A turnover of more than 10 hours is to be avoided, because already with this value the balance is shifted sensitively in the direction of undesirable off-flavours of an oil quality. If the FFA rises steadily more than 0,25%, one must assume from the fact that process is no longer under control. [4]

Possible causes which contribute the rise of the Free Fat Acids are: residue from cleaning medium or chemical additions, accumulations in the deep fryer or the oil circulation system (starch deposition, polymerized oil, tartar). Another possible cause is to lower productivity throughout, with its low oil exchange or too high percentage of small parts and airborne particles. Congested pipes in the heat exchanger because the catch box is defective and has let small parts pass conducts also to rise of Free Fat Acids. Non-ferrous metals (brass, copper) have a catalytic impact in the machinery. Free Fat Acids content grows also in case of condensation drips from the range hood back into the deep fryer. Condensation drips from defective water lock or defective bonnet isolation back into the oil is also a reason of Free Fat Acids content growing.

An abnormally high development of Free Fat Acids high than 0.5%, made conspicuous by the

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forming of deep brown colour, high viscosity, excessive effervescence and the smell of burnt material are all signs of declining oil quality due to excessive Oxidation and Polimerization.

Different reasons for this aspect are as follows: excessive ventilation of the hot oil, the influence of cooper and iron, the influence of remaining parts of cleaning mediums and combustion of the oil in the heat exchanger.

2.2. Condensate impounding basin

The condensation impounding basin is installed directly in the range hood below the steam chimney. It catches this itself during cooling of the exhaust vapors forming condensation drips in the chimney. If the impounding basin is not correctly installed, the condensation drips into the frying oil. The contaminating substances contained in the condensation would quickly ruin the oil.

2.3. Edible oil circulation system

The edible oil circulation system is an open system without pressure and exists on the deep fryer basin with entering and outlet canals, a fine material separation (Catch Box), a main oil pump, a temperature regulation system, a heat exchanger as well as one or more edible oil buffer tanks with the suitable pumps and conduit system for the filling and refilling. In addition, a heat exchanger is necessary for the edible oil cooling, to cool the edible oil quickly after longer equipment shutdowns or while shutting down the equipment.

With very low vaporisation and additionally with the exposure of the vaporisation in the deep fryer (shutdown, product lack among other things) is to be recognized as resulting in a dramatic lowering of the oil quality. To avoid vaporization the edible oil is to be as quickly as possible (within 15 minutes) to approximately 100 degrees centigrade. After a deep fryer shutdown from more than 15 minutes the Free Fat Acids content is to be measured, the sensorical character of the oil is to be checked and if negative results appear, is to be exchanged. With the help of the edible oil circulation system the thermal energy generated in the boiler will transfer by using a warm transference medium in indirect way on the edible oil. A direct heating of the deep fryers is not allowed. The edible oil transmits again the energy to the slices which are thereby heated up until in the end a large part of

the energy is discharged in the form of steam. The exhaust steam is then conducted away through the chimney as a exhaust vapor.

Every false function of the edible oil circulation system will lead to production problems and can lead, in the extreme case, to the flammable combustion of the oil into a fire.

2.4. Catchbox

In the Catchbox small components are filtered out. Thereby the oil is conducted to a filter belt. To proper run and flawless track of the belt is always to be maintained.

It is to be monitored that no slices are discharged from the deep fryer. Should this problem arise, the settings of the steam in the deep fryer, the correct placement of all armatures in the deep fryer and the free discharge of the oil out of the deep fryer are to be checked.

Furthermore, the correct steam stripping of the oil is very important. The steam regularly escapes from the oil already in the deep fryer. An incorrect setting of the steam can result in too much steam is swept with the oil in the Catchbox. This is characterised by an extreme bubble forming on the surface of the oil in the Catchbox. A correction of the steam must be done.

2.5. Acrylamide in chips potatoes

Acrylamide is a chemical which has been shown to be present in food as a result of cooking practices, some of which have been used for many years, even centuries. Therefore finding ways to reduce the levels is not straight-forward. In particular, starchy foods have been shown to be affected, such as potato and cereal products which have been deep-fried, roasted or baked at high temperatures. [3]

Acrylamide is formed by appreciated natural food ingredients like reducing sugars (especially glucose and fructose) and an amino acid (asparagine) through conventional heating processes commonly used in the food industry and in household food (preparation like baking, frying and roasting). Member States are recommended to carry out investigations in cases where the levels of acrylamide in a foodstuff, tested in the monitoring exercise, exceeds certain acrylamide indicative values. [5]

The Scientific Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) adopted on 19 April 2005 a

statement on acrylamide in food in which it endorsed the risk assessment on acrylamide in food carried out by the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) in February 2005. The margins of exposure for average and high consumers were low for a compound that is genotoxic and carcinogenic and that this may indicate a human health concern. Therefore, appropriate efforts to reduce Acrylamide concentrations in foodstuffs should continue. The food industry and the Member States have investigated pathways of formation of Acrylamide. The food industry has developed voluntary measures, such as the so-called 'toolbox' approach, which provides guidance to help producers and processors to identify different ways to lower Acrylamide content in their respective products. [1]

The 'toolbox' contains 13 different parameters ('tools'), grouped together in four main categories ('toolbox compartments') that can be

used selectively by food producers in line with their particular needs in order to lower Acrylamide levels in their products. The four compartments refer to agronomical factors, the food recipe, processing and final preparation. Extensive efforts have already been undertaken since 2002 in order to reduce the levels of Acrylamide in processed foods. [2]

3. Results and discussions

The frying oil is not only the warmth transferring medium, but it becomes, in terms of percentage, a strong influence as a product value giving component and also taste influence.

Under normal operating conditions and with 0,20% Free Fat Acids the frying fats start to smoke significantly below the frying temperature. The smoke mixed with steam contains a high degree of Free Fat Acids. (Fig.1)

Table 1

Ratio between Free Fat Acids and smoke point of frying oils	
Free Fat Acids [%]	Smoke point Temperature [°C]
0.04	218
0,06	210
0.08	204
0.1	198
0.2	190
0.4	176
0.6	171
0.8	165
1	160
1.2	154

Fig. 1. Schema of frying process

Table 2

Nr. Crt	Sample number	Fructose, mg/l	Glucose, mg/l	Asparagine, mg/l	Frying temperature in, °C	Frying temperature out °C	Moisture, %	Acrylamide ppb
1.	Sample1	1.7	2.5	428	179	164	1.88	230
2.	Sample2	1.7	2.5	428	179	164	1.89	250
3.	Sample3	2.2	4.5	307.6	179	164	1.79	270
4.	Sample4	2.2	4.5	307.6	178	164	1.80	380
5.	Sample5	2.2	4.5	367.6	179	163	1.63	260
6.	Sample6	2.2	4.5	367.6	179	164	1.88	400

Acrylamide can be predicted by its precursors reducing sugars (glucose and

fructose) and asparagine within a frame set of constants within the process. (Fig.1)

Fig. 2. Influence of Sugars and Aminoacid on Acrylamide content

4. Conclusions

Continuously checking of the Free Fat Acids content is mandatory. Should the Free fat Acids content rise above the specific limit, the production is to be stopped and the oil is to change to fresh oil and/or less contaminated oil. If the Free Fat Acids content climbs above >0,25%, the content is to be measured every 30 minutes.

The smoking point of frying oils decreases the more the Free Fat Acids content rises. If the frying temperature allows Free Fat Acids content to further rise disproportionately with the product, the danger exists that the oil is disturbed and can lead to considerable dangers for the employees and the enterprise. High content of Sugars and Asparagine drives to high content of Acrylamide. Acrylamide potential can only be reduced by a certain percentage in the manufacturing process. By knowledge of the

precursor amounts (reducing sugars and Asparagine) and constant process parameters, the result of Acrylamide levels shall be predictable.

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BEHAVIOUR OF SEVERAL POTATO (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) VARIETIES WITH DIFFERENT L ASCORBIC ACID CONTENT TO POTATO TUBER NECROTIC RINGSPOT DISEASE

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Abstract: *The research target was to evaluate the L ascorbic acid content of 10 potato samples (varieties with different resistance to potato virus Y: Dacia, Agata, Ostara, Romano, Roclas, Tampa, Koretta, Hermes) and the behaviour of these samples to potato tuber necrotic ringspot disease (caused by PVY^{NTN}). The L ascorbic acid content was significantly higher to the varieties. resistant to PVY (cv. Sante and Christian). In this case, after 3 months from harvest, the stored tubers didn't have visible tuber necrotic ringspot disease symptoms.*

Keywords: *potato virus Y, L ascorbic acid, varieties, necrotic strain.*

1. Introduction

L ascorbic acid (vitamin C) is the main vitamin in potatoes. Its nutritional contribution is about 40% of daily recommended intake (Vreugdenhil et al., 2007). The content of vitamin C in freshly tubers is in range 10-30mg/100g fresh matter (Han et al., 2004; Musilova J. et al. 2009), whereas according to Brown (2005) the average content 20mg/100g can represent up to 13% of total antioxidant capacity of tuber.

The improvement of identification's techniques of pathogen agents, knowing the biochemical composition of this kind of food, especially the components which could affect its fitosanitary status, is required for improving the quality of potato. Among the known pathogen agents infecting potato, the viruses produce serious damages to potato quality. Potato virus Y (PVY) (*Potyvirus*) is one of the most important potato's viruses, (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) (Ragsdale et al. 2001). High PVY level can cause stand loss, reduced yields, undersized tubers and reduced quality (Beemster and de Bokx, 1987, Hane and Hamm 1999). Over the past 20 years, PVY has become an increasingly serious constraint to seed potato production in the world (Davis et al. 2008, Lorenzen et al. 2006). Thus, efforts to control PVY are essential when producing potatoes for market or seed.

PVY induced symptoms can be diverse and depend on the cultivar and the virus strain. Potato virus Y^{NTN} (PVY^{NTN}) is a very aggressive and virulent strain belonging to the necrotic group of potato virus Y which causes the potato ring necrotic disease (PTRND) (Beczner et al. 1984, Le Romancer et al. 1994, Tribodet et al. 2005). Several researchers consider PVY^{NTN} as sub-strain of PVY^N and the identification of non-recombinant PVY^N inducing PTRND revealed that the recombinant structure of the genome is not a necessary prerequisite for PTRND phenotype (Glais et al. 2005, Nie and Singh 2003, Lorenzen et al 2008).

The potato tuber ring necrotic disease (PTRND) reported in many European countries has been identified also in our experimental plots of Bârsa depression-Braşov county. In the last 10 years on few varieties sporadically tubers with superficial necrotic ringspots or bows occurred. Firstly these are fairly protruding and light brown, then later becoming fairly deep and brown-black and the skin could be cracked (normally after harvesting).

The research work target was to estimate the L ascorbic acid content of several potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) tubers cultivars (varieties with different susceptibility or resistance to PVY). Another purpose of this research was to evaluate the behaviour of 10 potato varieties to the disease induced by PVY^{NTN} and to estimate the

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correlation between this behaviour and the vitamin C content of the tubers planted for the experience.

Until now, the quality of potato has been judged practically only from the aspect of cooking quality and taste, while the content of biologically important substances as L ascorbic acid has been overlooked. Increased demands on quality indicate that the vitamin C content will become of greater importance not least concerning the use of potatoes in the processing industry.

2. Material and method

Potato material

The positive and negative controls were used from the virus collection of the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov. Varieties tested:

- Christian, Romano, Roclas, Dacia, Ruxandra (roumanian cv.)
- Ostara, Desiree, Hermes, Sante, Koretta (foreign cv.)

Our researches regarding the behaviour of these varieties were done in green house conditions. From each variety, 8 pots (with 1 eye pieces) were planted. Plants were grown in 18 cm pots and were maintained at 18-22°C with 14 hour day length. After emergence, plants have been mechanically inoculated, using an Y^{NTN} isolate (Vital variety). After the inoculation, disease symptoms were observed and ELISA tests have been made. The infection of this material was confirmed by using antiserum from Bioreba (Switzerland). The percentage of tubers with necrotic symptoms was estimated at harvesting time and later (after 3 months).

ELISA test

A press with smooth roles was used for preparation leaf samples. For the tuber testing, the sap was extracted, diluted and dispensed directly into the plate using the extractor Microlab 500B/C (Hamilton). We tested sprouting tubers after natural break of dormancy, when the sprouts were 2-3mm long. The antiserum and conjugated used for viruses detection were obtained in our laboratory (Cojocaru et al., 2009). Microplates-NUNC microplates were coated with antibodies for overnight incubation in the refrigerator. The analysis was performed following essentially the protocol described by Clark and Adams (1977).

We used 100 µl from each reactivities solutions in each well of the plate (Clark and Adams 1977, Badarau et al. 2009, 2010). All experiments were repeated four times. Rinsed microplates were filled with substrate solution (p-nitrophenylphosphate) incubated 60 minute and the absorbance values were estimated at 405 nm (A₄₀₅) on PR1100 reader. The samples having A₄₀₅ values exceeding the cut-off (two times the average of healthy control samples) were considered virus infected.

Quality characteristics

Dry matter (thermoventilated oven at 105°C), vitamin C (enzymatic kit method, L ascorbic acid EnzyPlus from Loewe, Germany) were determined on healthy tubers before planting them in the pots. For vitamin C analysis we used a Spectronic Genesys 5 spectrophotometer (Milton Roy Company, USA). We choosed a representative sample of tubers per plot. The sample for these analysis were choosed from each 2 tubers (2 tubers/sample). The quality characteristics determination was made in four repetitions.

Statistical interpretation

Each set of comparable assay was conducted at the same time and with the same bulk sample. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's multiple range test were used to analyze the data. In the aim to illustrate the precision of the mean we use confidence interval (CI).

3. Results and discussions

After mechanical inoculation, about all of tested plants presented mosaic symptoms on leaves, associated with crinkling top leaves (Ostara, Desiree, Tampa and Hermes) or with necroses and streak on leaves, veins, petioles and stems followed by wilting of leaves (Koretta, Roclas and Romano). Our results confirme the former investigations of Le Romancer and Kerlan (1992, 1994) that Y^{NTN} is more virulent than Y^N strains. In most of the plants the virus began to multiply in the inoculated leaves four to five days after inoculation, at the time when the first local lesions appeared. We evaluated the foliar symptoms from primary infections in a greenhouse conditions. The virus then spread to the stem, followed by the upper, green parts of the plants and the roots at the same time.

Table 1

The frequency of tubers with potato ring necrotic disease (PTRND) symptoms

Variety	% plants infected after inoculation*	% tubers with symptoms**	
		At harvest	After 3months
Sante	0 (0/8)***	0	0,0
Christian	50 (4/8)	0	0,0
Dacia	50 (4/8)	3,3	6.6
Agata	100 (8/8)	4	8,0
Roclas	62,5 (6/8)	4,5	9,0
Romano	87,5 (7/8)	4	12,0
Ostara	62,5 (6/8)	0	22,2
Tampa	100 (8/8)	10	60,0
Koretta	87,5 (6/8)	53,1	87,5
Hermes	100 (8/8)	62,5	100

* ELISA test - 3 weeks after inoculation

** Tuber symptoms characterised by raised or sunken necrotic lesions, were scored at harvest and after 3 months storage at 4-8°C

*** In the brackets, the first number represents nr of plants found infected after inoculation, the following one represents the total number of plants inoculated for every variety.

Table 2.

The biochemical analysis results (tubers)*

Variety	Dry matter (% f.w.)	Acid L ascorbic (mg/100g fresh weight) ±SD**
Sante	21.2	22.362±0.084 a***
Christian	20.1	20.397±0.293 b
Dacia	19.8	18.187±0.156 c
Agata	20.6	15.767±0.082 f
Roclas	19.6	16.882±0.107 d
Romano	22.4	16.300±0.147 e
Ostara	20.8	15.570±0.118 fg
Tampa	21.8	15.350±0.265 gh
Koretta	22.6	15.342±0.081 gh
Hermes	22.2	15.180±0.172 i

* These characteristics were made to the tubers before planting them in the pots. Tissue was taken from tubers stored at 6-8°C six weeks after harvest. Half of every tuber was tested and the other one was planted in the pot.

** Mean values for 4 repetitions ± standard deviation. The L ascorbic acid content (mg/100g fresh matter) was determined using the enzymatic kit Lascorbic acid EnzyPlus and the protocol recommended by Loewe (Germany).

*** Values not followed by the same letter are significantly different (P=0.05) according to Duncan's test. Abbreviation: f.w. = fresh weight; S.D.=standard deviation.

The virus multiplied hardly in the potato cv. Koretta and Tampa similar phenomenon observed to the extremely susceptible variety Hermes, the percentage of infected plants being maximal in these situations (table 1). As expected, the virus did not multiply in the highly resistant cv. Sante. Excepting cv. Sante, Christian and Dacia which were very resistant and middle resistant to

mechanical inoculation, all the other varieties presented 62.5-100% infected plants.

At harvesting, symptoms could be identified on the tubers from all the other varieties, excepting the cv. Sante, Christian and Ostara. Concerning the other varieties, the appearance and evolution of symptoms on tubers is going on immediately after harvesting. After 3 months, the frequency of

tubers with symptoms was between 6.6-22.2% for varieties Dacia, Agata, Romano, Roclas, Ostara and for Tâmpa, Koretta, Hermes varieties this percentage was between 60-95.8% (table 1).

A.

B.

Fig. 1. Vitamin C content (mg/100g fresh weight) for the material planted in pots fonction on the variety (A) and on the behaviour to the Potato Tuber Ring Necrotic Disease (PTRND) induced by mechanic inoculation with potato strain Y^{NTN} (B). 95% CI= 95% confidence interval of the difference; (Error bars show 95% CI of mean).

The vitamin C content (mg/100g fresh weight) of tubers planting in the pots were very different. As shown in tabel 2, these values were significantly high to the varieties resistant and very resistant to

the inoculation like cv. Sante, Christian and Dacia compared with the sensible cultivars Hermes, Tâmpa and Koretta. On our opinion, it is a correlation between the vitamin C content of tubers planted in the pots and the behaviour of inoculated material to Potato Tuber Ring Necrotic Disease. So, the variants wich started in vegetation with high percentage of vitamin C were resistant to the inoculation (Sante, Christian, Dacia) (figure 1). Concerning these cultivars, the percentage of tubers with Y^{NTN} symptoms visible imediately after harvesting and after 3 months from the harvest was significantly

lower (0.0%-3.3%) comparatively with the other varieties. Symptoms of potato tuber ring necrotic disease (PTNRD) on roumanian varieties visibles after 3 months from the harvest of the inoculated material are visible in the figure 2. The behaviour of cultivars Hermes, Koretta and Tâmpa (which started in vegetation with lower vitamin C content) was different. So, after 3 months from harvesting the inoculated plants, the percents of tubers with Potato Tuber Ring Necrotic Disease symptoms were the highest (60-95.8%) (figure 1).

Fig 2. Symptoms of potato tuber ring necrotic disease (PTNRD) on roumanian varieties after 3 months from the harvest of the inoculated material from the romanian varieties: Dacia (A); Roclas (B); Romano(C); Tâmpa (D)

4. Conclusion

The variety and the vitamin C content (mg/100g fresh material) of tubers used for the experiment influenced the behaviour of the material after the inoculation with potato virus Y (Y^{NTN} strain).

Excepting the cultivars Sante, Dacia and Christian, wich were very resistant and resistant to mechanical inoculation, all the other varieties presented 62.5-100% infected plants. The first symptoms on the leaves have been observed on Hermes, Tampa and Koretta varieties and later on cv. Ostara, Romano, Roclas and Agata.

At harvesting, Potato Tuber Ring Necrotic Disease symptoms could be indentified on the tubers from all the other varieties, excepting the cv. Sante, Christian and Ostara. Concerning the other varieties, the appearence and evolution of symptoms on tubers is going on imediately after harvesting. After 3 months from harvesting the inoculated material, the frequency of tubers with symptoms was between 6.6-22.2% for varieties Dacia, Agata, Romano, Roclas, Ostara and for cv. Tampa, Koretta, Hermes this percentage was very high (60.0-95.8%). The samples with significantly higher vitamin C content (cv. Sante and Christian)

were resistant to PVY^{NTN} inoculation. In this case, after 3 months from harvest, the stored tubers didn't have visible tuber necrotic ringspot disease symptoms.

The research work for estimate the influences of vitamin C content on the behaviour of several potato inoculated with PVY(NTN) awaits further investigation, because the effectiveness of vitamin C in plants is often influenced by the presence of other compounds (bioflavonoides, flavone rutin and flavonol quercetin being the main effective ones).

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**EFFECTS OF *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita*
ESSENTIAL OILS TREATMENTS
ON HEALTHY AND POTATO VIRUS Y (PVY) INFECTED PLANTS
Solanum tuberosum L. (cv. CHRISTIAN)**

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Abstract: *The effects of the treatments with essential oils from 3 aromatic plants Satureja hortensis, Ocimum basilicum, Mentha piperita on pigments content, minituber yield and infection level were evaluated after potato virus Y mechanical inoculation. These treatments applied on positive potato plants reduced significantly the number of minitubers, increasing their weight, while leaf pigment content also increased. The stronger effects were obtain using Satureja hortensis essential oils treatments. Concerning the effect of the treatments on the infection level, all the treated plants with Satureja hortensis, Ocimum basilicum oils presented after PVY mechanical inoculation, values of absorbances at 405nm significantly lower than the untreated and inoculated controls..*

Keywords: *potato virus Y, essential oils, Satureja hortensis, Ocimum basilicum, Mentha piperita.*

1. Introduction

Potato virus (PVY) (*Potyviride*) is one of the most important viruses of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) (Ragsdale et al., 2001). High PVY level can cause stand loss, reduced yields, undersized tubers and reduced quality (Beemsteret al., 1987). Over the past 10 years, PVY has become an increasingly serious constraint to seed potato production in the world (Davis et al., 2008; Lorenzen, 2006). Thus, efforts to control PVY are essential when producing potatoes for market or seed (Bădărău et al., 2011; Bădărău et al., 2010; Bădărău et al., 2009; Beemsteret 1987; Lorenzen et al., 2006). Phenolic compounds and other well-known constituents of *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* plants (Family *Lamiaceae*, order *Lamiales*) have antioxidant activity (Bedoux G. t al., 2010; Petersen, 2001). They are also antimicrobial and antiviral, wich protects the plants. Oils extracted from these plants introduced in healthy and infected potato plants could be implicated in the stress signaling process (Triantaphyllou et al., 2001; Bădărău et al., 2011; Bădărău et al., 2010). Plant cells have defensive responses to pathogen attack associated with changes in oxidative metabolism

(Hammerschmidt et al., 2005). One of the consequences of stress is an increase in the cellular concentration of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are subsequently converted to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). These ROS, particularly H₂O₂, play versatile roles in normal plant physiological processes and in resistance to stresses. H₂O₂ produced in excess is harmful, but lower concentrations are beneficial (Quan et al., 2005). For example, exogenous application of H₂O₂ induced tolerance to high temperature (López-Delgado et al., 1998) and to chilling (Mora-Herrera et al., 2005) in microplants of *Solanum tuberosum*. Genetic and physiological evidence suggests that H₂O₂ acts as a signaling second messenger, mediating the acquisition of tolerance to both biotic and abiotic stresses and providing information about changes in the external environment (Apostol et al., 1998; Quan et al., 2008). Another molecule that participates in response to both biotic and abiotic stresses is ascorbic acid (AA), which acts as an antioxidant, protecting the cell against oxidative stress caused by environmental factors and pathogens. As a direct scavenger of ROS, protecting or regenerating carotenoids or tocopherols, AA is the major redox buffer in plants, and is present at high concentrations in most plant cell

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compartments, including the apoplast (Noctor, 2006). Changes in AA content can modulate PR gene expression and systemic acquired resistance, acting as a signal transducing molecule (Noctor, 2006; Pastori et al., 2003). Moreover, AA is a regulator of cell division, cell elongation and growth (Kerk et al., 1995). Considering that compounds from *Lamiaceae* plants oils have antiviral and antioxidant activity (Bedoux et al., 2010; Triantaphyllou et al., 2001) and that H₂O₂ and AA have been implicated in signaling gene expression against biotic and abiotic stresses (Foyer et al., 2005; Noctor et al., 2006), the objectives of this work were to evaluate the effects of treatments with *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils, hydrogen peroxide and AA on photosynthetic pigments in healthy and mechanical inoculated potato plants with potato virus Y (PVY).

2. Materials and methods

Plant material. *Solanum tuberosum* L. microplants cv. Christian, tested virus free, were obtained from the Biotechnology Department of National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov. Single node cuttings were propagated in test tubes on Murashige and Skoog (Murashige et al., 1962) medium, at 20±1°C under a 16 h photoperiod (fluorescent lights, 400–700 nm), in sterile conditions. The microplants were transferred to greenhouse conditions 30 days after the single-node subculture step. For obtaining positive material, a part of these plants were mechanically inoculated, using a PVY secondary infected plant from Record variety (Bădărău, Mărculescu, 2010)

ELISA test. A press with smooth roles was used for preparation of leaf samples. The antiserum and conjugated used for viruses detection were obtained in our laboratory (Cojocaru et al., 2009). The analysis was performed following essentially the protocol described by Clark and Adams (1977) (100 µl from each reactive solutions). Microplates were filled with substrate solution (p-nitrophenylphosphate) incubated 1 hour and the absorbance values were estimated at 405 nm (A₄₀₅) on PR1100 reader. The samples having A₄₀₅ values exceeding the cut-off (two times the average of healthy controls) were considered virus infected.

Chemical treatments. *Solanum tuberosum* L. microplants were transplanted to pots and after

10, 20 and 30 days. All plants (excepting the controls) were injected with *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils (ratio oil/suspension=1/100) 100µl each plant. For 7 days after the first injection, the plants were sprayed twice weekly with 10 mL per plant of either 1 mM H₂O₂ or 3 mM AA at pH 5.6 (Bădărău and Mărculescu, 2010). Controls and plants treated only with natural oil were sprayed with distilled water. Four virus infected (positive) and healthy (negative) plants were sprayed in randomized arrays for each chemical treatment, and each treatment was performed in four independent experiments.

Pigment analysis. Measurements were performed for each experiment on plants, 80 days after transplanting. Five leaf discs (about 1.5 cm diameter) per plant were taken from mid-shoot leaves of three plants per treatment. Samples for each assay comprised 15 discs, homogenized in 4 mL of 80% acetone at 4°C. Insoluble materials were removed by centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 10 min. Chlorophylls *a* and *b*, and carotenoids, were analyzed spectrophotometrically according to the method of Lichtenthaler and Wellburn (1983).

Statistical analysis. Data were analyzed by ANOVA and Duncan's Multiple Range Test and scored as significant if P<0.05. To illustrate the precision of the mean we used the confidence interval (CI)..

4. Results and discussions

The effects of treatments with *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils and H₂O₂ or AA, were compared on pigment contents and tuber harvest parameters of both healthy and PVY infected plants cv. Christian.

The changes in photosynthetic pigment contents were evaluated 80 days after transplanting (Figure 1A, B, C). Without chemical treatments, the positive leaves showed significant reductions, compared to uninfected leaves, in chlorophyll *a* (by 29%), chlorophyll *b* (44%) and carotenoids (57%). Treatments with essential oils and H₂O₂ + AA significantly increased pigment contents of virus PVY infected plant leaves to levels similar to uninfected plants (with exception of *Mentha piperita* oil treatments on chlorophyll *a* and *b*, and of *Ocimum basilicum* on carotenoids). *Satureja hortensis* oils treatments led to the higher level of pigment contents. No significant differences were induced

by these treatments in the uninfected plants (Figure 1A,B,C).

A.

B.

C.

¶ (5...7 mm)

Fig. 1. Chlorophyll a (A), chlorophyll b (B) and carotenoids (C) of leaves of healthy plants and potato virus Y (PVY) infected plant, following treatments with essential oils and spray with H₂O₂ (1mM) or AA (3mM) or water (controls). Data are means ± SD of four experiments (n=4). Columns with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test (P<0.05)

Final harvests were carried out at 90 days after transplanting. The number of tubers produced by positive control plants was significantly higher than the uninfected control (by 45%) (Figure 2). In uninfected plants no significant differences were obtained by the treatments relative to their controls (Figure 2). However, all the treatments significantly reduced the number of tubers produced per plant (by 20, 27 and 23% respectively) in the positive plants compared to their control (Figure 2). Interestingly, this reduced number of tubers was similar to that produced in uninfected plants subjected to any of the treatments (Figure 2).

Tuber weights of the uninfected control plants were significantly higher (by 72%) than the positive control (Figure 3). However, *Satureja hortensis* oil treatments significantly increased the weight of tubers (by 85%) in the positive plants compared to their control (Figure 3) The chemical treatments of positive plants resulted in tuber weights that were either not significantly different to, or greater than, those of uninfected controls (Figure 3). Significant reduction by the chemical treatments of the weight of tubers harvested was observed in the uninfected plants compared with their control, this effect remaining significant for the plants treated only with *Satureja hortensis* oil (Figure 3).

Fig. 2. Number of tubers produced by plants healthy or positive-infected plants with potato virus Y (PVY), following injections with essential oil suspensions and spray treatments with H₂O₂ (1 mM), AA (3 mM) or water (controls), twice weekly for 90 days. Data are means ± SD of four experiments (n=4). Columns with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test (P<0.05).

Effects of treatments with *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils and H₂O₂ or AA, were compared on absorbance values obtained after testing (by DAS ELISA technique) healthy and inoculated plants (cv. Christian) with potato virus Y (PVY).

The effects of treatments was evaluated 40 days after the last transplanting (Figure 4). Compared with their positive controls, with chemical treatments, the inoculated plants showed significant decreases of the absorbance values (Figure 4). Treatments with *Satureja hortensis* oils and H₂O₂ or AA significantly

decreased DO_{405nm} of samples prelevated from virus PVY infected plant leaves to levels similar to uninfected. No significant differences were induced by these treatments in the uninfected plants (Figure 4). The *Ocimum basilicum* and *Mentha piperita* oils had lower effect on plants responses to inoculation compared with *Satureja hortensis* (Figure 4).

Our data show potential benefits of *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils on the *Solanum tuberosum* L. plants inoculated with PVY. The effects of these oils

were amazing, the OD_{405nm} values being significantly decreased.

Fig. 3. Weight of tubers produced by healthy plants or positive-infected plants with potato virus Y(PVY), following injections with essential oil and spray treatments with H₂O₂ (1 mM), AA (3 mM) or water (controls), twice weekly for 90 days. Data are means ± SD of four experiments (n=4). Columns with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test (P<0.05).

Fig. 4. Absorbance (optic density) values at 405nm of healthy (□) and infected (■) potato plants inoculated with potato virus Y(PVY), following treatments with essential oil (dilution 1/100) and H₂O₂ (1 mM), AA (3 mM) or water (controls). Data are means ± SD of four experiments (n=4). Columns with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test (P<0.05).

Hydrogen peroxide is a diffusible signal-transducing molecule and its accumulation is perceived by the plant as a signal of environmental change, alerting the cell of both biotic and abiotic threats (Noctor et al., 2006). It also alters the concentrations and redox status of intracellular antioxidants, such as ascorbate (Foyer et al., 2005). The role of H₂O₂ in the induction of tolerance to stresses in potato plants

has been demonstrated. Wu et al. (1995 and 1997) observed that transgenic potato plants expressing a fungal gene encoding glucose oxidase, which generates H₂O₂ when glucose is oxidized, exhibited strong resistance to *Erwinia carotovora* subsp *carotovora*, and to *Phytophthora infestans*. This resistance to soft rot and to potato late blight was apparently mediated by elevated levels of H₂O₂. The results of the

present study demonstrated that plants mechanically infected with potato virus *Y* (PVY), suffered significantly harmful effects on pigment contents and on the number and weight of tubers produced. In general, these effects were reduced by injecting the plants with *Rosmarinus officinalis* oil and spraying H₂O₂ or AA. Concerning the changes in the leaves pigment contents, foliar mosaic (alternativ pale green and dark green areas) represents a common symptom of primary infection with potato virus *Y* (PVY). Our results show that the presence of PVY in potato plants significantly reduced the content of chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and carotenoids. Essential oil injections and H₂O₂ or AA treatments of mechanical infected plants with PVY significantly increased the levels of chlorophylls compared with positive control plants, while similarly treated uninfected plants did not show significant differences in these pigments after spraying.

Under greenhouse conditions, 90 days after transplanting, the infected plants produced a higher number of tubers than the uninfected controls, relative to uninfected controls. Increased number and reduced weight of tubers is a characteristic response to stress in potato. The virus also causes an array of symptoms suggestive of disturbances in the normal balance of plant hormones such as cytokinins and auxins (Dermastia, 1995). Increased number of tubers could be due to disturbance of plant hormones involved in tuber formation (Ferne et al., 2001). It has been suggested that a physiological balance of antioxidant components is necessary in order to obtain protection to generalized stress; however, antioxidants are not always accessible to some of the sites where they are most needed in times of stress (Foyer et al., 1994). Our results agree with this statement, since the *Satureja hortensis* and *Ocimum basilicum* essential oils suspensions injections and AA/ H₂O₂ treatments induced significant anti-stress effects only in the tubers from positive plants

5. Conclusions

The results of the present study demonstrated that potato plants mechanical infected with PVY suffered significantly harmful effects on pigment contents and on the number and weight of tubers produced. These effects were reduced by injecting the plants with *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* oils and spraying with H₂O₂ or AA. The treatments of

mechanically infected plants with potato virus *Y* significantly increased the levels of chlorophylls compared with positive control plants, while similarly treated uninfected plants did not show significant differences in these pigments.

Satureja hortensis oils treatments demonstrated a strong effect as potato plants mechanically inoculated with PVY and injected with these oils presented absorbance values at 405nm significantly lower than the untreated and inoculated controls.

The elucidation of the precise role played by *Satureja hortensis*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Mentha piperita* essential oils treatments in addition with H₂O₂, AA on potato virus *Y* infected and healthy plants awaits further investigation

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ENZYMATIC KITS (EnzyPlus BIOCONTROL) USED FOR L – ASCORBIC ACID AND STARCH DETERMINATION (PRACTICAL APPLICATION: TESTING OF NEW ROMANIAN POTATO VARIETIES)

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Abstract: *The accuracy of the results obtained using these enzymatic analysis depends on the enzymes specificity, respecting the reaction conditions (enzymes involed in), the mode of sample preparation. The principle of the method is based on measuring the absorbances of some solutions to a specific wavelength (340 nm for starch and 578 nm for L – ascorbic acid). One of the objectives of the paper is to perform a comparative study of enzymatic methods for determination of starch and vitamin C in food products (newest Romanian potato varieties). Of the advantages of methods that uses enzymatic kits we mention the simplicity of the test, the safety, high sensitivity, precision and the equipment that do not require a costly investment. The essential condition for safety testing is to respect the work conditions of the enzymatic kit imposed by the providing company (the pH and the temperature of the used solutions must be respected for safety outcomes).*

Keywords: *Starch, L-Ascorbic Acid, enzymatic kits, potato.*

1. Introduction

Due to the advantages of using enzymatic kits (simplicity, safety, high sensitivity, equipment and devices that do not require a costly

investment), these tests have gained in last years more and more land, being widely used in food industry (Fig. 1). (R. Hughes et al. 1999 Code of Practice for Evaluation of Fruit and Vegetable Juices, 1996)

Fig. 1. Advantages of using enzymatic methods (including enzymatic kits)

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This paper presents the results obtained using enzymatic kits for the determination of Starch and vitamin C in food products (potato tubers of the newest romanian varieties). The methods used were based on the use of specific kits that can identify a specific component of the food matrix. To estimate the concentrations of the tested chemical compounds were found the absorbances at:

- ✓ 340nm (NADPH + H⁺), for starch dosing (Beutler H. O. 1984)
- ✓ 586nm (Tetrazolium salt MTT [3-(4,5dimethylthiazolyl-2)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide]), for L-ascorbic acid dosing (Kunst A. et al. 1988).

A.
B.
Fig. 2 . A. The main components of the kit "EnzyPlus Starch"
B. Samples and blanks prepared for incubation

2. Determination of starch in potato tubers

Biological material used for analysis: romanian varieties of potato tubers from the National Research Institute for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov (Christian, Roclas, Romano, Cumidava, Zamolxis – organic material)

The kits from the set "EnzyPlus Starch" (Biocontrol company, www.biocontrolsys.com) used for the determination of Starch have the following supplies components (Fig. 2A):

- ✓ R1 – Buffer Solution: Imidazole buffer, magnesium chloride and preservative;
- ✓ R2 – NADP⁺, ATP;
- ✓ R3 – Hexokinase (HK) (300 U/ml), Glucose- 6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase (G6PDH) (400 U/ml);
- ✓ R4 – (Lyophilized) Citrate, pH about 4.6, 250U amyloglucosidase (AGS).

The principle of the method arises from the reactions listed below, reactions which are actually also the main stages. (Brautechnische Analyzenmethoden, Band III, S. 1982)

I. Starch is hydrolysed to D-Glucose at pH 4.6 in the presence of AGS (amyloglucosidase):

II. D-Glucose is phosphorylated in the presence of the enzyme HK (Hexokinase):

III. Oxidation of Glucose-6-Phosphate in the presence of G6PDH (Glucose- 6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase):

The method targets the following steps:

1. Sample preparation: mince, treatment with DMOS/2% hydrochloric acid, 60 min incubation at 60°C, cooling, dilution, pH adjustment to 4-5 with sodium hydroxide, 100 ml volumetric flask transfer, filtration.
2. Buffer solution preparation with AGS (R4 kit) dissolved in 5 ml distilled water.
3. Pipetting AGS buffer solution into cuvettes (blanks and samples) (Fig. 2B), pipetting 100 µl sample.
4. 15 min incubation at 60 ° C.

5. Adding 100 µl buffer solution (R1), 100 µl ATP and NADP⁺ (R2) and 2 ml distilled water.
6. 3 min homogenization.
7. Reading absorbances A₁.
8. Adding 20 µl solution HK and G6PDH (R3), reading absorbances (A₂) after 10 minutes.
9. Calculation of results: Determine the absorbance difference between sample and blank (A₂-A₁). The difference between the absorbances obtained from the blank samples is reduced from the difference between the absorbances obtained from the samples being calculated as ΔA:

$$\Delta A = (A_2 - A_1)_{\text{sample}} - (A_2 - A_1)_{\text{blank}}$$

$$C = \frac{V \cdot MW}{\varepsilon \cdot D \cdot V_s \cdot 1000} \cdot \Delta A (g/L)$$

V – Final Volume (mL);
 V_s – Sample Volume (mL);
 MW – Molecular weight of Starch (MW_{Glucose} – MW_{Water});
 ε – extinction coefficient of NADPH at 340nm=6.3 (L/(mmol·cm));
 d – light path (cm);

Preliminary results obtained are presented in Table 1. It can be noted that the highest starch content was recorded in Roclas variety which is suitable also for industrialization (starch production).

Sample concentration is calculated as follows:

Table 1

Experimental data obtained in the determination of starch from different potato varieties

Variety	Sample		Blank		ΔA	Starch content (g/100g)
	A ₂	A ₁	A ₂	A ₁		
Romano	1,252	0,352	1,097	0,326	0,129	16,066
Christian	1,269	0,353	1,11	0,328	0,134	16,688
Cumidava	1,271	0,392	1,089	0,329	0,119	14,820
Roclas	1,263	0,344	1,101	0,325	0,143	17,809
Zamolxis	1,291	0,382	1,099	0,339	0,120	14,822

A₁, A₂ = absorbances at 340 nm (average, 4 repetitions)

The poorest varieties in starch were Zamolxis and Cumidava. The obtained results were verified by other methods (chemical, polarimetric, gravimetric), recording the same hierarchy of varieties in terms of the starch content of potato tubers.

3. Determination of vitamin C in potato tubers

Biological material used for analysis: romanian varieties of potato tubers from the National Research Institute for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov (Christian, Roclas, Romano, Cumidava, Zamolxis – organic material).

The kits from the "L ascorbic acid EnzyPlus" set (Biocontrol company, www.biocontrolsys.com).

com) used for the determination of vitamin C are made up of the following supplies:

- ✓ 2 x R1 Phosphate/Citrate Buffer pH 3.5
- MTT
- ✓ R2 PMS
- ✓ 2 x R3 (Powder) Ascorbate Oxidase (700U)
- ✓ R4 L-Ascorbic Acid

The principle of the method is based on the fact that L-Ascorbic Acid and some reducing compounds (x-H₂) reduce the Tetrazolium salt MTT [3-(4,5dimethylthiazolyl-2)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide] in the presence of an electron carrier PMS (5-methylphenazinium methosulfate) at pH 3.5 to a formazan. (Henigger G., A. Schutz 1987)

In the test is determined the amount of reducing substances :

For the specific determination of L-Ascorbate, in a sample blank assay only the L-Ascorbate fraction as part of all reducing substances from the sample, is oxidized by

Ascorbate Oxidase (AAO) in the presence of oxygen from the air. The Dehydroascorbate formed does not react with MTT / PMS.

The absorbance difference between the sample and the absorbance difference of the sample blank is equivalent to the quantity of L-Ascorbate in the sample. The obtained MTT is the measuring parameter and its concentration is estimated by determining the absorbances in the visible range at 586nm wavelength.

The method targets the following steps:

1. Sample preparation: 50g sample is minced in 50 mL of 1M potassium phosphate buffer solution. Adjusting to pH 3.5 – 4.0 with 2M potassium hydroxide solution. Quantitatively transfer the mixture into a volumetric flask of 500 ml with distilled water, fill up to mark with distilled water then is mixed and filtered.
2. Reagents preparation: enzyme solution R3 (Ascorbate Oxidase) is dissolved in 0.5 ml distilled water.
3. Pipetting the enzyme solution R3 in cuvettes: blanks and samples.
4. Pipetting sample (filtered) 100 µl test tube only.
5. Mixing and 15 min incubation to 37°C.
6. Reading blank and sample absorbances (A₁).
7. Adding 100 µl of R2 (PMS) to trigger the oxidation reaction.
8. Mixing, then the solutions are allowed to stand for 10 minutes at 37°C and then read the
9. absorbance of the sample and blank solutions (A₂).

10. Calculation of results: Determine the absorbance difference between sample and blank (A₂-A₁). The difference between the absorbances obtained from the blank samples is reduced from the difference between the absorbances obtained from the samples being calculated as Δ A_{L-Ascorbic Acid}:

$$\Delta A_{L-Ascorbic\ Acid} = (A_2-A_1)_{sample} - (A_2-A_1)_{blank}$$

The concentration of L – Ascorbic Acid can be calculated as it follows:

$$C = \frac{V \cdot MW}{\varepsilon \cdot d \cdot V_s \cdot 1000} \cdot \Delta A(g/L)$$

V – Final Volume;

V_s – Sample Volume;

MW – Molecular weight of L-Ascorbic Acid [176.13 g/mol];

ε – extinction coefficient of MTT – Formazan at 578 nm=16.9 (l/(mmol·cm));

d – light path (cm);

Preliminary results obtained are presented in Table 2. It can be noted that the highest content of vitamin C has been recorded to the variety Cumidava. The lowest L-ascorbic acid content was recorded in Zamolxis and Christian varieties. The results obtained were verified also by chemical methods (Palladian), recording the same hierarchy of varieties in terms of vitamin C content of samples (potato tubers).

Table 2
Experimental data obtained in the determination of vitamin C from different potato varieties

Variety	Absorbance (578nm) (average, 4 repetitions)				L-Ascorbic Acid content (mg/100g)
	Sample A ₂	Sample A ₁	Blank A ₂	Blank A ₁	
Desiree	0,348	0,112	0,229	0,094	22,1
Christian	0,435	0,099	0,293	0,055	21,4
Cumidava	0,252	0,081	0,108	0,048	24,2
Roclas	0,406	0,118	0,243	0,052	22,7
Zamolxis	0,445	0,099	0,303	0,055	21,5

4. Conclusions

The practical applications of enzymatic kits used to estimate Starch and L-Ascorbic Acid content in some samples of potato crops from the green (new Romanian varieties) have provided similar results to other common methods. Thus,

there was the same hierarchy of varieties in terms of starch and vitamin C content of the samples analyzed. The essential condition for safety compliance testing is to respect the conditions imposed by the providing company of the kits. Starting from the fact that the methods are based on the use of enzymes, for the safety of the tests,

the pH and the temperature of the solution must be strictly observed.

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LEAD, CADMIUM, ZINC AND COPPER CONTENTS IN SOME LEAFY VEGETABLES

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Abstract: Heavy metals are important contaminants that can be found on the surface and in the tissue of fresh vegetables and can produce harm to human beings. So, this study was conducted to analyze the contents of Pb, Cd, Cu and Zn of leafy vegetables with emphasis on their toxicological implications. The vegetables were collected from farms near Bucharest and were cultivated in areas with no contamination risks. Metal concentrations for soil and vegetable samples were estimated by means of AAS. For spinach, the analyses indicated the following values: 0.070 ± 0.014 mg/kg for lead, 0.048 ± 0.010 mg/kg for cadmium, 2.864 ± 0.977 mg/kg for copper and 6.175 ± 1.247 mg/kg for zinc. For lettuce, the found concentrations were: 0.059 ± 0.010 mg/kg for lead, 0.045 ± 0.008 mg/kg for cadmium, 2.771 ± 1.094 mg/kg for copper and 6.861 ± 1.067 mg/kg for zinc.

Keywords: heavy metals, lead, cadmium, nickel, zinc, pollutants, vegetables.

1. Introduction

Heavy metals are important environmental pollutants and many of them are toxic even at very low concentrations. Anthropogenic activities such as agriculture, industry and urban life increase the heavy metals content of soils and waters and, therefore, have an effect on the metal content of vegetables [1].

Heavy metal accumulation in soils and vegetal products is of concern in agricultural production due to the adverse effects on food quality (safety and marketability), crop growth (due to phytotoxicity) [2,3]. Essentially, the heavy metal contents have become a focus of public interest since analytical techniques have made it possible to detect them even in very small traces and also since it has been scientifically demonstrated that in small quantities, these metals produce harm to human health [4,5].

The uptake of metals from soil depends on different factors such as their soluble content in it, soil pH, plant species, fertilizers and soil type [6,7]. Phosphate fertilizer application is a significant contributor of trace element, especially for Cd accumulation in cropland soils [8,9].

It is known that plants translocate larger quantities of metals to their leaves than to their

fruits or seeds [10-12]. Vegetables, especially leafy vegetables, accumulate higher amounts of heavy metals because of the fact that they absorb these metals in their leaves [7,13].

Cadmium is an environmental pollutant that presents high toxicity to humans [14]. Its presence in nature and entrance to human's food chain, causes serious damage in kidneys, lungs, bones and also anaemia and sometime hypertension [15]. Significant sources of cadmium include shellfish, grains (especially those grown on high cadmium soils) and leafy vegetables.

Lead as a well-known toxic heavy metal that accumulates in human's body through food chain and endangers mankind's health [16]. Foods such as fruit, vegetables, meats, grains, seafood, soft drinks and wine may contain significant amounts of lead. As far as it known till today, lead has no essential function for plants, animals and microorganisms. It inhibits the thiolic groups of some enzymatic systems, especially those that potentate haemoglobin synthesis [17]. Chronic effects of lead on heme synthesis have been reported, with inhibition and reduction of various enzymes in blood and urine [18,19].

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The World Health Organization (WHO) reported tolerable weekly intakes of Cd and Pb as 0.007 and 0.025 mg/kg body weight, respectively, for all human groups [20].

Zinc is less toxic than other metals (cadmium, lead) and has an important role in the nutrition and health of plants, animals and man. Zinc is a component of a variety of enzymes (dehydrogenases, peptidases, proteinases and phosphohydrolases) [21]. Generally, vegetables are rich in zinc. Potatoes, cabbage, carrots, kale, kohlrabi and onions deliver 18 to 30 mg Zn/kg dry matter, pulses and radish 30 to 50 mg Zn/kg dry matter, and lettuce, cauliflower, cucumber, spinach and especially asparagus 50 to 100 mg Zn/kg dry matter [21].

Copper is an essential micronutrient for normal plant metabolism, playing an important role in a large number of metalloenzymes, photosynthesis-related plastocyanin and membrane structure but it has been reported to be among the toxic heavy metals [22,23]. Fruits, vegetables, grain products, baked products, roots and meat products had copper contents varying from 0.2 to 4.1 mg/kg [24].

The vegetal products produced in Romania and destined for markets or for export must

follow the European Union regulations regarding safety and quality.

The levels of heavy metals (lead, cadmium, copper and zinc) were subject for many studies developed worldwide. For example, Fytianos et al.[25] studied the contents of heavy metals in vegetables grown in an industrial area of North Greece. Zalewski et al. [26] determined the content of iron, manganese, zinc, copper, nickel, lead and cadmium using AAS method in vegetables grown in Poland.

This research was developed as a consequence of requirements of European Union regarding food safety and its' aim was to determine levels of lead, cadmium, zinc and copper in leafy vegetables (spinach, lettuce) provided from individual farmers near Bucharest (Ilfov County), during 2007-2009 and sold in local markets. The need to determine contents of zinc and copper in vegetal products becomes very important due to its possible role as a nutritional or toxicological element meanwhile lead and cadmium are pollutants that endanger human health. The obtained results were correlated with limits imposed by Romanian and European legislation and were compared with previously reported studies carried out in other countries.

2. Material and methods

2.1.Samples and analyses

Atomic absorption spectrometry, a modern method with high sensibility for the analysis of metals' contents, allowed us to detect their concentrations in spinach and lettuce.

A total of 12 vegetable samples and 12 corresponding soil samples (0-20 cm depth) were collected during 2007-2009 from producers located in Ilfov County, a non-industrialized region and with no potential risk regarding environmental heavy metal content. For metal analysis, all vegetable samples were washed with distilled water in order to eliminate the air pollutants. The samples were sliced and dried on a sheet of paper in order to eliminate the excess of moisture. After these procedures, samples were precisely weighted.

The samples were calcinated at 450°C increasing gradually the temperature. The obtained ashes are dissolved in hydrochloric acid and then are evaporated. The final obtained residue is dissolved in nitric acid 0,1 mol/L. The

The calibration curves applied are linear for the studied ranges. Each sample was analyzed in

obtained solution is analyzed in order to assess the heavy metal contents'.

Soil samples were analyzed in order to assess the concentrations of mobile forms of lead, cadmium, zinc and copper. The mobile form of heavy metals was quantified by FAAS means according to method developed by Lacatusu et. al [27]. A soil sample of 10 g was treated with 50 mL extractive solution EDTA 0.01M + CH₃COONH₄ 1N buffered at pH=7.00 and then was stirred for 2 hours and filtered off.

2.2.Instrumentation

In order to effect the measurements it was used an atomic absorption spectrometer Zeenit 700 from Analytic Jena equipped with autosampler AS52 S for dilution. The deionised water was obtained with ELIX 3 system and the ultrapure water was obtained using Simplicity UV system, both of them provided by Millipore. For calcination it was used a furnace with muffle, thermostat programming, model L9/11/B170, provided by Nabertherm/Germania.

three replicates and the presented values represent the average of determinations and for vegetables are expressed as fresh weight.

2.3. Reagents and solutions

In order to obtain the calibration curve it was used Merck standard solution of lead, cadmium, copper and zinc. It was used freshly prepared standards that were storage in polyethylene

vessels. For standards preparation and also as diluent for calcinated samples was used 0.1N HNO₃ made from Merck suprapure concentrated HNO₃ 65%, (d=1.39g/mL) and HCl p.a. 37% (d=1.19g/mL) Merck. It was used ultrapure water. All the materials and vessels that were used were kept at least 24 hours in a plastic container filled with HNO₃ 10% v/v and washed for several times with deionised water.

3. Results and discussions

Analyses performed on soil samples in order to achieve the mobile forms of heavy metals indicated that there are no hazardous levels for mobile forms of lead, cadmium, copper and zinc. For lead, the concentration ranges between 1.95-2.36 mg/kg, much lower than maximum admitted level for mobile form set by Lacatusu et al. [28]. In the case of cadmium, the concentration vary between 0.08-0.12 mg/kg, this being a normal content and below maximum admitted level [28]. Mobile copper concentration was in the range 3.82-4.03 mg/kg, higher than value 1.5 mg/kg that indicate high content [28]. Mobile zinc ranges between 6.12-7.45 mg/kg, this interval suggesting a high level for mobile form of this metal [28].

The concentration of heavy metals in mobile forms generally reflects the degree of their accumulation in plants [29].

Average values of metal contents for analyzed leafy vegetables are described in table 1. The values given as mean \pm SD are means of three replicates for each sample and then the overall average of 12 samples.

Chemical analyses for vegetables revealed that lead content is: 0.070 ± 0.014 mg/kg (range 0.050-0.092 mg/kg) for spinach and 0.059 ± 0.010 mg/kg (range 0.040-0.072 mg/kg) for lettuce. The lead content is in both cases below limits imposed by European legislation for leafy vegetables. These values are higher than those previously determined for tomatoes (0.03 mg/kg) [30], tomato sauce [30] or fruits (plums, strawberries, apples) [31,32]. In non-polluted area the Pb concentrations in vegetables and fruit range between 0.07 and 0.46 mg/kg dry weight [33].

Cadmium levels were lower than those registered for lead, spinach and lettuce presenting similar concentrations (0.048 ± 0.010 mg/kg for

spinach and 0.045 ± 0.008 mg/kg for lettuce). These values were below value set by European legislation, but higher than results recorded for tomatoes [30] and fruits [31,32]. This behaviour could be a consequence of leafy vegetables tendency to accumulate heavy metals. There are studies indicating that leafy vegetables contain higher levels of heavy metals in comparison with non-leafy ones [33,34].

There are studies according to which, lettuce samples grown in intense polluted areas present higher levels of lead and cadmium (1.59 ± 0.45 mg/kg for lead and 0.81 ± 0.25 mg/kg) in comparison with vegetables grown in rural areas [35] and with our results.

Other studies indicate that in non-polluted areas the concentrations of Cd in vegetables and fruit range from 0.02-0.11 mg/kg [33] and in polluted areas the content in plants is higher (0.01-2.31 mg/kg) [37].

The copper content for analyzed vegetables is almost the same (2.864 ± 0.977 mg/kg for spinach and 2.771 ± 1.094 for lettuce). For copper and zinc in leafy vegetables there are no legislative regulations. For fresh vegetables, other than leafy ones, the Romanian legislation [38] set as maximum admitted level 5 mg/kg fresh weight for copper and 15 mg/kg fresh weight for zinc. For fruits, Romanian legislation set as safe limit the value 5 mg/kg fresh weight for copper and zinc, as well.

Demirezen and Ahmet [7] reported that levels of Cu (22.19-76.50 mg/kg) were higher in the leafy species than the non-leafy vegetable species from Turkey. Some researchers [39] analyzed copper content in vegetables and found for onion 0.36-0.99 mg/kg, 0.95-1.26 mg/kg for spinach, 0.36-0.48 mg/kg for lettuce and the value found for endive was between 0.67-0.94 mg/kg.

Zinc content in analyzed vegetables ranges between 4.126-7.346 mg/kg for spinach and 5.673-8.431 mg/kg for lettuce. Our results were higher than those reported by Schuhmacher et al. [39] (3.73-4.11 mg/kg for spinach and 1.02-1.52 mg/kg for lettuce). Demirezen and Ahmet [7] analyzed various vegetables (cucumber, tomato, green pepper, lettuce, parsley, onion, bean, eggplant, pepper mint, pumpkin and okra) and reported that the Zn concentration (3.56–4.592 mg/kg) was within the recommended international standards.

For spinach, Farooq et al. [40] found that lead content was 2.251 mg/kg, cadmium 0.035 mg/kg, copper 0.217 mg/kg and zinc was 0.461 mg/kg. For lettuce, the same researchers [40] found 2.411 mg/kg (Pb), 0.049 mg/kg (Cd), 0.851 mg/kg (Cu) and 0.743 mg/kg (Zn).

Accumulation tendency of lettuce and spinach for lead, cadmium, copper and zinc was found to be similar. The overall heavy metal levels in analyzed vegetables fell under safe range of concentration without any exceptions.

Table 1. Concentrations of Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn for spinach and lettuce (mg/kg) expressed as fresh weight

Vegetable	Element	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	Range (min-max)	CV (%)	MAL (mg/kg)
spinach (n=6)	Pb	0.070 ± 0.014	0.050-0.092	21.10	0.3*
	Cd	0.048 ± 0.010	0.030-0.061	21.91	0.2*
	Cu	2.864 ± 0.977	1.462-3.784	34.11	-
	Zn	6.175 ± 1.247	4.126 -7.346	20.20	-
lettuce (n=6)	Pb	0.059 ± 0.010	0.040-0.072	18.58	0.3*
	Cd	0.045 ± 0.008	0.032-0.055	18.75	0.2*
	Cu	2.771 ± 1.094	0.782-3.662	39.50	-
	Zn	6.861 ± 1.067	5.673-8.431	15.55	-

n=number of analysed vegetable samples;

MAL =maximum admitted level;

*MAL for leafy vegetables according to European legislation [36];

SD=standard deviation; CV(%)=coefficient of variation.

4. Conclusions

Vegetables are the starting link of the food chain, which is the principal source of heavy metals for animals and humans. The determination of metal content in vegetal products is important from the view point of crop yield technology, food nutrition and health impacts.

In order to identify the level of heavy metals in some leafy vegetables, it was analyzed 12 samples of spinach and lettuce collected from farmers that produce vegetables. The results indicated that Pb, Cd, Cu and Zn contents in spinach and lettuce were below limits imposed by

European legislation and there is no danger regarding consuming them. The tendency for accumulation of heavy metals of the spinach and lettuce was found to be similar. The obtained results for leafy vegetables were higher than those previously reported for tomatoes and fruits (apples, strawberries, plums) and sustain the statement according to which leafy vegetables present the tendency to accumulate heavy metals easier than other species.

In view of this, the estimated concentrations of metals in leafy vegetables under investigation do not cause health hazards for consumers.

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MANGANESE CONTENT IN WINE SAMPLES FROM TOHANI-DEALU MARE

G.SCAETEANU*, C.CALIN**, L.ILIE*, M.PELE*, O.PANTEA**

Abstract: A set of 72 wine samples collected during 2009-2011 from Tohani Dealu Mare were analyzed with flame atomic absorption spectrometry with the aim to assess the manganese content. The found manganese content was within normal ranges, according to previously published data from wine producing countries. Manganese content in white wines was lower than in red and rosé ones. The average manganese content ranges between 0.856-0.963 mg/L for Tamaioasa Romaneasca, 0.788-0.947 mg/L for Sauvignon Blanc, 0.621-0.738 mg/L for Riesling Italian, 0.488-0.595 mg/L for Feteasca Alba, 1.261-1.340 mg/L for Busuioaca de Bohotin and 1.231-1.354 mg/L for Feteasca Neagra.

Keywords: manganese, heavy metals, wine.

1. Introduction

Wine is a complex matrix which contains a great variety of components: tartaric acid, malic acid, phenolic compounds, vitamins, minerals, water, sugar and alcohol. Moderate wine consumption contributes to the daily intake of many essential elements, such as Ca, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Ni, Zn [1]. Also, it is a source of heavy metals, some with nutritional value but other could expose the consumer to toxic effects. The concentration of heavy metal in wine is very important because can influence the wine quality and could lead to toxicological implications. The mineral content is often used to characterize the wines by their authenticity and geographical origin [2].

Some metals influence clarity, aroma and sensorial properties of wine [3]. For example, Cu, Fe, Mn participate in destabilization of wine and in their oxidative evolution [4], meanwhile Fe, Al, Zn, Ni produce undesirable changes of aroma and taste [5]. Cu, Fe and Mn are involved in oxido-reductive reactions resulting from wine browning, case, turbidity or astringency [6].

The concentrations of metals and trace metals in wines depend primarily on the metal content in the vineyard soil, which influence the degree of metal uptake by the vine [7]. Contamination of grapes in a vineyard could be originating from soil which means that depend on geographical location or could have environmental origin wine oxidation, formation of acetaldehyde during oxidation [16] and regarding toxicological issues, (atmospheric deposition of airborne particulate

matter) [8,9]. Others like usage of fertilizers could affect the metallic content of wines. Application of some pesticides can influence the higher contents of Cu, Mn and Zn in wines [10].

Also, the components of the pipes, barrels and other materials involved in the winemaking process could influence the metal content of the wines [11].

The content of metallic elements has been evaluated from nutritional and toxicological purposes [12,13].

For humans, manganese is an essential trace element and both deficiency and excess of manganese have detrimental health effects and are associated with disease states. Excessive intake of manganese (inhalation, ingestion), may result in central nervous system pathology. Health effects caused by lower levels of manganese exposure are not well defined, due to more subtle signs, this aspect requiring further investigation [14].

This study was undertaken in order to assess the manganese content of some wine samples from Tohani Dealu Mare. The study was developed during 2009-2011. It were also determined the mobile form for manganese according to the method developed by Lacatusu et al. [15]. It is important to know the manganese concentration because of it importance regarding This research was undertaken considering that manganese have an important role in wine processes and to our knowledge, similar studies regarding manganese content for Romanian wines are poor represented.

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2. Material and methods

2.1. Description of the area

Tohani is a locality in Prahova County, Romania. From geographical point of view, Tohani is located in a downy area covered by the Curvature Sub-Carpathians and it became known over time because of the important wine-growing areas.

In Tohani area, the most common soils are cambisol, luvosol, regosol. These are soils with medium texture in the upper horizon and are characterized by moderate natural fertility.

The climate is temperate continental with cold winters and hot summers. The average annual temperature is 11.3°C and the recorded mean annual precipitation is 642 mm.

2.2. Soil sampling and analyses

The investigation was carried out during 2009-2011 on vineyard plots from vineyard Tohani-Dealul Mare, a vineyard of almost 20 years old. It was collected soil samples (0-20 cm depth) from plots where are different varieties of vine: Tamaioasa Romaneasca, Sauvignon Blanc, Riesling Italian, Feteasca Alba, Busuioaca de Bohotin and Feteasca Neagra. Before proceeding to analyses, the soil samples were air dried, lightly grounded and sieved through 2 mm nylon sieve.

The mobile form of manganese was quantified by FAAS means according to method developed

by Lacatusu et. al [15]. A soil sample of 10 g was treated with 50 mL extractive solution EDTA 0,01M + CH₃COONH₄ 1N pH=7, then was stirred for 2 hours and filtered off. The resulted extract was used to evaluate mobile forms for zinc and manganese by FAAS means.

2.3. Wine samples

It was analyzed 4 wine samples (bottled) from each variety (6 varieties) every year. Wine samples it was microwave digested using a mixture HNO₃/H₂O₂ (1 mL of wine + 7 mL HNO₃ 65% + 1 mL H₂O₂ 30%). After cooling the samples were transferred into 25 ml balloon flask with MilliQ water and analyzed using FAAS means.

2.4. Reagents and materials

All used reagents were of analytical grade. High purity water from a Milli-Q apparatus was used to prepare the standard solutions. The calibration curve for manganese is linear for the

studied ranges and was plotted by running different concentrations of standard solutions prepared from a stock solution of 1000 mg/L manganese provided by Merck.

All the materials and vessels that were used were kept at least 24 hours in a plastic container filled with HNO₃ 10% v/v and washed for several times with deionised water.

3. Results and discussions

Mobile manganese content of the vineyard soils was monitored during study and the chemical analyses revealed for all soil samples concentrations between 18.50-25.46 mg/kg. This interval expresses a middle content according to Lacatusu et al. [15].

A set of 72 wine samples obtained from six grape varieties (white, red, rosé) were analyzed in order to determine the manganese content. It was analyzed the white varieties Tamaioasa Romaneasca, Sauvignon Blanc, Riesling Italian, Feteasca Alba, rosé variety Busuioaca de Bohotin and red variety Feteasca Neagra, produced by Tohani Dealul Mare. From each wine variety has been 4 samples/year analyzed, totalizing 12 samples of each type.

The results are presented in table 1. Low CV values indicate that the average is representative for all series.

It is also important to estimate the manganese level in wines because influence the formation of acetaldehyde during oxidation processes [16]. Acetaldehyde is formed in the processes of wine aging by oxidation of ethanol, being the intermediary between ethanol and acetic acid [17]. At low levels, acetaldehyde can contribute to fruity aromas of a wine.

Manganese is a microelement that plays an important role in plant growth and its traces are naturally present in wine. Higher concentration may come from vineyard soil, equipments and phytosanitary treatments [18].

The Organisation International de la Vigne et du Vin (OIV) fixed an uppermost level for some heavy metals in wine, but there is no legislative limitation for manganese level.

The manganese content in wines could reach accidentally the value 10 mg/L, this being a consequence of fungicide contamination (Maneb, for example) or to fraudulent treatments with potassium permanganate (to intensify the colour of red wines or to desulfitation of white wines) [19]. According to Ribereau-Gayon et al. [18], usually small quantities of manganese are present

in all wines (1-3 mg/L). The average manganese content ranges between 0.856-0.963 mg/L for Tamaioasa Romaneasca, 0.788-0.947 mg/L for Sauvignon Blanc, 0.621-0.738 mg/L for Riesling

Italian, 0.488-0.595 mg/L for Feteasca Alba, 1.261-1.340 mg/L for Busuioaca de Bohotin and 1.231-1.354 mg/L for Feteasca Neagra (table 1).

Table 1. Manganese content in wines from Tohani-Dealu Mare

Wine sample	Year	Mn content, mg/L (min-max)	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	CV, %
Tamaioasa Romaneasca (white)	2009	0.784-0.892	0.856±0.048	5.695
	2010	0.950-0.982	0.963±0.013	1.426
	2011	0.804-0.883	0.830±0.035	4.308
Sauvignon Blanc (white)	2009	0.925-0.968	0.947±0.017	1.859
	2010	0.760-0.820	0.788±0.024	3.149
	2011	0.878-0.948	0.906±0.029	3.305
Riesling Italian (white)	2009	0.703-0.774	0.738±0.029	4.015
	2010	0.603-0.645	0.621±0.018	2.898
	2011	0.697-0.745	0.719±0.020	2.857
Feteasca Alba (white)	2009	0.566-0.618	0.595±0.022	3.699
	2010	0.456-0.512	0.488±0.024	5.082
	2011	0.498-0.534	0.519±0.015	2.926
Busuioaca de Bohotin (rosé)	2009	1.204-1.345	1.261±0.060	4.809
	2010	1.297-1.356	1.321±0.025	1.896
	2011	1.310-1.376	1.340±0.029	2.194
Feteasca Neagra (red)	2009	1.124-1.332	1.231±0.085	6.907
	2010	1.312-1.378	1.354±0.030	2.216
	2011	1.243-1.276	1.262±0.013	1.092

(Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation for n=6)
SD=standard deviation; CV(%)=coefficient of variation

The quantification of the manganese concentrations, led us to the following observations:

- level under 0.6 mg/L - 10 samples (Feteasca Alba, all of them); 13.88% from total;
- level between 0.601-0.800 mg/L - 18 samples; 25% from total;
- level between 0.801-1.000 mg/L - 20 samples; 27.77% from total;
- level between 1.001-1.400 mg/L - 24 samples (red and rosé wines); 33.33% from total.

For all white wines the manganese content was below 1 mg/L. The lowest manganese content was recorded for Feteasca Alba variety. The found manganese levels were lower than those found in wines from France (0.674-2.203 mg/L) [20]. In Croatian white wines it ranged between 0.287-3.00 mg/L [21].

Analyses indicated that white wines accumulate lower manganese than red or rosé wines. Literature reports indicate that winemaking techniques for red wines increase the manganese level [18].

Manganese content of red and rosé wines it is in all cases higher than 1 mg/L. Manganese content in wines from France it ranges from 0.435 to 7.836 mg/L in red samples and from 0.844 to 1.805 mg/L in rosé ones [20]. Ferreira et al. found that the content of manganese in some wines varied from 0.78 to 2.89 mg/L [22].

Literature studies indicated that manganese levels in wines from Stefanesti-Arges vineyard are in average 1.12 mg/L for Feteasca Alba, 0.98 mg/L for Pinot Gris and 1.30 mg/L for Tamaioasa Romaneasca [23]. It also can be noticed in this case that red wines accumulate higher quantities of manganese, as is presented in table 2.

Table 2

Wine	Mn content, mg/L (min-max)	Average, mg/L
White wines		
Feteasca Alba	0.50-2.00	1.12
Pinot Gris	0.55-1.60	0.98
Tamaioasa Romaneasca	0.84-2.70	1.30
Red wines		
Cabernet Sauvignon	3.90-4.87	4.43
Feteasca Neagra	0.94-2.80	1.53

4. Conclusions

A set of 72 wine samples obtained from six grape varieties (white, red, rosé) from Tohani-Dealul Mare were analyzed in order to determine the manganese content, taking into account its importance and also the lack of information regarding this metal content in Romanian wines.

The analyses allowed us to conclude:

1. red and rosé wines contain higher manganese levels than white ones;
2. white wine Tamaioasa Romaneasca contain the lowest manganese content;
3. all white wines contain manganese below 1mg/L and all red and rosé wine samples present concentrations higher than 1 mg/L;
4. there is no legislative limitation for manganese level in wine, but the manganese concentration in analyzed wines is among the results presented in literature studies.

Considering vinification processes, metals determine wine quality and have a great effect on human health and well-being. Knowledge of the metal content of wine is crucial for not only winemakers but also consumers. Certainly, because of the nutritional value of metals in wine, analysis of the total contents of major, minor and trace metals is of a particular interest with respect to quality and safety of wine.

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SENSORIAL ANALYSIS – METHOD FOR ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES QUALITY CONTROL

C.M. CANJA* V. PADUREANU**

Abstract: *Sensorial analysis is the examination of a product through the evaluation of the attributes perceptible by the five sense organs (organoleptic attributes), such as colour, odour, taste, touch, texture and noise. Used in many fields, sensorial analysis allows establishing the organoleptic profile of food products and can be useful in knowing how they are perceived by the consumer.*

Keywords: *sensorial analysis, sensorial quality, food and beverage products*

1. Introduction

The quality of a food product could be defined by different ways from a widely manner to a more detailed one. One of the most usual meanings is define the quality as in conformity with consumer's requirements and acceptance, is determined by their sensorial attributes, chemical composition, physical properties, and level of microbiological and toxicological contaminants, shelf-life, packaging and labeling. In order to manage the quality of a food product most industries have defined quality control and quality assurance programs [2].

Sensorial quality is the ultimate measure of food and beverage quality, based on determining sensorial quality, and comprises a variety of powerful and sensitive tools to measure human responses to food and beverage analyzed. Sensorial quality of alcoholic beverages is given by all sensorial characteristics like: appearance, colour, clarity, taste, aroma, etc. [3]

Sensorial quality sets the first impact of consumer with alcoholic beverages:

- role in alcoholic beverages selection;
- assess the acceptability of the beverages consumption;
- role in purchase decision.

Sensorial quality provides clues as the cleanliness, state of freshness and the quality of alcoholic beverage products. He characterizes the extent to which alcoholic beverages products answer at consumer demands through sensorial characteristics.

Sensorial quality is a component of food and beverage Total Quality (which includes also

nutritional quality, hygiene and sanitation quality, aesthetic quality, etc.).

Sensorial analysis represents examination made by using the senses (visual, gustatory, olfactory, and tactile) by qualified, trained and experienced persons followed by statistical assessment of registered impressions. Before sensorial analysis is checked the real capacity of appreciation of sense organs and accuracy of testers judgment.

She is a part required in research and food and beverage quality control (especially tea, coffee, wine, champagne, beer, butter, cheese, milk, bread, etc.)

The aim for use sensorial analysis is to assess and evaluate the quality of alcoholic beverage products, improve their quality, design and development of new products, testing consumer preferences towards products made, and other [2]

Sensorial analysis has many advantages among which the following one: requires less time than laboratory tests, does not require special equipments, have maximum efficiency when is applied to large groups of products (provided that the lots to be homogeneous). Associated with statistical and mathematical methods sensorial analysis is a fundamental factor in making the quality reception of food and beverage batches.

2. Sensorial quality of the beverages products

In alcoholic beverages, the sensory perception mainly implies sight, smell and taste. The flavor is one of the main attributes that have an influence on the overall acceptability of this kind of products.

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Flavour is a wide and complex term that has generated much discussion between a significant number of researchers, both in academic and industrial circles. Commonly, flavour is considered as a combined perception of odour and taste; however, other authors consider it as a comprehensive response, which involves not only the olfactory and gustative systems, but also the somatosensory, visual and auditory systems [4].

When an alcoholic beverage (or a beverage in general) is analyzed by our senses, each sense is stimulated and the information generated is guided to the brain where it is interpreted. For example, the colour of a wine is perceived when the visual light wavelengths reach the human retina, whose cells send a signal via the optical nerve to the brain.

Regarding to the flavour, as a combined perception of taste and odour, the sensory activation is due to chemical compounds that can be either volatile or non-volatile. Taste is perceived by the taste buds located on the tongue and other parts of the mouth, and mainly describes the perception of the attributes sweet, sour/acid, salt, bitter, astringent, hot and cooling.

The human sensory system is extremely important in food and beverage control. This is because, usually, food and beverage quality control is carried out by sensory panels that assess the flavour, providing results that can ensure the success of new launches of products and services [4]

3. Sensorial perception in wine and beer

Once the quality sensory standards were defined the optimum sensorial method was chosen. The choice of sensorial method depends of:

- the objective of the quality control program;
- the type of standard established;
- whether or not the perceptible variability of a product can be defined by specific sensorial attributes;
- the magnitude variability that must be detected;
- the level of quality to be assessed

The characteristics of a product are important to chosen the sensorial method. In order to perform a sensory quality control some preliminary steps must be taken into account, the first one the sensorial quality specifications.

The complex chemical nature of alcoholic beverages especially referred to wines and beers induce to an active participation of the sense organs involved mainly in the flavour and colour perception. Below there is a brief description of this perception and the participation of the senses in the sensations originated when wines or beers are tasted.

The main factors which determining the sensorial quality are:

- nature of raw materials (choice of raw materials conditioning obtaining the colour, consistency, aroma, taste, etc, of beverage product, and rational use of auxiliary materials can improve the taste, flavour, consistency or nutritional value);
- manufacturing technology (correct application of technology contribute to maintain quality product or net improvement of initial products characteristics);
- appearance (depending of the state of aggregation food products need specific requirements for sensorial evaluation);
- color;
- flavor and taste.

Quality characteristics must be identified with precision and then they must to be controlled. These quality characteristics can be: sensorial characteristics - identifiable and perceptible (smell, aroma, taste); physical characteristics – readily identifiable and perceptible (shape, size, color, structure, consistency); and hidden features – hardly identifiable (physico-chemical characteristics, nutritional value, microbiological characteristics, purity, safety, and other else).

Sensorial characteristics applicable to all types of beverage alcohol products are presented in Figure 1.

Fig.1 Sensorial characteristic for beverage alcohol products

3.1 Visual perception

Visual perceptions are the first information that we obtain from the product. The visual appearance reveals much about the quality, style, condition and even possible defects of the product. In beers and wines, the utility of the visual perception is mainly focused on the colour evaluation, although other properties like clarity, brightness or turbidity can also be visually evaluated.

In red wines, the compounds responsible of colour are the anthocyanidins, which are always found in their glycosidic form, called anthocyanins. The original grape anthocyanins are responsible of the initial purple-red colour of young red wines and these are displaced progressively by more stable pigments, which are responsible for the brickred colour of the aged wines [1].

In beers, the colour is a critical parameter for the consumers and it requires a careful control. The colour formation in beers, which is mainly attributed to a pigment called melanoidin, is produced during the malting and the production of the brewing must. The oxidized polyphenols and even traces of metals are also considered as responsible of the colour [3].

The colour in beers, and especially in wines, can vary substantially and provide clues about varieties, regions and climates, among other characteristics. Indeed, it is well known that the deep colour in wines can give indications of its structure and ageing. In any case, it is obvious that the colour of these alcoholic beverages will affect their quality perception.

3.2. Olfactory perception

The olfactory perception is based on chemical interactions between aromatic volatile

compounds and the olfactory receptors located in the nasal cavity.

The aroma is perhaps the most complex sensation, very difficult to be described. The stimuli available to create taste sensations are limited; there are hundreds of volatile compounds in wines and beers that can contribute to aroma perception, depending on their concentration and sensory threshold.

They belong to very different chemical families like acids, alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, acetals, among others. Because of this complexity, it is difficult to characterize wine and beer aroma in a few well-defined components.

In wine, the major chemical constituents generate gustatory rather than olfactory influences. In contrast, minor or trace volatile constituents produce a wine's distinctive aromatic characteristic.

In beers, the main groups of compounds related to the aroma are the esters, alcohols, diketones, sulphur compounds. The esters are the main group of fermentation-derived flavour-active components.

3.3. Gustatory perception

The tongue is the main sensorial organ to detect the taste.

The sweetness in wines or beers is hard to judge. The perception threshold between persons can be different and the perception itself may also be ambiguous.

Chemically, sweetness is attributed to the molecules of glucose and fructose in wines and fructose, sucrose, glucose and maltose in beers. A characteristic of the sweetness sensation is that it is often associated to viscosity.

Sensorial characteristics and attributes are evaluated using five grading categories, like we can see in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1

Category	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory
Quality Level	Exceptional	Superior	Typical	Weak	Faulty

Table 2

Characteristics & Attributes	Grading Categories					Comments
	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	
Appearance & Colour		x				
Aroma & Bouquet	Correctness	x				
	Intensity	x				

	Quality			X		
<i>Taste</i>	Correctness			X		
	Intensity				X	
	Finish			X		
	Quality			X		
<i>Harmony</i>				X		

Like we can see in Figure 2 temporal dominance of sensation (TDS) for red wine is first sweet, then sour and finally dominated by strong astringency and some bitterness.

Fig. 2 Temporal dominance of sensation for red wine [P. Schlich, Centre Européen des Sciences Du Goût, France]

4. Conclusion

In the last years the use of sensorial analysis as quality control in the food and beverage industry has increase its use. It is vital to continue the research in sensorial analysis in order to ensure the optimum results.

Sensorial analysis is an invaluable set of methods for research. Knowledge of food and beverage product variability, stability, comparison to competitor products, relationships to instrumental analyses and consumer understanding are all requirements for a successful product. Sensorial analysis techniques alone can provide the answers to all of these questions.

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BIOTECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ENZYMES AND THEIR APPLICABILITY FOR MEDICAL CURATIVE PURPOSES

A. CHESCA

Abstract: *The bio-techniques combine modern techniques applicable in multiple scientific fields. The significance of the applicability of the results obtained using the biotechnologies is a nowadays success. From this point of view, the study of enzymes and their use in therapy, in various types of pathologic diseases, allow the improvement of the patients' life quality, making it possible to heal their diseases.*

Key words: *biotechnologies, enzymes, applicability, diseases, treatment*

1. Introduction

Biotechnologies represent a vast field, with wide applicability aiming at agriculture, food, chemical, and pharmaceutical industry and last but not least medicine. From this point of view, we may assert that the production of enzymatic products by biotechnologies plays an important part in the adjustment of metabolic processes holding an important role in certain techniques of live matter processing. (H. Dellweg).

At the same time, to highlight the importance of enzyme applicability in medicine for curing purposes, it is useful to describe in detail the information on the enzymes. In this context, we believe that the enzymes are the parotid origin biologic catalysts that include a complex sequence of essential amino acids to which a non-protein part is attached, required for the catalyst activity. The enzymatic catalysis defines the intervention of enzymes in all the metabolic reactions, accelerating them by specific activation. The enzymes intervene through chemical processes in the transformation of the nutrients and of the metabolites into specific compounds using the biotechnologies in the field (S. Silver).

The beneficiaries of these changes are all classes of live organisms, human beings, animals and plants. In this context, the enzymes used for medical curing purposes represent an actual field and the modern biotechnologies facilitate the applicability of the enzyme therapies to various types of pathologies.

2. General Data on the Enzymes

As life evolved century after century, starting with bacteria and up to superior mammals or

plants, there are similar reactions of organic layers degradation. They use the chemical energy freed by anaerobe fermentation or by aerobic respiration. This way, similar compounds with high energy potential are obtained which represent a proof of the operation unit of live beings. From the approximately two thousand types of enzymes presently known, approximately fifty are highly important in industry. Among them: proteases, amylases, amylo-glucosydases, glucose-isomerase, pectinases, celulases.

According to the classification drafted by the International Union of Biochemistry created in 1955 and taking into account their activity, the enzymes are classified in six important classes. This way of classification defines the particularities of the enzymes action. From this point of view, the classes of enzymes include oxidoreductases, transferases, hydrolases, isomerases, ligases and synthetasis. It must be noted that each class of enzymes is divided in subclasses so that an enzyme is defined by four figures designating the class, subclass, the nature of the catalyzed reactions as well as the degraded sublayer.

In comparison with most of the technologic processes that need high temperatures and pressures, the enzymatic reactions are carried on at normal pressures and at temperatures that do not surpass 50-60° C. Furthermore, it may be consigned that the enzymes present a high specificity reaction and sublayer, characteristics that allow the synthesis of a sole organic compound and of a sole optic or geometric isomer.

In order to distinguish among the chemical catalyzators, the specificity in enzymatic fixing and in transforming the organic sublayer is due to

certain functional groups called active centers of the enzyme, which are coupled on the organic sublayer by means of hydrogen or Van der Waals connections (P. Pravel).

As the reproduction of the enzymes by means of chemical synthesis is possible in a percentage relatively reduced and only for certain types of enzymes, their extraction is achieved especially from certain microorganisms.

The interest in applying the bio-techniques in the production of different types of enzymes is different. In the context, the animal enzymes as the pepsin extracted of the gastric mucous of bovines and swine, are currently complexly involved, being mainly involved in biotechnologies applied in the production of drinks. Their usage in the technological processes is limited due to the thermal sensitivity of the enzyme at temperatures surpassing 55°C. The current studies show that the pepsin was extracted of the gastric mucous of certain animals as the morun, seal or the chicken (H. Dellweg).

The perspectives concerning the diversification of the fermentative processes in which these are involved are aimed at by the microbial enzymes. In the context, the significant number of microorganisms that produce enzymes replaces the relatively reduced enzyme sources that could be extracted of human, animal or vegetal tissues.

The enzymes that may be obtained of tissular extracts or of cells cultures, are rarely used, being mainly valued in achieving certain vaccines against certain viruses that cause diseases, among these ones we may mention the poliomyelitis or the measles.

Taking into account the multitude of the requests concerning the increase and the development of the active biologic products and also of the organic substances metabolized by enzymatic means, it is considered the possibility of finding new technologies, in the context. These aim at producing enzymes, respectively at dividing and purifying them, with high efficiency and low costs. From this point of view, after 1970, there were tested hundred species of microorganisms that were proven to be fit for producing enzymes, inside the microbial cells, or diffused in the culture environment. The first enzymes that were taken by means of the biotechnologies were accomplished by the Japanese J. Takamine, 1894, who produced amylase of *Aspergillus oryzae* (S. Silver).

It was noticed that the microorganisms have certain advantages in producing the enzymes.

From this point of view, the wild strain of microorganisms, which produce degradation enzymes of the organic material, are found on certain layers in the nature, which are rich in substances that they elaborate. The increase of the capacity to produce an enzyme may be determined by means of mutagenesis techniques in that particular microbial species or genetic engineering techniques, taking into account the gene cloning from a species to another (R. Scriban).

According to the studies resulted of concrete observations and on grounds of the accomplished statistics, it is appreciated that most of the microbial enzymes are obtained of aired submerge cultures, in fermenters with a conventional equipment for a strictly aseptic fermentation. This aims at preventing the contaminations risks with foreign strains. Furthermore, some of the enzymes are produced in a semisolid environment that favors the biosynthesis of these catalizators (S. Silver).

3. Applicability of the enzymes for therapeutic purposes

A current field, which benefits of the favorable contribution of certain enzymatic products is represented of enzyme-therapies.

These ones define the implication of the enzymes, by their activity and by their action specificity in remedying certain pathologic diseases, resulted of certain hereditary or acquired deficiencies, which occur in the enzymatic system.

For the purpose of increasing the effect of the enzymes used in the medical therapy, it was used the immobilization system by covalent connection to non-toxic polymers and to synthetic or natural non-immunogens. On these grounds, the enzymes are associated to a protective enzyme represented for instance by albumins, dextrin, Polyethylene glycol that may hinder the destructive activity of the proteases of the organic layer.

Also, for the purpose of using the enzymes for medical curative purposes, we may choose the total insulation of the enzymes against the corporal enzymes, by including them inside the hamates, method that is applied in the treatment of leukemia.

The use of the experimental animal samples for the study of diverse pathology represents a current practice. In this context, the procedure of inclusion of the enzymes in polymer

microcapsules is used, for experimental purposes, on laboratory animals. In the case of this type of study, the walls of these artificial capsules are accomplished of polyamides and polyurethanes that may be metabolized from the polylactic acid, avoiding the accumulation of the polymer in the organism. The microcapsules represent places for depositing the enzymes whose action is used for medical, curative purposes. For instance, in these biodegradable microcapsules, urease may be incorporated for decreasing the uremia, catalase for healing the catalasemia or asparaginase for the regression of the asparagine-dependent tumors. The technical principles take into account the fact that the global mass of the enzyme together with the microcapsule must not surpass 100.000 Daltons, in order to ensure the normal diffusion of the enzyme in the organism (S. Silver).

The implication of the enzyme in therapies may be accomplished also in their incorporation into liposomes. These are represented by phospholipid microvesicles that may penetrate in the cells of the organism endocytosis, being afterwards easily metabolized.

The Liposomes are microvesicles in which are included the amyloglucosidase that plays a significant role in healing the glycogenoses or the glucocerebrosidase. The later play an important role in healing the Gaucher malady that deals with the deregulation of the metabolism of the glucocerebrosides accumulated in the reticulo-endothelial system. The current studies show that on the extern surface of the liposomes there may be graphed certain vectors, represented by monoclonal antibodies, which direct the transport of the liposomes towards the affected area in the organism. At this level, these ones are coupled on a certain compound that presents a partial extern configuration against the vector. The liposomes free the included enzyme in the interior, for the purpose of exercising the intended therapeutic effects, only after a certain interval of time, taking into account the release speed of the enzyme that may be regulated by determined factors, in terms of the density of the walls of the liposomes or of the microcapsules. „The erythrocyte ghosts”, which are obtained by the partial hemolysis of the erythrocytes and by filling them with the intended enzyme, are used as artificial cells, which are enzymes bearer. The mentioned artificial cells are efficient in the enzymatic therapy, in the case of the diseases as the Gaucher malady and its healing by means of the immobilized glucocerebrosides.

In the medical therapy, the applications of the enzymes comprise complex fields. From this point of view, due to the frequent cardiovascular pathology among the population, the enzyme-therapies concerning this complex category of the human pathology are found on one of the first places. In the case of the myocardial infarct, the natural inhibitors of the proteolysis enzymes play a benefic role, decreasing the necrotized area and favoring the collateral circulation. Also, the enzyme-therapies are currently used in the treatment of the vascular thrombosis. The type of disease represents one of the main causes of the mortality for the old aged persons and it occurs by the formation of blood clots at the level of the blood circulation system. The treatment in the thrombolytic therapy is achieved enzymatically in two ways. One of the possibilities is represented by the use of certain enzymes that play an activation role, intervening in the transformation of the plasminogen in plasmin. Among these ones, we may mention the immobilized streptokinase on dextrans or urokinase, having relatively rapid effects in healing the pulmonary embolism and the myocardial infarction. Another possibility is the use of certain proteolysis enzymes, which have a direct fibrinolytic action. Among them, we mention the trypsin, chemotrypsin, plasmin, efficient both in the hydrolysis of the clots and also in healing the various diseases of the blood vessels, as arterial or thrombophlebitic thrombosis, thrombophlebitis, as a consequence of the activation capacity of the anticoagulant system and of the anti-inflammatory properties. If the blood vessels present the narrowing of the lumen by deposits of cholesterol on the interior walls, we may use the cholesterol – esterase, enzyme that has direct effects of hydrolytic scission of the cholesterol.

The role of the enzyme-therapies in the digestive diseases was noticed in numerous persons, especially in the case of the older ones when the decrease of the hydrolyzed enzymes activity occurs, which determines digestion disorders, especially noticed after the excessive consumption of fat food, and also in the case of the endocrine insufficiency, at the level of the pancreas (R. Scriban).

The healing of more than one hundred hereditary enzymopathies or of the enzymopathies acquired during the lifetime represents a current issue, concerning the current substitution therapy, which aims at the compensation of the functional failure of the

endogen enzymes. For this purpose, it is recommended the hexogen administration of different enzymes, with the possibility of easily diffusing in the gastric juice, where they have immediate positive effects. For these ones there are frequently used compositions of medicinal products with complex enzyme content, formed by instance of trypsin, amylase and lipase. These enzymatic combinations help the digestion, mainly after copious meals or in the case of the patients suffering of chronic gastric, pancreatic or cholecyst diseases. Other vegetal and animal enzymes, among which we may mention the pepsin, bromelain, protease and celluloses, have similar effects. For avoiding the inactivity of the enzymes by the gastric juices, by the oral administration of the products that contain enzymes, it is recommended a combination of alkaline substances, which raises the value of the pH of the gastric juice above 4.

According to the current studies, concerning the enzyme-therapy in the medical practice, there were used natural inhibitors of the proteolysis enzymes, which have effects in the hereditary deficiencies and in the pathologic activation of certain diseases that involve proteolysis mechanisms, as for instance the pancreatitis. The above-mentioned inhibitors are represented by proteins with relatively small molecular masses, excerpted of the pancreas, as the trypsin, chemotrypsin, kalikrein, tissular and leucocytes proteases. These inhibitors are administrated in fibrinolytic hemorrhages that occur after the surgical interventions, for the purpose of healing the acute pancreatitis, of the bacterial endotoxic shock, of the allergic reactions, of the mechanic and thermal traumas or of the inflammatory or degenerative articular diseases.

A distinct field of the substitution therapy is represented by the lysosomal maladies. Among these ones there are registered the mucopolysaccharidosis, glycogenoses and the lipidosis, diseases that are treated by the intravenous administration of certain enzymes that are absent in the normal metabolic activity. The difficulties concerning this type of treatment consist in the rapid elimination of the enzymes of the blood flux, their capture in the liver where these ones are catabolized, and also the impermeability of the hematoencephalic barrier

which hinders the passage of the enzymes in the lysosomes of the neurons (P. Pravel).

A specific field of applicability of the biotechnologies with enzymes is represented by paraclinical investigations, which are carried on in the sixth pregnancy week, by means of the restriction enzymes. These may provide very accurate information, concerning the possibility of the newborn baby of bearing certain defective genes. Furthermore, the paraclinical investigation manners allow the reduction of the percentage of the viable newborn babies is depicted with a malformation or with a hereditary disease.

In oncology, the enzymes used for ensuring the quality of the patients' life, are represented in most of the cases by diverse proteases, nucleases and mucopolysaccharidosis that present direct lithic actions on the neoplastic tissues. Also, in the cancer therapy it is described the use of the enzymes that participate to the catabolism of the folic acid and of the folic coenzyme. The most efficient enzyme in degrading the folic acid and its derivatives, is the G carboxypeptidase, playing a significant anti-tumor role. Furthermore, it is well-known that the Methotrexate, inhibitor of the dihydrofolate - reductase, is a cytotoxic playing an efficient antineoplastic role, being also a great immunedepressive having an antipholic action, inhibiting the synthesis of the nucleic acids. It is used as a palliative medicine, in diverse forms of neoplasm, with different localizations. Its high toxicity imposes certain reserves and even usage restrictions, fact that offers an ample opening, concerning the opportunity of applying the G carboxypeptidase for therapeutic purposes.

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STUDIES CONCERNING COLLOIDAL STABILITY'S BEER USING ABSORPTION METHODS

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Abstract: So as to ascertain a higher stability between 6÷12 months, it is necessary that breweries perform the colloidal stability of beer. This work shows own research upon colloidal stability improvement by means of two stabilizing substances' addition bentonite and silica gel into the beer as finished product. Also, it was observed the influence of those substances upon the beer's sensorial features.

Keywords: beer's stability, absorption, stabilizing agents

1.Introduction

Both the continuous increase in beer production and consumers' trend to keep beer at a different temperature than the common one (8÷10°C) impose the obtainment of some beers having higher stability.

As it is known, beer stability is quite limited. The storage period for limpidity is shorter than 6 weeks, and depends on the following factors: absolute quantity and the structure of the colloidal substances having proteic, polyphenolic and polysaccharide origins existing in the beer, that are responsible in the set up of muddiness; substances' quantity in beer, which have catalytic actions upon the muddiness' setting (oxygen and heavy metals), or slow actions (reductionists); pasteurization, transport and storage conditions (influences of temperature, agitation and light). The muddiness' appearance is often accompanied by taste changes of beer; thus, owing to the crossing of some proteins into insoluble aspect has depreciated upon beer fulfillment and could lead to "proteins" uncomfortable taste, while owing to the polyphenols' polymerization the beer could get a rough taste. The causes getting the beer fulfillment's loss can have colloidal or biological origins. Beer stability depends on the concordance of these two aspects, so that a beer is initially stable from colloidal standpoint, and it loses this feature later simultaneously with the appearance of biological origin muddiness and reversing [2, 3, 4].

In a large measure taste stability depends on colloidal and biological one, and the factors leading to their improvement have a positive influence upon the taste stability, too. Among factors having influences upon the beer's colloidal stability it is mentioned:

- Barley's quality; among barley's components the most important for beer stability are especially the proteic and polyphenolic substances which are long afterwards forerunners for the muddiness from the beer;
- Malt solubility in the germination; the richest malts and the intensely proteolytic soluble one to germination supply of beer wort with higher content of nitrogen substance during germination, that leads to color intensification, foam, taste and colloidal stability's depreciation;
- Dry temperature of the malt; higher dry temperatures for the malt produce on one hand an intensive coagulation of macromolecular proteins, and an intensively inactivation of proteolytic enzymes on the other hand;
- Malt's crushing procedure;
- Mashing-saccharifying procedure applied in the mashing temperatures' conditions used;
- Hop's quality and decoction conditions of beer wort; a short standing decoction of wort only by 30 minutes depreciates beers' colloidal stability, their muddiness trending to be about two times higher than that for a 90 minutes-long fermentation;

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- Cooling and clearing procedures of used beer wort;
- Fermentation and maturation conditions; for instance, fermentation at higher temperatures result in a faster decreasing of pH, and a more intensive proteic fractions' separation from beer. Thus, the colloidal stability is improved, but the foam and fulfillment of the beer is decreased;
- Filtration and pasteurization of beer; beer's pasteurization having as main target the biological stability of it, producing colloidal stability's depreciation or even some "pasteurizing" muddiness.

So as to ascertain a higher colloidal stability between 6÷12 months it is necessary the colloidal stability of the beer. Colloidal stabilizing methods of beer consists of two groups:

- Absorption methods (bentonites, silica gels, polyamides and polyvinylpyrrolidones, active carbon), which absorb proteic, polyphenolic fractions and other substances from beer;
- Chemical methods, which act on precipitating reaction of some muddiness forerunner's fractions (gelatin, tannin, formaldehyde), and the depreciation enzyme reactions of macromolecular fractions leading to muddiness' appearance (proteolytic enzymes, glucanases), or these can act on diminishing beer's pH (SO₂, ascorbic acid, natural reductionists obtained from malt).

All these stabilizing substances used, are insoluble to beer and they can be eliminated from beer by filtrating after their stabilizing actions, or even used as filtrating auxiliary material. Owing to these advantages there has been already found a wide spreading usage, even though the countries' standards do not permit strain substances into beer production. This paper observed colloidal stability's improvement of the beer by addition of bentonites and silica gels into finished product.

2. Materials and methods

For the experiments was used blonde beer samples obtained in the laboratory conditions, and were achieved in the filtration section from brewery of Suceava, using beer samples filtrated before the bottling production phase. As stabilizing agents were used:

- Bentonites – aluminum silicates having adsorption action, especially for the proteic fractions with molecular weight more than

4600 or even for some fractions having lower molecular weight;

- Silica gels – synthetic compound on the basis of silicic acid having adsorption action upon proteic fractions with molecular weight more than 12000 value [1, 5].

According to Romanian standard method, the bottled beer is kept into thermostat at 20°C, no agitation, and the days' number starts count from the bottling day of beer till the day when the limpidity fails or some sediment appears. That day's number means the beer stability.

In the investigation of beer's colloidal stability was used the cooling "compelled" method and the warming one (0/40/0°C), too. This method permits a faster determination for the colloidal stability of the beer foreign the muddiness appearance by the alternative maintaining of the beer at 0°C and 40°C for 24 hours, thus establishing the days' number until muddiness appears. An estimate for the beer's stability depending on day's number is done as following:

- Less 1 day – low stability;
- 1÷2 days – satisfactory stability;
- 2÷5 days – very-good stability.

The stability on 0/40/0°C can be transformed into foreseeable stability of the beer (for instance, the determined one by the standard method) by means of the formula:

Beer's stability (days) = stability on 0/40/0°C (days) x 10

(1)

As analysis methods, were used:

- Color of beer – observing of view comparison of the analyzed sample's color with the iodine solution's color having a known concentration;
- pH of beer – using the electrometric method, by means of a laboratory pH-meter;
- Foam stability – using the number of times measuring for persistent foam, starting from the moment when beer touches the tasting glass until it totally vanishes;
- Stability of beer – using the cooling and warming "compelled" method.

3. Results and discussions

The beer samples treated with stabilizing agents have been alternatively kept at 0°C and 40°C temperatures until the moment beer's stability was lost. After that, it was investigated the performed treatment's efficiency making the organoleptic and physico-chemical features of the treated beer samples in comparison with a control

sample, too. Using the bentonite (BENTOPUR) following experimental results, shown in Table 1. as colloidal stabilizer there were obtained the

Table 1

The bentonite's influence upon beer's colloidal stability

Sample number	Bentonite quantity [g/hL]	Physico-chemical indicators			
		Color [mL/I ₂ 0.1N]	Foam's stability [sec.]	pH	Beer's stability [days]
1	-	1.5	130	4.35	1
2	30	1.4	128	4.30	4
3	50	1.4	129	4.40	5
4	70	1.3	128	4.29	7
5	90	1.1	122	4.25	13
6	110	1.0	123	4.38	20
7	130	0.98	120	4.45	28
8	170	0.95	117	4.50	32
9	200	0.85	108	4.30	40
10	220	0.83	97	4.35	41

Using the silica gel (SILICALIT) as colloidal stabilizer, there were obtained the experimental results of Table 2.

case of the bentonite addition. This stabilizing substance has a smaller influence on the sensorial features of beer, than the silica gel addition.

It is observed that to the same added stabilizing substance's dose the beer's color is lighter for the

Table 2

The silicagel's influence upon beer's colloidal stability

Sample number	Silicagel quantity [g/hL]	Physico-chemical indicators			
		Color [mL/I ₂ 0.1N]	Foam's stability [sec.]	pH	Beer's stability [days]
1	-	1.5	130	4.35	1
2	30	1.5	128	4.32	4
3	50	1.5	129	4.40	6
4	70	1.4	127	4.29	7
5	90	1.3	127	4.25	12
6	110	1.3	125	4.37	21
7	130	1.2	126	4.40	27
8	170	1.0	123	4.53	33
9	200	0.95	122	4.27	37
10	220	0.95	124	3.90	15

For the analyzed beer samples, the foam stability has presented dose values, exception being the beer samples having bentonite dose increased to 200÷220 g/hL beer, which registered the lowest values of foam stability (fig. 2). The performed calculus for beer's foreseeable stability estimated beer's stability depending on the day's number.

The graph (fig. 1) shows that bentonite usage as stabilizing agent leads to a very good stability for samples 8, 9 and 10. Using silica gel, it was obtained a very good stability for samples 8 and 9, the increase of silica gel dose to 220 g/hL leading to the depreciation of beer's stability.

Fig.1. The influence of the stabilizing substances upon beer's stability

4. Conclusions

The increase of silica gel doses from 30 to 220 g/hL has improved beer's colloidal stability, but its sensorial features (color, foam stability)

depreciated. When the bentonite doses increase from 30 to 220 g/hL, beer's color becomes lighter and the sensorial features are almost the same.

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TYPES OF PECTIN FOR THE MEDICAL-PROPHYLACTIC NUTRITION AND MODERN APPROACH TO DECISION OF TASK AT THE CHOICE OF STABILIZING AGENT BY A PRODUCER

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Abstract: *The types of pectin are offered for the medical-prophylactic nutrition and modern approach to decision of task at the choice of stabilizing agent by a producer.*

Keywords: *pectin, medical-prophylactic nutrition, toxic metals, radionuclide, stabilizing agent.*

The nutrition of modern man during the last decades changed considerably. Predominance of the refined products on a background the insufficient receipt in the organism of food fibers registers in a food ration, micro- and macroelements, and vitamins [1,2,3]. That is why the problem of optimization of nutrition of man remains actual and presently.

Attention to the problem of correct nutrition increases both from the side of different layers of population and from the side of scientific specialists of state organs and international organizations.

The special place in the rational nutrition of man is taken to the indigestible carbohydrates, i.e. to structural polysaccharides of vegetable origin – food fibers. They create sense of satiation and reduce consumption of energy; the motive function of intestine, jelly-producing, is stimulated; speed of suction of glucose is changed from an intestine; the level of cholesterol is diminished in a blood; positively influence on intestinal microflora [4,5,6].

One of representatives of food fibers is pectin which behaves to the compound carbohydrates and there is natural prebiotic (antibiotic of natural origin).

Pectin is a complex carbohydrate, which is found both in the cell walls of plants, and between the cell walls, helping to regulate the flow of water in between cells and keeping them rigid. You'll note some plants begin to lose part of this complex carbohydrate as they age. Apples left out too long get soft and mushy as pectin diminishes. When apples are just ripe, they have a firm and crisp texture, mainly due to the

presence of pectin. Pectin is in some garden trucks in a quantity to 1% from mass of fruit. The traditional fruit sources of pectin are apples, red currant. Usually 75-80% of pectin's are in the indigestible form of protopectin, from which the mastered form of pectin's turns out in the process of hydrolysis. For example, subjecting apples to thermal treatment in the two-bit of water, is multiplied the amount of the mastered pectin in 2-3 times.

The content of pectin in different food stuffs is representing in the table.

Pectin absorbs lead from your blood through your gut so the lead won't cause damage to your brain, heart and other soft organs or deposit in your bones. Pectin might help people with neurological damage from lead exposure. Lead exposure also causes colon cancer so pectin might help to prevent colon cancer.

The basic role of pectin's consists in suppression of processes of fermentation in an organism, fastening and destroying of salts of heavy metals and radionuclide. That is why there is the necessity of increase of production volumes of food products with pectin as natural detoxicants, which link and

destroy from an organism the foreign matters and promote unspecific resistance of organism.

Table.1. Contents of pectin in some food stuffs

Amount	Food products
Very large	Bran's a wheat, beans, currant, oat grouts, nuts, dates, strawberry, fig, whortleberry, cranberry, raspberry,

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	raisin, mountain ash, gooseberry, black plum, dried apricots
Large (1-2,0)	Grouts are the buckwheat, pearl, made of ground barley, oat flakes «Hercules», peas, potato, carrot, cabbage of, a pea is green, egg-plants, a pepper is sweet, pumpkin, sorrel, quince, orange, lemon, cowberry, mushrooms are fresh
Moderate (0,6-0,9)	A bread rye, millet, grouts are corn, a bow is green, cucumbers, beet, tomatoes, garden radish, a colored cabbage, melon, apricots, pear, peaches, apples, vine, bananas, mandarins
Very small (0,1-0,2)	Bread a wheat from the flour of top grade 1st and, farina, macaronis, baking

Pectins are mainly used as gelling agents, but can also act as thickener, water binder and stabilizer. Low methoxyl pectins (< 50% esterified) form thermoreversible gels in the presence of calcium ions and at low pH (3 - 4.5) whereas high methoxyl pectins rapidly form thermally irreversible gels in the presence of sufficient (for example, 65% by weight) sugars such as sucrose and at low pH (< 3.5); the lower the methoxyl content, the slower the set. The degree of esterification can be (incompletely) reduced using commercial pectin methylesterase, leading to a higher viscosity and firmer gelling in the presence of Ca²⁺ ions. Highly (2-O- and/or 3-O-galacturonic acid backbone) acetylated pectin from sugar beet is reported to gel poorly but have considerable emulsification ability due to its more hydrophobic nature, but this may be due to associated protein impurities [7,8,9].

Due to its complexogenesis, jelly-producing, to emulsion properties pectin's are used in production of pastry, canning wares, medical preparations, in baking of bread, medical-prophylactic nutrition. It is also set that bringing in the dough of pectin's influences on the

biological, colloid and microbiological processes of preparation of test [10].

Due to the special physical and chemical properties pectin influences for the term of storage of freshness of bread, cakes, baking, biscuits, cake Researches in this region are shown, that it is a process goes slower almost in 2 times.

Theoretical researches were shown, that pectin's can be effectively used for treatment and prophylaxis of diabetes mellitus that serves as foundation for development on the basis of these sources of diabetic products for correction of carbohydrate exchange.

Also the pectin matters are instrumental in the reliable decline of level of radionuclide in the organism of man, therefore flour pastry wares with pectin can be recommended for including in the rations of nutrition of persons resident in ecologically unfavorable regions.

Pectin's possessing high ability of complexogenesis brings over to itself particular interest for the use for the prophylactic and clinical nutrition in the conditions of ecological contamination.

In formation of medical-prophylactic nutrition with addition of pectin there were two basic directions. First from them is characterize by the receipt of traditional food products (fruit jellies, jelly, juices, drinks and other). Here limitation of quantity and physical and chemical indexes of pectin execute simultaneous technological functions of thickness, jellies, and stabilizer. In this case the task of concordance of technological properties and compounding amount of pectin with his day's dose and necessary physical and chemical indexes as long as concrete efficiency is extraordinarily complicated and, as a rule, is decided in harm to medical-prophylactic properties of preparation [11,12,13,14].

The second direction includes medical-prophylactic products not possessing taste dignities and being powdery and tablets preparations that allow fully eliminating the lacks of the first direction.

In the products of both directions as basis the ingredients of vegetable origin are used: juices, purees, pulp of garden-stuffs and vegetables, medical plants and other

The choice of raw material is conditioned by his vitamin-cationic composition, common requirements of utility of the used garden-stuffs and vegetables, and medical property of medical plants. Criteria of estimation of compatibility of raw material with a pectin and influence on his

efficiency as a medical-prophylactic mean are not developed.

The purpose of the conducted researches consisted in development of criteria of estimation of vegetable raw material for the medical-prophylactic nutrition with a pectin, intended for destroying from the organism of toxic metals and radionuclide.

As a result of the conducted experiments as evaluated by co-operation of cationes of toxic metals with pectin in water environments, depending on physical and chemical indexes and pH, the perspective types of pectin were exposed and a maiden attempt to form the criteria of assessment of vegetable raw material is done.

For research were taken high- and low-molecular pectin's (degree of etherification according to 57 and 37%), and also fresh fruit and vegetable juices (raspberry, cherry, pepper, cheap restaurants, carrot, tomatoes) and water extractions of medical plants (grass of st-john's-wort, flowers of calendula, bark of oak, garden-stuffs of wild rose). The selection of raw material is conducted on the basis of results of the researches became before, which from the experiment raw material resulting in the sharp decline of ability of pectin to link cationes of lead was eliminated in obedience to (pumpkin, seabuckthorn, apricot, peach).

Ability of pectin to link cationic of lead in foregoing juices and extractions is explored by the method of differential polarography on the wave of renewal of cationes of lead on a mercury dropping electrode (background KCl, 0,1M). Absence of polarography activity of the explored pectin's, components of juices and water extractions in the explored region of potentials is set in the preliminary experiments.

Influencing of components of juices was assessed on the difference of heights of wave of cationes of lead in presence pectin and in the setting of juices and water extractions.

Determination of polyphenols in vegetable raw material is conducted by a photocolometric method by the Foly-on-Cheokal'teu reagent.

Researches are performed at molar correlations of pectin and lead 1:1 and 1,5:1.

The degree of fastening of lead in the explored objects was determined as change in relation to fastening of lead by pectin in water solution, accepted after 100%.

Obviously, that our results of fastening of lead reflect the integral influencing of components of vegetable raw material.

Research of influencing of maintenance of polyphenol in raw material on the degree of fastening of lead (fig. 1) showed that it had of the same type character for both types of pectin.

So, at low maintenance of polyphenol (to 100 mg/l) and correlation of pectin and lead 1:1, there is sharp growing of degree of fastening, thus it is the increase substantial for low-molecular pectin, however it does not correlate with the change of degree of him etherification. It is possible to suppose that in this case pectin's and polyphenols do not co-operate or small co-operate with each other, abandoning free communications, which their co-operation with a lead is on. It is known that fastening of metals by pectin's take place due to substitution of atom of hydrogen of free carboxyl groups. Polyphenols possess a capacity for substitution of hydrogen of hydroxyl group on a metal.

Further growth of maintenance of polyphenols (more than 100 mg/l) results in the sharp decline of degree of fastening of lead (till about the level of fastening by his pectin in a water environment). The competitiveness of process of co-operation of pectin-polyphenols rises, results what diminishment of ability and pectin's and polyphenols to link lead.

Fig. 1 Influence of concentration of polyphenols (C) on degree of linkage of lead: 1 - high etheriphic pectin at molar a parity pectin:lead 1:1; 2 - low methylene pectin at molar a parity pectin:lead 1:1; 3,4 - high etheriphic pectin and low methylene at molar a parity pectin:lead 1,5:1.

A similar effect is observed at growth of maintenance of pectin (curve 3, 4), however fastening of lead at low maintenance of polyphenols considerably less. Thus the degree of fastening small depends on maintenance of polyphenols on both types of pectin.

Research of influencing of pH showed that regardless of type of pectin mechanism of fastening of lead different at maintenance of polyphenols less and more than 100 mg/l (fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Connecting ability of pectin (L) depending on p H

In first case growth of pH causes linear change of degree of fastening. The increase of pH results in the increase of fastening of lead by a low-methylene pectin, that shows the primary fastening of cationes by carboxyl' groups. Growth of pH, as is generally known, multiplies dissociation of pectin on carboxyl' groups and, as a result, capacity of them for an exchange on the ions of metals. The deposit of ionic co-operations in this case is great enough. Weakening of acid properties of high-etherification pectin results in the increase of competitiveness of process of fastening of metal by the hydroxyl groups of polyphenols, in this connection, fastening depending on pH takes place in retrograde. Presumably, stake of the lead linked polyphenols, which are more weak acids as compared to pectin, higher, than in presence low-methylene pectin.

Blocking of reactionary groups in particular carboxyl, at the increase of maintenance polyphenols results in the decline influences of pH on the process of fastening of pectin, and only at p H4 (curve 2) or p H5 (curve 1) capacity for fastening a few is increased. Presumably, at the value of pH in a range a 3-4 stake of fastening of cationes of lead by carboxyl' groups is comparatively small and begins to be increased only at p H5.

The got results allow doing next conclusions.

1. Polyphenols of fruit and vegetables are co-operating with pectin, having influence on the degree of fastening of metals.
2. At maintenance of polyphenols higher 100 mg/l they do not influence on the degree of fastening of lead. A polarography method can be recommended used for the estimation of vegetable raw material for medical-prophylactic nutrition stuffs with pectin.
3. The developed criterion of degree of fastening of lead reflects ability of pectin to link cationes of lead in this concrete environment. A criterion can be successfully applied for estimation of vegetable raw material as basis of medical-prophylactic food stuffs during intoxication by heavy metals and radionuclides.

Presently there is a new approach to the decision of tasks at the choice of stabilizing agent by a producer.

For giving to the product of the required original appearance, properties and consistency it is necessary correctly to walk up to this problem. About pectin's already it is much written and said. To our producers, sure, technology of their application in practice is interesting, in production of different products with a different amount of stable types of pectin's. Preparation of product, on the face of it, seems very simple, however at producers is here present row of difficulties.

In pastry industry it is often necessary to search a compromise between the receipt of the desired properties and components which are easily applicable in production. Pectin's for pastry wares are specially standardized and is responded to request processes and quality of the prepared products. The rich assortment of pectin's corresponds to the necessities of modern technologies of production and provides permanent high-quality and functional descriptions.

Pectin's are applied in pastry industry as the thickness, jellies and stabilizer in the systems with a different maintenance of sugar.

Pectin's of high-technological and apply for different ways of production: extrusion, continuous process, transplanting of mass at high (low) temperatures.

The products of pectin's are well acquainted to the producers of pastry wares, however unknown other types of products are too many.

It is possible to apply at production of masticatory fruit jellies, along with gelatin, pectin of the special product. It will shorten time of transplanting; will improve the structure of eventual good. The however got product at 30°C can become a not attractive delicacy far, that will not allow him to recommend for the use in regions with a hot climate. That to evade it, it is necessary to work in two directions.

First, simplest method – to use the special type of pectin, and then masticatory wares will not change the form, and will not stick together.

The second, interesting and perspective direction is complete replacement of gelatin (product of animal origin) on the product of vegetable origin. Thus time of technological process diminishes and a production cost goes down. The most important result is absence of problems with the got product in a hot period of year.

Pectin's apply forms and fixings of the set aero-structure at making of beaten up the sorts of pastry wares for saving, for example, marshmallow. There is the row of other products interesting on the consistency, which is not produced at our market.

At our market presently there are various products from milk raw material. Along with traditional drinks from milk (sour milk and yogurt), new products are milk puddings, yoghurts which also found the user appeared.

Pectin's are widely used for giving to the milk products of certain consistency and stability. The choice of stabilizer, sure, is determined by his concrete function, descriptions of the finished product. However much such stabilizer, as gelatin or starch, not always can create necessary consistency, and the more so to prevent formation of sediment or separation of whey.

Pectin is able to strengthen natural viscosity of yoghurt and, presently, is a unique stabilizer fully protecting milk albumen in products with the lowered acidity.

Except for simple drinkable yoghurt with different aromas, even small milk enterprises aim to make, so-called yoghurt of «Swiss» type, with introduction of natural fruit. Consequently, making of additives for yoghurts becomes attractive and perspective. They are produced on the basis of the frozen fruit, purees and concentrates of juices. If to say about preparation of fruit additions for yoghurts, it is here possible to select pectin's which will give the improved rheological properties to the finished good. Fruit mass easily interfuses with basis of yogurt, pectin

multiplies viscosity, and fruit are evenly distributed on all volume of packing.

Now the great number of innovative ideas in area of milk drinks with a different maintenance of dry matters, viscosity and numerous additions which definitely affect the organism of man is offered in the world (food fibers, vitamins, extracts of plants). The real producers continue to fill up the assortment row of products on milk raw material. A refreshing drink which is made from fat free milk and fruit juice became one of them. Development of this direction continues to develop with new types of pectin's.

A next conception lies in basis of stabilization of all milk drinks and products. To prevent besieging of casein particles and development in the product of sandiness taste, it is necessary to stabilize soul-milk drinks and drinkable yoghurts of thermal method of production by influence of pectin matters on the caseins of milk.

Fruit processing: preparation of jams, confitures and cooking on the basis of fruit or berry raw material with addition of sugar and different food acids is one of the eldest methods of saving of garden-stuffs and berries not only in domestic but also in production terms.

A buyer hopes to get in products the naturally stored vitamins, microelements and ballast matters and, certainly, to enjoy taste. From that how a commodity will look what taste properties will possess, his further advancement at the market depends.

Presently there was a new direction of the fruit processing. Experimental producers and over nascent enterprises began to produce fruit products for the further production processing:

- thermo stable fillings for pastry wares;
- inundations for cakes;
- fruit preparations for yoghurts, ice-cream, curd;
- caramels for an ice-cream.

From all aforesaid it is possible to do a conclusion, that for all transferred products it is possible to apply the special brands of pectins, allowing creating various and high-quality fruit ready-to-cook foods. A magnificent chance to force out the imported analogues and create the market of domestic commodities appears at producers. Having highly skilled specialists, modern powerful equipment and well equipped laboratory base, it is possible successfully to move forward at our market ingredients for different regions of food retail industry, in particular:

- fruit preparations for milk products and ice-cream;

- jams, jellies, confitures;
- sour-milk products;
- caramel and chocolate additives and sauces;
- fruit jellies and marshmallow wares;
- spread;
- lightly alcohol drinks;
- juices and drinks;
- fruit preparations for pastry wares.

Thus, the competent conduct of technological process and choice of stabilizing agent will be instrumental in correct embodiment the set problem in production.

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STUDIES CONCERNING THE SENSITIVITY OF BACTERIA FROM WINE TO ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS

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Abstract: *The paper presents the sensitivity of wine bacterial strains to antimicrobial agents. The lactic acid bacteria were isolated from two wines on the specific media and were tested to six antimicrobial agents, frequently used in human therapy for enteric disorders. The growth inhibition zones determined by antimicrobial agents had different values, but bacterial strains presented a similar sensitivity to antimicrobial agents with standard strain of Staphylococcus aureus.*

Keywords: *wine, lactic acid bacteria, antimicrobial agents*

1. Introduction

Lactic acid bacteria are heterogeneous group of bacteria, widely spread in nature. These bacteria naturally occurring as indigenous microbiota in gastrointestinal and urogenital tract of humans and warm-blooded animals are inhabitants of many food products too, like dairy foods, meat, wine and other food stuffs.

Lactic acid bacteria play an important role, especially in wine production [2]. In addition to yeasts and acetic acid bacteria, lactic acid bacteria are involved in winemaking process, the different categories of these bacteria could improve or decrease the quality of wine because the malolactic fermentation [5]. The malolactic fermentation leads to reduce acid in wine, improve the flavour and increase the microbiological stability of wines. In the same time, high levels of lactic acid bacteria can produce damages and decrease the alcoholic fermentation speed or even stop it [1].

Some wild strains of lactic acid bacteria are studied like prospective bacteriocin producers [4], [7] or probiotics [6], in terms of biotechnological importance.

In course of time, large scale use of broad-spectrum antibiotics without prescription according antibiogram induced to increase the bacterial resistance to antibiotics effects.

The antibiotic resistance phenomenon in bacteria is a worldwide problem in healthcare and it has been noted ever since the discovery of

penicillin. The antibiotic drug resistance of bacteria may be natural, mutational or acquired. While the natural and mutational resistance cannot be influenced by man, the easiness of resistance genes transfer from cell to cell is the motive of concernment for medical world.

It is happening in a constant presence of antibiotics in human body, which bind bacteria to preserves the resistance genes.

The lactic acid bacteria from wine and food may come across the normal enteric microbiota and their sensitivity or resistance spectrum could be important on this line.

The aim of this paper was to relieve the sensitivity of lactic acid bacteria isolated from wine to the effect of antibiotic drugs used in human therapy of enteric disorders.

2. Materials and methods

The isolation of lactic acid bacteria strains

For experiments were used 23 strains of lactic acid bacteria, isolated from two red wines, Cabernet – Sauvignon and Burgund Mare.

The bacteria were obtained on the specific solid medium Lafon – Lafourcade. The wine samples were homogenously distributed on the medium surface in Petri dishes and then the plates were incubated at 28°C for 24 – 48 hours (Figure 1). The distinct colonies were passed over the slant in tubes to the aim of obtain pure bacterial culture.

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Fig. 1. The lactic acid bacteria colonies on the Lafon – Lafourcade medium (original)

Antibiotic sensitivity testing

The pure culture of lactic acid bacteria were testing by diffusimetric method antibiogram [3]. Six antibiotic drugs were used, chosen according to applicability to human therapy: Amoxicillin (AML), Amikacin (AK), Tetracycline (TE), Ciprofloxacin (CIP), Furazolidon (FR), Colistin sulfate (CT).

The effect of antibiotics was tested against a standard strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, too.

The effect of antimicrobial agents against lactic acid bacteria consisted of the bacterial growth inhibition zone. The diameters of these zones were measured with ruler in three directions.

3. Results and discussion

The number of bacterial strains isolated from each of two red wines is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Source	Strain number	Total
Cabernet - Sauvignon	15	23
Burgund Mare	8	

The tested strains were sensitive to antibiotics. Their sensitivity was similar to sensitivity of *Staphylococcus aureus* strain.

The diameters of inhibition growth areas were between 12-28 mm for strains isolated from Cabernet – Sauvignon (Figure 2), between 10–32 mm for strains isolated from Burgund Mare and between 9–32 mm for *Staphylococcus aureus* strain.

All those 15 lactic acid bacterial strains from Cabernet – Sauvignon presented almost the same sensitivity to a certain antibiotics. For example, diameters of inhibition growth zone determined by Tetracycline were between 22–24 mm, and those determined by Ciprofloxacin were between 23–25 mm.

The most effective antibiotic against bacteria from Cabernet – Sauvignon was Amikacin (28 mm on average), followed by Ciprofloxacin (24 mm on average) and the least of all was Colistin sulfate (12 mm on average).

All those eight lactic acid bacterial strains from Burgund Mare presented almost the same sensitivity to a certain antibiotics, too. For example, the diameters of inhibition growth zone determined by Furazolidon were between 26–28 mm, and those determined by Tetracycline were between 31–33 mm.

The most effective antibiotic against bacteria from Burgund Mare was Tetracycline (32 mm on average) and the least of all was Colistin sulfate (10 mm on average), followed by Amoxicillin (19 mm on average).

The standard strain *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 presented the higher sensitivity to Amoxicillin (32 mm), followed by Furazolidon and Amikacin (31 mm) and the higher resistance to Colistin sulfate (9 mm).

In Figure 3 are presented the average of values for inhibition growth zones diameters for strains isolated from sources and the values of inhibition growth diameter for standard strain.

The spectrum of sensitivity to each antibiotic drug was similar, the most efficient antibiotic was Amikacin and the small inhibition zone was determined by Colistin sulphate.

Fig. 2. Antibiogram for lactic acid bacteria (strain 33) from Cabernet - Sauvignon (original)

Fig. 3. The lactic acid bacteria colonies on the Lafon – Lafourcade medium

4. Conclusions

Analyse of dates obtained in these experiments emphasized the sensitivity of lactic acid bacteria strains to antimicrobial agents.

The sensitivity spectra for bacterial strains isolated from two red wines are various, dependent on antibiotic. All bacterial strains (including standard one) had small sensitivity to Colistin sulfate and high sensitivity to

Tetracycline and Amikacin, from all six tested antibiotics.

The bacterial strains isolated from Burgund Mare had a sensitivity spectrum allied to those of *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, standard strain. The bacterial strain from Cabernet – Sauvignon had smaller averages of diameters than those for other strains (except to Colistin sulfate).

Because the lactic acid bacteria strains isolated from red wines were sensitive enough to antibiotic drugs, it is improbable to induce the antibiotic resistance for enteric microbiota of human hosts.

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CHANGES IN THE TOTAL ANTHOCYANINS AND POLYPHENOLS DURING PROCESSING OF WILD BERRIES INTO FRESHLY PRESSED JUICES

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Abstract: The present study evaluated the changes in the total anthocyanins and polyphenols during processing of wild berry, bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and lingonberry (*Vaccinium vitis-idaea*), fruits into freshly pressed juices. While almost equal distributions between the juice and press-cake were observed for the lingonberry, the bilberry juice possessed 1.5 and 3.2 times lower recovery rates for the polyphenolic and anthocyanin content, respectively. Correspondingly, 1.8–3.0 times higher values, on a fruit weight basis, were obtained for the antioxidant capacity (DPPH and FRAP assay) of the bilberry press-cake. The results obtained show that considerable amounts of polyphenolic antioxidants remain in the press-cake during processing of wild berry fruits, especially bilberries. Therefore, these by-products may be used as potential sources for the recovery of berry polyphenols, thus allowing development of new functional foods and beverages

Keywords: anthocyanins, polyphenols, wild berries, processing

1. Introduction

Bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and lingonberry (*Vaccinium vitis-idaea*) are the most important wild berry species in Europe and are widespread in Bulgaria occurring in the semi-mountain regions at 1200 - 1500 meters of altitude. Among the different bioactive substances in berries, phenolic compounds including anthocyanins, flavanols, flavonols and phenolic acids have received considerable interest due to their multiple biological effects such as antioxidant, antimutagenic, antiinflammatory, antiproliferative and antimicrobial activities (Badjakov *et al.*, 2008).

A great number of *in vitro* studies showing berry polyphenols as powerful dietary antioxidants are available (Beattie *et al.*, 2005; Heinonen 2007). The antioxidant effectiveness of anthocyanins and other polyphenols *in vitro* is essentially due to the ease with which a hydrogen atom from an aromatic hydroxyl group is donated to a free radical (Rice-Evans *et al.*, 1997). In addition, their ability to chelate transition metal

ions involved in radical-forming processes such as Fenton reactions could also contribute to antioxidant efficacy of the compounds (Ferrali *et al.*, 1997).

Berries generally have a short shelf life and they are widely processed into juices, wines, liquors, jams and fruit preparations intended for ice-cream, yoghurt and confectionery. Therefore, the effects of processing and subsequent storage methods on the polyphenolic content need to be considered when assessing the potential health benefits. Recently, significant losses of anthocyanins and polyphenols during blueberry processing have been reported (Skrede *et al.*, 2000; Lee *et al.*, 2002; Rossi *et al.*, 2003; Srivastava *et al.*, 2007).

Therefore, the present study evaluated the changes in the total anthocyanins and polyphenols, as well as in the antioxidant capacity, during processing of wild berries into freshly pressed juices.

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Fig. 1: Flow diagram for processing of the frozen berries.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

For the analytical purposes the following reagents were used: DPPH [2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl] and Trolox [(+/-)-6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethyl-chroman-2-carboxylic acid] (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); TPTZ [2,4,6-tripyridyl-s-triazine] and gallic acid monohydrate (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland); Folin-Ciocalteu's (FC) reagent (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). All the other reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade.

2.2. Plant materials and processing

Bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.) and lingonberry (*Vaccinium vitis-idea* L.) fruits, at a commercial maturity stage (harvest 2011), were picked from the region of Velingrad (Bulgaria) and transported to the laboratory within 24 h. After sorting to eliminate unripened, overripened or damaged fruits, berries were placed in polyethylene bags (~ 200 g) and frozen stored until used. Frozen berries were processed according to the flow diagram shown in Figure 1.

The freshly pressed berry juice was obtained in duplicate.

2.3. Sample preparation

Approximately 100 g of frozen fruits were thawed at room temperature and ground using a MR 300 Minipimer compact blender (Braun, Kronberg, Germany). Aliquot (25 g) of the berry mash was mixed with 40 mL of acidified methanol (0.1% HCl) and homogenized in a laboratory disintegrator (MPW-309, Mechanika precyzyjna, Warsaw, Poland) for 2 min. The mixture was diluted with acidified methanol in a 250 mL volumetric flask and extracted overnight in a refrigerator (4 °C). Aliquot (10 g) of the press-cake was extracted in the same way, while the juice aliquot (25 g) was directly diluted in the volumetric flask. The extracts were filtered through a paper filter. All extractions were performed in triplicate.

2.4. Chemical analyses

All measurements were performed with a Helios Omega UV-Vis spectrophotometer equipped with VISIONlite software (all from

Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madison, WI, USA) using 1 cm path length cuvettes.

2.4.1. Determination of the total polyphenols

The content of the total polyphenols (TPP) was determined by the method of Singleton and Rossi (1965) in the following modification: appropriately diluted extract (0.1 mL) was mixed with 0.5 mL of FC-reagent (diluted with distilled water 1:4, v/v) and 1.5 mL of sodium carbonate solution (7.5%, w/v) and the volume was made up to 10 mL with distilled water; the mixture was incubated for 2 h at room temperature before the absorbance was measured at 750 nm. The results were presented as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 g of sample (fruit, juice or press-cake) on a fresh weight basis.

2.4.2. Determination of the total monomeric anthocyanins

The amount of the total monomeric anthocyanins (TMA) was determined by the pH-differential method (Giusti and Wrolstad 2001). The extract was diluted in parallel with buffer pH 1.0 (0.025 M potassium chloride) and buffer pH 4.5 (0.4 M sodium acetate). After 2 h of incubation at room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 520 and 700 nm. Results were calculated using a molar absorptivity of 26900 L/(mol cm) and molecular weight of 449.2 g/mol (Moyer *et al.*, 2002) and expressed as equivalents of cyanidin 3-glucoside (CGE) in mg per 100 g of sample (fruit, juice or press-cake) on a fresh weight basis.

2.4.3. Determination of the antioxidant capacity

The total antioxidant capacity was determined by the DPPH (free radical scavenging activity) and FRAP (ferric reducing antioxidant power) assay. Trolox, a water-soluble vitamin E analogue, was used as a reference in both assays and the antioxidant capacity was expressed as μmol Trolox equivalents (TE) per 100 g of sample (fruit, juice or press-cake) on a fresh weight basis.

2.4.3.1. DPPH assay

The procedure was based on the method of Brand-Williams and others (1995) modified as follows: 2250 μL of of DPPH methanolic solution (6×10^{-5} M) was mixed with 250 μL of extract (diluted with distilled water 1:3, v/v); absorbance at 515 nm was measured after 15 min of reaction in a cap-sealed cuvette kept in dark at room temperature.

2.4.3.2. FRAP assay

The reaction was performed according to Benzie and Strain (1996) with some modifications. The FRAP reagent was prepared from 2.5 mL of a TPTZ solution (10 mmol/L) in hydrochloric acid (40 mmol/L) and 2.5 mL of a FeCl_3 solution (20 mmol/L) mixed with 25 mL of an acetate buffer (0.3 mol/L, pH 3.6). In the assay, 2250 μL of FRAP reagent and 250 μL of extract (diluted with distilled water 1:3, v/v) were mixed in a cuvette. The absorbance at 593 nm was measured after 4 min.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The results reported in the present study are the mean values of at least three determinations, and the coefficients of variation, expressed as the percentage ratio between the standard deviations and the mean values, were found to be < 5% in all cases.

3. Results and discussion

The juice yield was 69.7% and 73.3% with the press-cake residue accounting for 23.7% and 20.5% of the starting material for the bilberry and lingonberry fruits, respectively (Table 1).

Thus, there were approximately 7% material losses in the crushing and pressing unit operations for both berry types.

As shown in Table 1, the content of total polyphenols in the wild berries varied from 693.9 to 794.2 mg/100g, whereas the total anthocyanin content was much higher for the bilberries.

Table 1. Yields, total anthocyanin (TMA) and polyphenolic (TPP) contents and antioxidant capacity (DPPH and FRAP) values depending on the processing of wild berries

	BILBERRY			LINGONBERRY		
	Fruit	Juice	Press-cake	Fruit	Juice	Press-cake
Yield (% w/w)	100	69.7	23.7	100	73.3	20.5
Total anthocyanins¹						
Sample (mg CGE/100g)	432.1	117.0	1098.7	44.7	29.2	86.7
Berries (mg CGE/100g)	432.1	81.5	260.4	44.7	21.4	17.8
Total polyphenols¹						
Sample (mg GAE/100g)	794.2	431.7	1951.0	693.9	262.2	781.9
Berries (mg GAE/100g)	794.2	300.9	462.4	693.9	192.2	160.3
FRAP¹						
Sample (μmol TE/100g)	3468.9	1156.1	10163.9	3116.7	1728.9	6927.8
Berries (μmol TE/100g)	3468.9	805.8	2408.9	3116.7	1267.3	1420.2
DPPH¹						
Sample (μmol TE/100g)	3011.7	1472.8	7968.1	2385.0	987.5	5537.5
Berries (μmol TE/100g)	3011.7	1026.5	1888.4	2385.0	723.8	1135.2

¹ The data are presented for both the actual sample (row labeled Sample) and that derived from 100 g of berries (row labeled Berries).

These findings are in accordance with the results obtained in previous studies (Dinkova et al., 2011; Yoncheva et al., 2010).

While almost equal distributions between the juice and press-cake were observed for the lingonberry, the bilberry juice possessed 1.5 and 3.2 times lower recovery rates for the polyphenolic and anthocyanin content, respectively. Correspondingly, 1.8–3.0 times higher values, on a fruit weight basis, were obtained for the antioxidant capacity of the bilberry press-cake. These results suggest that additional processing steps are required to increase the recovery of anthocyanins and polyphenols during bilberry juice extraction. On the other hand, the wild berry processing waste

represents a potential source for manufacturing extracts rich in anthocyanins and/or polyphenols.

The two assays used represent different mechanisms of evaluating antioxidant capacity. While the DPPH assay measures the ability of plant extracts to scavenge free radicals, the FRAP assay quantifies the total concentration of redox-active compounds (Magalhães et al., 2008).

Recently, radar charts have been demonstrated to be useful characterizing the activity profile of water-soluble antioxidants in various food matrices (Terashima et al., 2007).

Antioxidant activity of wild berry samples (Figure 2), including the corresponding fruit juices, appears to be mainly due to the presence of polyphenols possessing simultaneously hydrogen- and electron-donating ability.

Fig. 2. Radar charts of the antioxidant activities in extracts from different bilberry (A) and lingonberry (B) samples.

4. Conclusion

The results obtained show that considerable amounts of polyphenolic antioxidants remain in the press-cake during processing of wild berry fruits, especially bilberries. Therefore, these by-products may be used as potential sources for the recovery of berry polyphenols, thus allowing development of new functional foods and beverages. On the other hand, additional processing steps e.g. enzymatic treatments are required to increase the concentrations of anthocyanins and polyphenols in the bilberry juice.

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LABEL RESEARCH REGARDING THE NUMBER OF FOOD ADDITIVES OF SOME PRODUCTS FROM THE ROMANIAN MARKET

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Abstract: *Food additives, substances that are not characteristic alimentary ingredients, unfortunately became the main constituents of a great majority of food products. This paper presents a survey of the labels regarding the number of food additives of some food products, on the Romanian market. The paper aims to highlight that reading the food labels is mandatory, especially regarding of the fact that producers do not mention all the food ingredients on the labels and this is a manner by which consumers can ask for their legitimate rights.*

Keywords: *food additives, labels, ingredients.*

1. Introduction

Food additives are chemical substances used for technological reasons in the food industry. Food additives are situated in the class of the xenobiotics, that are substances alien to biologic systems and they are not natural substances, and what's worse is that they have cumulative effects. That's why even though studies regarding their safety are still in progress; the great majority of them are noxious for human organisms. [1]

Food additives have a general bad reputation, mainly because of those chases when they were used without a clear judgment, excessively, for the adulteration of food or for hiding some ambiguous properties of some food, with the aim of deceiving the consumer and without the fact that their properties or combined effects to be well known. [1]

The processing, the storing and the commercialization of food were millenary activities that had to be regularized, for ensuring an equitable balance between the interest of the consumers and the interests of the producers and traders. Assyrian vestiges mention people's preoccupation for assessing some standards and general prescriptions in the food industry. This kind of rules, that were more or less precise were established during the history in many countries. [1]

A very precise set of rules and general prescriptions in the food industry was *Codex Alimentarius Austriacus* that appeared in the year 1897 in the Austral – Hungarian empire and

served as a model and source of inspiration for subsequent international regulations in the food industry. In the same period, the food chemistry was gaining more credibility and importance, because it starting to provide not only methods for the preparation and processing of food, but methods for detecting food that is adulterated, toxic or not so qualitative. [1]

In the year 1945, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) is formed and in the year 1948, the World Health Organization (WHO) is formed, both organisms appertaining to the United Nations Organization. As a matter of some influences from different associations of producers and traders of food products, FAO and WHO intensify their undertaking for the instituting in the Member States of some rules and general prescriptions for the food fabrication, with the main role of facilitating food trade. [1]

The preoccupations regarding food additives, over the facts that they were used without knowing their effects over people's health were concretized in the year 1955, with the occasion of the commune conference of FAO and WHO, regarding the setting of the *Expert Commission for Food Additives*, commission which since then is reuniting from two to two years and having as a purpose the assessment, based on the laboratory results, of the degree of danger and harmfulness and establishing prescriptions for their use. [1]

In the year 1963, the *Codex Alimentarius Commission* is formed, organism of regulation at Global level, with the role of elaborating a collection of food standards, guides, leading

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brochures and recommendations regarding food quality, the rules of labeling, packaging, standards of hygiene, the use of food additives and other food contaminants. The *Codex Alimentarius Commission* has many expert commissions, by which the Expert Commission for Food Additives. Beside of the above mentioned organisms, the European Union's citizens can benefit of supplemental protection, by the institution in the year 2002 or European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), which has the main role of defending the public interest. [1]

The use of food additives in Romania is regularized by the Commune Decree of Health Ministry and Agriculture Ministry number 438/295/2002, publicized in The Official Monitor of Romania. This establishes what are the admissible food additives, the food categories and the doses in which they can be used. [1]

In Romania, the demand for ensuring food safety for the global population is in the area of competence simultaneous of the Health Ministry, the Agriculture Ministry and of the National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority. For the facilitation of the commercial trade with food products, the above mentioned authorities emit commune Orders and other rules that transpose the European normatives. [1]

At present times, at European level, there is interest in adopting supplemental measures for informing consumers about food additives, especially of the ones that posed adverse effects. Though, two supplemental regulations are to be adopted, with the role of informing consumers what are the food additives authorized for use in food. [3]

The two regulations institute two new lists. The first list refers to food additives from food products and will be in force only in the year 2013 and the second one has regard for the additives from food ingredients, as some enzymes, flavors and nutritive substances and will be in force at 20 days after the publication in the Official Journal of European Union. [3]

2. Materials and Methods

The paper aims to evaluate the problem of food additives, by explaining the importance of ensuring the means for consumer information, through correct and complete labeling and evaluating the degree of danger of some food additives that are used in some products.

From all the food additives, some of them are very dangerous for consumer's state of health, independent of the dose or of the food product. By these, there are:

- E 110 – Sunset yellow FCF (Sunset yellow);
- E 122 – Azorubine (Carmoizine);
- E 129 – Allura Red (Allura Red AC);
- E 155 – Brown HT;
- E 211 – Sodium benzoate;
- E 249 – Potassium nitrite;
- E 250 – Sodium nitrite;
- E 310 – Propyl gallate;
- E 311 – Octyl gallate;
- E 312 – Dodecyl gallate;
- E 319 – Butylhydroxinon;
- E 320 - Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA);
- E 321- Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT);
- E 334 – L-(+)- tartaric acid;
- E 355 – Adipic acid;
- E 356 – Sodium adipate;
- E 357 – Potassium adipate;
- E 620 – Glutamic acid;
- E 621 – Monosodium glutamate (MSG);
- E 622 – Monopotassium glutamate;
- E 623 – Calcium diglutamate;
- E 624 – Ammonium glutamate;
- E 625 – Magnesium glutamate;
- E 951 – Aspartame (Canderel, Nutrasweet, Equal);
- E 952 – Cyclamates (Cyclamic acid and it's sodium and calcium saults);
- E 954 - Sacharine and it's potassium and calcium saults;

Food labels of different products were tested regarding the number of additives mentioned. This study was conducted along with specialists from the *National Authority for Consumer's Protection and the Promoting of Programs and Services* from Romania. [4]

It was established a hierarchical classification of the investigated food products regarding the number of food additives mentioned on their labels.

The study aims to pull an alert signal mainly over the conscience of the producers, but both of the consumers. It was established the fact that food products contain a very large number of food additives, at least one food additive and generally between two and five food additives.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 – The results of the survey on the food labels [4]

No.	Food product	Number of food additives	The numerical code of the food additives	Dangerous food additives
1.	Grilled cheese	2 - 13	E 120, E 160a, E 202, E 250, E 251, E 270, E 301, E 316, E 330, E 331, E 332, E 339, E 339(iii), E 341, E 410, E 415, E 425, E 450, E 451, E 451(i), E 452, E 1404, E 1422, E 1442.	E 250, E 251, E 450, E 451, E 451(i), E 452.
2.	Vegetal pie	0 - 12	E 120, E 150, E 296, E 300, E 301, E 316, E 321, E 325, E 330, E 407, E 410, E 412, E 415, E 452, E 481, E 621, E 635.	E 321, E 452.
3.	Beverages	2 - 11	E 150, E 150a, E 150d, E 160a, E 160e, E 163, E 202, E 211, E 296, E 300, E 330, E 331, E 331(iii), E 338, E 412, E 414, E 950, E 951, E 952	E 211, E 950, E 951, E 952.
4.	Margarine	3 - 8	E 100, E 160b, E 200, E 202, E 250, E 304, E 306, E 322, E 330, E 385, E 471, E 472, E 476.	E 250.
5.	Meat pack	1 - 8	E 120, E 250, E 300, E 301, E 316, E 339, E 407, E 410, E 450(i), E 451(i), E 452, E 500, E 508, E 600, E 621, E 1404.	E 250, E 450(i), E 452, E 621.
6.	Chocolate	0 - 8	E 120, E 150, E 160, E 161b, E 163, E 200, E 202, E 270, E 322, E 330, E 331, E 335, E 336, E 412, E 414, E 440, E 444, E 476, E 950, E 965, E 966, E 1103.	E 444, E 950.
7.	Bread	0 - 8	E 170, E 200, E 262(ii), E 263, E 270, E 282, E 300, E 322, E 330, E 471, E 472e, E 475, E 481, E 920.	-
8.	Chips	0 - 7	E 100, E 150a, E 160b, E 160c, E 260, E 262(ii), E 270, E 296, E 322, E 330, E 471, E 551, E 621, E 627, E 631, E 635, E 951.	E 621, E 951.
9.	Fruit yogurt	0 - 5	E 100, E 120, E 141, E 160a, E 160b, E 330, E 330(iii), E 331, E 339(iii), E 410, E 414, E 415, E 440, E 440(i), E 472b.	-

Table 1 is a synthesis of the survey on the labels of the mentioned food products. The survey took place between may 2011 and February 2012, with the help of the *National Authority for Consumer's Protection and the Promoting of Programs and Services* from Romania. [4]

These results were represented only from the labels of the food products. [4] Subsequent studies may be oriented on the laboratory analysis of these products, so we can have the certitude that the labeling is correct and complete.

From Table 1, we can see that the food products analyzed contain a very large number of food additives. Studies undertaken to evaluate the damage potential of these chemical compounds are on one hand still in process and on the other hand are not conclusive. Even though the specified compound wasn't found to be dangerous for people's health, this is not a sufficient fact for being sure that it cannot produce any harmful action, especially having regard for the cumulative effects. More than that, the great majority of the food additives are chemical substances, that's why they are for sure harmful for the human organisms.

One of the causes for the invasion of food additives and the radical change in the recipes is mainly because food additives are easy to purchase, store, they are ready to use and they are very cheap. The natural normal composition of the food products was very affected, this can be observed in the organoleptic properties of the food, mainly on the taste, but also on the aspect and smell.

Food additives, may conduct, when the Acceptable Daily Intake is exceeded, to the following adverse effects: hyperactivity, allergies, intolerance, gastric irritation, anorexia, headache, regurgitation, lethargy, weakness, shivering, dizziness and even skin or liver affections, genotoxic effect, hemoglobin destruction, irreversible damage on the central nervous system, skin eczema, gastric injury, DNA lesion, adverse effects upon the reproduction system, teratogenic and mutagenic effects. [2]

Even though from the large number of the identified food additives, not too much of them proved to posed clear adverse effects, the rest of are fore sure unhealthy for human organisms.

A doubtfully thing is that the great majority of the identified food additives on the labels were in the category of the ones that are not so harmful for consumers. Unfortunately, we cannot have the certitude that producers were sincere when they composed the food labels. In the case of the absence of the laboratory testing and of a serious administrative and legal control, cases when producers deliberately hide some technological aspects, that reflect in the lack of information for the final consumer are more and more frequent. That's why, for sure, we don't know what food products we buy and eat.

4. Conclusions

Food additives are chemical compounds that posed adverse effects over consumer's state of health. These compounds invaded the food products, radically changing the recipes and having long time effects over the general state of health of the consumers.

An alarming thing is that the analyzed food products contained a very large number of food additives. Studies regarding the safety of these compounds not only that are in progress, but did not evaluated their associated effects, because as can be seen, every analyzed food products contained at least too food additives. There are food products that contain thirteen food additives.

In the context of the free market and in transferring the main responsibility to the producer, national authorities do not exercise all their legal attributes, for the insurance of the food safety concept.

Though, at European level, there is interest in adopting supplemental measures for informing consumers about food additives, especially the dangerous ones, and that's a positive aspect.

Producers hide many aspects that are not favorable for them and that could reduce their sales and that's both available in the case of food additives. They for example tend to avoid mentioning the food additives that are in the "very dangerous" class.

Every consumer should read the labels of the food products they buy; this is the only way by which they can ask for their rights in the case of some issues that could affect their state of health.

Even though food labeling is not always correct and complete, by reading the label, consumers can take notice of some unconformities and can ask for their legitimate rights.

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TOXIC SUBSTANCES FROM FOOD: DISTRIBUTION AND HEALTH EFFECTS

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Abstract: *The paper presents a well documented classification of toxic substances from food. This subject was not treated extensively till the present by certain authors and that is not a positive issue, having regard of the fact that these compounds have serious health effects over the consumers. Being aware of the presence of these compounds in food and knowing their effects is an important step in preventing the apparition of negative effects over the state of health. By using the tool of information, consumers can gain important elements by which they can be in consciousness of cause.*

Keywords: *toxic, effects, food, information.*

1. Introduction

Toxic (noxious) substances from food were always in the attention of specialists, but in the last decade, the chemification of the agriculture, the environmental pollution, the high industrialization of the alimentation, by using of numerous additional substances, created more and more problems, with direct implications over consumer's state of health. [1], [3]

Toxic substances from food are an ample class of compounds of which properties and effects over consumer's state of health were not published too many scientific articles. [1]

In the actual context of intra-communitarian commerce we are assaulted with many food products that are more and more sophisticated and about which we don't know too much. Producers tend to hide those aspects that could cause them the reduction of the sales. [1]

The analytic control methods of food are much diversified and are hard to apply in a unitary format. That's why the confidence that the specified food, analyzed using a certain method, reflected in the analysis bulletin posed a certain degree of relativity and could indubitably be put under question by the consumer. [1]

The varying of the recipes and especially the apparition of the additional substances that do not derive from natural sources is a concrete element. More than that, the environmental pollution, the radical changes of food production technologies and the apparition of the Genetically Modified Organisms (GMO's) are elements that really took us by surprise. [1]

Today we are hearing about the commercialization of meat originating from cloned animal, without the need of labeling. [1]

Chemical substances from food, agricultural and industrial pollutants, different kind of particles with pathogenic potential, that could be found in finite food products, as in the agricultural products, convey certainly, sometimes in the case of high doses to serious adverse effects on consumer's state of health.

It is worthily of notice that any toxic or nontoxic compound was not tested how it interacts with the rest of food compounds, even some molecules were not tested at all about how they interact with human organisms. [1]

2. Materials and Methods

The primarily source of information in composing this paper was the book *Problems of harmfulness in habitual food*. [1]

The aim of this paper is to take an account of the toxic substances that could be present in food, and also their effects on human health. This could be an important source for consumer information, with the main role of defending the general state of health.

The most important aspect of which consumers should be aware is that the correct information over the food properties can be done only using scientific authorized sources.

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3. Results

Table 1 – A classification of toxic substances from food [1]

No.	Toxic substance	Distribution	Health effects
1.	Residues of pesticides	Wide	Cancer, neuro-toxic properties, changes in the nucleic acids structure, even death.
2.	Residues originating from industrial waste	Wide	Chlorine-acne, cancer, hepatic and renal toxicity, weight losses.
3.	Heavy metals	Wide	Damage of the nervous system, weight losses, anemia, teratogen effects, cancer, affecting the capacity of procreation, diarrhea and death.
4.	Residues of veterinary drugs	Wide	Allergic reactions, nervous, teratogen or toxic effects, anti-bio-resistance, headache, disruption of the hormonal status, disturbance of the intestinal flora.
5.	Toxic substances formed through cooking	Wide	Cancer, mutagenic effects.
6.	Food additives	Wide	Allergies, intolerance, irreversible damage on the central nervous system, DNA lesion, hemoglobin destruction, adverse effects upon the reproduction system, teratogen and mutagenic effects.
7.	Mycotoxins	Moderate	Carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogen effects, hepatic lesions, hemorrhage, convulsions.
8.	Bacterial toxins (food poisoning)	Moderate	Sickness, gastroenteritis, enterocolitis, neuro-toxic effects, paralysis, headache, septicemia, meningitis, necrosis.
9.	Food allergens	Moderate	Inflammations, urticaria, respiratory difficulties, sickness, even death.
10.	Genetically modified organisms (GMO's)	Moderate	The apparition of new types of food allergens, the induction of resistance to antibiotics.
11.	Cloned animals as a source of food products	Moderate	The problem of the technique of breeding, that doesn't seem to produce genetically normal descendants.
12.	Biogenic amines	Moderate	Hypertension, palpitation, serious headache, even intracranial hemorrhage.
13.	Toxic substances of vegetal and animal origin	Limited	Gastrointestinal signs, paralysis, edemas, dermatitis, serious toxic effects.
14.	Species of animals that synthesize toxic substances	Limited	
15.	Toxic plants	Limited	

This classification does not contain all the toxic substances that could exist or could be formed in food, but it offers a good synthesis on the problem of noxious substances.

The source of information in composing this table was the book *Problems of harmfulness in habitual food*. [1]

4. Discussion

From Table 1, it can be seen the great variety of the toxic compounds that could be present in food. It should be noticed that there are not mentioned all the toxic substances that could be formed and that could exist in the food structure.

Some substances existed since the earliest times, but some of them appeared a very short time ago, for example the Genetically Modified Organisms (GMO's), as the food additives or food allergens.

It has been established through long time studies that every chemical element, particle or other specific compound that is not natural or hasn't been present in the natural food structure could posed adverse effects, of diverse gravity over the consumer, when being ingested. It is also known the fact that studies for evaluating the degree of safety for a certain compound are generally obtained by experiments upon animals, but certainly if a compound is noxious for an animal, it has a degree of harmfulness for people too.

A very important element is the interaction between these substances inside the human organism. Very few substances or compounds were tested how they interact with other food constituents, toxic or non-toxic.

The life style, the general metabolism and the individual reactivity are also important elements in the way that toxic substances interact and exhibit their effects. Some individual are more resistant and some are very sensitive, but certainly all the toxic substances have cumulative effects and in time the adverse effects could appear from nowhere. Toxic substances are one of the main causes for cancer apparition at people.

Toxic substances from food have cumulative effects that generate adverse effects upon the human organisms, like the cancerous, mutagenic, teratogen or other specific toxic effects. The human organism has the capacity of accommodating to the action of some toxic substances in small dose and that do not possess cumulative effects. [1]

The human organism's response to these chemical compounds is represented by a dynamical balance that could be easily altered by a large number of elements, like some other disease, physical or mental demands, the simultaneous action of some chemical substances, as the insufficient or unbalanced alimentation. [1]

The relation between agriculture, alimentation and health is becoming more and more evident, because the modern civilization's diseases are put upon an inadequate alimentation, as a consequence of the excessive use of chemical substances. [1]

Food poisoning can be of two types: intoxications that appear in natural conditions and intoxications that appear in some circumstances that are created by people. The second class is the main cause of food poisoning and is due to industrial pollution, pesticides, chemical fertilizers, the adverse action of medicines, food additives. [1], [3]

At present times, at Global level, there is a general preoccupation for obtaining food products of high quality and with a low content of chemical substances, aspects that implies two main directions, that are the application of the Ecological Agriculture's principles and the use of the food technologies and biotechnologies that ensure the concept of food safety. [1]

The Ecological Agriculture is a system that aims to offer fresh, tasty and authentic food to the consumers and that in the same time respects the natural life cycle of the systems. [1]

Food safety is a concept that implies the fact that food will not determine adverse effects over the consumer, when the consumer has regard and takes notice of the producer's prescriptions. In a more arrow significance, food safety involves the food's quality of not being harmful for consumer's state of health. [2]

Nowadays, it is more and more obvious that producers use many chemical substances in the recipes of their products. Also, it can be deduced that they use this substances because they are easy to achieve, prepare and store and obviously they are cheaper than the natural compounds.

Unfortunately, these chemical substances have long or short time effects over the consumer's state of health. Probably, the damaging effects over the general health state of consumers will appear after some decades.

On the other side, the environmental pollution is another element that directly affects the consumer's state of health. Food has a direct connection with the environment, so the noxious elements from the environment will appear in a certain form and concentration in the agricultural or food product. That's why national authorities have the main responsibility regarding the insurance and the maintaining of the general state of health and that should start by the environment's health.

5. Conclusions

Toxic substances are a very large class of compounds that posed a wide range of effects over consumer's state of health. Some of them are very noxious, some are noxious depending on the dose and some of them are not very noxious or the studies carried on weren't able to establish their impact over the consumer or other biological systems.

Anyhow, the presence of toxic compounds in the food structure is not a desirable thing, especially for the consumer.

Unfortunately, producers do not give enough attention to the effects that their products could have over the consumer, because they are more interested of gaining money than offering healthy food on the free market and to the final consumer.

What's worse is that food safety standards are not as standard as it is suggested by their description. Every Member State has to line up to the European Directives that offer only some general prescriptions that do not have the power of law.

More than that, the legislation of some countries as for example Romania offers producers the possibility of establishing internal standards, based on the general prescriptions of the Directives, but does not offer a strictness of applying standard rules.

The concept of the free market in the European Union is another element that is not very opportune for the possibility of ensuring food safety. The control, both the administrative and the analytical one is heavier to apply, because of the large number of food products, as their characteristics and their provenience. More than that, the food hazards can be spread more easily in this context, because food products could originate from many sources and could arrive finally in some places that were intact in the aspect of food contamination.

An important element for protecting our state of health is being informed, that's why sources of information should be very well selected. It is known the fact that the media offers much information that is not so true, because it is purposely denaturalized, with the role of influencing people.

The sources of information should be only the scientific ones, because they offer the confidence for the reproducibility of the results. What's more, by scientific research, you can obtain facts

or results that were empirically tested and were based on much scientific rigor.

Even though toxic substances exist and unfortunately, they are in some cases very dangerous, by taking notice of their presence, consumers could avoid some situations in which they didn't had too many information about a food or its property and took some wrong decisions, that affected their state of health. These informations should be correlated with all the scientific knowledge and data from the food industry, respecting the principle *from farm to fork*, so the food chain could be one that in the context of integrated management system could offer safe and healthy food to consumers.

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THE CONCENTRATION EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANTS SUBSTANCES FROM RED WINES

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Abstract: *The paper presents the important role of antioxidant substances from wines. In red wine, tannins and anthocyanins are the most important phenolic classes; they have recently been considered as antioxidant, bactericide, and cardiovascular protective. The quantities of polyphenols and anthocyanins were spectrophotometric determined for different types of red wines from Valea Călugărească. The colour intensity has been correlated with the anthocyanins content.*

Keywords: *polyphenols, anthocyanins, red wine .*

1. Introduction

Epidemiological, experimental and clinical investigations have shown that diets supplemented with moderate quantities of alcoholic beverages lead to biochemical changes that are widely regarded to prevent atherosclerosis. Red wine contains naturally rich sources of antioxidants which may protect the body from oxidative stress.

Many beneficial properties such as antioxidant, bactericide, and cardiovascular protective have recently been associated with phenolic compounds (German and Walzem, 2000).

Although phenolic compounds found in wine can also originate from microbial and oak sources, the majority of the phenolic constituents found in wine are grape-derived.

The major phenolic compounds from a wine quality perspective are the hydroxycinnamic acids, anthocyanins, and tannins. Recent work on tannin biosynthesis in the seed coat of *Arabidopsis* has revealed an unexpected relationship between anthocyanins and tannins (Xie *et al.*, 2003).

Anthocyanins are synthesised in the skin of red grapes after veraison; flavonols are synthesized around flowering and in the last few weeks of ripening. Unlike anthocyanins and tannins, flavonols are only synthesized when the grapes are exposed to light. In grapes, tannin accumulation starts before flowering and is most active between flowering and fruit set. Wine made from grapes grown with artificial shading had lower colour density, total phenolics, anthocyanins and tannins (Robinson, 2007).

It is accepted that phenolic compounds are important to the quality of wine. The phenolic production in the grape is influenced by the vintage (Cortell *et al.*, 2007), the fruit exposure, (Cortell and Kennedy, 2006), processing in the winery, the cultural practice and environment around the developing fruit (Pena-Neira *et al.*, 2007).

Because anthocyanins are localized in the skin tissue of most grape cultivars, fermentation and maceration have a profound effect on the amount of anthocyanin present in the final wine.

Once a wine is pressed, the concentration of grape phenolics is maximal, declining with wine aging. In red wines, the initial blue red color anthocyanins are transformed into brick-red pigments (Kennedy, 2008).

The anthocyanins accumulation in grapes varies depending on biological features of varieties, climate conditions, nature of the soil and growing conditions (Pomohaci and Stoian, 2000).

But, the nutritional properties of wine is a challenging task, which requires that the biological actions and bioavailability of the >200 individual phenolic compounds be documented and interpreted. Although the benefits of the polyphenols from fruits and vegetables are increasingly accepted, consensus on wine is developing more slowly (German and Walzem, 2000).

In present paper we estimated the quantities of polyphenols and anthocyanins, for different red wines, using spectrophotometric methods. The wine colour intensity has been correlated with the anthocyanins content.

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2. Material and methods

The study was made upon some red Romanian wines: Cabernet Sauvignon, Fetească Neagră, Merlot, Burgund and Pinot Noir. Wines made by wineries from Valea Călugărească area were bought from a local store. The wines were from 2009 and 2010 vintages.

Transmission and absorbance spectra of these wines (380-770nm) were recorded using a Perkin Elmer UV-VIS spectrophotometer Lambda 25, with double-beam, coupled with a computer IBM-PC, in a 1 mm pathlength quartz cell.

The phenolic compounds, anthocyanins content and the wine colour have been determinate by the spectrophotometric dosage (Giosanu et al., 2011).

The *Glories method* was set as chromatic parameters: the *colour intensity*, noted IC* and the *colour tint (tonality)*, noted T, taking into account the percent with that each pigment category (red, yellow, blue) could influence the total wine colour.

$$I.C.* = A_{420nm} + A_{520nm} + A_{620nm}$$

$$T = \frac{A_{420nm}}{A_{520nm}}$$

The absorbance measurement at 420 nm provides an estimate of the yellow brown pigments present in wine. The absorbance measurement at 520 nm provides an estimate of the anthocyanins and other red coloured compounds present in wine. The absorbance variation for the antocyanins colour is measured, at two pH values, namely 0.6 and 3.5, compared with the distilled water. The measurements are taken at the wavelength of 520 nm, the absorbance of the samples being proportional to the antocyanins content.

3. Results and discussions

For the colour analysis we have studied the absorbance spectra of some red wines from Valea Călugărească area. The spectra for three different sort of red wines: Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir are presented in figure 1, for different vintage (2009 and 2010).

Using the dates from these spectra, we have calculated the colour intensity and the colour tint of wines.

Fig. 1. The absorbance spectra for Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir, in 2009; inset:2010)

The quantitative determination of anthocyanins from the red wines aims to track the evolution of the phenolic ripening process of the grapes and the establishing of the anthocyanins content. This determination is made by the visible spectrophotometry and is based on the colour change of antocyanins function of pH (Țârdea, 2007).

We started our observation with the compare of the anthocyanin content for three red wines: Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir, from the same place (Valea Călugărească) on the same vineyard management, but different vintage (2009 and 2010).

From the results presented in figure 2 it remarks that the anthocyanins accumulation in grapes varies depending on climate conditions.

Fig.2. The antocyanins content in 2009 and 2010

Although the studied samples had the same biological features of varieties (Cabernet

Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir) and have been cultivated on the same soil, the anthocyanins content was different due to the meteorological factors in those years: 2009 and 2010. In all three cases, the amount of anthocyanins was higher in 2009 comparative with 2010.

Grape tannins and anthocyanins are both important fruit quality components that contribute to the colour and taste of red wines. Tannins contribute to the mouthfeel of wines but they also form pigmented polymers in association with the anthocyanins to provide the stable pigments required to give red wine its colour. In fact, anthocyanins provide the visual component in wines.

We observed, like other authors (Marais, Iland) that the anthocyanin concentrations in red wines

are highly correlated with wine colour intensity (Marais and October, 2005, Iland *et al.*, 2000).

The anthocyanins content and the total polyphenols are presented in Table 1; they are correlated with the chromatic characteristics (colour intensity and tonality, determined by Glories method). The studied wines were from 2010 vintage.

The wine tonality registered values between 0.61 – 0.81 and the higher intensity of colour was noticed at Merlot sample.

The tonality of wine and the colour intensity are inversely proportional; the Pinot Noir sample had the higher tonality.

Table 1.

The correlation between the anthocyanins content and the chromatic characteristics for wines (2010)

Wine	Cabernet Sauvignon	Burgund d Mare	Merlot	Fetească Neagră	Pinot Noir
Parameters analyzed					
Total polyphenols (mg/l)	419	372	478	340	290
Total anthocyanins (mg/l)	341	256	393	284	179
Colour intensity	1.033	0.746	1.522	0.931	0.624
Tonality	0.63	0.72	0.61	0.68	0.81

Fig. 3. The influence of each colour pigments to the total wine colour

Anthocyanins are primarily responsible for the red colour of grapes and wines. In all the studied wines, the red pigments dominated the influence on total colour, while the contribution of blue pigments was less than 25% (figure 3).

4. Conclusions

It has been established that the anthocyanins content in wines are positively linked to the wine quality.

Depending on climate conditions, the anthocyanins quantity in wines varies from year

to year. For example, in 2009, the anthocyanins accumulation in Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir was higher than in 2010.

These results could lead to an improvement in grape and wine phenolic management.

Red wine with its content of anthocyanins and polyphenols, confers additional health benefits. So, the moderate consume of red wine could increase the nutritional quality of individual foods, in a personalized diet.

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Rationale for non-waste technology of processing of skim milk for the production of whipped dessert production

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Abstract: *Work is devoted to a scientific substantiation and development of technology of semi-finished items for whipped dessert production on the basis of low-fat dairy raw material.*

Keywords: *skim milk, cornelian cherry, sloe, foam froth ability, stability of foam, albuminous-carbohydrate clot, albuminous-carbohydrate semifinished item, whipped dessert production.*

Whipped dessert production - mousses, sambuc, parfait, blancmange, whipped cream, souffles, ice cream have a high popularity among consumers they have excellent consumer indicators - high taste, delicate texture and attractive appearance and high digestibility thanks to foam drink structure. This foam with the ability to form structure positively influences to the perception of flavoring and ease of such products are associated with rapid growth in world output and consumption production of whipped dessert. However, it should be noted that as part of dairy products mainly is the use cream and whole milk. This greatly increases the calorie content and production costs. For fixing these drawbacks can use as a component of milk skim milk.

In this regard, studies aimed at development and implementation of food production on the basis of a comprehensive non-waste processing of milk, is relevant. One way to expand the range and increase the share of output in total output is to develop technologies semi-finished items high degree of readiness. Such preparations are widely used in restaurants and catering enterprises in the technology of whipped dessert production, which will not only rational use of raw materials, but also expand the range of this group of foods and significantly reduce production costs.

Existing methods of processing of skim milk are based on protein component selection that leads to the accumulation of large quantities of serum, which is a by-product.

We have developed a complex non-waste technology of processing of skim milk to obtain preparations for the production of aerated products, the essence of which is thermalacidic complex selection of skim milk proteins, forming the basis of their protein-carbohydrate semi modified functional and technological properties, based on a dry mixture of whey released from foaming and foamstable properties.

It is known that the most promising in terms of the full allocation of the protein component is thermal calcium and thermal acidly ways and methods that based on the application as precipitately complex carbohydrates. However, the most cost effective way of deposition of milk proteins is thermal acidly method using, as precipitately acid whey. However, this method provides a deposition only 29...46% whey proteins, and they lost the rest of the serum [1]. The authors [2] have proved that provide to more precipitation coagulated whey proteins may be, subject to availability of additional centers of coagulation, as which may make complex carbohydrates (cellulose, pectin).

Therefore our hypothesis was formulated, according to it the allocation of skim milk proteins may be achieved through the use of a coagulant berry puree cornelian cherry and sloe, which contain organic acids and pectin.

In developing the modified method of deposition of proteins of skim milk (SM) from its own acid and pectin substances berry puree for maximize the allocation of proteins there is necessary to determine the technological regimes of deposition (the ratio of coagulant and SM, the temperature and duration of deposition).

In the first stage to determine the ratio of skim milk and coagulant for efficient deposition conditions of complex proteins there were investigated changing the pH SM from particles making berry puree.

Review of changes in pH SM of brought particles by mashed shown (fig. 1), when have been added mashed with 1.0% pH varies little way, because the buffer capacity of SM, and in further increasing the share of mash pH decreases linearly.

For the pH range 4.4...4.7, corresponding to the isoelectric state of casein and whey proteins, making it necessary 9.8...11.2% cornelian cherry and 11.0...12.3% puree sloe. But these relations visible coagulation of protein at 20°C occurs almost

immediately, and received clot has high humidity, a pinch of color consistency and pronounced herbal supplements. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to consolidate the share making mashed within that interval provides pH above isoelectric point mixture

of milk proteins. This will facilitate protein-pectin complex due to not neutralized ions of hydrogen, which accumulate as a result of dissociation of organic acids puree, carboxyl groups of dicarboxylic acid and hydroxyl groups of phosphoric acid SM.

Fig.1. PH dependence of mixtures containing SM and mashed berries, brought by the share of mashed units: -▲-, -□- - PH of the mixture with mashed SM cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively.

The degree of precipitation of proteins by herbal SM affecting three main factors: the percentage entered in mash, temperature deposition of proteins and duration of exposure of composition at a temperature of deposition. To search for rational values of the parameters used classical approach - the method of Gauss-Seidel.

The next step in the study of the deposition process of proteins in pasteurized SM at a

temperature of 80...82°C with constant stirring a certain amount of mashed, heated and kept at 92±1°C for 10-60 sec. Then the clot filtered, subjected ownpressing for (20...30)-60 sec. and cooled to a temperature of 12...14°C.

Results of experimental studies have shown that application, under prescribed conditions, puree berries significantly affected the clotting process and the degree of selection SM proteins (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Influence of particles brought by the degree of mashed precipitation of proteins SM, %: -▲-, -□- - SM composition of mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively.

According to fig. 2, the maximum yield of protein is observed when making mashed cornelian cherry 2.5%, 3.0...3.5% puree thorns and is 91.6%, 91.0%, respectively. It was also found that any content mashed berries more than 3.5% does not increase the output of proteins.

By organoleptic characteristics of these samples were characterized by homogeneous and plastic consistency, taste - pure milk with a slight smell of pasteurization, color - pink.

To set the efficient deposition temperature studied the influence of heat treatment on the yield of protein compositions "SM-mashed" with cornelian cherry mashed 2.5% and 3.0% mashed sloe.

With the above in fig. 3 graph shows that temperature significantly affects the degree of urinary protein. Thus, the elevated temperature of 80°C to 94°C the degree of urinary protein increased by 27.22% and 30.01% for tracks with mashed cornel and thorns, respectively.

The greatest degree of deposition of protein SM is observed within 90...94°C. However, temperatures over 93°C is critical for early reaction melanoidin, destruction sulfur-containing amino

acids, accompanied by loss of -SH-groups and the emergence of smell and taste of pasteurization, and losing of tryptophan.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the degree of precipitation of proteins SM from treatment temperature, %: -▲-, -□- - SM composition of mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively.

Increased deposition temperature significantly affects the water-binding ability of the finished bunch. Thus, at 80°C humidity of bunch is 80.1% and 79.5%, and at 94°C - 68.3% and 67.14% for tracks with mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively. Reduced humidity with increasing temperature, in our opinion due to the denaturation of proteins and protein gel seal, accompanied extruded moisture from the structure of protein-carbohydrate polymers clot.

Thus, rational deposition temperature is 92±1°C, at which the degree of deposition of protein SM is 91.6% and 91.0% for tracks with mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively.

The next step examined the influence of duration of exposure of the compositions of SM coagulants deposition at 92±1°C on the degree of precipitation of proteins (fig. 4). Whereas the denaturation and coagulation processes are not instantaneous, and are prolonged in the time, samples were taken after 5-60 sec. exposure.

Fig. 4. Dependence of the degree of precipitation of proteins from SM exposure duration at 92±1°C, %: -▲-, -□- - SM composition of mashed cornelian cherry and sloe.

As shown in fig. 4, with increasing duration of exposure tracks the degree of the allocation protein increases and reaches a maximum duration of the process (10...15)-60 seconds for tracks with mashed cornelian cherry and 15-60 sec for compositions with mashed sloe. Upon further aging with for 20-60 sec. with a selection of proteins is

increased by only 0.3% and 0.2% for tracks with mashed cornel and thorns, respectively. To check the adequacy of the obtained profiles of modified protein SM precipitation method studied the chemical composition of whey, which is cleared (table 1).

Table 1. Chemical composition of whey, which is cleared when the modified method of deposition of proteins SM and control, mass fraction, %, ($\alpha \leq 0,02$)

DESCRIPTION	Coagulant		Control - cheese whey
	mashed cornel	mashed thorns	
Dry matter, including:	7,58	7,61	6,20
Protein crude, including:	0,51	0,58	0,80
Protein	0,30	0,30	0,52
Fat	0,01	0,01	0,30
Carbohydrates	6,18	6,19	4,7

The data show that the modified method developed by the degree of deposition of proteins of skim milk is much more better than traditional thermalacid coagulation.

As a result of experimental studies to maximize the SM proteins and a albuminous-carbohydrate clots (AC Q) with the best quality indices were grounded following profiles modified method of deposition of protein SM by plant material: temperature pasteurization SM - 91...93°C for 10-60 sec, the following cooling SM to 80...82°C, making 2.5% mashed cornelian cherry or mashed sloe 3.0% with temperature 80...82°C,

coagulation at a temperature of 92±1°C for (10...15)·60 seconds, cooling to a temperature of 12...14°C, filtering the clot and own pressing for (20...30)·60 seconds.

The next step was carried out optimization of the obtained profiles of modified method of deposition of protein SM. Option of optimization has been selected the degree of complex deposition (D, %) protein SM, optimization factors - part of making mashed (x_1 , %), temperature of precipitation of proteins (x_2 , °C) and duration of exposure of composition at a temperature of deposition (x_3 , ·60 sec) . It returned the following equation:

$$\text{- Coagulant - mashed cornelian cherry: } D_1 = 60,65+1,40 \cdot C+0,275 \cdot t +4,20 \cdot \tau, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{- Coagulant - mashed sloe: } D_2 = -119,94+20,68 \cdot C+2,175 \cdot t +448,2 \cdot \tau - 0,20 \cdot C \cdot t - 4,80 \cdot t \cdot \tau. \quad (2)$$

Thus, the results of the research allowed to determine the optimal technological parameters of deposition of complex proteins SM, which were:

- Coagulant - mashed cornelian cherry: the share of mashed - 3.3%, the temperature of deposition of proteins - 91,2°C, duration of exposure of composition at a temperature of deposition - 12,8·60 sec;
- Coagulant - mashed sloe: the share of mashed - 3.8%, the temperature of deposition of proteins - 92,1°C, duration of exposure of composition at a temperature of deposition - 15,2·60 sec.

On the next step explored possibilities for realization of surface-active properties of caseins ACC by their conversion into soluble state that can be achieved by shifting the values of active acidity of the isoelectric zone of milk proteins at 40...90°C, with the apparent surface-active properties of proteins and increases the moisture capacity bunch.

As acidity regulator selected dietary supplement consisting of equal parts of pyrophosphate (E 450) and triphosphate (E 451) sodium. Decalcium heat treatment was carried out with the addition of ACC supplements among whey.

The need for attraction for heat treatment of whey clot caused by the need to create conditions for a uniform distribution of phosphate by volume, to prevent local overheating of proteins at the surface of the thermal equipment due to evaporation during thermal processing. With this, is the principle of producing without waste is too.

Rations clot and whey established experimentally for consistency heat treated clot. Rational consistency heat treated for the next bunch of air dispersion observed in the ratio of ACC : Whey as 80:20. A temperature of processing was recorded at 80±2°C. Criteria of decalcium casein and accumulation of soluble proteins we determined the value of surface tension. As a result of research (fig. 5) found that the dynamics of accumulation of surfactants for both clots is the same. The difference in surface tension values for equivalent systems based on cornelian cherry and sloe ACC can be explained by different initial pH of clots, which is 6,34 ± 0,01 and 6,43 ± 0,01 units, respectively. Also, probably proteins sloes ACC are more accessible form for dissolution.

Fig. 5. The dependence of surface tension of the solution cornelian cherry (A) and sloes (B) ACC from heat treatment duration and concentration of phosphate, N/m:
 1 - phosphate concentration at 0.60%, 2 - 0.70%, 3 - 0.80%; 4 - 0.90%, 5 - 1.00%.

In fig. 5 shows that at the chosen temperature the maximum reduction of surface tension of the solution of cornelian cherry and sloe ACC achieved additive concentration phosphate 0.90% and 1.00%, respectively, and is $(42,42) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$ and $(42,13) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$, $(41,70) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$ and $(41,35) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$. However, due to the presence of systems with additive concentration 1.00% there is an alkaline taste, so this concentration is not desirable to use. Time of heat treatment for $(10...12) \cdot 60 \text{ s}$ significantly affects the reduction of surface tension. Further heat treatment of both clot within $(12...20) \cdot 60 \text{ seconds}$ reduces the value of surface tension only to 0.12...0.95%.

Thus, for accumulation of soluble protein as surfactant, rational parameters of thermal treatment

of ACC at $80 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ should be considered additive concentration $0,90 \pm 0,01\%$, the duration of the process $(10...12) \cdot 60 \text{ seconds}$.

Based on the obtained ACC with functional-technological properties (FTP) modified by adding berry puree modified can be obtained for semifinished item for whipped dessert production.

With this proteins ACC should act as a surface active agent, that's why determined a rational pH zone in which the most sold surface-active properties of modified proteins ACC. Previous research found that the maximum allowable value and berry puree ACC is 50:50, while the mixture pH is within 5.2...5.6 units. Therefore, the lower limit pH range that was investigated, limited 5.2 units.

Fig. 6. The dependence of surface tension of 1% solution of pH ACC:
 -■-, -□- - the surface tension of cornelian cherry and sloe ACC respectively.

In fig. 6 shows that the ultimate use of surface-active properties of 1% solution of ACC observed within pH 6.7...6.1 un. In this range the surface tension increases only by 2.62% and 2.81% for the cornelian cherry and sloe ACC, respectively. With further decrease in pH surface tension is growing rapidly, and at 5.2 un. matter $52,50 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$ and $54,01 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$ for the cornelian cherry and

sloe ACC, respectively, at 25.01% and 26.70% higher than at pH 6.7. The loss of surface-active properties of the ACC with a decrease in active acidity can be explained by the formation of intra molecular protein-carbohydrate complexes. Thus, the pH of the compositions of the modified ACC berry puree to a maximum of surface-active properties of proteins should not be less than 6.1 un.

In establishing a rational relationships of ACC and berry mashed studied form froth ability (FFA), stability of foam (SF), active acidity of the compositions and the surface tension of 1% solution of these compositions. To prevent irreversible reactions of calcium and pectates ACC, mixing ingredients performed at or above 70°C, for which there is no chemical interaction between them. Tracks heated to of 80...82°C, in which consist of complex conditions, cooled and whipped up.

Analysis of fig.7 shows that for both semifinished items maximum values of FFA and SF observed in the compositions of 10...20% content of the modified berry mashed. In these concentrations are lower mash pH to 0.56...0.61 un. Which causes an increase in surface tension of only $1,20 \cdot 10^{-3}$ N/m and $1,40 \cdot 10^{-3}$ N/m for tracks with cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively. At that the ultimate use of the surface properties of milk proteins, which is

reflected in the increase of FFA respectively 57.2% and 56.1%. Increasing SF can be explained by a complexation between proteins and soluble pectins by calcium ions, resulting in the formation of calcium and pectates protein-carbohydrate complexes, which significantly increases the viscosity and causes the formation of spatial jelly-like grid. Formation pectates calcium and protein-carbohydrate complexes provide increased resistance of the compositions of 61.29% and 47.06% compared with the SF ACC.

Further increase of berry puree, accompanied by a decrease in pH of the systems and the gradual loss of surface properties, leading to a decrease in FFA. SF is also deteriorating, but with less dynamics, which can be explained by a slight phase containing air, which has a destructive effect due to coalescence of air bubbles.

Fig. 7. Dependence of the structural-mechanical and physical-chemical parameters of the compositions on the ratio of ingredients: A - Composition of the mashed cornelian cherry, B - Composition of the mashed sloe;

- ▨, ▩ – in accordance form froth ability (FFA), stability of foam (SF);
- , —□— surface tension of 1% solution compositions;
- ▲—, —Δ— pH of the compositions.

Using the method of compromise solution of problems by optimizing multi conjugated gradients using add «Search of decisions» MS Excel package was determined that the optimum content of mashed cornelian cherry is 16.5%, mashed sloe - 15.1%.

Develop final dessert of the product of sugar on the one hand, creates a consumer product and organoleptic properties, including taste, and, on the other hand, can significantly affect the functional,

technological and structural-mechanical properties of this product.

In order to determine the efficiency of sugar content in the final product a study on the influence of sugar on the structural, mechanical and technological properties of functional compositions ACC with berry puree. The research results provided in fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Dependence of functional-technological and structural-mechanical properties of compositions cornelian cherry ACC with mashed cornelian cherry (A) and compositions ACC with mashed sloe (B) of sugar: ▨, ▩ - according FFA and SF; -▲-, -Δ- - effective viscosity.

Analysis of the data shows that the addition of sugar inhibits FFA. This is due to the fact that sugar increases the surface tension of the compositions, thereby complicating the process of foaming. Thus, FFA compositions ACC with mashed cornelian cherry (Fig. 8.a) and with mashed sloe (Fig. 8.b) and 5% sugar content increases slightly, to 0.70% and 1.63%, and 10% sugar

Viscosity of the compositions of mashed cornelian cherry and sloe by adding sugar to 15% increases by 18.39% and 20.27%, which, in our opinion, allows slow thinning of the walls of the foam and the destruction of the structure, and for sugar content 20% 'viscosity is reduced by 7.14% and 3.92% respectively. Reducing the viscosity of the compositions in sugar content exceeding 15% due to its dehydrating effect, which leads to synerezy with visible drainage.

Thus, studies have shown that the addition of sugar in the number 5...20% give a negative impact on FFA compositions ACC with mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, which is reduced by 33.54% and 34.84% respectively. At the same time, the sugar content to 15% of tracks are characterized by high stability. This suggests that sugar should be minimal.

The best sugar content, which is calculated by the method of conjugate gradients for ACC with mashed cornelian cherry and sloe is 7.5% and 7.8% respectively.

The despair developed a comprehensive method involves precipitation of proteins SM released further processing of whey, which, through use as precipitant plant material, different from the usual cheese whey containing a percentage of complex carbohydrates. Therefore, to further research was to develop technology-based powdered semifinished items serum for whipped dessert production.

content is reduced by 10.13% and 8.39%, for the content of 15% - 22.78% and 20.00% respectively.

SF by adding sugar to 10% increases and becomes absolute. In compositions containing sugar 20% FFA hardly seen, and SF is reduced by 9.00% and 7.00% for tracks with mashed cornelian cherry and sloe, respectively.

According to table 1 presents the chemical composition of whey is mainly carbohydrates, proteins and minerals. To ensure the FFA and was chosen semi SF guar gum, which is a neutral polysaccharide and consists of 64...67% D-mannose and 33-36% D- galactose and has the properties of the thickener and stabilizer. Natural source of guar gum - xanthan gum seeds - bean tree *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* (L). The high degree of branching molecules guar gum provides good solubility even in cold water [3, 4].

The next step determined rational relationship such prescription components like whey, gum and sugar. The samples were exposed drying with mixtures of sugar making in the amount of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% by weight of whey.

Analyzing the composition of semifinished items prescription shows that the optimal amount of sugar is 50%. Sugar content in the dry mixture affects the rate of drying, and high content results in a product with a distinct brown color due to accumulation of reaction products melanoidin and caramelization.

Established that the solubility of dry semifinished items varies with the increase of sugar in different ways. Higher solubility characteristic of semi-finished products is in products with a sugar content of 50% of the total. Increase sugar to 100% equally as reducing it to 25% leads to a deterioration of solubility.

As noted earlier, as a stabilizer in the manufacture of semi-finished products used guar gum. Studies have shown that this formula mixture to make guar gum in an amount 0.5% of the mass of serum, as more stabilizer contributes to rubber weight on drying.

The main stages of the process are as follows: serum mixed with sugar, injected previously dissolved in water, guar gum (duty of water 1:10) and boiled at 90...95°C for (10...15)-60sec. Then the mixture whisk in hot over

(15-60) seconds to obtain a dense homogeneous mass, cooled to a temperature of 48...50°C and dried at 50...65°C for (240-60) sec. After drying milk and vegetable composition crushed into a powder. The result is a white powdery mass, which dissolves well in liquids.

Thus, realized non-waste processing complex in SM preparations for whipped dessert production, which can be used for making sweet dishes and desserts, cooking finishing preparations, drinks and cocktails.

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WHAT THE PROTECTED AREAS WORTH TO THE TOURISM SECTOR. MARAMUREȘ MOUNTAINS CASE STUDY

B.POPA *

Abstract: *This paper is a starting point for communicating information that proves the biodiversity and ecosystem services can be priced and has a market in tourism sector. Data were collected and interpreted starting from a baseline situation and value; business as usual (BAU) and sustainable ecosystem management (SEM) scenarios applied on Maramureș Mountains Natural Park bring the idea of additional value added by SEM. Thus, the paper is sustaining the funding decision of protected areas management*

Keywords: *tourism, protected areas, ecosystem services valuation.*

1. Introduction

This paper recognises the distinction between ecological and biodiversity capital and the flow of economic benefits that is produced by this capital. While the primary goal of PAs (Protected Areas) is biodiversity conservation, they commonly have a significant economic influence at the local, national and, in some cases, at global level: stock of natural capital (recreation, fisheries, non-timber products, pasture, landscape, etc.), flows of goods and services (producing outputs, supporting consumption, generating income, reducing costs, avoiding losses, minimising risks, protecting infrastructure, etc.), positive economic outcomes (sectorial income, GDP, employment, forex earnings, fiscal revenues, business profits, etc.) (UNDP, 2011).

Different stakeholders appreciate the services provided by PAs in different ways. Public and corporate decision makers, facing increasing pressure on funding, tend to allocate less financial resources to PAs relative to other sectors, which are perceived to be more productive in development terms. PAs are an important and productive asset providing a significant flow of economically valuable goods and services and this need to be clearly communicated to decision makers. Economic studies drawing out the significance of these services in monetary terms and their contribution to local, regional and national economies can be a powerful way of demonstrating the significance of PAs to decision makers.

Tourism is an important and rapidly-growing sector in Romania's economy, and one of the most important and emphasised development priorities (MRDT, 2007). In 2009 and 2010 around 6.1 million visitors were recorded accounting for 17.3 million and 16.0 million bed nights respectively: 22% were international arrivals and 94% are leisure visitors (NIS, 2010, 2011).

The present paper is a starting point for gathering and collating information that proves the biodiversity and ecosystem services can be priced and can have a market in the tourism sector, the costs and losses associated with PAs degradation and loss can be accounted and the calculation of the economic value relative to the tourism sector sustains funding decisions.

2. Methodology

Protected areas are important location for both domestic and international tourism. Generally speaking, visitor data are not available for the PAs, but there are a number of studies from which a conservative estimate of Romania's PA tourism sector has been derived. Starting with a baseline situation and value (year 2010), BAU (Business as Usual) and SEM (Sustainable Ecosystem Management) scenarios bring the idea of additional value-added by SEM.

Based on the link between ecosystem services and human wellbeing, the study overlies the framework that has now long been used by environmental economists to categorize and define the total economic value of ecosystems and biodiversity. The innovation is, from an

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Fig. 1: *BAU and SEM approach*

economist’s perspective, that this recognizes that biodiversity and ecosystems generate values that far exceed those that have conventionally been calculated by economists, and included in decision-making – they do not just support commercial resource uses, but also generate a wide range of non-market values, and broader sources of support to production, consumption and wellbeing (Pagiola, 2004).

A second framework that the study draws on is that provided by TEEB – the EU-sponsored initiative on “The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity”. This has recently gained a great deal of publicity and currency with decision-makers. TEEB suggests an approach which has three stages: identifying and assessing ecosystem services, estimating and demonstrating their value in economic terms, and capturing these values and seeking solutions (TEEB, 2010). The present valuation paper deals with the first two of these steps, while the future initiatives may also extend to the third.

The third framework that the study focused on is comparing scenarios. This paper compares two scenarios, and shows their economic implications. The first is the Business As Usual Scenario and illustrates what would happen if the current practices and activities continued at their current level of under-financing; under this scenario on-going ecosystem degradation and loss is anticipated. The second is an effective, well-managed and adequately-funded PAs management. We look at how the state of ecosystems under each scenario, and the goods

and services that they provide, and the impact on local and national economic output and wellbeing where possible.

The scenarios are based on the assumptions in Table 1 which have been developed by the author or collected through governmental strategic targets. This valuation paper focuses on conducting valuation exercise for the Maramureş Mountains Natural Park (MNP). The study involved micro-level analysis of key tourism related ecosystem values and economic linkages for the MNP. Although the resulting data can be used to advocate for investments in PAs conservation to national decision-makers, it is only able to present information on selected PA values, and does not express the economic returns from investing in conserving the Romanian network of PAs. However, the methods used in the current valuation study (and to some extent the data generated) should be able to be scaled up to the entire network of PAs in the future.

The current study principally relies on the collection, synthesis and interpretation of existing data sources (e.g. national and local-level economic and sectorial statistics, data sets from previous surveys and studies). Only limited primary data has therefore been collected, focused mainly on ground-truthing, verifying and gap-filling existing records and statistics. Contrary to initial expectations, there is a fairly good (although in no way comprehensive) body of secondary information and studies on tourism ecosystem values in Romania, including work

already carried out under other UNDP-GEF projects, and various academic and research publications. The valuation estimates presented in this report are not comprehensive, and depend on many assumptions. The study also relies to some extent on extrapolating the few data that are available for Romanian system of PAs, and of

necessity employs “value transfer” techniques. There are many limitations to the value transfer approach which are mainly to do with the credibility of applying data about a particular site or ecosystem to another context which might have very different biological, ecological and socio-economic characteristics

Table 1:BAU and SEM scenario description

Indicator	Changes from the baseline 2011-2035	
	BAU	SEM
Total visitor arrivals	Increase 4.8% per year till 2026 (MRDT 2007), stagnant after that	
Total visitor overnights	Increase 6.8%/year till 2026 (MRDT 2007), 2.5% per year after that	
Recorded no visitors to PA	Increase in ecotourism emphasis in total arrivals: 15% of total arrivals increase till 2016, 20% of total arrivals increase till 2026, stagnant after that.	Increase in ecotourism emphasis in total arrivals: 25% of total arrivals increase till 2016, 50% of total arrivals increase between 2016 and 2026, stagnant after that.
PA entry fees	No change	
Average expenditures per visitor per visit (food & hotel)	No change over short-term, but decrease over longer term as PAS stagnates	No change over short-term, but increases over longer term as PAS improves
% PA tourists spending on food & hotels	No change over short-term, but decrease over longer term as PAS stagnates	No change over short-term, but increases over longer term as PAS improves
Average contribution to conservation per visitor	No change until 2016, after which decreases	No change the first 5 years then increases by 1% the following 5 years and then 1.5% until 2025; stagnant after that
Total PA tourist consumer surplus per visitor	No change until 2016, after which decreases	No change the first 5 years then increases by 1% the following 5 years and then 1.5% until 2025; stagnant after that

Where value transfer techniques have been used, a conservative approach has been taken. The primary source of data is valuation studies that have been carried out in Romania as well as in Central, South and Eastern European countries with similar economic, institutional and ecological conditions to Romania. All values have been adjusted to bring them to 2012 Romania price levels, applying a consumer price index (CPI) deflator to account for domestic inflation, and using appropriate Gross Domestic Product Purchasing Power Parity (GDP PPP) conversion rates to equalise differences between Romania and other countries. The resulting analysis should therefore be seen as an initial (and incomplete) assessment of the economic contribution of MNP to the tourism

sector. The estimates presented remain highly speculative, and involve many assumptions and approximations. It is to be hoped that when new data become available, or as more detailed studies are undertaken, the figures presented in this report can be supplemented, improved, updated and replicate.

3. Results and discussion

Visitors data are not available for MNP, except for the data recorded in the MNP management plan (MNP, 2007) and some studies (Ceroni, 2007) showing that around 10,000 visitors were recorded in the Vaser Valley (where records are kept by the rail way operator) in 2007. Based on interviews with park administration employees, it

is likely that the number of people visiting Maramureş Area (including MNP) is far higher than this, as the available data are based on those sites for which visitor records are kept. To account for this, the study makes a conservative estimate that half as many tourists are visiting areas in the MNP for which visitor numbers are not recorded. In addition, the estimation of visitors in 2007 was translated using the national change percentage in number of arrivals to a today estimate of 8.700 visitors in 2010.

Based on the survey in 2007 (Ceroni, 2007) all respondents show that, even if they are not aware about the MNP values, their visit includes enjoying one of the promoted values or sites in the Park.

One important source of economic impact is from the expenditures that are made by visitors. In 2010, MNP didn't generate direct revenues (from entry fees and other charges), however, visitors to MNP spent money on hotels and restaurants. The study in 2007 (Ceroni, 2007) has calculated that average expenditures per visit and visitor on food and accommodation in MNP was RON 483.5 in 2007, equivalent to €135.5 per visitor per visit (2012 prices). Based on the findings of the same study, the average period of visit was 5 days, meaning a total daily expenditure per visitor of €27.1 (Ceroni, 2007). These estimates seem to be conservative compared to data collected at Durmitor National Park in Montenegro, which found a gross turnover of €1.6 million for hotels and restaurants, translating into an average accommodation fee of €2.6, plus typical spending on food, drinks and other services of €46.0 per visitor day (UNDP, 2011). They also appear to be conservative when comparing with the data from nearby countries. In Tatra National

Park in Poland visitors spend on about €45 per day, and in Slovakia's Slovensky Raj National Park total visitor expenditure averages €54 per person day (Getzner, 2009)

Assuming that 75% of the tourists are visiting MNP as part of longer stays or holidays, direct spending on hotels may therefore account for annual revenues of €1.3 million. This is a conservative estimate, as there is evidence that spending on hotels in areas with attractive natural landscapes tend to be greater than that in other places. Work carried out in Croatia by the Institute of Tourism has for example found that there is a premium of as much as 24-32% attached to the price that visitors are willing to pay for hotels located in forest areas, and that landscape is a decisive factor in visitors' choice of hotels (Pagiola, 1996).

The total economic value of PA tourism is however greater than the amount of money that people spend. Expenditures on entry fees, hotels and restaurants, travel costs and other purchases only tell us the minimum amount that visitors are willing to pay to visit PAs. For most tourists, the total value they ascribe to their visit to PAs exceeds the market prices they pay. The net economic benefit or "consumer surplus" to PA visitors is their total willingness to pay for PA tourism less expenditures actually made on their trip. In Romania, a study carried out in 5 PAs finds an average consumer surplus per visitor of €42, including an average willingness to pay for conservation of €15 (Dumitras, 2008, Dumitras *et al*, 2011) at the level of 2007. In present prices (using PPP conversions), that would be an average consumer surplus per visitor of €50.7, including an average willingness to pay for conservation of €18.2.

Table 2: Value of MNP tourism sector

EUR	
Direct revenues and earnings	1,326,206.3
Visitor consumer surplus	661,635.0
Total PA tourist value	1,987,841.3
Including (note: values not additive)	
Revenues to PAs	-
Revenues to hotels and restaurants	1,326,206.3
Visitor conservation values	237,510.0
Other not captured visitor benefits	424,125.0

Fig. 2: Tourism sector values MNP –BAU and SEM

Fig. 3: Winners and losers in BAU and SEM scenarios – MNP, tourism

Even if those are average estimations from 5 Parks, MNP not being among them, still the data can be used without significant doubt as long as another survey, less precise, done in MNP in 2007 shows that just under 60% of visitors expressed their willingness to contribute between €18 (for the conservation of traditional landscapes) and €21 (for wildlife conservation programmes) to PA funding (Ceroni, 2007).

Doing the calculation, this equates to a total consumer surplus of some €0.7 million a year, including a willingness to contribute to conservation of €0.2 million (Table 2).

Applying the designed models for BAU and SEM generated a NPV of just above €14 million

in BAU scenario and around €1.6 million in SEM (Figure 2). In BAU, even if initially there is an increasing tendency, after that, the values drops together with decreasing attraction for degraded landscape and improper ecosystem management. In SEM, the values are permanently increasing with a slower slope at the end of the considered period.

We can differentiate two main groups that are economically impacted by PAs: the private sector, and non-commercial users. In MNP case, private sector is the main champion, showing that, in case of MNP, the payment for ecosystem services systems are to focus the private sector (Figure 3). It worth mentioning that the

improvement in private sector revenue may also lead to increased revenues for local and national budget, based on the profitability of the sector.

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MONITORING THE QUALITY OF TOURISM TRANSPORTATION SERVICES BY USING ONLINE INSTRUMENTS

A. I. NECHITA D. M. DĂNILĂ

Abstract: *The papers presents the importance of an online monitoring system for assessing the quality of tourism transportation services and the benefits of using such a system.*

Key words: *car rental, quality, online system, questionnaire .*

1. Introduction

Today, quality has become a strategic component of business management because it determines the highest degree the competitiveness of products and services both domestically and internationally. Quality is the main factor regulating the market through customers entitled to choose what best suit their needs and expectations.

When it comes to quality assessment, clients do not refer to a particular service of a company. Rather, they evaluate quality by referring to all services and relationships that they have with the company, such as the operator's behavior, the agent's professionalism, the resolution of complaints, etc.).

Quality of tourism transport/transportation services can be easily monitored by online questionnaires. The advantages of such online surveys include large coverage, relatively low administrative costs, and greater convenience for the respondent, as the client is able to complete the survey at his/her convenience.

2. Assessment of car rental services quality

Car rental services, or rent-a-car – in the Anglo-Saxon – represent more than global transportation options as an alternative to personal cars.

Rent a car services have registered an important development, making possible the appearance of new national companies covering a significant market share next to traditional companies with experience in the field (Hertz, Avis, Europcar, etc.).

EuroCars is the Romanian online leader in providing tourist transportation services: car rental with or without a driver, as well as rental of minibuses and limousines.

In this paper, we analyze the quality assessment of tourism transportation services (car rental) on the basis of data obtained from an online monitoring system.

The online car reservation management is a system operated and managed over the Internet. Therefore, it provides a lot of options and advantages compared to the database systems. One important such advantage is that car rental employees, partners and clients can all utilize the system from anywhere in the world: office, home or when traveling. The only condition is possession of a computer connected to the internet.

3. Evaluation of car rental services quality through online questionnaires

Unlike in the case of material goods, assessment of service quality can only be made after using them. Assessing service quality is not always clear and objective enough, because it has a higher degree of subjectivity, difficult to quantify. When quality does not meet the customers' expectations, they immediately express their displeasure, while perhaps satisfied customers do not always take the time to express their satisfaction.

The evaluation of car rental services used in this paper was made by customers who used services from www.eurocars.ro, a site that offers car rental services in Romania. It has, among other modules, a system monitoring service quality.

After the rental period, customers received a questionnaire to assess the main components of the service used: the agent's professionalism and solicitude, quality of rented car, cleanliness of the car, the period of time needed for returning the car. The result were tabulated/centralized using the online monitoring system and were then

analyzed in order to improve service and increase customer satisfaction.

Customers had the chance to assess the quality of the car rental service by giving marks from 1 to 5 (1- disastrous, 5- excellent).

A pooling of the data obtained through the monitoring system in 2011 showed that tourists who requested a rent a car service in Romania came mostly from Europe (80%). There were also customers coming from outside Europe, but in substantially lower percentages (America 15%, Asia 4%, Australia 1%).

In terms of age, 32% of people who used a car rental service from EuroCars were in the 31-40 year old age category, 24% in the 41-50 year old group, 21% in the 21-30 age group, 16% in the 51-60 ge group and 7% in the age group over 60 years old. Of these, 80% of clients were male and 20% female.

Table 1 benchmarks the assessment of quality of services resulting from the online monitoring system for the years 2010 and 2011.

Table 1. Assessment of car rental services – mean responses

Questions Year	Agent's professionalism and solicitude	Quality of rented car	Cleanliness of rented car	Period of time needed for returning the car
2010	4.3860	3.9009	4.3032	4.1460
2011	4.4956	3.9697	4.2723	4.3747

On average, an improvement in car rental services in 2011 can be observed compared to the previous year.

Regarding professionalism and solicitude of the agent, it can be seen from Figure 1 how the number of customers who appreciated the qualities of the agent increased from one year

to the other. In 2010, 61.7% of clients assessed the agent's professionalism and solicitude as excellent, while in 2011 this percentage increased by 3.6%. During this time, the number of dissatisfied customers fell from 2.9% to 1.3%.

Figure 1. Assessment of the agent's professionalism and solicitude

With respect to the rented car's quality (Figure 2), the number of customers who were not at all pleased was in 2011 reduced by 1.8%

and the number of customers who felt that the car was excellent in terms of quality increased by 5.4% from 38.3% to 43.7%.

Figure 2. Assessment of the quality of the rented car

Overall, over 50% of clients were very pleased with their rental experience. In 2011 the number of customers giving top ratings of the service increased by 4.8% from a year earlier.

4. Conclusions

Although customers can have a positive attitude towards a company and its services, buying behavior can be unpredictable. It is therefore very important for businesses to have a system to shorten the reaction time to customer requests, providing quality support and services.

Implementation of an online customer relationship management system contributes to improving the company's relationships with its customers.

Customer relationship management philosophy consists in recognizing that a long term relationship with customers can be one of the most important assets of an enterprise, providing competitive advantage and improved

profitability.

The data analyzed in this work showed that implementation of an online monitoring system has increased the quality of tourist transport services in 2011 compared with 2010.

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TRENDS AND STRATEGIES IN PROMOTING TOURIST DESTINATIONS IN RURAL AREAS

V. GHERASIM*

Abstract: Rural areas generally, and the Romanian, in particular, offers a variety of attractive landscapes, and ancient traditions preserved from generation to generation, traditional architecture and folk costumes specific to different areas, a simple and healthy lifestyle, based on an organic diet, various festivals organized by local communities and tourist accommodation in guesthouses opportunity that offering tourists the comfort and facilities to spend a beautiful holiday. These elements of rural tourism offer can be emphasized by applying an effective strategy, based on promotion through branding, but also by actions to promote its national and international tourist market.

Keywords: rural tourism, promotion strategy, rural tourism trends, Romanian brand

1. Introduction

Investment promotion agencies have an important role in the development of a country's tourism industry as growing international competition between tourism destinations and higher contestability of foreign direct investment projects make effective promotion to attract investors in the sector (*United Nations Publication UNCTAD*, 2010).

A better promotion of tourist destinations in rural areas involves the marketing policy tailored national and international market demands. To be effective, promotion must be applied simultaneously on two coordinates, horizontal and vertical respectively. Horizontal coordinate tourism product aimed at creating an image of rural space, transforming it into tourist brand and then launch that brand. Vertical coordinate leads the tourist promotion of rural guesthouses at the tourist village where they are located, then to regional and finally at the national level. These two coordinates need to be preceded by implementing a sustainable tourism development in rural areas concerned.

Such a strategy should be based on completion of three stages: analyzing conditions, problems and opportunities from the perspective of the viability of enterprises, capacity issues, market trends, environmental degradation, or community concerns about future development; identifying objectives and making strategic choices which should embrace concerns for given to issues such as alleviating poverty, supporting conservation or reducing negative environmental impact; developing policies and action programmes, that

should indicates lead agencies, approximate resources, targets, timescale and associated monitoring (*United Nations Environment Programme* and World Tourism Organization, 2005, p. 60 - 62).

As a marketing tool, in recent years, the Internet has further refined the distribution of travel products. The industry now use the *traditional distribution*, which can be done without using the Internet and *digital distribution* by Internet. Basic online tourism marketing consists of activities such as: *partnering and clustering* – including information on the website that tells the customers about things to do and see while visiting a destination; *issuing media releases* – to make an announcement about the business and direct traffic to the website; *banner advertising* – allows operators to display a clickable advertisement on websites with high traffic and is an excellent way to increase brand awareness; *email marketing* – email remains the most used tool of the Internet which allows operators to collect email addresses from existing or potential customers and use those email addresses, with prior permission, to continue to develop a relationship with the tourist customers over time (*The Australian Tourism Data Warehouse*, 2010).

Promotion strategy for rural destinations require three levels of approach: a national tourism strategy where are mentioned the objectives of tourism development, the ways to attract foreign investors, a regional strategy between different countries and an individual promotion strategy of tourism agencies. An investment promotion

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strategy for the tourism sector should follow the 10-step process (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. *Developing and implementing an investment promotion strategy*

(Source: UNCTAD, 2010)

2. Promotion of rural tourism trends in international tourist market

International tourist market rural tourism has a variety of ways to promote tourism offer. It is, on the one hand, the original tourist products, such as "Holiday farmers 'households' (Germany), which allows tourists to know the typical atmosphere of such households, on the other hand we talk about tourism products made by farms equestrian, rural family holiday villages (France, Belgium, etc.). We also mention, camping sites and tourist products of rural farm etc.. (UK, France etc..).

The tourist offer is promoted through leaflets, maps, videos, travel guides, brochures and dedicated national tourism products made by each region or area basis. They are distributed both in traditional fashion (Fig. 2), in printed form and on electronic media, the tourist information centers, the offices and tourist offices, participation in tourism fairs and specialized exhibitions halls, Internet (websites, social media - Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Flickr), media advertising, by mail, by organizing events and conferences (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Traditional Distribution Channels

(Source: *Industry-Planning-for-Inbound-Success*, <http://www.tourism.australia.com/marketing>)

International distribution are used as instruments of rural tourism offers the following channels: "Farm Holiday Bureau" (United Kingdom), "Irish Farm Holiday Bureau", "Country Carrib Ltd.", "CO for National Rural Tourism" (Ireland), "Turismo Verde", "Agriturismo" (Italy), "Agriculture et Tourism", "International Café - Conette", "Maison de la Randonnée", "Ocean Gîtes et Loire Itinéraires", "National Federation of Gîtes de France" (France), network size BELSUS promotion, "Gîtes of Wallonie", "Fetourag" (Belgium), "Country Base" (Spain) etc..

An example of good practice in use marketing and information services in influencing sustainability of tourism in rural areas was a programme called *REDTURS* supported by the International Labour Organization (ILO), in latin America, first in Bolivia, Ecuador and Peru and then extended to other countries in the region for help small and rural community based tourism enterprises to prosper and grow. Another example is the *Leave No Trace programme* developed in the USA and now this is being established in some Latin American countries and elsewhere. The programme develop a sustainable behaviour by visitors which can also be achieved by educational activities, either on site or in the visitors' home, school or social environment (*United Nations Environment Programme and World Tourism Organization*, 2005, p. 118 -122).

Australia is another example of a competitive tourism product promoting. Its seven key experiences which both promoting rural tourism and urban tourism products are: *aboriginal Australia* – learning about traditional Aboriginal practices as well as contemporary interpretations; *nature in Australia* – discover and learn about distinctive plants and intriguing wildlife that cannot be found anywhere else in the world; *outback Australia* – enjoy the vast open spaces and meet the people that make this uniquely Australian landscape what it is; *aussie Coastal Lifestyle* – offers some of the most diverse, least-crowded and unspoilt coastal experiences in the world; *food and Wine* – enjoy Australia's fabulous food and wine served by friendly Aussies in great locations; *australian Major Cities* – enjoy Australia's way of life and culture; *australian Journeys* – discover the diversity, the wonders, the towns, the people and their unique way of life (*Industry planing for inbound success*, Tourism Australia, p. 15).

Fig. 3. *New Distribution Channels*

(Source: *Industry-Planning-for-Inbound-Success*, <http://www.tourism.australia.com/marketing>)

3. Some characteristics of promoting sustainable tourism in rural areas in Romania

Due to difficult marketing individually, several Romanian entrepreneurs in the private sector were associated in the National Association for Rural Tourism, Ecological and Cultural (A.N.T.R.E.C.).

A.N.T.R.E.C. is part of the European Federation of Rural Tourism EUROGITIS. This organization aims to identify, develop and promote rural tourism. Its main functions are: representation (the lobby), marketing (promotion), quality control tourist services provided (requires that certain standards), training, rural tourism offer information and reservations.

As marketing methods used by A.N.T.R.E.C. mention promotional catalogs (printed or online) of tourist accommodation units, accompanied by icons that show, by appropriate conventional signs, type of facilities and equipment that personalizes the household.

Another independent network of regional and national tourism stakeholders and Romania's first supra-regional tourism cluster of national interest is a Carpathian Tourism Cluster. This network has the following objectives (Fig. 4): development of innovative touristic offer and services to attract new tourists to the area of the Carpathian Mountains; optimize the value chain in the local tourism industry; promote the Romanian Carpathian Mountains as "destination of excellence" within the national tourism

Fig. 4. The Romanian rural areas coordinates

(Source: <http://tourism-cluster-romania.com/>)

promotion strategy “Romania – explore the Carpathian Garden” etc..

An useful possibility to promote the tourism offer of Romania are the Internet’s websites, like: <http://www.romaniatourism.com> – website of The Romanian National Tourist Office (the official representative of the Romanian Ministry of Regional Development and Tourism) with all the information about tour operators, travel agencies, tourist attractions and travel conditions, the events and tourist facilities within Romania, traditional villages with pastoral landscapes of Transylvania, Marginimea Sibiului, Apuseni Mountains, Bucovina, Maramures.

- other websites of this type are <http://www.ruraltourism.ro/>; <http://www.agrotur.ro>; <http://www.discoverworld.co.uk/romania/rural-tourism>; <http://www.agroturism.com/>; <http://www.infoghidromania.com/>;

http://www.promoturism.ro/ro/attractii/turism_rural.html; <http://www.vacantelatara.ro/> etc..

4. Proposals for a Romanian brand

Developing a brand for sustainable development of rural tourism is the stage delivering a tourism management strategy embracing planning, product development and marketing to bring about positive economic, social, cultural and environmental impacts. As a case study we chose the *Fagarasului Land*, an ethnographic area with a rich cultural and historical heritage and a special offer for rural tourism, ecumenical, and mountain tourism in the area bordering etc. This area is located in central Romania, the administrative territories of the counties of Sibiu and Brasov, in the area of contact between the Transylvanian Plateau and the Fagaras Mountains, which are part of the Carpathians.

Our proposal for the tourist brand to be promoted those rural areas which meet the conditions of practicing a quality tourism is the "Happy Land & Happy Tourist". This concept propose to establish a network of community-based tourism projects, for joint promotion within a common brand. To join a network as a member, an area must fulfil and maintain the brand values and its quality and adherence to sustainability principles.

In order *Fagarasului Land* tourism management from the perspective of sustainable development, we propose to create an organization that works as a corporation under the name "The Fagarasului Land Trust" with the brand "Happy Land & Happy Tourist". This corporate structure allows to identify what issues should be covered like managing donations and funds for development of this area, promote a local tourism culture, facilitate education rural tourism programmes for local people, adopt a good environmental practices for contribute to the quality of their surroundings, improving the experience for guests and the living standards of local communities, finance tourism infrastructure and local products development, ensure experienced tourism industry and environmental consultants for an efficient use of tourism resources and of energy and water resources, implement and invest in renewable energy systems such as solar water heaters, solar pumps, windmills, photovoltaic

systems and other low wattage appliances, promotion of local tourism products under the brand "Happy Land & Happy Tourist", creating a distribution network for selling their tourism products at the national, European and international level. This corporation should involve as a management board consulting the government stakeholders (e.g. Development Agency Centre), the district stakeholders (e.g. County Tourism Association and Rescue Sibiu), local stakeholders (e.g. representatives of mayors of villages and towns in *Fagarasului Land*) and set up with these a formal partnerships. As members of shareholders "The Fagarasului Land Trust" representatives propose local communities (e.g. entrepreneurs in tourism), other tourist service providers in this area (e.g. working in the accommodation, catering, leisure and entertainment, cultural, etc.), non-governmental organizations acting in the field of rural tourism in this area, other businesses (e.g. investors interested private business development in tourism).

Romanian rural areas have an important tourism potential and it need to be capitalized through a good promotion of villages with their local traditions and cultural heritage, promotion of agrotourism services.

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AN ADEQUATE CONTENT FOR A TIMBER HARVESTING MAP

STELIAN ALEXANDRU BORZ*

Abstract: *In the paper are presented the problems, concerns and benefits in designing adequate maps for timber harvesting sites, by taking in consideration of a wider range of elements to be represented. Current production practices do not provide the necessary data for an adequate design, especially by comparison with other activity fields as well as with forest sector activities from other countries.*

Keywords: *timber harvesting site, map, content, best practices.*

1. Introduction

Timber harvesting, as any industrial production process has to be developed by considering high technical and productivity conditions, with minimum effort provided by labor force, as well as in low cost conditions. In the same time, timber harvesting must comply to applied silvicultural systems, as well as with environment protection directives.

Technical conditions refer to existing ground situation as well as to the applied technological procedures in order to better realize the timber harvesting process. Productivity is a consequence of the applied technology, as well as an adequate planning of timber harvesting operations. The cost component is related to the applied technology as well as to the other factors such as field conditions, stand conditions and the way in which the entire process is organized.

Any activity needs as prerequisite a proper planning, which is done in order to provide better conditions for its realization. Planning means that an activity needs a deployment plan, which, in timber harvesting is commonly named a Timber Harvesting Plan.

An important part form such a plan is represented by the afferent map which has to provide all the necessary elements for a proper realization of the production process. Other extractive activities require by law comprehensive surveys in order to be provided with an adequate site map. And this in conditions in which the cost of the final product may be lower or comparative with timber harvesting final products. Timber harvesting is a process which can be quite expensive, having production costs of 10-18 euro/m³ [7]. Also, for the specialized

commercial agents, the investments could be greater, by the need to acquire the timber biomass which presents high acquisition costs, in average 18 euro/m³ [9]. In perspective, the timber harvesting-logging process costs could decrease especially by assuring an appropriate accessibility for the forests, as well as by using new concept machinery in the process.

Currently, the process organization as well as the harvesting site planning is made empirically in Romania, or, more than that are not done at all. Both situations lead to inappropriate outputs for the process application: reduced productivities, higher costs, damages on the remaining trees, soil disturbance and erosion, decreased quality for water, etc.

The empirical approach in harvesting site planning considers the usage of a map, and some calculations regarding the overall productivity and process timing. Design elements, if they are realized, are poorly transposed in the field, or, after case, they are realized on site, without a proper planning. These approaches could be the result of the lack of knowledge or expertise, as well as the result of improper endowment with planning tools.

2. Data sources to be used in a timber harvesting site map

The necessary elements in a timber harvesting site map are those which are becoming necessary from the timber harvesting objectives. Due to the technology progress, some of these elements are currently available from different data sources: DEM, aerial or satellite photographs and remote sensing, forest managements and timber harvesting-utilization acts (bulletins). In the same

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time, most of the necessary data has to be collected from the field in order to realize an accurate map.

2.1. An overview of used timber harvesting site maps around the world and in Romania

Different scales are used in representing a timber harvesting site map. In Romanian conditions, are encountered the following scales:

-In production: usually 1:20,000 without contours map, provided by the forest management plans, and summarily equipped with some details (logging units, logging roads, transport roads and landing sites);

-In learning activities: usually between 1:2,000 – 1:5,000, provided by field surveys or contour maps realized at scales 1:5,000 – 1:10,000 (equidistance between 2.5 and 5 meters); for learning purposes these maps are better equipped, showing logging units, logging roads, transport roads, logging sub-compartments, landing sites, as well as an appropriate legend;

-Other countries maps: require different datasets [10] such as: harvest plan map, contour map and soils map. The required scale varies between 1:500 and 1:1,000 and each of them present specific requirements, as follows:

-the harvest plan map: timber stands, logging units, existing or proposed truck roads and landings, water resources (lakes, ponds, rivers, streams, springs and seeps), wetlands, Best Management Practices (BMPs) – stream and wetland crossing, buffer strips;

-the contour map: property boundaries, topography (20 foot contour resolution or better), existing or proposed truck roads and landings etc.

-the soils map: soils symbols and mapping units, soil survey used with date issued for land data, water resources.

2.2. What kind of data should be used in timber harvesting maps from Romania

Romanian forests are managed by considering two main groups [4]: group no. I, including forests with special protection functions and group II, including forests with production and protection functions.

The first group contains five subgroups: water protection forests, soil and erosion control forests, harmful climatic and industrial factors protection forests, social and touristic interest forests, scientific interest and genetic-ecologic purposes preserving forests. The second group

contains two subgroups, having different management strategies such as: timber production for different purposes and game-hunting interest forests.

The adopted strategies are enforced by adopting for each subgroup and category a functional type, which reflects the management strategies and operations to be done.

In order to preserve the forest functionalities, a timber harvesting site map has to consider all the elements which assure the best practices in timber harvesting organization, accordingly to the forests functionality.

In order to respond to the above mentioned problems, a timber harvesting site map should contain data belonging to the following data groups (alphabetically ordered): Geology and soils. Soil mechanics; Hydrology; Limits and boundaries; Other details; Stand; Technology; Terrain.

In the following, are described and justified all the necessary data for a timber harvesting site map realization, by considering the above presented categories.

2.3. Geology and soils. Soil mechanics

Geology, soils and soil mechanics are widely used in all civil applications, being a prerequisite for constructions realization as well as for its duration. In timber harvesting these aspects present an important role which influences the overall system. Geology is employed to establish the ground material as well as its behavior under the external influence factors whereas soils represent the main infrastructure for equipment and machinery movement in timber harvesting. Usually, soils provide the support environment for ground-based timber harvesting systems, influencing this way the passing capacity of machinery, as well as the system productivity [2].

Interaction from machine and soil generates repercussions on the soil, especially in case of the poor resistance soils. In time the machine's footprints can lead to erosion events, which affect both, the soil quality as well as other environment components quality. In order to limit or eliminate the negative effects, there is important for a timber harvesting site map to be provided with geological and soil additional data, in order to establish the best strategies.

Geotechnical (especially soil mechanics) data is important in establishing the investments in ground-based logging systems, by knowing the behavior of dislocated earth masses as well as

their properties. Knowing these aspects, and corroborated with technological limits of the used machines could lead to better practices, by limiting or eliminating the ground-based logging systems, especially in case of fragile materials, exposed to run-over events.

Geological parental material is usually provided by specific maps realized at 1:50,000 scale for Romania. Additionally data may be provided by field surveys in order to obtain an accurate map. Soils data is provided by forest management plans, either by compartment description or specific usually 1:20,000-1:50,000 soil distribution maps. Due the fact that a single soil type may appear in a certain compartment, using the compartment description may be sufficient.

Other geotechnical, geological or soil events may be represented by wetlands, exposed rocks, or rocky soils, erosion zones or zones in which the erosion danger exists. Usually this kind of data is accordingly inscribed in compartment description, but the forest management maps do not provide the amplitude or location of these elements. This represents one of the reasons for which the field survey must be realized in order to acquire this kind of data, especially regarding these elements location.

2.4. Hydrology

Current orientation in forest management activities underlines the necessity of a sustainable development, by considering all the involved factors and decisions. Water is regarded as an important resource, and assuring its quality must be enforced by corresponding strategies. Due to its characteristics, timber harvesting activity is realized mostly in superior basins, overlapping on the small streams, which are cumulating and generating downstream the rivers. Affecting the integrity of the upper basins and basinsets may lead in affecting the quality of water downstream, especially in case of water protection forests. In order to provide best management practices and organization, a timber harvesting site map has to contain all relevant data regarding the water and water sources: dry channels which must be protected due the fact that erosion events may occur in case of exceptionally heavy rains (after soil disturbance due to logging activities), the crossing points, as well as the necessary constructions in order to realize them, existing crossing points and their state, buffers for

preventing streams erosion as well as to protect mineral, thermal or other kind of water resources. According to their flow regime, the water resources are represented on topographic maps, or can be deduced by analyzing a contour map. Usually, the crossing constructions (especially temporary culvers in the harvesting site) are not represented on maps. This, as well as establishing the best crossing locations and necessary crossing constructions, represents another reason for which field survey must be done in order to provide an adequate map.

2.5. Limits and boundaries

Any construction, exploitation or other civil application site becomes identifiable on a map by providing accurate limits, resulted from field or remote-sensing surveys. A particularity for timber harvesting sites is represented by the fact that they can be organized in different circumstances. Thus, they may contain a single forest compartment, several forest compartments or portions from one or multiple forest compartments.

Also, the felling areas present their own internal compartments [2], [6], represented by different logging units. A particularity for forest compartments from Romania, and other similar management practices from other countries, is the fact that a larger compartment may contain a smaller one in which forest logging operations are not realized simultaneously. In this case, the smaller compartment must be accordingly represented on the timber harvesting site map, in order to apply the necessary measures. Also, different properties may be grouped in the same forest compartment, reason for which, the property limits (boundaries) have to be represented on the map. In fact, this is a specific reality for Romanian forests.

By considering the above specified problems, two types of limits and boundaries must be provided by a timber harvesting site map: management and property limits, as well as technological limits. From the first category, the following are presenting interest in map designing: property or administration limits (Forest District limit, owner limit), management unit limits, parcel limits, compartment limits, other property, enclave or management nature limits. The second category includes: felling area limits, felling-logging limits, other technological compartments limits.

Generally, the limits from the first group are provided by management plans, and they can be acquired from contour maps or forest management maps. In case of existence of an adequate GIS, these can be provided to a better accuracy. Otherwise, field surveys are necessary in order to collect this kind of information.

The limits from the second group may overlap on some limits from the first one. If their accuracy is good they can be used for map design. In other cases field survey may be required. Logging units and other technological compartments are designed after all data acquiring, being in fact an applied design process in order to optimize the timber harvesting-logging process. These limits must be drawn in the field, as well as all designed elements, by using field data collectors, after their office design activity.

2.6. Other details

Generally, maps contain a wide range of details, representing the ground situation. In order to adopt the best strategies in timber harvesting and logging a specific map must contain additional details, in order to use or preserve certain objects, elements or phenomena. According to functional classification of the Romanian forests, several details may be of interest in realizing a comprehensive timber harvesting site map, as follows:

- Hunting, forest management, or other nature constructions or lodges;
- Game food constructions, game salt constructions, game observation constructions or other game-hunting objectives (if they are realized in the future harvesting site);
- Electrical, gas, water, or other network types which cross over the timber harvesting site;
- Touristic, historical, scientific, or other reserved objectives.

Being constructions or objectives of greater importance, these are usually represented correspondingly on the forest management maps or other types of maps. Lower importance objectives may not be represented on such maps.

2.7. Stand

Forest stand provides the work object which is represented by the harvested timber. It also provides specific conditions for timber harvesting and logging [8], by the necessity of assuring the best regeneration and functionality for the forests.

Different applied silvicultural systems provide different technical and organizational conditions [1], [5]. Clear cuttings offer the most advantageous condition (both, as productivity-cost, as well as process organization) [5]. In case of selective cuttings, appears the necessity of remaining trees and seed protection. This objectives lead to specific organization of the harvesting process. Also, natural calamities may occur, case in which parts or entire stands are wind felled or attacked by insects. Such situations must be accordingly represented on timber harvesting site map in order to better develop the logging infrastructure.

Several situations present interest for an adequate map realization:

- Species of increased value, dispersed on the felling area surface. Knowing their position is an advantage, due the fact that logging network may be developed in their proximity, reducing complete dragging distance which may occur in timber degradation (venerer timber, acoustic properties timber, etc.);
- Protected species or natural monument trees (*Taxus bacata*, etc.). Knowing their position is an advantage in their protection by limiting the development of logging infrastructure in their proximity;
- Trees designed as seed production, or for other scientific purposes. Knowing their position is an advantage in their protection by limiting the development of logging infrastructure in their proximity;
- Shrub or herbaceous protected species. Knowing their position is an advantage for their protection by limiting the development of logging infrastructure in their proximity;
- Regeneration areas, especially in case of group shelter-wood silvicultural system applying. Knowing their position is an advantage in their protection by limiting the development of logging infrastructure in their proximity, as well as adopting an adequate logging system;
- Trees or zones covered by trees affected by different calamities (wind felling, snow breaking, insect attacks, etc.). Knowing their position is an advantage in their recovery, by adopting an adequate development for logging network, presenting increased productivities and lower costs.

Usually, for some of these elements, adequate data may be obtained from remote-sensing data sources, especially in case of zones affected by calamities, in conditions of recent data. This data may come at high costs, which are prohibitive for

small logging companies. An alternative is represented by a field survey, in order to delimit these areas.

Other elements may not be provided by current data sources, and a filed survey is required in order to obtain their location.

2.8. Technology

Generally the timber harvesting technology is regarded as being applied in several work places, leading to the final timber harvesting product – the timber assortment [1], [5]. When this product is delivered on the landing site, a short path is followed, and the technological process ends at landing site. There exist situations in which the process continues by timber transportation in order to be processed in specialized plants, obtaining this way the final product of timber harvesting [5]. In this last case, there can be distinguished two major timber movement networks: the logging network which is usually developed in the felling area, sometimes externally, and the transportation network, realized from consolidated forest roads. A reminiscence of the past transportation means is reflected in approximately 300 km of forest train ways, which currently serve also to other purposes [5].

Both networks present an actual state as well as a development state. In case of timber logging-yarding network, and by considering the current state in a given situation, the following elements present interest for a timber harvesting site map:

-Logging roads or corridors provided by anterior timber harvesting operations, as well as their current state and improving necessities. Some of the existent elements may be used in other operations, and they may contain the following: animal logging roads, previously used, tractor roads or corridors, and, in the last time, harvester-forwarder corridors. These elements are not provided by the forest management maps, and can be poorly provided by the topographic maps. Using remote-sensing data may provide an adequate situation in conditions of most recent recorded images. In high density stands, these features may not be visible. The most efficient, low-cost technique for their acquiring is field data survey using different data collectors.

-Skyline corridors, provided by the previously realized operations. Usually these can be collected from remote-sensing data sources if the last ones are recent. Also, in case of some corridors, the forest management maps provide

the necessary data, or this data can be found on topographic maps. An alternative is represented by field survey in order to collect the necessary data.

-Landing sites, usually present importance in design activities. If previously used landing sites are in order to provide adequate conditions for further operations, these should be recorded and represented on the timber harvesting site map.

Design activity is employed for a suitable organization in timber harvesting. For different situations, additional logging roads may be required. By having all the necessary data (soil, hydrographic, terrain, etc.), the necessary roads and streams crossing are designed on the timber harvesting site map. After design activities, these elements are transposed in field by using the necessary equipment. The design elements may consist in the above mentioned elements: roads, skylines, landing sites, crossing constructions, etc.

Having permanent usage nature, the transportation network is, usually, well represented on all the maps. Specific situations may occur in case of new forest roads portions development, when, they may not appear on any kind of data. In such cases, recent remote-sensing data may be used. A low cost alternative is represented by field surveys realized in order to acquire this kind of data.

2.9. Terrain

Any design activity is conditioned by existing terrain conditions. Ground situation is widely expressed as contour maps, which are the most used information background for design activities. In the last time, terrain representations may be realized by using grid or tin formats, resulting from different data sources interpolation.

In past, the most used data source for forest sector was represented by contour maps usually realized at equidistance of 2.5-10 m, and having representation scales between 1:5,000-1:25,000. Currently, a lot of data sources became available especially from satellite and aerial flights. Some of them provide better representations but come to higher costs, and some provide poorer representations but come to no cost. Decision in using them is referred to the necessary precision and available capital.

Due the fact that design activities in timber harvesting involve field surveys, the best way in realizing an adequate map is to realize a

topographic survey. Several procedures are provided by the specialty literature [3], [5], [6]. An integral topographic survey usually involves higher costs, but better accuracy, especially for further design activities. Empirical topographic procedures may be used, resulting in adequate accuracy, low investments and overall good maps realization.

Most of the required elements in a timber harvesting map realization are to be collected by field surveys. But certain cases may not require extensive surveys, case in which other more easily to use data sources can be used.

An adequate terrain representation also serves to harvesting and logging machinery establishing, due the fact that certain machines present technical limits. In case of skylines, better terrain representations are in order to provide better profiles, used in technical documentation to be elaborated. For tractor-based systems, a better terrain representation can lead to accurate cut volumes determinations in order to estimate the logging network cost.

Most of forests logging practitioners have to use both procedures for a timber harvesting site map realization: some of the data is provided without field surveys and some of the data is provided by field surveys.

3. Conclusions

In order to adopt the best strategies in timber harvesting operations, a first step is to realize a suitable map, which to provide all the necessary elements for design activities. The designed elements have to be field transposed as a prerequisite for process deployment.

Currently, in Romanian forest sector are used empirical approaches, despite the fact that learning and education sources do provide solutions for these purposes. A poor design leads to poor practices, as well as environmental factors affecting.

The immediate solution for these activities is standardization, especially by considering that most of the extractive and construction activities present their own standards in design activities. Most of the developed countries do require standard maps for approving timber harvesting in

certain sites. This is not the case of Romanian forest sector, and there is a lot of place for improvement.

This paper tries to justify the necessity of considering an ample range of factors to be included in a timber harvesting site map. Some of the required data (for elements presented in the paper), may come to high costs, but there is always a field survey alternative.

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KNOWLEDGE DISSEMINATION ON INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: *The information flows and relations in agri-industry are very complex if we consider the institutes, industrial and commercial companies, banks, government, which are related to this sector. The higher education and research institutions play very important rule in research on ICT. It is essential to disseminate more and more research results in the agri-food sector. In the innovation systems several actors are seen as relevant to agricultural innovation, including agricultural entrepreneurs, researchers, consultants, policy makers, supplier and processing industries, retail, customers. Forces at play in today's economic and social environment create a need for greater communication and coordination among specialists in value-added partnerships. The dissemination of research and development on innovative information technologies in agriculture project was a part of the Social Renewal Operational Program, New Hungary Development Plan. Within this national program the project helped the diffusion of R&D research results on ICT in agriculture.*

Keywords: *ICT research, ICT dissemination, innovation.*

1. Introduction

The Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics is a professional society, whose members are both individuals and organizations, which are interested in agricultural development of the IT area. The organization was founded in 1998 with goals to represent the interests of those who apply and want to use the tools of modern information technology in the agricultural sector. The Association's constitution formulated the following objectives:

- The Hungarian IT professionals in determining agricultural organizations contribute to the information society, within the agricultural economy to flourish. In addition, care of the Hungarian agriculture, informatics tradition.
- Have an active participant of the professional life: engage in professional research, application-development projects, advice, preparation of, the professional public life forum for the development and organization of events to facilitate the greyhound professional awareness, and encourage the professional life for constructive participation: make call for proposals, establish and award prizes.

- Play active role for increasing the IT knowledge and skills, distribute the Internet culture. Pay attention to the talent: organize and sponsor competitions for information technology in the national agricultural sector.
- Make effective collaborative relationships in the IT area of the domestic government and corporate-sector and international organizations.
- Provide legal services to individuals and members represent the interests of members.
- The professional tasks and services of the Alliance to ensure social demands increase in proportion to the number of members in terms of growth and pay special attention to young people and make them interested in participation in professional life.

As the innovation and research dissemination more and more important (Klerks and Leeuwis, 2008; Li and Kozhikode, 2009; März at al, 2006) the Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics implemented "The dissemination of research and development on innovative information technologies in agriculture" project within the New Hungary Development Plan. The objectives of the project are the following (Figure 1.):

- Developing a scientific website

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- Launching the electronic journal "Agrárinformatika/Agricultural informatics (Information technology in the agricultural sector)".
- Publishing research results in books
- Organising scientific international and national conferences
- Supporting the scientific work of students and young researchers.

Figure 1. *Work packages of the project*

There are two web portals. The first one is the Scientific web portal, which integrates the different publications, research results, news, conferences, events, etc.. The other one is the Hungarian/English language e-Journal (Journal of Agricultural Informatics) (Lengyel et al., 2011).

2. Materials and methods

The project based on the HAAI (Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics) activities, which have been executed during the past years. This present project gives help to do the main activities on higher level and start new tasks, such as the establishment of new scientific journal and publishing books on scientific agricultural informatics studies.

The main aim of the project is to collect R&D results on ICT from universities and distribute them towards different target groups. Based on this aim there are two target groups for the project. One target group of the project is those higher education institutions, departments, which are deal with relevant research topics and they are the legal members of the HAAI, furthermore we consider potential members as well as teachers in higher education / research persons and doctoral students of schools. The personal and legal members of the Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics are from academic

institutions in which higher education is based on academic major, graduate school education in the context of the sciences dealing with research topics, and cultivated. These institutions are the University of Debrecen, Budapest Corvinus University, Szeged University of Sciences, Róbert Károly College, University of Pannonia, St. Stephen University, University of West Hungary. The project will enable the opportunity to provide these teachers / researchers / students to publish their scientific results as peer-reviewed publications in journal or book. Other target group members of the project are the government of agriculture and specialized administrative and corporate actors who can utilize the research results more effectively. The governance, public and specialized administration an important task using information systems, which can give more efficient operation of the e-services to its users within the organization and external partners, customers, operators and farmers.

The project proposal has been motivated by lunched educational programs in the past in Hungary. Looking back to 80s we started to teach computing subjects 30 years ago. After introducing a few subjects we create specialization curriculum with applied oriented informatics subjects (Herdon, 1997). During this period we developed more curricula and accredited education programs.

Doctoral Schools are also important target group for the project. The publications of the results of research works are important both student and supervisors. This possibility is important for colleagues who are doing research work on the same or related research topic, so they can inform each other and they can exchange their results.

The journal and publishing services very important for the Hungarian agri-food sector because the peer-reviewed publishing facilities very limited in this topic. The doctoral schools, the application of the main characteristics were collected, which may be useful in the preparation and implementation of the project. We would like to highlight two Doctoral Schools at the University of Debrecen, which have an informatics subject.

The content of the informatics subject is the following: Information technology in agriculture, Databases, Database Management Systems, GIS, remote sensing, Computer Networks; Internet, Internet services; WWW; Research works: - Database creation tasks - to develop your own Web site - Studies on Agricultural informatics publications in relation to their own PhD research topic. Another School is the Business and Management Doctoral School deals with agribusiness. The research areas are the following in this School: the wider macro-and micro-agribusiness, and rural development-related issues. It has an Information management subject and the content of it is the following: System and information theory; The organization and information systems; Information management concept; The information management tools; Data and database management systems, data mining; IT Infrastructure; Corporate information systems; Management information systems, business intelligence; Data and information management on the Internet; The information technology application in agribusiness; Information systems in agriculture.

3. The carried out tasks

The project tasks have been established according to the objectives set. These were divided some 120 sub-tasks and have been implemented during the project.

Project management tasks were the proposal preparation, submission of the application, project management, organization, financial tasks.

There was a preliminary task of developing the Scientific Portal in which participants assessed the information needs of executive functions. After this it was followed by the portal's content and form design. Technical experts participated to implement the developed plan. The development took place after the implementation, testing, upload contents, and periodic content updates.

Part of the e-journal tasks and repetitive tasks once created:

One-time tasks:

- Create Operating Rules,
- Board was set up,
- Editorial Committee was set up,
- e-Journal system design,
- Implementation of e-Journal system.

Repetitive tasks release was preceded by the numbers, and was followed by:

- proposals reception, filing,
- formal verification,
- selecting lecturers,
- sending proofreading,
- repair proposals return,
- improved reception and control of goods,
- edit, publish, distribute,

The objective of publishing studies the tasks were very similar due to the nature of the repetitive tasks of e-journals.

Annually the scientists and scientific results are worth viewing mapping

- Selection,
- Research requests,
- compilation of research studies,
- , revision process,
- Processing,
- Printed by
- Dissemination and promotion functions.

The support for young researchers within the calling for proposal system has been implemented.

Sub-Tasks:

- Call for tender,
- Projects reception,
- Proofreading,
- Setting up sequence,
- Award Ceremony, which was held in the current year, Agricultural Information, or within the Summer School the Award was handed over on the ceremony.

The professional programs within specific sub-tasks included in the annual event plan, event preparation, invitation of lecturers, operation of

conference system, reviewing papers, editing and occasionally proofreading, maintain contact with the authors, lecturers, publications, preparation of CD and / or printed form, published in electronic form.

4. Results

The scientific information portal

The scientific information portal (<http://tamop.magisz.org/>) assures possibilities for the dissemination and awareness of higher education research and development, innovation results in the agri-food sector. Moreover, it gives

an opportunity for members and teachers, researchers and professionals of this field to ensure their active participation in professional fields. It offers services to individual and corporate members, as well as for those interested. The phases (or milestones) are on Figure 2. In the portal development we tried to meet the up to date requirements:

- Interoperability
- Scalability
- Modularity
- Easy to use
- Links to social networks
- Web 2.0 applications (Facebook, RSS).

Figure 2. *Scientific Portal development plan*

The main menu of the portal:

- Project description: we publish the objectives of the project.
- Journal of Agricultural Informatics: this is a link to the scientific journal.
- Conferences: this side shows our conferences, partner conferences and professional meetings.
- Publications: here one can find studies on Agricultural Informatics, conference proceedings, edited issues of 'Journal of Agricultural Informatics' and other proceedings and books.
- News: the latest news items are published here.
- Message board: this is an opportunity for users to send messages, event notifications to the editors.
- Partners: this is a list of the associated organizations and legal members.
- Document repository: this is a system for the documents with different user rights.

The Journal of Agricultural Informatics

The Hungarian / English language journal (<http://journal.magisz.org/>) publishes research and application results in advanced information technologies in agriculture. This niche journal improves scientific knowledge dissemination and innovation process. The aim of the journal is to help innovation processes by delivering results of research and best practices to the companies and farms. The task of the journal is to assist the publication of the farm management information systems and technologies, applied methods and knowledge. In addition, besides a number of other application possibilities, the food safety, the internet and mobile application are also important domains for the agri-food sector. A number of research institutions, university doctoral schools work on related topics to agricultural informatics. The journal will be a medium to ensure publishing the research results and help the information exchange between researchers and practical professionals. The peer-reviewed

journal is operating with editorial board and trustees-advisory board.

The publishing plan of the journal is on Figure 3.

Figure 3. *Publishing plan of Journal of Agricultural Informatics*

Within the project four journal volumes have been published. The published volume are available free of charge. The total number of the published articles was 33 in English or Hungarian.

Publishing books of studies

Studies on Agricultural Informatics enhance the awareness on the topic of agricultural informatics studies by publishing the attained results of research work. It also helps to inform professionals in the field of agricultural informatics. Teachers and researchers of this field have a very limited number of opportunities available to share their research results with publicity. Since material resources for publications are restricted and English resources do not include research results on Hungary's domestic environment, it offers a useful opportunity for teachers/ researchers and the results of PhD research work to be divulged, published in study books.

During the project in four volumes 24 studies have been published. Expensive nature of this activity can be continued only if have new aid.

Conferences

Conferences help to improve and assist professionals of the Hungarian non-profit and entrepreneur sphere to share experience with

each other and to strengthen international connections by organizing international scientific conferences and domestic programs. The Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics has regularly organized conferences during its activity of 10 years, furthermore acted as a co-organizer in preparing and holding conferences. The project aims to improve the assistance of the professionals and the profession. Furthermore, its goal is also to ameliorate the opportunities of organizing international conferences in Hungary.

The international scientific events and conferences nationwide, as well as smaller workshops were held. The events surrounding outstanding:

- Summer School 2010
- Organic.Edunet International Conference 2010
- Harnos Memorial Conference 2011
- Information Technology in Higher Education Conference 2011
- 2011 International Conference on Agricultural Informatics

Supporting scientific researches of students

The scientific work of students and young researchers will be supported by calls for proposals, the formation of awards and giving awards. To support talent, it plays an important role in the organization of national and local programs. The organization has been calling for

tenders for five years now for thesis and Students' Scientific Conference papers. Today, more and more papers are written on the topics of the application of informatics in several fields of agriculture. The expansion of the association's activities is important because of the three following reasons. First of all, to be an incentive for obtaining high-level research works. Secondly, it provides opportunities for young researchers (PhD students) to be appreciated in the professional field. Furthermore, it acquaints the results of research work with a wide range of enquirers.

5. Conclusions

Both social and scientific actors were involved in great importance of innovation in the agricultural area, whether they were agricultural entrepreneurs, researchers, advisors, decision-making about, their suppliers, manufacturing sector, retail industry players, or even the end-users. The important actors were higher education institutions in the innovation process. It is therefore particularly important that the results generated for public knowledge. This plays an important role in the activities of the Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics, which contributes to increase the efficiency of the innovation process. This activity, however, should not end with the completion of the project, as continues to be extremely important to perform tasks previously undertaken. However, the duties are necessary in the interaction between the academic, research, institutional and management body. This bridge role is intended to provide by the Association in the future.

In the innovation systems perspective, several actors are seen as relevant to agricultural innovation, including agricultural entrepreneurs, researchers, consultants, policy makers, supplier and processing industries, retail, customers. The higher education institutions play very important rule in applied ICT research and the innovation process too. Based on education and research potential of the higher education the Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics started a dissemination project for knowledge distribution to increase the efficient of innovation processes. The parts of the project should be successful because of they based on similar activities which were carried out in the past and successes which have been achieved during the first half period.

We started the Journal of Agricultural Informatics, the Scientific Portal has been lunched, we organised different conferences and the number of student has been increased who participated in competition of scientific papers.

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THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN CATERING PRODUCTION SYSTEMS UPON REAL AND APPARENT RETENTION OF Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+}

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Abstract: *The catering industry is considered relatively new in Romania and has emerged in response to the changes in population's life-style. Modern catering production systems have several advantages from financial, managerial and product quality stand points. From an investment standpoint, centralized production allows restaurant operators with multiple locations to produce their high-end, signature items with less financial stress. The advantages to high-volume feeding situations are obvious, and chain restaurants can use it to centralize production and distribute to smaller units. Regarding the effective time management, restaurants can organize their kitchen staff's time for best results, cooking high-volume items when business is slow and having them ready to use when the kitchen is busiest. When done correctly, the cook-serve, cook-chill and cook-freeze processes produce foods with no or limited loss of colour, flavour, texture or nutrients. Because of their importance in human nutrition, Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} contents and retention coefficients in fish-based (salmon fillet, carp fillet) and minced meat-based (beef and pork mixture) dishes were assessed. The evolution of these minerals has been studied by using three main catering systems: cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze, and two types of heat treatments: microwave and conventional heating. The study revealed that Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} are generally stable during processing and, in some instances, the losses could be influenced by the processing and heating system. While cook-serve systems provide better calcium retention than the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems, the remained amount of iron in the samples, after processing, is influenced mainly by the type of meat and by the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters such as: temperature, time, humidity, water activity, pH etc.*

Keywords: *cook-serve, cook-chill, cook-freeze, catering production systems.*

1. Introduction

Most foodservice businesses already do some advance food preparation starting from "scratch". Using cook-chill and cook-freeze systems has several advantages when compared with the conventional cook-serve. Production of convenience food is suitable for any size operation and helps to manage effectively the working time. Also, these cooking systems could help to streamline production, minimize waste, and improve food safety at the same time.

In a cook-serve system, most food items are prepared primarily from ingredients on the day they are to be served. The food items are then held hot until their consumption.

With a cook/chill system, foods are prepared from basic ingredients with the full range of processing done on the premises. Foods are prepared, appropriately packaged, then quick chilled and stored under refrigeration. The

cooked food is cooled so quickly that it does not stay in the "danger zone" (5 to 57°C) long enough to support harmful bacteria growth. The prepared foods are subsequently brought to their appropriate serving temperatures as near to meal times as possible and maintained at these temperatures until served.

In a cook-freeze system foods are prepared from basic ingredients, appropriately packaged, and then quick frozen. The prepared foods are brought to their appropriate serving temperatures as near to meal times as possible and maintained at these temperatures until served.

Because preserving nutritional characteristics is a major concern of any food processor, the content in minerals could be seen as an indicator of the end product. Minerals are recognized as being essential components of human diet.

They can serve as cofactors in the enzyme-controlled reactions that take place into the body

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cells, thus contributing to the normal course of metabolic processes and growth [1].

Throughout the body, minerals can form critical structural elements, control the action of nerves and muscles, help maintain the body's water balance, and buffer the acidity of the cell and extracellular fluids. Although minerals only make up a small percentage of the body weight, their physiological role is significant and life would not be possible without them [2, 3].

The minerals that have been identified to be necessary for specific metabolic functions or whose absence would result in physiological impairment are also referred to as essential "elements". These must be obtained through consumption of our foods and then through the absorption process which takes place in intestines. Dietary minerals are categorised into two groups: i.e. major minerals and trace minerals. The difference between them depends solely on the daily required amounts: at least 100 mg of major minerals, i.e.: Ca^{2+} , and less than 100 mg of trace minerals, i.e.: Fe^{2+} .

Calcium, as a macro-element with plastic role, participates in maintaining the functional integrity of central and peripheral nervous system, integrity of the cells' membrane, blood clotting. It is also a cofactor of some enzymes. Calcium deficiency may lead to different levels of hypocalcaemia and disorders like osteoporosis.

Component of haemoglobin, myoglobin, the cytochromes and several enzymes of the respiratory chain, Fe^{2+} is one of the essential elements for life. Because it is an oxygen carrier, iron plays an important role in cellular respiration. Other proteins, such as those needed for DNA synthesis and cell division, also rely on iron. Furthermore, iron is used to help produce the connective tissues in our body, some of the neurotransmitters in our brain, and to maintain the immune system. Hence, iron is necessary for allowing the cells that need oxygen to obtain O_2 , for supplying the body with a reliable source of energy, and for maintaining several other important structures and systems in the body. A dietary deficiency of iron causes typical nutritional anaemia.

Several studies provide information on mineral stability during technological processing and underline the complex interrelationship, such as synergy and antagonism, which could exist between minerals [4].

Because a major influence on the nutritional value, respectively on the minerals content of the foods is played by the method of processing, the

aim of our study was to evaluate the evolution of Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} ions in two types of catering products: fish- and minced meat-based dishes. The two catering products were processed in different systems: cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze. The rationale of studying the evolution of these two minerals lies on their importance in human nutrition.

2. Materials and methods

Samples preparation. Refrigerated meat and fish were purchased from a local store. The vegetables were purchased from the fresh market.

After the preliminary cleaning procedures, meat and fish meals were portioned, assembled, packed, and processed according to the chosen cooking system. The fish meal portion had 267 grams and minced meat meal had 229 grams. In Table 1 are presented the structure of the meals and the specific consumption per portion.

Before processing, products were divided in batches and coded according to: type of product, applied catering processing system, respectively the type of heating treatment (Table 2).

The specific operations for cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze systems and the working parameters are described in Table 3.

Product analysis. All samples were analyzed from the stand point of dry matter, Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} contents, and Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} retention.

Determination of the dry matter content. The dry matter content of the samples was determined according to the standard SR 9036/3-2003. The samples, previously weighed, were dried into an oven, at $102 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, until their weight was constant. The dried matter content was expressed as grams per 100 grams of product.

Determination of Ca^{2+} and Fe^{2+} . Calcium content was determined by flame photometer SHERWOOD and iron content was measured with Cary 50 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Retention coefficients were calculated according to Berechet and Segal (2006).

To determine the potential influence of processing on nutritional characteristics, three determinations were performed. For calcium, the coefficient of variation of reproducibility was 3.66 (VCR % = 3.66), and measured uncertainty is 5.4 (M = 5.40 %), and for iron the coefficient of variation of reproducibility was 4.3 (VCR % = 4.3) and measured uncertainty is 6.20 (M = 6.20 %).

Table 1
Meals composition and specific consumption per portion

Meals composition		Specific consumption (kg/kg)			
		„cook-serve” ^a	„cook-serve” ^b	„cook-chill”	„cook-freeze”
Fish meal	Salmon fresh file	0.7586	0,7333	0,8148	0,8800
	Carp fresh file	0.6897	0,6667	0,7407	0,8000
	Tomatoes	0.1379	0,1333	0,1481	0,1600
	Sweet cream	0.0345	0,0333	0,0370	0,0400
	Frozen carrot	0.0276	0,0267	0,0296	0,0320
	Sun flower oil	0.1034	0,1000	0,1111	0,1200
	Green parsley	0.0345	0,0333	0,0370	0,0400
	Garlic	0.0138	0,0133	0,0148	0,0160
	Black pepper	0.0007	0,0007	0,0007	0,0008
	Sweet paprika	0.0007	0,0007	0,0007	0,0008
	Salt	0.0172	0,0167	0,0185	0,0200
Minced meat meal	Deboned pork chops	0.6000	0,5802	0,6429	0,6923
	Fat pork meat	0.3333	0,3224	0,3571	0,3846
	Lean beef meat	0.2000	0,1934	0,2143	0,2308
	Red bell pepper	0.1000	0,0967	0,1071	0,1154
	Morcov congelat	0.0333	0,0322	0,0357	0,0385
	Onions	0.0667	0,0645	0,0714	0,0769
	Sun flower oil	0.1333	0,1289	0,1429	0,1538
	Green parsley	0.0133	0,0322	0,0357	0,0385
	Garlic	0.0133	0,0129	0,0143	0,0154
	Black pepper	0.0007	0,0006	0,0007	0,0008
	Sweet paprika	0.0007	0,0006	0,0007	0,0008
	Salt	0.0167	0,0161	0,0179	0,0192

a - Heat treatment performed into a convection oven

b - Heat treatment using microwaves

Table 2
Description of the product code and type of cooking system

Type of product	Description of products	Product code
Fish dish	Raw product	A0
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A2
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment using microwaves	A3
	Cook-chill system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A4
	Cook-freeze system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A5
Meat dish	Raw product	B0
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B2
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment using microwaves	B3
	Cook-chill system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B4
	Cook-freeze system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B5

Table 3

The specific operations and working parameters for cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze systems

Process operations and working parameters		Catering products									
		A0	A2	A3	A4	A5	B0	B2	B3	B4	B5
Preliminary operations	Working time/ 30 kg charge/operator (hours)	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3
	Temperature (°C)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Thermic treatment (baking)	Temperature (°C)	-	170	-	170	170	-	220		220	220
	Time (minutes)	-	20	15	20	20	-	20	20	20	20
	Power (watts)	-	-	567	-	-	-	-	567	-	-
Cooling (from 63 to 20°C)	Time (minutes)	-	60	60	60	60	-	60	60	60	60
Cooling (from 20 to 4°C)	Time (minutes)	-	60	60	60	60	-	60	60	60	60
Freezing (from 4 to -18°C)	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	-	60	-	-	-	-	60
Storage	Time (days)	-	-	-	3	20	-	-	-	3	20
	Temperature (°C)	-	-	-	4	-18	-	-	-	4	-18
Thermal regeneration	Temperature (°C)	-	-	-	100	100	-	-	-	100	100
	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	5	10	-	-	-	5	10
	Power (watts)	-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-	-
Cooling (from 63 to 4°C)	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	60	60	-	-	-	60	60

3. Results and discussion

Influence of catering processing on the content of Ca²⁺

The real and apparent retention of Ca²⁺ during the different processing systems are presented in Table 4.

Among the treatments, high values of real retention could be observed for the samples A3 and B3 which were processed in cook-serve system, using the microwave heating.

Extensive processing such as cook-freeze results in reduced Ca²⁺ retention coefficients as could be observed for the sample A5, which displays a real retention coefficient of 80.41%, and B5, whose calcium real retention value is 75.58%.

Cook-serve systems provide better calcium retention than the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems. Regarding the cook-serve systems, the higher values of calcium retention for A3 and B3 samples when compared with A2 and B2

samples, show that the type of heating treatment could also influence the content in minerals.

The differences in retention coefficients between fish and minced meat dishes are based on the total calcium content of the samples.

Similar results were obtained regarding the total content in calcium. From Figure 1 it can be observed that, for all the treatments, fish-based meals have calcium content higher than those based on minced meat.

After processing, the amount of calcium losses is influenced by the working parameters such as temperature and storage time. Therefore, we could observe the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems trigger greater calcium losses than the cook-serve systems.

From the calcium content of the fish-based samples, A3 and A4, and minced meat-based samples B3 and B4 it could be observed that the calcium content is lesser affected by the microwave heating, whereas the traditional thermal processing, in a convection oven is leading to higher losses.

Table 4
 Dry matter content, calcium content and retention coefficients for raw, cook-serve, cook-chill and cook-freeze products

Product code	Dry matter content (%)	Ca ²⁺ content (mg/100g product)	Real and apparent retention of Ca ²⁺	
			Ra (%)	Rr (%)
A0	30.6	27.31	100.00	100.00
A2	32.01	25.82	90.38	94.55
A3	31.39	26.13	93.27	95.68
A4	33.59	25.63	85.49	93.84
A5	33.88	24.32	80.41	89.03
B0	34.07	11.32	100.00	100.00
B2	35.62	11.03	93.16	97.40
B3	34.07	11.12	98.21	98.21
B4	37.89	10.98	87.21	96.99
B5	41.21	10.35	75.58	91.42

Fig. 1. The Ca²⁺ content of raw, cook-serve, cook-chill and cook-freeze products (mg/100g dry matter)

Cook-serve systems provide better calcium retention than the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems. Regarding the cook-serve systems, the higher values of calcium retention for A3 and B3 samples when compared with A2 and B2 samples, show that the type of heating treatment could also influence the content in minerals.

The differences in retention coefficients between fish and minced meat dishes are based on the total calcium content of the samples.

Similar results were obtained regarding the total content in calcium. From Figure 1 it can be observed that, for all the treatments, fish-based

meals have calcium content higher than those based on minced meat.

After processing, the amount of calcium losses is influenced by the working parameters such as temperature and storage time.

From the calcium content of the fish-based samples, A3 and A4, and minced meat-based samples B3 and B4 it could be observed that the calcium content is lesser affected by the microwave heating, whereas the traditional thermal processing, in a convection oven is leading to higher losses.

Influence of catering processing on the content of Fe²⁺

From the data presented in Table 5 and Figure 2, could be observed the evolution of iron content and retention coefficients for the samples cooked in different systems.

The amount of iron remained in the samples, after processing, is influenced by the type of meat. In the case of fish-based meals, for all the cooking systems, the iron content remained lower than that of minced meat-based meals.

The higher values of iron content could be correlated with higher retention coefficients. For example, in the case of sample A5, the iron content (mg/100g dry matter) is 6.29 and the real retention coefficient is 81.76%.

Similarly, the sample B3, with iron content of 9.28% (mg/100g dry matter), displayed a real retention coefficient of 85.76%.

It seems that the evolution of Fe²⁺ in the samples is determined by the high instability of iron: the transformation of ferric form from into ferrous form is highly favoured by intrinsic and extrinsic parameters (i.e.:

temperature, time, humidity, water activity, pH etc.).

4. Conclusions

Catering production systems do not affect dramatically the content and the retention of calcium and iron in the analysed products.

The values of the apparent retention and real retention of calcium and iron are influenced by several factors such as: type of meat, production system and heating system.

It was observed the cook-serve systems prevent the calcium losses compared with the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems which have the potential to trigger greater calcium losses.

Reduced Ca²⁺ retention coefficients characterize the extensive processing such as cook-freezing system.

The amount of iron remained in the samples, after processing, is influenced mostly by the type of meat and higher values of iron content could be correlated with higher retention coefficients.

Table 5
Dry matter content, iron content and retention coefficients for raw, cook-serve, cook-chill and cook-freeze products

Product code	Dry matter content (%)	Fe ²⁺ content (mg/100g product)	Real and apparent retention of Fe ²⁺	
			Ra (%)	Rr (%)
A0	30.6	2.37	100.00	100.00
A2	32.01	2.01	81.07	84.81
A3	31.39	1.96	80.62	82.70
A4	33.59	2.03	78.03	85.65
A5	33.88	2.13	81.17	89.87
B0	34.07	3.68	100.00	100.00
B2	35.62	3.206	83.33	87.12
B3	34.07	3.156	85.76	85.76
B4	37.89	2.966	72.47	80.60
B5	41.21	3.012	67.67	81.85

Fig. 2. The Fe^{2+} content of raw, cook-serve, cook-chill and cook-freeze products (mg/100g dry matter)

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INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES WORKING FOR AGRI-FOOD AREA

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Abstract: *The paper presents new contribution of ICT development in the last years in food and agriculture field. Some useful case studies are presented, emphasizing the role of ICT in each example, and each activity with food and agriculture topics. The paper shows the emerging factors of ICT in development of society trough actives initiatives like WFP, web portals, NGO-s.*

Keywords: *ICT, agriculture, food.*

1.Introduction

The rise of ICT as a tool for general interaction is evident from the wide acceptance of the Internet as a platform for communication and knowledge sharing. Knowledge and information are important factors for increasing agricultural development by increasing agricultural production and improving marketing and distribution. ICTs can improve the integration and efficiency of agri-food systems by new communication pathways and reducing transaction costs, given greater accessibility of

information on prices, transportation, and production technologies. [1]

2. Instruments of ICT working in agri-food

ICT and food assistance. WFP case study. Development of ICT has also a social dimension, with huge impact on the global way business of organizations. Humanitarian organizations working in food and agriculture area are no exception.

Fig. 1 WFP's use of information technology [2]

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Most donors, United Nations agencies, civil society, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and even beneficiaries are experimenting the new changes in ICT frame.

For example in the frame of humanitarian organizations such as WFP, beside of provides operational support, ICT begun to change and enable programmatic activities through new capabilities.

WFP's use of information technology can be classified into three broad areas[2]:

- Front-end services refer to technologies that are directly handled by endusers, and may include software, hardware or communications technologies.
- Middleware services refer to the underlying technologies to support the tools that end-users utilize, typically solutions or technologies such as databases, workflow or mail systems, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and others that make up the application platform. For example, GIS technologies are used in WFP's Emergency Preparedness and Response Web (EPWeb) and in the GeoNetwork Opensource service, which provides a publicly available repository for geo-referenced databases, cartographic products and other related data.
- Infrastructure services refer to the basic server, operating system or telecommunications services

on which both middleware and front-end services rest.

Web portals. Food galaxy case study

Web portals combine information from diverse sources in a unified way, offering to the customer a collection of data related to a specific subject. They contain standard web search features and offer custom services sensitive to the identity of the user accessing the portal.

In agrifood area there are also some significant improvements. One interesting project is foodgalaxy.eu (<http://www.foodgalaxy.eu>).

This is a part of TRACK_FAST, which is an European project entitled "Training requirements and careers for knowledge-based Food Science and Technology in Europe". TRACK_FAST has outlined four key areas [3]:

Identification and definition of personal skills requirements in food job market (WP1)

• Developments for the regulation of food science and technology professions in Europe (WP2);

• Establishment of a framework for continual professional training and career development for the FST professional (WP3);

• Motivation of young people to enter and pursue of a career in food science and technology in Europe (WP4).

Fig. 2. Foodgalaxy portal, part of "Training requirements and careers for knowledge-based Food Science and Technology in Europe" project

The main topics of foodgalaxy projects are:

- the taste of life;
- I eat therefore I am;
- to eat or not to eat;
- I am the king of the kitchen;
- brave new food;
- a small product for the costumer – a giant process for the producer;
- mission possible;
- once upon a time.

A special topic is entitled “My food career” and is providing information about: studying food science; new challenges for old problems; jobs&internships; successful stories in food science, useful addresses.

NGO-s. ROSITA case study.

NGO are small and mobile entities which help to dissemination of information related to new agri-food technologies, food safety, consumer protection, quality of food and life etc. Since they are very adaptive and sensitive to new information and communication technologies, NGO consist a good instrument for social education and disseminations of information to costumer.

There are a huge number of NGO working in the are of AF sector, but there are some with specific target to link between news in ICT and agri-food area.

In Romania, for example, can be mention the activity of Romanian Society for Information Technologies in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism (www.rosita.ro). Starting from april 2011 is doing an intensive activity, joining specialist form academic, social and enterprise area.

ROSITA wants to promote new trends in information technology and to apply the latest IT concepts in agriculture and food, environmental and tourism.

Like other prestigious European associations, **ROSITA** is working in interdisciplinary areas that are founded in modern methods of information, communication and data processing. The association's activity is supported by an enthusiastic group of researchers, teachers and students of the Faculty of Food and Tourism in Brasov, Romania, and a number of other

employees of software companies, engineering and applied research institutes in Romania.

At the institutional level, the association collaborates with other educational research entities and companies, especially from Central Romania.

According to the statute of **ROSITA**, [4] the goal of the association is to promote specific IT applications in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism according to Romanian laws and regulation in the field. In order to achieve the stated purpose, the association aims to achieve the following activities such:

- a) Developing and publishing books, periodicals, flyers, posters, brochures, software and other informative materials.
- b) Providing consultancy and advice to people interested in the areas converted by the association's purpose.
- c) Promotion of innovative ideas in using new IT technologies (web design, GIS, specific-applications) in the fields of, agriculture, food, environment, tourism.
- d) Conducting informative campaigns
- e) Organizing conferences, workshops, seminars, specialized training, thematic meetings.
- f) Participating in national and international scientific conferences.
- g) Granting of scholarships in in the field for students, doctoral students, experts in the field.
- h) Proposing projects with national and international funding.
- i) Collaborating with other associations, public institutions in the field
- j) Advancing proposals for patent.
- k) Carrying out basic and scientific research in the field.
- l) Editing the Journal of EcoAgriTourism.
- m) Designing and marketing of software applications and products in the field
- n) Providing specialized consulting projects.
- o) Providing of consultancy and audit services, according to the standards in the field organize the initiation, training and improving technical training and conduct of club members.

Fig. 3. ROSITA webpage and logo [4]

So far, **ROSITA** was involved in project such: Studies regarding the management of data content for the agritouristic pension websites.

- Journal of Food and EcoAgriTourism;
- Researches on using spices in traditional bakery products;
- NUTritional LABELing Study in Black Sea Region Countries;
- Researches regarding the control of the drying process using infrared data acquisition;
- Research on the promotion of innovative techniques for drying plant seeds of cereal and technical procedures by heating-oscillator in order to produce ecologic finished products;
- Studies and researches on grain dryer with variable design, in order to obtain ecological finite products;
- Research regarding the improvement of the germination capacity for cereal seed and technical plants, through the control and monitoring of the drying process. Applications in corn and soybean;
- Designing a controlled drying plant and cereal seed crops.

3. Conclusions

The paper is an examination of ICT conceptual frameworks for development of agri-food area. By presenting specific instrument like infrastructure services, web portals, NGO activities linked to ICT, paper contributes to the

building of ‘descriptive’ (explanatory) knowledge, and it may also be useful as the basis for developing ‘prescriptive’ (actionable) knowledge.

The case studies presented can be an invitation to the research community to reflect, explore and influence the use of ICT in developing countries.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE CHARACTERISTICS OF AGRITOURISM

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Abstract: *Having established a theoretical method for the study of the particularities of agritourism, the paper brings a contribution to the better knowledge of concrete aspects of agritourism and agricultural operation, and allows for a optimum manufacturing and operational parameters and environmental impact of agricultural farms*

Keywords: *tourism classification, agritourism, environment*

1. Generalities

Agritourism is the form of tourism that, through its activities, uses the economic potential of local farms, by developing some housing services and the capitalization of the products obtained through self-exploitation or other exploitations in the area.

The main characteristics of agritourism, that define it as a form of tourism, are:

- It acts as an extension of the agricultural activity in the household or agricultural farm, through tourism activities.
- Tourism's resource base is the natural environment of the rural or natural area.
- It utilizes the excess of housing and equipment in the common households and agricultural farms, but also separate buildings arranged as pensions, with specific equipment for the tourism industry.
- It guides the consumption of tourists towards fresh, organic products, made in private farms.
- The agritourism package involves combining and integrating the tourist in the rural society, in all its complexity.
- Agritourism activities contribute to the sustainable development of rural areas (the material grounds, the infrastructure, the framing of households in the territorial local arrangement plans, the creation of new workplaces, the avoidance of the rural depopulation process, etc.).

The agritourism industry contains two important sectors: the agricultural sector and the tourism sector.

The agricultural activity, performed by the owner of the private farm is materialized by

traditional producing and processing of agriculture and food products, and their capitalization in the agritourism pension or other commercial networks.

The main tourism activity consists in hospitality (accommodation, dining services and/or catering), recreation (travel, fishing, horseback riding), curative activities (clean water, sun, mud), therapeutic activities (mineral water, tea, natural extracts), etc [1].

Between the two sides there is a connection that goes both ways: farming supports the tourism activity through traditional and organic food products, while the agritourism package may include agricultural activities done by tourists (milking, mowing, harvesting, crop maintenance, food preparation, etc.).

There are also other agritouristical services, permanent or periodic, meeting the various requirements of tourists, or that disseminate the benefits of this type of tourism, playing a role both in the business marketing, and in the training of visitors.

"The selling point on the farm" is a form of service offered to the customers, consisting of arranging the selling points in the farm land under the slogan "farm products". This way, the visitors have the possibility to choose from a wide range of traditional products, many of which are produced in private farms or other farms in the area.

"Vacation at the farm" is a tourist package destined, in general, for teens and adolescents, during their schooling. Educational activities are held here, through which the realities of the agriculture world are seen and explained.

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The activities held at the farm are accompanied by classic touristic activities, by leisure and relaxation. "Open farm" is a periodic activity, in which the farmer proposes an informational visit on his farm, on certain days called "the open gates days". Here, he holds discussions with the guests about exploitation and about the economic, social and natural environment in which he conducts his activity. The guests will serve, at the end of the visit, a small treat offered by the farmer, from his traditional products and beverages, made in the farm or in the area [3].

The inn farm offers hospitality services (housing and food) with a more traditional

2. Research regarding the development of agri-tourism in Europe

The rural tourism, as well as other forms of tourism, usually interfere, such as agritourism or ecotourism, were strongly influenced by taken by the various initiatives taken at European Union organizations, especially in the last 20 years.

A priority direction that surely had a strong impact on the touristic development of various regions in Europe, was the one referring rural tourism and its integration into a global policy, with objectives related to protecting the environment and the local cultural identity, that can contribute to European integration.

In this aspect, a guide for promoting "intelligent" tourism was created, ie promoting a tourism that revitalizes the rural areas, protects the environment, and represents a complementary source of financial resources for the rural population, with a result of reducing or stopping the depopulation of rural settlements.

The European Union regulations, aimed to improve the efficiency of agricultural structures, envisage a system of financial aid for increasing investments in touristic activities on peasant farms. A limit has been set from which the farm activity can be considered agritourism, more specifically only farmers that obtain more than 25% of their income from the agricultural activity on their farm.

There are also exceptions, cases in which specific measures apply, where financial aid is provided for the disadvantaged areas (west of Ireland, parts of Italy, etc.).

The European regional development policy in the rural domain implied adopting some initiatives like LEADER or EXPERT programs,

character, specific to the area, particularly addressing transit tourism [4].

The rural tourism in general, but especially agritourism, are regarded as promising options for the future, as it can achieve a specific economic development for the settlements with predominantly agricultural and forestry specific, with favorable consequences regarding retaining and attracting the population into the rural environment, to step up disadvantaged agricultural regions in terms of natural resources, as well as social and cultural development.

having as main objectives, ways of implementing and developing the rural tourism, agritourism and ecotourism, with the purpose of steering subsidies for financing the natural or rural areas with touristic potential, for the professional training of the workforce and providing technical assistance, for encouraging the exploitation and marketing of local agricultural products.

All these programs were based on the principles of innovation, transferability, sustainability and profitability.

In France, the rural tourism and/or the agritourism are practiced especially by families, that can enjoy the holiday fragmentation, allowing the spending of more leisure time in more traditional areas like: Savoie, Loire, Cote d'Armor, Bas-Rhin, Bourgogne, Bretagne or Alsace.

These forms of tourism are promoted and developed through the work of various associations: „Gîtes de France” (with the European version EUROGÎTES –Federation Européenne de Logement Rural), „Logis et Auberges de France”, „Station vertes de vacances”, „Tourism en espace rural”, who are concerned about providing complex and complete services to tourists that are staying in the rural or natural areas.

Portugal is one of the countries that have experienced an intense development in rural tourism, focusing on the classic rural tourism (rural hotels, inns, fig.1) and on agritourism, getting closer to the French spirit of "observing" nature's beauties and ecosystems.

In Belgium, the activity in this field is coordinated by associations like Gîtes de Wallonie, Fetonrog sau UTRA, who consider the rural tourism as a way to exploit the cultural

Fig.1 La valeé des cerfs (gîte et ferme), Chenots, France

Fig.2 Rural hotel in Mortagua, Portugal

heritage of rural areas, a service provided for agriculture and farmers, a complementary activity which may become the main one, having as goals: exploiting the heritage,

obtaining financial income and breaking the rural exodus. As housing, spaces there are: rural hotels, farm homes, rural rest areas, farm camping, inn-farm, guest rooms, children rest areas, etc.

a)

b)

Fig.3 Ecological house (a), observation point (b), Charlerois, Belgium

3. Particularities of the touristical development in the Bran-Moeciu region

The region's development from a touristical point of view can seem surprising, mostly because the biggest share of tourists represents those coming from Bucharest. These tourists, in their way towards Bran, are passing through established touristical areas, from the plains (Snagov), hills (Campina, Breaza, Valeni) and mountains (the famous Prahova Valley, with its

well-known touristical towns of Predeal, Sinaia and Busteni). The reasons tourists prefer the Bran-Moeciu region are increasing in number, and they can be found in the touristical offers of the area, different from the other areas not only because of the practiced tourism types, but also because of the different environment or the contribution of local inhabitants, known for their diligence, hospitality and initiative.

The structure of the touristical offer in the perimeter can be observed in figure 4.

Fig. 4 The structure of the touristical offer in Bran-Moeciu region

From the point of view of its natural touristic potential, the Bran-Moeciu region has an aspect of a platform, broken up by numerous valleys, a platform that represents a continuation of the tectonical depression Tara Barsei, with a geomorphological structure in which calcareous or mixture areas alternate with crystalline rocks. From the mountainous surroundings, the altitudes decrease towards Bran and Turcului Stream, forming a more uniform stage, the one of interfloods of $\pm 900\text{m}$, covered with pastures, with numerous shelters and valleys strictly defined by mountain peaks.

This sector is characterized by the originality of settlements. The geomorphological landscape is completed by

the Moeciu keys and waterfalls, and by Liliəcilor Cave and Magura Abyss.

The climate is specific to the mountain regions. The average yearly temperature is situated around the value of 6°C , so, in the lower regions between the villages of Simon and Predelut-Sohodol, the average is of 7°C , while in the areas around Magura and towards Fundata the average is below 5°C . The yearly and monthly average of precipitations have values that don't affect tourism. The ozoned air, the atmospheric calm of depression areas, the persistence of snow, are useful elements to practice touristical activities.

Another attraction for tourists is the spontaneous vegetation, represented by forests and lawns. Forests occupy the biggest

surfaces (86% of the 193km surface of the Bran platform), being situated mostly at the edge of mountains, while lawns occupy the platform's central areas. Beech is predominant, and can be found even at 1200 m towards Piatra Craiului mountains, taking advantage of the rock and aesthetical expositions of the side, while spruce fir is well represented on the Western side of Bucegi Mountains, where it can be found at 900m. On the more abrupt slopes, with the role of protecting the soil, we can find clusters of birce forests, scattered at the lower limits of the spruce fir forest.

The fauna, by its aesthetical, recreative and cynegetical value, asserts itself by variety. We can find different animals, like bears, wild boars, wolves, deers, herissons, or fish like trout, barbel and chub.

The specific touristical hospitality structures are hotels, motels, cabins, campings, rural pensions and agrotouristical pensions. The most searched for are the agrotouristical pensions, which bring to the tourist the following specific offers [4]:

- The basic touristical resource is the rural or natural environment
- It utilizes the accomodation surplus and personal endowments of rural households, but also separate buildings, arranged as pensions
- Directs tourist consumption towards fresh and ecological products, produced in the agrotouristical farm. The agrotouristic package implies tourist's cohabitation and integration in the rural society, regarded in its whole complexity
- Income obtained from agrotourism generally has a complementary nature, because rural households obtain income from the agricultural activities, workmanship, traditional crafts, etc.
- Agrotouristical activities contribute to the durable development of the rural area (material base, infrastructure, affiliating the rural households in local plans, creating new work places, avoiding the process of rural depopulation, etc [6].

The development of rural tourism in the Bran-Moieciu region appeared during the increase in hospitality demand, constructions of agrotouristical pensions alternating with rural pensions or private vacation houses.

The outlining of touristical inheritance of the Bran-Moieciu region, and the capitalization of the natural and anthropical touristic fund's components, are realized through the already existing technical and material base. In tight harmony with the size, functionality, modernization and integration degree in the rural area of Bran-Moieciu, this base satisfies the tourist demand at a very high level.

The general infrastructure represents a priority element in the touristic development, its modernization and adaptation to the demands of the tourism market, polarizing the movement of touristic flows and favourably modifying the unwinding of touristic activities [2].

The ethnical region of Bran is formed by three large communes, each being composed of multiple villages:

- the Bran commune, with a population of approximately 5700, most of them being commuters towards the urban areas around Brasov (Râșnov, Codlea, Zărnești etc.), is composed of the villages: Bran, Predeluț, Sohodol, Șimon and Poarta;
- the Moeciu commune, with a population of approximately 6000, on a much larger surface, is composed of the villages: Moieciu de Jos, Moieciu de Sus, Cheia, Măgura and Peștera;
- the Fundata commune has a population of approximately 3900, which can be found in the villages: Drumul Carului, Fundata, Fundățica and Șirnea.

Identifying the particularities of each village with the purpose of contributing to a better launch of the national and international tourism, was obtained using multiple criteria: economical potential, quantity and quality of natural and anthropical touristic resources, ways of transportation, traditions, habits, etc. Thus, these three communes can be

considered climatic and landscape villages, as well as ethnographic-folklorical, with archaeological, historical and cultural monuments.

The entire area is covered by DN75, accesible to all types of cars, as well as public buses, which facilitate the arrival of tourists.

The area disposes of a well developed telecommunication network, with tendencies of extending towards the villages scattered at high altitudes (Moieciu de Sus, Măgura, Peștera, Șirnea, Fundățica).

The Bran-Moieciu area has a considerable portion covered by the network of drinking water, methane gas and sewerage system. In the isolated areas, family associations were formed, with 10-15 families connected to one spring [6].

The first touristic structures created with the purpose of practicing rural tourism were created after 1965. Thus, besides the Bran Chalet, built in 1965, the Bran Motel appears in 1970, and, after 1990, the offer of the Craiasa Muntilor-Moeciu pension appears in 1992, and the Bran-Moeciu pension in 1994. 1994 is the year in which rural tourism kicks off, this being the year of the first official

registering of offers from already established touristic structures. Next to these, the offers from agrotouristical farms are added, which in the next years will change their names to agrotouristical pensions.

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Biorefinery for Biomolecules (1st edition)

Date event: 16 - 17 April 2012

Website event: www.vlaggraduateschool.nl/courses/biorefinery

venue: Hotel & conference Centre "Hof van Wageningen", Wageningen, The Netherlands

6th Food Proteins Course 2012

Date event: 17 - 19 April

website event: <http://www.bridge2food.com/Food-Proteins-Course-Europe-Bridge2Food-2012.asp>

Venue: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

XXIV Conference Processing and Energy in Agriculture - PTEP 2012

Date Event: 22 - 27 April 2012

Website Event: www.ptep.org.rs

Venue: Hotel Omorika, Tara Mountain, Serbia

More Information: mbab@polj.uns.ac.rs

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Date event: 6 - 9 May

Website event: www.i-SUP2012.org

Venue: Bruges, Belgium

7th Food Proteins Course 2012

Date event: 14 - 16 May

website event: www.bridge2food.com/proteinnetwork.asp

venue: Singapore, Asia

6th International Conference on the Food Factory for the Future

Date event: 4 - 6 July 2012

Website event: www.food-factory.fr

Venue: Laval, France

11th International Symposium on Maillard Reaction

Date event: 16 - 20 September

Website event: www.maillard-nancy.fr

Venue: Nancy, France

2nd Protein Summit 2012

Date event: 26 - 27 September

Website event: www.bridge2food.com/proteinnetwork.asp

venue: The Netherlands
